

**Telling the Untold Story: Discourses, Cultural
Regeneration and the Hybridity of Placemaking in
Paisley**

By

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Abstract

This thesis explores how discourses of cultural regeneration are formed and represented in newspaper reporting. Though heavily critiqued, the notion that culture-led regeneration initiatives can leverage improved place perceptions has come to represent a truism within urban regeneration discourse. I argue that it is important to resist viewing the interaction(s) between culture, place and reputation as a monolith. Culture-led regeneration suggests a more explicitly instrumentalised role whereby culture is principally leveraged as a vehicle for economic growth. In contrast, cultural regeneration is said to provide a more holistic version of culture driven urban regeneration. I explore a specific case of cultural regeneration in the Scottish town of Paisley that has been characterised by its negative area reputation. Local policy makers and stakeholders have increasingly utilised cultural regeneration as a means to changing Paisley's negative reputation and revitalise the town's economy. This research utilised qualitative data including documentary data, newspaper data, semi-structured interviews and online workshops. I present findings suggesting that discourses of cultural regeneration invoke images of post-industrial decline to legitimise regeneration itself. Furthermore, discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley tend to foreground flagship cultural facilities, developing the visitor economy, putting the town on the map and town centre regeneration. I argue that discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley retain the logics of culture-led regeneration and urban neoliberalism. However, Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration cannot be reduced to the neoliberal logic of culture-led regeneration despite these similarities. There is the emergence of 'hybridised placemaking', which incorporates the more holistic language of cultural regeneration while retaining the logics of culture-led regeneration. In exploring these debates, this thesis contributes to debates about culture-led regeneration, cultural policy and the construction of area reputations.

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List of abbreviations

ABI	Area Based Initiative
CCSE	Centre for Culture, Sport and Events
CDP	Community Development Project
DA	Discourse Analysis
ECOC	European Capital of Culture
FDA	Foucauldian Discourse Analysis
FPPB	Future Paisley Partnership Board
FT	Financial Times
MPRE	Masterplanned Residential Estates
NDFC	New Deal for Communities
UKCoC	UK City of Culture
SC	Social Constructionism

Chapter 1: Introduction

In this thesis, I explore discourses of cultural regeneration in the Scottish town of Paisley, drawing on newspaper representations and the broader construction of the town's area reputation. Culture and creativity have increasingly been at the forefront of contemporary attempts to regenerate de-industrialising towns and cities in the Global North (see Miles, 2020; Vickery, 2007; Oakley, 2015; Mould, 2016). Miles (2020) argues that culture-led regeneration has 'long been lauded as a panacea for the ills of the contemporary urban condition' (p.210). Amid the backdrop of intensified globalisation, proponents argue that cities can rely on culture 'as a means of surviving and thriving' in this new economic paradigm (ibid). Aside from the anticipated economic value of culture-led (re)development, the perceived ability of culture to transform the image and reputation of place has been a long-held truism within discourses of culture-led regeneration (Garcia, 2005; Miles and Paddison, 2005). Cultural investment, it is argued, makes cities more competitive within a globalised economic landscape. However, little is known about the conditions of possibility which enable (or constrain) the formation discourses of culture-led regeneration. While it is clear that culture-led regeneration is implicated within broader global processes of neoliberalism (see Mould, 2018; Peck, 2005), it is less clear how the subjectivities of local decision-makers reflects these dominant global discourses. This reflects a Foucauldian understanding of discourse, insofar as discourse delineates the boundaries of knowledge by determining *how* the construction of subjectivity itself is implicated in a broader set of power relations (McHoul and Grace, 1993).

In this introductory chapter, I begin by providing necessary background context on the town of Paisley – the empirical focus of the research. I explore the persistent socio-economic

inequality experienced within the town as an outcome of (sub)urban decline. Following this, I outline the emergence of culture-led (and laterally cultural) regeneration strategies as a response to town centre decline and broader socio-economic inequality. However, I also discuss the critique of culture-led regeneration, which remains - as Oakley (2015: 2) argues - 'manifold and persuasive'. Finally, I outline the research aims and objectives and provide chapter outlines for the thesis. The chapter concludes with an outline of the contribution to knowledge made by this study.

1.1 Context: Paisley

Paisley is the largest town in Scotland, located only 10 miles from Glasgow city centre in the West of Scotland. The broader Renfrewshire region is the 10th biggest local authority area in Scotland with socio-economic and demographic conditions similar to the city of Dundee in the north-west of the country (McCandlish, 2019). Paisley is a town characterised by both its strong industrial heritage and sharp urban decline in the latter half of the 20th century. At the beginning of the 20th century, however, Paisley had a thriving manufacturing economy, specifically centred on the weaving and textile industries, specifically its world famous Paisley Pattern and the Paisley Shawl (*The Untold Story*, 2014). However, the intense pressure of global competition in the post-industrial epoch has created a myriad of economic and social problems within the town (Scottish Government, 2020; Wilson, 2021a). Socio-economic inequality has led to concentrated areas of deprivation within the Renfrewshire local authority area, and within Paisley itself.

Ferguslie Park, a peripheral estate on the outskirts of the town, has consistently featured within the top 5% of the most deprived areas in Scotland (McCandlish, 2019). Wright (2018) demonstrates the impact of manufacturing decline on peripheral areas of the town including

– but not limited to – Ferguslie Park. Without the manufacturing jobs located nearby, Ferguslie Park has been left spatially and economically separated from the rest of the town, which can in part explain the persistence of unemployment and inequality in the area. However, there is some evidence that the situation is improving. In the most recent update of the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD), Ferguslie Park was no longer categorised as the most deprived area in Scotland, moving up three spaces on the index (Scottish Government, 2020).

More generally, however, there have been persistent narratives about the realities of town centre decline in Paisley. Paisley town centre has been said to have declined from the ‘hustle and bustle’ of the 1970s/80s to become a local ‘disgrace’ (Vision for Paisley Town Centre, 2020: 8). The decline of Paisley town centre reflects the broader discourse of town centre decline, amid the rise of the post-industrial society and changing consumptive practices (see Tallon, 2013; Rice, 2009; Auge, 1990; Hughes and Jackson, 2015). However, there has been no meaningful academic attention paid to Paisley area reputation, though Ferguslie Park has attracted some attention from an urban policy and regeneration perspective (see, for example, Collins, 2003; Kintrea, 1996). It is, therefore, difficult to draw meaningful conclusions about the impact of de-industrialisation, poverty and inequality on the town’s area reputation. In any case, however, it is clear that the local authority has increasingly turned towards cultural regeneration as a means of transforming Paisley’s area reputation and growing the town’s economy.

1.2 The development of cultural regeneration in Paisley

Paisley has historically been the focus of urban regeneration policy actions. Ferguslie Park was, for example, the location of one of twelve Community Development Projects (CDP) that

were based in deprived areas in 1979 (Crow et al, 2018). In addition to this, Ferguslie Park has also been the target of regeneration under the 'New Life for Urban Scotland Programme' (Tarling et al, 1999). In recent years, Paisley has turned towards culture and heritage as a means for regenerating the town, developing its visitor economy and improving its reputation (Centre for Culture, Sport and Events, n.d). However, it is important to resist viewing Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration as homogenous without considering the internal debates that have shaped the development of the approach to cultural regeneration within the town. With this in mind, it is necessary to consider Paisley's changing approach to cultural regeneration through three key stages; the publication of *Paisley: Untold Story*, bidding for UK City of Culture (UKCoC) status and the formation of Future Paisley to oversee cultural regeneration activities in the town.

A baseline for cultural regeneration in Paisley is the publication of *The Untold Story* in 2014. Broadly speaking, the report sought to draw attention to undiscovered and under exploited cultural assets that could be used as a foundation for the broader economic regeneration of the town. In that report, heritage, it is argued, plays 'an important role in the economic regeneration of the town centre' (*The Untold Story*: 1) in that historic assets and more contemporary cultural activities (undefined by the report) hold the potential to attract visitors and increase visitor spend. Throughout the report, the regeneration strategy advocated is heritage-led, whereby the local government is charged with exploiting heritage assets to drive tourism, investment and grow the economy of Paisley and the wider Renfrewshire region. *The Untold Story* appears to closely replicate well-worn models of culture-led regeneration insofar as culture and heritage activities are instrumentalised and implicated within a broader economic development agenda (Richards and Wilson, 2006; Oakley, 2015). More specifically,

the strategy talks of developing the visitor economy and constructing flagship cultural landmarks including the redevelopment of Paisley Museum.

Following the publication of *The Untold Story*, in 2015 it was announced that Paisley would bid to become the 2021 UKCoC. Ultimately, Paisley lost this bid to the city of Coventry, however it was the first town to be shortlisted despite not having city status (CCSE, n.d; Bold, 2018). Following the conclusion of the UKCoC bid campaign, there was a renewed commitment from the local authority to ensure the bids' legacy, by ensuring the bid had an economic, cultural and social impact (ibid). The approach to regeneration fostered by the UKCoC bid campaign remains similar to culture-led approach outlined in *The Untold Story*. The UKCoC bid focused on the use of a large-scale cultural event as a catalyst for economic and social regeneration. This clearly reflects – to at least some extent – top-down, event-led regeneration strategies (see Richards and Wilson, 2006; Richards and Diuf, 2019; Cunningham and Platt, 2018). Indeed, Cunningham and Platt (2018) demonstrate that this is consistent with the broader event-led strategies fostered by the UKCoC bidding process. For Cunningham and Platt (ibid), the top down nature of the bidding process encourages (to put it mildly) bid cities to demonstrate a commitment to using the title to develop the 'creative industries' and to develop the 'visitor economy'.

In the post-bid period, however, there has been shift in language and approach to cultural regeneration in Paisley. Even a cursory glance at the evaluation documentation available reveals a substantial shift from the culture-led regeneration approach outlined in *The Untold Story* towards a more holistic cultural regeneration strategy. In this new approach, Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration is described as an integrated process in which culture can both lead and support a broader economic, social and physical transformation of the town

(Centre for Culture, Sport and Events, n.d; Wilson, 2021a). Central to the development of the post-bid regeneration programme has been the inception of Future Paisley, a wide-ranging programme of 'events, activity and investment' using the town's 'internationally significant' culture and heritage to 'transform' Paisley's future (Renfrewshire Council, n.d). Alongside this Future Paisley also involves the redevelopment of Paisley Town Hall, the construction of a learning and culture hub on Paisley town centre and transforming outdoor public spaces (ibid).

However, a large part of the Future Paisley programme to 2024 remains dependent on major cultural investments including a multi-million pound refurbishment of the Paisley Museum, and growing a significant new dimension to Paisley's economy with an annual programme of cultural events and festivals (Centre for Culture, Sport and Events, n.d). Investment in flagship culture landmarks and events suggests that there is some degree of continuity with the previous epoch of culture-led regeneration insofar as flagship cultural landmarks and developing the visitor economy remain integral to the strategy of cultural regeneration in Paisley (see Richards and Wilson, 2004, 2006; Mould, 2018). However, the commitment to cultural regeneration that has emerged in the post-bid landscape also more closely resembles values of creative placemaking. Markusen (2013) argues that creative placemaking is the process whereby 'partners shape the physical and social character of a town, neighbourhood, city or region around arts and cultural activities' (p.292). There is, therefore, a need to connect the evolving discourses surrounding cultural regeneration in Paisley with broader academic debates about the emergence of culture-led regeneration as an urban policy prescription.

1.3 Situating Paisley's approach: culture, regeneration and area reputation

The decline of post-industrial towns and cities has, in turn, negatively impacted their image and reputation (Kearns et al., 2013; Wassenberg, 2004). Discourses of decline and deprivation closely mirror scholarship of territorial stigmatisation. Territorial stigma, as initially understood by Loic Wacquant (1993, 2009), refers to the negative public image of specific places. This negative image reconstructs the inhabitants of stigmatised places as social outcasts (ibid). There have been myriad attempts to *change* negative area representations using culture-led regeneration (Garcia, 2005; Mooney, 2004; Richards and Diuf, 2019). Indeed, there is a large body of literature extolling the value of culture and creativity in the regeneration of de-industrialising towns and cities in the Global North (see Evans, 2005; Vickery, 2007; Oakley, 2015; Mould, 2018). Aside from the anticipated economic value of culture-led (re)development, the perceived ability of culture to transform the image and reputation of place is often leveraged as evidence of the apparent success of culture-led regeneration (Garcia, 2005). This in turn – it is argued - makes cities more competitive within a globalised economic landscape.

Harvey (1989) has located the increasing importance attributed to the image and reputation of place within a broader shift in the nature of urban governance from urban managerialism to urban entrepreneurialism in the neoliberal epoch. Central to this argument is the increasing focus from the local state on attracting mobile capital to post-industrial cities by re-imagining the city. Urban spaces are now frequently branded and marketed with an overarching brand-narrative attached to urban places. The symbolic economy has become increasingly central to the economic wellbeing of post-industrial cities (Zukin, 2011). A useful marker of this new, image conscious urbanism is the increased significance attributed to

bidding for, and delivering, cultural events and festivals as a means towards reconstructing a city's image (Richards and Palmer, 2014). Garcia (2017) points out that one of the key claims often associated with cultural events is that they can transform the image of the host city. This, in turn, supposedly leads to a myriad of economic and social benefits by boosting local pride and attracting tourism and investment (see Richards and Wilson, 2004; Miles and Paddison, 2005).

Discourses of culture-led regeneration itself have, however, been the subject of rigorous academic critique (see Peck, 2005; Mould, 2018; Miles, 2020). Oakley (2015: 2) demonstrates, critiques of culture-led regeneration are 'manifold and persuasive'. More specifically, culture-led regeneration has been criticised for its top-down imposition that reflects the dominant imperatives of urban neoliberalism and inter-urban competition (see Peck, 2005; Oakley, 2015; Mould, 2018; Slater, 2006). Additionally, myriad links between culture-led regeneration and gentrification have been made (see Mould, 2018; Aspen, 2013; Peck, 2005). As Pritchard (2016) claims, culture-led regeneration enlists artists as foot soldiers in the gentrification process. In a less polemical account, Zukin (2011) argues that art and culture can be utilised in the (re)production of what is (re)constructed as an authentic urban place. She argues that the interaction between art, culture and the city is not necessarily politically neutral, insofar as authenticity is selectively (re)constructed to make cities more marketable and amenable to inward capital investment.

One of the most heavily critiqued discourses of culture-led regeneration are creative city development strategies which necessitate that cities become trendy or bohemian places to attract a new creative class of residents. Creative city development strategies have been frequently linked to issues of gentrification, neoliberalism and inter-urban competition.

O'Callaghan (2010) argues that creative city narratives 'co-opt creativity into the status quo of neoliberal capitalism' (p.1607). Florida's (2004) creative class thesis hinges on the argument that the cities most endowed with the three t's (talent, tolerance and technology) will attract the coveted creative class, thereby gaining competitive advantage of other, presumably less creative, places (O'Callaghan, 2010). The rise of creative city development strategies has emerged precisely because of their compatibility with the neoliberal logic of interurban competition and place marketing. In doing so, Florida's thesis elides – or even risks celebrating – urban class inequality and gentrification performed under the guise of creative bohemia (Stevenson, 2004; O'Callaghan, 2010; Peck, 2005). As Slater (2006) argues, the image of the hip, bohemian, cool neighbourhoods with street-level spectacles, trendy bars and luxury coffee shops supersede the actually existing reality of working-class displacement, rent-increases and landlord harassment.

However, despite its popularity, the links between the creative city, neoliberalism and gentrification do not necessarily discredit culture-led regeneration per se. Oakley (2015: 2) argues that it is necessary to 'go beyond critiques of cultural regeneration, not to negate them but to build on them'. In doing so, a counter-narrative is possible, which can 'test the possibility of new narratives about the relationship between place and culture'. For Oakley (ibid), creative placemaking appears to harness the positive effects of culture at neighbourhood level 'without the harmful effects of gentrification' (p.8). However, Kovacs and Park (2021: 101) argue that while creative placemaking is 'almost always' framed in a 'positive light', familiar links to gentrification, and displacement still remain. Mould (2018) argues that, despite the progressive rhetoric associated with it, creative placemaking can be reduced to little more than state-imposed gentrification schemes performed under the rubric

of civility. There is, therefore, a plethora of critical literature that draws consistent links between culture-led regeneration, neoliberalism, gentrification and territorial stigma. However, this is typically done from a (neo)Marxist perspective, in which culture is instrumentalised to further the economic interests of the ruling class (Mould, 2018; Gray and Mooney, 2011; Eisinger, 2000). In this study, I utilise a Foucauldian methodology to construct a perspective on the debates discussed previously. Despite the enduring intellectual legacy of Foucault throughout the social sciences, academic debates about cultural regeneration and creative placemaking pay insufficient attention to Foucauldian theory. In the context of this study, a Foucauldian understanding of power/knowledge and discourse enables this study to understand the conditions of possibility through which discourses materialise. This study explores discourses of culture-led regeneration, cultural regeneration and creative placemaking in greater depth and, in doing so, sheds new light on the distinctions and tensions between different forms of culturally informed regeneration from a Foucauldian perspective.

1.4 Situating the researcher: maintaining criticality in an academic-industry partnership

Having situated Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration, it is important to situate my positionality as a researcher and the factors that have shaped the development of this study. This is important given the status of this research is a collaboratively funded studentship, and the subsequent involvement of the local authority, have clearly affected the direction of this study. Collaborative studentship awards through academic-industry partnerships have become an increasingly prominent PhD funding arrangement (see Edwards, 2018; Santos and Mari Thune, 2021; Malfroy, 2011). One potential pitfall of collaborative studentship awards is that the researcher is limited in determining the direction the research can take and that

the researcher can be beholden to stakeholder expectations (Malfroy, 2011). Additionally, there is also a risk that receiving funding from a stakeholder with a vested interest in the research can create a reticence to adopt a more critical stance (Edwards, 2018).

In the wake of Paisley's UKCoC bid in 2017, the University of the West of Scotland entered into a partnership with the local authority with the aim to form the Centre for Culture, Sport and Events (CCSE). The CCSE aims to 'provide a space to undertake collaborative research and development work that has relevance for the Renfrewshire area, nationally and internationally' (CCSE, n.d). In the context of Paisley, more specifically, the establishment of the CCSE has been integral to the evaluation of the UKCoC bid campaign, and broader research of cultural regeneration in Paisley. This project was established as a collaborative studentship that was designed to feed into the broader evaluation work currently ongoing within the CCSE. This research has, therefore, been collaboratively designed in partnership with key stakeholders from the local authority - specifically within the marketing and communications department, the CCSE steering group and the Future Paisley Partnership Board (FPPB). This studentship has been funded with the expectation of delivering a research project that explored the role of media and communication in changing perceptions of Paisley. It is clear, therefore, that the basis of this project was in place prior to my recruitment as a doctoral researcher. This invariably removes some degree of autonomy from the researcher, as it was inevitable that from the beginning of the project that I would have to forfeit some degree of control over it. That does not suggest, however, that this project was predetermined or that I have not been given license to develop this research beyond the initial brief. Rather, this raises the interconnected issues of independence, accountability, and access.

The collaborative nature of this project has an inevitable fetter on the independence of the researcher. This presents a challenge insofar as key stakeholders have maintained certain expectations, which could have influenced the development of the research. However, in recruiting a doctoral researcher as opposed to, for example, an external consultant or advisor to the local authority an important distinction can be made. The former denotes an independence that cannot be necessarily ascribed to the latter, insofar as a PhD thesis remains the work of an individual irrespective of funding arrangements. However, it is clear that the funder can still have an impact on the overall direction of the research. Explicitly, as discussed above, the input of stakeholders has been essential to initial formation of this project prior to my involvement. Implicitly, however, the power dynamic between stakeholders and the researcher could exert a pressure to conform to stakeholder expectations. This could, in turn, sacrifice the integrity of the research itself by, for example, creating a reticence to engage critically with material that potentially diverges from stakeholder expectations. This is, of course, predicated on the assumption that such relationships are inherently conflictual, and does not consider that collaborative research can exist for the benefit of both researcher and stakeholders. While it is important to acknowledge the potential pitfalls that emerge from this power dynamic, the presence of stakeholders and funders cannot be assumed to dominate or coerce by their mere existence. Edwards (2018), reflecting on her own academic-industry partnership, acknowledges that the relationship between funder and student need not be a battle of competing priorities, but can be a mutually beneficial relationship.

Accountability, in the context of this project, can be seen in the form of reporting to not only my immediate supervisory team, but also a number of external stakeholders such as the CCSE

steering group and the FPPB – the board that oversees the activities of Future Paisley discussed above. From early on in this project, I have been given the opportunity to present regular updates on my research progress to both the CCSE steering group and the FPPB. As above, this raises the potential issue of independence, insofar as continued monitoring by key stakeholders ensures that the project is in line with their expectations. However, this has also given me access to a pre-existing network of academics and practitioners with expert knowledge of the field. Far from being a fetter on the development of this project, the collaborative nature of this project has allowed access to a reservoir of existing knowledge that has informed, but by no means dictated, the direction of this research. This is demonstrated by the critical tone evident throughout this thesis.

Finally, the collaborative nature of this project has the undeniable advantage of allowing access to high-level participants, documents and insider knowledge that perhaps would not have been available under different circumstances. The specific details of how access to participants and data is, of course, laid out in further detail throughout chapter four. However, it is worthwhile to reflect on the relationship between collaborative research and access to undertake empirical work. Beyond simply being granted access to a group of participants, this project necessitated a level of embeddedness within both the CCSE, Future Paisley and the local authority more broadly. This can be seen not only in my aforementioned presence at key meetings such as the CCSE steering group and FPPB board meetings, but also, for example, in strategic events such as the ‘FPPB field trip’. The FPPB field trip was held in September 2019 and explored different approaches to regeneration, cultural development and social change by visiting sites in the east end of Glasgow, as well as meeting partners and stakeholders with the aim of informing the development of Renfrewshire’s cultural strategy.

Embeddedness within both CCSE and FPPB activities has enabled a reflective practice that supplements the data collection and literature review, by augmenting my understanding of the research area and context by enabling me to observe the tensions, debates and conversations that were driving the development of the bid legacy and broader cultural strategy in Paisley. In other words, I was able to become an outsider within.

Grounded in ethnographic research, the insider/outsider dichotomy broadly refers to the roles and relationships that are formed between researchers and participants (see Bucerius, 2013; Adler and Adler, 1987). For Bucerius (2013: 690) this denotes the level of integration of the researcher into the group/field setting based on 'participation in group activities, commitment to group values and norms and level of group affiliation'. While greater emphasis has traditionally been on achieving maximum integration into the group, thereby achieving 'insider' status, there is a growing emphasis of the role of the 'trusted outsider' with 'inside knowledge' who can contribute a different perspective (see Bucerius, 2013). While this research is not necessarily ethnographic, it is useful to reflect on my own interactions with key stakeholders, both within and out with my institutional setting.

Various markers create an obvious material distinction between myself and the broader CCSE networks. An obvious example of this is a significant age gap that makes achieving 'insider' status seem unlikely. As previous research indicates, being ascribed 'insider' status goes beyond shared values and is intrinsically linked to power and privilege (See Bucerius, 2013). In the context of this project, the obvious age gap combined with a critical engagement with the research area has created a distance between the researcher and key stakeholders. This has, however, been advantageous for the development of this project, by enabling the researcher to maintain a degree of independence, while being able to provide a perspective

that is tied to the broader CCSE/FPPB context but not necessarily within it. This, in turns, creates a mutual benefit for both researcher and stakeholders, in that I have been granted a high degree of both access and autonomy, as well as having access to shared knowledge and networks within the CCSE, while being able to deliver a project that is in line with stakeholder expectations. It is clear, therefore, that involvement of the CCSE and FPPB in this project has been beneficial for this project. By positioning myself as an ‘outsider within’, I have been able to work with but not within key organisations, which in turn has allowed this project to benefit from the existing knowledge and understanding of key stakeholders while maintaining a critical distance. With this in mind, attention can turn to the over-arching research aim and objectives that will guide this study.

1.5 Research aims and objectives

Having considered both the context of Paisley – as the site of this research – the development of cultural regeneration within the town and my own positionality, the aim of this thesis is to explore how discourses of cultural regeneration are formed and subsequently discussed in newspaper reporting of Paisley. The objectives of the study are to:

- i. Explore how Paisley’s decline and regeneration are represented in newspaper reporting between 2014-2020.
- ii. To understand the conditions of possibility that enable or constrain discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley.
- iii. Critically analyse how representations of Paisley reflect discursive shifts in cultural regeneration and the extent to which this reflects a changing relationship between culture, place and regeneration in Paisley.

In this thesis, I argue that the construction of cultural regeneration discourse in Paisley reflect the imperatives of culture-led regeneration and urban neoliberalism.

1.6 Chapter outlines

Chapter two provides one facet of the theoretical context for this thesis by exploring the emergence of neoliberalism, territorial stigma and the broader construction of area reputations. I explore the emergence of urban entrepreneurialism in local governance in which the local state has become increasingly focused on selling the city, developing a positive image for their destinations and opening up urban space for inward investment. Building on this, I explore the construction of territorial stigma. This is relevant insofar as the spatial taint of de-industrialisation connects closely with both the neoliberal imperative to manage area reputations and contemporary discourses of urban regeneration. Indeed, I emphasise the way in which the area-based focus of urban regeneration is, paradoxically, implicated in the (re)production of territorial stigma and the negative area reputation of socio-economically disadvantaged places.

In chapter three, I consider the emergence of culture-led regeneration, in which arts and cultural investment is leveraged in the regeneration of post-industrial cities. Specifically, this chapter offers a critique of creative city models of culture-led regeneration. This is achieved by contextualising the creative city within the literature on neoliberal urban development and gentrification. The chapter concludes by considering what a more equitable model for cultural regeneration might look like, offering two conclusions. Firstly, I argue that it is important to consider the role of local context, and resist viewing cultural regeneration as a monolith. This is particularly true of smaller towns and cities, unaffected by gentrification. Second, I conclude

that while there is evidence to suggest that bottom-up, small-scale cultural projects can have a positive impact on local communities, dominant neoliberal assumptions still prevail.

Chapter four takes the theoretical considerations sketched out in the preceding chapters and fashions them into a coherent methodological structure. More specifically, this chapter begins by outlining a methodological approach informed by the work of Michael Foucault and an understanding of power as *productive* as opposed to merely repressive. From this perspective, power is not merely a matter of what is said, but rather what *can be said*. Building on this, the chapter outlines a qualitative methodological approach, utilising various different forms of data: newspaper reporting, documentary data, semi-structured interviews and group workshops. Newspaper reporting of Paisley, as well as documentary data, is used to analyse official discourses of cultural regeneration within the town. Additionally, I also outline the use of semi-structured interviews with key decision makers and personnel involved in the UKCoC bid campaign and broader cultural regeneration programmes, as well as workshops with local residents, to understand how discourses of regeneration are produced and their impact on local place perceptions.

In chapter five I present the findings from the analysis of newspaper reporting on Paisley and cultural regeneration between 2014-2020. I outline the key narratives produced about Paisley and cultural regeneration during this time. In doing so, I demonstrate how newspaper representations of Paisley foreground issues of de-industrialisation, town centre decline and poverty to legitimise cultural regeneration strategies. Additionally, narratives of cultural regeneration foreground the international significance of Paisley's culture and heritage offer. In turn, this has been used to produce what I call the underdog narrative, which posits that Paisley, for a small town, has made a disproportionately large contribution to the world. The

underdog narrative posits that the significance of Paisley's cultural offer can be used to leverage (inter)national attention and change perceptions of the town. Finally, in this chapter I explore the similarity between the official discourse of regeneration as produced through documentary data and newspaper reporting.

In chapter six I present the findings from interviews with decision makers and key personnel and workshops held with local residents. In doing so, I explore how both Paisley's negative area reputation and discourses of cultural regeneration are produced and enacted in representations of the town. More specifically, I explore how Paisley's (negative) image and reputation is constructed by discourses of town centre decline, poverty and inequality, and a vision of Paisley as a potentially violent and dangerous place. Indeed, I argue that Paisley has been represented as a 'poster-boy' for post-industrial decline. In addition, I demonstrate how discourses of regeneration have been produced and legitimised both through engagement with broader professional networks within the local state, and through selective engagement with local residents.

Chapter seven analyses the findings presented in previous chapters. I discuss how discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley are implicated in broader discourses of neoliberalism, inter-urban competition and the post-industrial society. Additionally, this chapter uses Paisley as a case study to explore recent debates about culture-led regeneration and creative placemaking. I express the need for a degree of caution regarding claims that cultural regeneration is either an ad hoc reproduction of the creative city discourse and thus a by-word for gentrification (see Mould, 2018) or a radical departure from dominant strands of top-down regeneration (see Markusen, 2021). I outline the emergence of what I call

'hybridised placemaking' that reflects the hybridised nature of cultural regeneration in Paisley, which is neither a departure from, nor a continuation of, culture-led regeneration.

Chapter eight pulls together the arguments presented in this thesis into a clear conclusion. I outline the key findings from this research and outline the contribution to knowledge this thesis has made. I argue that Paisley is a town that is characterised by a poor area reputation that plays on imaginaries of post-industrial decline, poverty and inequality to justify cultural regeneration strategies. I outline the emergence of what I have called 'hybridised placemaking' wherein Paisley approach to cultural regeneration reflects *both* the more holistic language of cultural regeneration and creative placemaking, while the logic of culture-led regeneration persists, particularly with flagship cultural investment. I conclude by reflecting on areas for future research in light of the findings of this study.

1.7 Conclusion and contribution to knowledge

This introductory chapter has outlined the context through which this thesis has emerged. I have provided an introduction to Paisley, as well as the relevant developments in the town's approach to culture-led (and laterally cultural) regeneration. Building on this, I have situated this approach within the literature on culture-led regeneration, cultural regeneration, creative placemaking and area reputation. In doing so, I have acknowledged the recurrence of critiques which connect discourses of culture-led regeneration to urban neoliberalism, gentrification and inequality. The recent popularity of creative placemaking as something that might transcend the well-worn critiques of culture-led regeneration appears as a source of optimism for many. However, I have stressed the need for some degree of caution insofar as the familiar logic of inter-urban competition and the spectre of gentrification continue to haunt creative placemaking discussions.

While cultural regeneration, and more recently creative placemaking, are well-trodden paths of academic inquiry, there remain two significant gaps in current knowledge that I address in this thesis. First, culture-led regeneration and/or creative placemaking in smaller cities and towns remains an under-researched area. There have been some recent developments within the literature (see Richards and Diuf, 2019), there remains a clear lack of (critical) research on cultural regeneration in 'ordinary' places (Hopkins, 2019). In this regard, Paisley is an excellent case study for this research insofar as it is a peripheral town undergoing a process of cultural regeneration. There is a considerable literature on both the approaches taken under the banner of cultural regeneration (see Edwards, 2018) and the narratives projected to represent cultural regeneration strategies under the banner of place branding (see Garcia, 2005; Garcia et al., 2010; Richards and Diuf, 2019). However, there has been little research that explores production of discourses. In other words, current literature tells us *what* discourses of cultural regeneration are but does not tell us the conditions of possibility that enable or constrain the formation of these discourses.

This thesis makes a clear and substantial contribution to knowledge by addressing the gaps outlined in the previous paragraph. This thesis makes a contribution that enables a deeper understanding of how urban area reputation is constructed. Given the lack of research on Paisley and the town's reputation, understanding *how* the town's reputation is constructed is important in and of itself. I demonstrated that Paisley is a town characterised by a poor area reputation, with persistent ties to poverty, inequality, violence and town centre decline. In this sense, Paisley's reputation reflects both discourses of 'post-industrial decline' and 'territorial stigma'. Finally, I explore how discourse of decline is essential in legitimising cultural regeneration itself. With this in mind, I outline what I have called 'post-industrial

Paisley'. Post-industrial Paisley, as a discourse, foregrounds industrial decline, unemployment, inequality and changes to the retail sector. In turn, post-industrial Paisley invokes, or at the very least leans into, imaginaries of Paisley as a former industrial hub blighted by broader global processes. In doing so, post-industrial Paisley legitimises cultural regeneration by suggesting there is a need to rethink the traditional role of town centres.

Finally, this thesis contributes to broader debates about culture-led regeneration, creative placemaking and neoliberal urban development from a Foucauldian perspective by considering Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration. I outline the emergence of 'hybridised placemaking'. Hybridised placemaking reflects the messiness of placemaking insofar as processes of regeneration or placemaking do not develop or evolve harmoniously. Adapting Brenner and Theodore's (2002) concept of actually existing neoliberalism, I propose that hybridised placemaking accounts for the development and mutation of placemaking in conceptually impure, situated and varying ways. In Paisley discourses of cultural regeneration are hybridised insofar as they reflect *both* the more holistic language of cultural regeneration and creative placemaking merge with the logic of culture-led regeneration, economic transformation and flagship cultural investment. Hybridised placemaking, therefore, utilises a Foucauldian understanding of power/knowledge and discourse to explore the conditions of possibility through which discourses materialise. In doing so, I advance an analysis of hybridised placemaking that contributes to critical literature from outwith the (neo)Marxist orthodoxy that dominates.

Chapter 2: Neoliberalism, social pathology and constructing area reputations

2.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to provide the conceptual underpinning for this research. More specifically, in order to explore the construction of Paisley's image and reputation and discourses of cultural regeneration in subsequent chapters, it is necessary to first understand *how* area reputations are constructed. Additionally, area constructions are not coincidental nor politically neutral but rather mediated by broader political and economic forces (Schwarze, 2021; Wassenberg, 2004). From this perspective, *negative* area reputations can legitimise specific policy initiatives to leverage more *positive* newspaper reporting (Schwarze, 2021; Devereux et al., 2011). This chapter begins by situating this research within the emergence of neoliberalism as a 'hegemonic mode of discourse' (Harvey, 2006: 2), exploring how the city has become an increasingly important arena in the expansion of 'actually existing' neoliberalism (Brenner and Theodore, 2002). Building on this, I explore how the prominence of neoliberal ideas necessitate a renewed interest in the image and reputation of towns and cities by drawing on Harvey's (1989) concept of urban entrepreneurialism. Urban entrepreneurialism, for Harvey, emerges as the logic for managing the neoliberal state that places a greater emphasis on the production of urban spectacles and managing the image of places to leverage inward investment (ibid).

In the latter part of the chapter, I explore the construction of area reputations. More specifically, I discuss the role of newspaper reporting in constructing area reputations while situating such constructions within the emergent discourse of territorial stigma (Wacquant, 1993, 2008). Building on this, I explore the construction of territorial stigma through the policy responses to the perceived problems of urban decline via area-based urban regeneration

strategies. A common theme throughout this chapter is the extent to which urban regeneration policy, and Area Based Initiatives (ABIs) more specifically, relies on constructing places as problematic and thus in need of regeneration. In doing so, urban regeneration policy stigmatises local residents by reproducing dominant discourses of social pathology. When taken together, I advance the argument that discourses of territorial stigma and neoliberalism are central to the formation culture-led regeneration discourse in the UK.

2.2 Everywhere and nowhere: where and when does neoliberalism actually exist?

Despite the ubiquity of its use, there remains a great deal of debate and conceptual confusion when defining neoliberalism (see Castree, 2006; Brenner and Theodore, 2005; Peck, 2004; Peck et al, 2013; Venugopal, 2015). As Castree (2006) argues, what counts as neoliberalism, or how it might be defined, is not a matter of consensus amongst academics. However, it is clear that neoliberalism – however defined - marks a shift away from the Keynesian economics of the post-war period towards market-driven social and spatial transformations (Brenner and Theodore, 2005; Rice, 2009). Neoliberalism, as Harvey (2007) argues, has become a hegemonic mode of discourse that (re)shapes how we live in, view and interpret the world. Rooted in the intellectual tradition of scholars such as Milton Friedman and Friedrich Hayek, the neoliberal doctrine, in its purest form or ideal-type, champions individual liberty, deregulation, free markets and trade, private property rights and entrepreneurial freedoms (Boyle et al, 2008; Harvey, 2007; Hackworth and Moriah, 2006). The fruits of this intellectual labour came to fruition throughout the 1970s and 1980s with the rise of both Reaganism in the US, and Thatcherism in the UK, though it could be argued that a proto-neoliberalism could be seen prior to this throughout the developing world in places such as Chile (see Boyle et al, 2008; Fisher, 2009; Klein, 2007).

The implementation of the neoliberal project across the globe, however, has been far from a monolithic, unfettered implementation of pure, ideal-type neoliberalism. Rather, the neoliberalism is inherently localised, diverging and mutating in different actually existing, contextually specific forms (Brenner and Theodore, 2005; Peck et al, 2009). The lack of a clear, uniform implementation of the neoliberal doctrine, and the conceptual confusion this creates, has led critics to contend that neoliberalism has diminished in conceptual value (see Venugopal, 2015; McGuirk and Dowling, 2009; Mudge, 2008). As Venugopal (2015: 166) claims, 'neoliberalism is everywhere, but at the same time, nowhere'. Much of the conceptual critique of neoliberalism has centred on this omnipresent model of neoliberalism that does not account for the wide contextual variance and contradictory outcomes (Brenner and Theodore, 2002).

Hackworth and Moriah (2006) identify four interlinked strategies offered by sceptics to 'challenge the homogeneity and coherence of ideal-type neoliberalism' (p.512). First, neoliberalism is challenged on geographical grounds (i.e the local context). It is argued, here, that the economic structure, political culture and historical context determines the extent to which neoliberalism is actualised in policy form (see Brenner and Theodore, 2002; Wilson, 2004). Hackworth and Moriah (2006) argue that neoliberalism should be viewed as a locally contingent process rather than pure ideal type that simply lands in different localities.

The second challenge to ideal-type neoliberalism relates to the apparent paradox of state intervention within an ideology that, itself, decries it. Gough (2002), for example, points out that attempts to implement neoliberalism as a policy imperative necessitates *some* form of state intervention. This contradicts the ideological tenant of state minimalism, which is often central to the neoliberal ideology. This is summed up by Peck (2004: 51) who contends that:

While neoliberalism aspires to create a utopia of free markets, liberated from all forms of state interference, it has in practice entailed a dramatic intensification of coercive, disciplinary forms of state intervention in order to impose versions of market rule, and subsequently, to manage the consequences and contradictions of such marketization initiatives.

Fisher (2009) posits that whilst neoliberalism is frequently associated with anti-statist rhetoric, it is not opposed to state spending *per se* (see the bank bail outs in 2008, for example), but rather a specific forms of state spending – such as spending on public services and welfare services. It appears, therefore, that ‘ideal-type’ neoliberalism is an impossibility in that state intervention is perpetually required to actualise neoliberal policy despite the clear ideological contradiction.

The third main area of critique of ideal-type neoliberalism rests upon the persistent presence of other processes and ideologies (Hackworth and Moriah, 2006). One of the most vocal proponents of this perspective is Jessop (2002), who argues that viewing neoliberalism as an omnipresent force fundamentally fails to account for various other forces that exist in conjunction with neoliberalism. Focusing exclusively on neoliberalism, it is argued, ignores ‘actually existing’ hybridity and the importance of other ideologies (Brenner and Thodore, 2002; Jaffee, 2019).

McGuirk and Dowling (2009) posit that this can be seen upon closer examination of neoliberal development in Sydney, Australia and Masterplanned residential estates (MPRE). MPREs are a form of gated community development, which, like all gated developments, can be characterised by a secure perimeter (usually with walls or a fence), and singular secured entrance (Low, 2001, 2006). The development of gated (or ‘masterplanned’) residential

estates have been frequently associated with neoliberal urban development – with an increased focus on privatisation, extending private property rights and infusing market logics (see Low, 2006; Webster, 2002). Harvey (2019) argues that gated communities should be viewed as emblematic of the spatial representation of wealth and power within the city itself, in which cities become ‘fortified fragments’. Privatised and gated, the city becomes a playground of elite consumption. However, McGuirk and Dowling (2009) claim ‘MPREs cannot be simply interpreted as contingently rendered sites of urban neoliberalism’ (p.178). While, it is argued, neoliberal governance projects may be present, they cannot be assumed to dominate other competing and complex ideological forces that exist in any given context. Similarly, Grant and Rosen (2009) claim that the influence of global ideological forces (i.e neoliberalism) cannot be assumed to dictate local conditions on the ground. The extent to which the presence of other ideological forces represents a contradiction within neoliberalism itself is, however, questionable. As Hackworth and Moriah (2006) point out, the presence of non-neoliberal aspects of policies does not necessarily mitigate the influence of neoliberalism, and to assume this would be to (wrongly) assume that neoliberalism can only exist in a fully hegemonic form.

Finally, the fourth criticism of ideal-type neoliberalism posits that it has often been used to describe any processes loosely connected to liberalism or associated with any ‘right wing’ ideas (see Hackworth and Moriah, 2006; Wilson, 2004; Lerner, 2003). Gough (2002) shows, for example, that neoliberalism is frequently used to describe any form of business practice. The problem, here, is that this neglects to consider forms of business practice which do not conform to ideal-type neoliberal consensus. From this perspective, it would seem that neoliberalism is overly broad precisely because it cannot account for governing practices that

do not fit within a hegemonic neoliberal paradigm (Larner, 2003). Or, to return to the work of Venugopal (2016: 166), neoliberalism is at once both 'everywhere and nowhere'.

I argue that neoliberalism cannot be viewed as a meta-narrative of global economic and urban development. Neoliberalism always exists in a more than neoliberal context, in that neoliberal development happens in conjunction with other ideological forces (Peck, 2004; Brenner et al, 2004; Boyle et al, 2009). It does not converge around a singular archetype, but rather develops and mutates in situationally specific, often contradictory and divergent forms. On this basis, critics would argue that the conceptual value of neoliberalism has thus diminished (see Venugopal, 2016; McQuirk and Dowlinling, 2009). In this thesis, I acknowledge these criticisms and take seriously the need to examine the complex and contextually specific forms of neoliberal development. However, I do not accept the conclusion that neoliberalism has diminished in conceptual value and argue that there is value in persisting with the term. While the implementation of global neoliberalism is chaotic, uneven and divergent, there is virtually no place that can claim immunity from its influence (see Harvey, 2007; Wilson, 2004; Peck et al, 2004; Brenner and Theodore, 2002). Market forces seldom operate uninhibited by broader cultural, political and historical forces, however it does not necessarily follow that these forces offset the influence of global neoliberalism (see Rice, 2009; Brenner and Theodore, 2002; Klein, 2007). Neoliberalism is parasitic, attaching and living off other policies and ideological forces, which are not necessarily neoliberal. To illustrate this, it is useful to draw upon Brenner and Theodore's (2002) concept of 'actually existing' neoliberalism, which accounts for the *embeddedness* of neoliberal discourses within local, regional and national contexts. Actually existing neoliberalism is predicated upon three main components: path dependency, creative destruction and the city.

2.2.1 Path dependency

Gains et al (2005) argue that path dependency describes the choice being made when an institution is being formed, or a policy is being initiated, will continue to have a largely determining influence upon the future development of the institution or policy respectively. Simply put, decisions that can be made in the present are inhibited and influenced by the decisions that have been made in the past (Greener, 2005; Grube, 2016; Birch and Mykhenko, 2009). Given that, as discussed above, neoliberalism cannot be viewed as a meta-narrative of global development, it is useful to explore the influence of neoliberalism from a more situated, local perspective. Peck et al (2004) demonstrate that attempts to impose neoliberal policy reforms are likely to demonstrate strong properties of path dependency, in which established institutional arrangements hold significant influence in determining the scope and trajectory of reform. As such, pre- or non-neoliberal institutions must not be viewed as anachronistic, as their interpretation and interaction with neoliberal modes of economic restructuring will shape the pathways and outcomes in distinctive, divergent and contextually specific ways (Peck et al, 2004; Jessop, 2002).

Rice (2009) demonstrates the importance of path dependency within the emerging neoliberal urban development of Glasgow city centre, and the 'path' created by the broader economic and political climate of 'roll back' neoliberalism of the 1970s and 1980s under Margaret Thatcher's Conservative government. Evidence of Glasgow's path dependency can be seen by examining the continued shift away from manufacturing, as the service sector grew and became ever more integral to Glasgow's economy (see Livingstone and Clark, 2019; Tallon, 2013). Rice (2009) argues that the growth of the service economy (embodied in developments such as the Buchanan Galleries shopping centre) are not simply a 'mere continuation of

previous political decisions' (p.194), but rather part of a historically specific, ongoing process of market-driven socio-spatial transformation. Path dependency, then, is a useful way of understanding and accounting for the mutating, contradictory and contextually specific forms of neoliberal development. Understanding the path dependent nature of neoliberal development simultaneously rejects the omnipresent view of neoliberalism, whilst retaining the conceptual worth of the term itself.

2.2.2 Creative destruction

The second component of Brenner and Theodore's (2002) actually existing neoliberalism thesis is creative destruction. Creative destruction, as popularised by Schumpeter (1942), describes an essential fact about capitalism, in which the relentless search for profit dictates a constant renewal through the gale-like forces of the market that make way for the new at the expense of the old. Creative destruction is the process of industrial mutation which changes the economic structure from within while destroying the old and creating the new (Rice, 2009; Holgersen, 2014). Klein (2007) provides perhaps one of the most succinct articulations of this process, albeit without directly naming it. Klein draws on the metaphor of 'shock therapy' to illustrate the necessity of destruction in forging a new economic order (ibid). In relation to neoliberalism, creative destruction becomes a means of theorising the path dependent interaction between existing institutional forms and emergent neoliberal projects (see Brenner and Theodore, 2002; Peck and Tickell, 2002; Harvey, 2006; Weber, 2002). Indeed, Weber (2002: 525) argues that 'obsolescence has become a neoliberal alibi for creative destruction'. Peck et al (2004) posit that the dialectic of creation and destruction provides a framework for understanding the emergence of neoliberalism in that:

...the (partial) *destruction* of extant institutional arrangements and political compromises through market-orientated reform initiatives; and second the (tendential) *creation* of a new infrastructure for market-oriented economic growth, commodification and capital-centric rule (p.55, emphasis original)

This quotation illustrates the interplay between the destruction of previous institutional forms and the creation of a new infrastructure for capital accumulation that lies at the heart of path-dependent neoliberal restructuring. As Harvey (2019: 16) puts it, 'violence is required to achieve the new urban world on the wreckage of the old'. Neoliberal restructuring, then, combines the *rollback* of oppositional forms through the destruction of collectivist and redistributive economic intervention, as well as the *rollout* of new modes of (de)regulation for the institutional arrangements better suited to the new economic paradigm (Peck et al, 2004).

2.2.3 The neoliberal city

Brenner and Theodore (2002) contend that cities have a 'strategic role in the contemporary remaking of political-economic space' (p.349). Cities are increasingly entangled within a global-local disorder, in which most local governments are now constrained by broader economic forces, irrespective of both political orientation and national context (Peck and Tickell, 1995, 2002). Leitner and Sheppard (1998) posit that this, in turn, imposed powerful modes of fiscal control upon cities – the result of which is major budgetary cuts and 'the retrenchment of national welfare state regimes' (Brenner and Theodore, 2002: 367). In this context, cities (including peripheral suburban spaces) have become increasingly central to neoliberal urban development as the locus of neoliberal policy initiatives. Place marketing, enterprise and empowerment zones, local tax abatements, urban development corporations

and public private partnerships have become increasingly prominent within urban policy (see Brenner and Theodore, 2002; Leitner and Sheppard, 1998; Tallon, 2013; Stein, 2019). This does not suggest, however, that cities are simply localised arenas in which the hegemonic force of global neoliberalism unfold (see Harvey, 2007). Rather, the path-dependent development of urban space has been central to the reproduction, mutation and perpetual reconstruction of neoliberalism itself (Brenner and Theodore, 2002; Rice, 2008; Peck and Tickell, 1994). Smith (2002) demonstrates that, under these conditions, cities have become the incubators of neoliberal restructuring through which the dominance of neoliberalism is sustained, albeit in mutating and divergent forms.

Based on the Brenner and Theodore's (2002) conception of actually existing neoliberalism, it is important to resist reading neoliberalism as a metanarrative of global development, or as everywhere and nowhere (Venugopal, 2015). Instead, neoliberalism always exists in a more than neoliberal context. In this sense, neoliberalism is a divergent, dialectical and mutating process. The apparent contradictions and divergence within neoliberal discourses does not, therefore, render the concept of neoliberalism itself obsolete. Rather, it (re)focuses attention towards 'mapping and explaining the genesis, trajectories and path dependencies' of neoliberal experiments (Boyle et al, 2008; 314). Taking up this challenge, I now explore the trajectories of 'actually existing' neoliberal restructuring in the context of Paisley, and in discourses of cultural regeneration more generally. This is important, in the context of this thesis, as understanding the influence of neoliberal ideas is essential to understanding how discourses and representations of Paisley are constructed and *why* they are constructed in the way that they are. As I will demonstrate in both this chapter and chapter three, neoliberal

ideas are at the forefront of both the 'stigmatisation' of 'declining' urban places and in debates about culture-led regeneration.

2.3 The politics of (mis)representation: urban entrepreneurialism, area representation and territorial stigma

Cities are, then, strategically crucial geographical arenas for a variety of neoliberal initiatives (Brenner and Theodore, 2002). Given the focus of this research on discourses and representations of culture-led regeneration, it is important to understand how neoliberal ideas connect with the emerging importance attributed to image and reputation in the neoliberal epoch. This can be mostly clearly articulated by the concept of urban entrepreneurialism. Urban entrepreneurialism, broadly speaking, refers to the increasing importance of selling the city and opening up urban spaces for capital investment (See Harvey, 2019; Wood, 1998; MacLeod, 2002). Harvey (1989), for example, suggests that 'the city has to appear as an innovative, exciting, creative and safe place to live or visit, to play and consume in' (pg.9). Importantly, Harvey's analysis identified a 'shift of emphasis from the production of goods (most of which, like knives and forks, have a substantial lifetime) to the production of events (such as spectacles that have an almost instantaneous turnover time' (Harvey, 1990: 157). This is to say, therefore, that area reputation becomes increasingly important within the neoliberal paradigm. If Harvey's urban entrepreneurialism marked the beginning of the process of neoliberal urban restructuring in the 1980s, then it is necessary to return to actually existing neoliberalism to understand and track how neoliberal urban development has changed in recent years (Boyle et al, 2008). Brenner and Theodore (2002) posit that neoliberalism renders cities as the contingent site of national competitiveness. Boyle et al (2008: 314) posit that:

Neoliberalism has pushed cities to the forefront of the drive for national competitiveness. Whether it be in terms of filtering of national and regional programmes of state reform into specific cities, or reforms beginning and ending in the city itself, neoliberal thinking has become woven into the localities in different ways as a consequence of their unique social, cultural, economic, political and institutional histories

It is clear that the actually existing neoliberal logics of inter-urban competition and competitiveness have become incorporated into the broader management and government of the local state. From this perspective, managing the image and reputation of place takes on a greater significance for urban managers as cities need to manage their image to attract mobile capital and outside investment (Harvey, 1989; 2007). Miles (2020) contends that the city that emerges in the epoch of entrepreneurialism is an 'image-driven entity' with trickle-down effects (p.213). The encroachment of such image-driven urbanism is problematic inasmuch as it places too much onus on the city as a rhetorical entity (ibid). As a result, the marketing of a city has come to have significant social and political implications (ibid; see also Paddison, 1993). With this in mind, it is important to critically explore the construction of place reputation as a facet of the entrepreneurial imperatives of the neoliberal state. While the policy outcomes, in the form of culture-led regeneration, are discussed in chapter three, the remainder of this chapter is dedicated to exploring the socio-political constructions of area reputation. More specifically, I situate newspapers in producing negative area reputations, as well as the political functions of territorial stigma. From this perspective, negative area reputations are not an unfortunate by-product of urban decline. Rather, area representation and territorial stigma serve broader political functions in the neoliberal epoch.

This relates to the aims and objectives of this thesis in that it is necessary to frame discussion of decline and regeneration in Paisley within the broader literature on area representation and regeneration.

2.3.1 Constructing area reputations: newspapers and territorial stigma

Kearns et al (2013) argue that while all places have an identity, it is only places with a particularly negative image that gain a reputation. Compounding this, it is argued that once a negative area reputation is constructed, it can be difficult to unseat negative stereotypes about 'bad' areas (ibid; see also Avraham, 2004; Wassenberg, 2004). It follows, therefore, that a deeper examination of *how* area reputations are constructed and the role of media representation in mediating and perpetuating negative place representations. Media representation plays an instrumental role in the construction of external place images because it is the medium through which we become aware of events and places out with their immediate locality (see Kearns et al., 2013; Bradley, 2002). Bradley (2002: 38) argues that media representations of place becomes the constructed, objective and true reality of places we have not directly experienced:

Reality is constructed through shared, culturally specific, symbolic systems of visual and verbal communications and the media play a fundamental role in the construction of this reality, by selectively providing knowledge about the lives, landscapes and cultures of different social groups

From this perspective, media representations are essential to the construction of how a place is perceived externally by shaping what images are projected about it. In terms of local perceptions, Kearns et al (2013) argue that newspapers play a significant role in the (re)production of negative place images and area reputation. In local terms, it is argued that

local newspaper(s) reporting of a specific area has a tendency to (re)produce negative stereotypes about a place (ibid). More specifically, newspaper stories tend to play on local anxieties about crime and anti-social behaviour and in doing so, reinforce the problems which are faced by socio-economically disadvantaged areas (ibid; Schwarze, 2021).

It is important to resist viewing the negative construction of specific places through newspaper coverage as a mere by-product of an objective reality of socio-economically disadvantaged areas. Newspaper reporting is neither politically neutral nor detached or independent of the broader political economic forces (Devereux et al, 2011). As Schwarze (2021: 11) argues, 'newspapers are not autonomous and independent from influences within the socio-cultural and political environment in which they operate'. Rather, newspaper reporting needs to be placed within the broader political economy of stigma production (ibid). In sum, newspapers are implicated in the production of *discourse* and thus the construction of reality itself (Bradley, 2002; Schwarze, 2021). However, this does not mean that newspapers have an unfettered rein to construct whatever 'reality' or 'truths' they please. Indeed, *how* newspapers can report on area has predefined boundaries insofar as newspapers are not independent of the socio-political and political environment in which they operate (Schwarze, 2021; Devereux et al., 2011b). This connects with Foucault's (1978) insofar as it merits attention be paid to the conditions of possibility that enable or constrain the construction of certain discourses. As discussed in chapter four, this is reflected in the Foucauldian methodology adopted in this thesis, which positions power as *productive* and therefore essential in governing the subjectivity of elite discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley. In sum, while newspaper reporting is essential in the construction of area reputations, they do not do so from an omnipotent position. Newspapers are at once

implicated in yet influenced and constrained by the construction of dominant discourses and broader political economic forces.

The construction of negative area reputations closely resembles the emergent discourses of territorial stigma that have proliferated in recent decades (see, for example, Wacquant, 2009; Slater, 2014; Larsen and Delcia, 2019; Sisson, 2021; Cuny, 2019). Indeed, a myriad of studies have directly implicated newspaper reporting in the production of territorial stigma (see Schwarze, 2021; Wassenberg, 2004; Watt, 2020). Territorial stigmatisation, as originally advanced by Loic Wacquant (2008; 1993) had the somewhat broad aim of exploring ‘blemishes of place’. In less opaque terms, territorial stigma referred simply to the negative image and reputation of specific neighbourhoods. This negative image reinforces socio-spatial inequality, enforces a ‘symbolic dispossession’ of their inhabitants and ‘recasts them as urban outcasts while depriving them of their representation and identity’ (Wacquant, 1992 cited in Larsen and Delcia, 2019: 542). From this perspective, territorial stigma seeks to bridge the subjective individual experience(s) of stigma with broader socio-political production of stigma itself (Larsen and Delcia, 2019).

More recently, territorial stigma has come to occupy a more refined position within urban sociology and geography (Larsen and Delcia, 2019). In *Urban Outcasts*, Wacquant (2009) refines the concept, fusing his original thesis with Erving Goffman’s account of ‘stigma’ and the management of ‘spoiled identity’. More specifically, the concept of territorial stigma weds with:

Bourdieu’s theory of “symbolic power” Goffman’s model of the management of “spoiled identity” to capture the blemish of place impacts the residents of disparaged districts, the surrounding denizens and commercial operators, street-level public

bureaucracies, specialists in cultural production (such as journalists, scholars and politicians) and state officials and policies (Wacquant et al., 2014: 1270)

Through this expanded rubric, territorial stigma can be understood as the collective demoralisation of inhabitants of stigmatised places. Examples of 'stigmatised' neighbourhoods are varied including the Red Row housing estate in Glasgow, (Kearns et al., 2013), Molyross housing estate in Limerick (Haynes et al., 2011); and South Shore in Chicago (Schwarze, 2021).

It is important to explore the role of mass media representation more generally in the (re)production of territorial stigma insofar as this connects with the broader political project(s) of neoliberalism. Fisher (2021) demonstrates that stigmatising discourses are communicated through media portrayals of welfare dependence and disorderly behaviour in working-class communities, particularly in reality TV shows such as the now notorious UK Channel 4 show 'Benefits Street'. The show attracted criticism as a particularly egregious example of sensationalised discourse of 'welfare dependency' and 'dependency culture', which has proven pervasive in representations of working-class communities (see Tyler, 2015). Benefits Street reflects a growth in negative media representation of people experiencing poverty, and in particular the unemployed, disabled or those in receipt of benefits (Tyler, 2015; Paton et al, 2017; Crossley and Slater, 2014). More specifically, the programme reflects particular trends in media representation with the growth of reality TV that dramatizes the lives of benefit claimants to fit the familiar social pathologies of worklessness, laziness, dependency and personal irresponsibility (Paton et al, 2017). This emergent brand of what has been called poverty porn (ibid) fits neatly with the political discourse that produces territorial stigma.

Crossley and Slater (2014) suggest that negative media representations of deprived areas can simultaneously produce, leverage and activate territorial stigma for political capital. For Crossley and Slater (ibid: 4), the production of negative media representation is itself political:

The effect of this collusion between politicians, think-tanks and journalists and the validation and legitimacy that they offer each other via one-sided interpretations of social issues, allows politicians to “procure consent for a political backlash against Britain’s poor”

From this perspective, territorial stigma is something that is done *to* a community from above, serving an explicitly political end. Mass media representations of stigmatised areas operates on a top-down, outside standpoint which (re)produces narratives of place (Larsen and Delcia, 2019). From this perspective, residents lose control over their own representation, in the sense that they are spoken *about* and rarely given a platform to respond or challenge dominant narrative constructions of place (Larsen and Delcia, 2019; Wacquant et al., 2014). Considerably less is known, however, about the process involved in the (re)production of stigma *within* local communities (Larsen and Delica, 2019; Kearns et al., 2013). Sisson (2021) argues that the production of territory and space, consisting of both *practices* and *representations*, is the central site through which stigma is produced but also resisted. More specifically, for Sisson:

The active politico-institutional production of territory is naturalised by such representations; it is made to appear pregiven or innate (and thus, in the case of territorial stigma, innately pathological) (p.660)

Sisson (2021) argues that territory can also be the site of grassroots resistance, whereby territorial stigma is an active, antagonistic process which is produced *from above* but can be resisted *from below*. What this account elides, however, is the extent to which local communities (who produce discourse *from below*) might become participants in the production of stigma itself. From this perspective, local perceptions of place become implicated in the production of stigma. Garbin and Millington (2012) argue that the problem with 'representational' strategies for managing territorial stigma is that they tend to reproduce the stigmatising constructions of place from which they are trying to escape. Cuny (2019) argues that these tactics enacted to resist territorial stigma operate within a space defined by the dominant representations of place. With this in mind, resisting stigma *from below* may be able to adjust the dominant representation of their place, but never appropriate them nor the power relations which shape them (ibid).

Limited research suggests that local residents' internal perceptions of place tend to be more positive than external perceptions (Kearns et al, 2013). This is, on first reading, unsurprising given that local lived experience and positive attachments to place can, to some extent, offset negative representations of an area. What this elides, however, is a more nuanced account of the relationship between the internalisation of territorial stigma and negative newspaper representation. However, there is a need to explore the link between discourses of territorial stigma, media representations of socio-economically disadvantaged areas and local receptions in more depth. In doing so, it is possible to explore how local residents become participants in the (re)production of negative place representations, and that stigmatising area representations cannot be undone with a simple discursive rebrand. Simply leveraging

more positive representations of place may not, in and of itself, deconstruct negative place reputations.

2.3.2 Urban policy and the production of stigma: urban regeneration and territorial stigma in the UK

The process and production of territorial stigma does not sit outwith broader discourses of urban regeneration and neoliberalism. Cuny (2019) argues that territorial stigma and urban marginalisation are the outcomes of symbolic power through which elites justify their own interests through the defamation of others' places. Territorial stigma, therefore, as a theoretical standpoint 'endows images with performative power' (ibid: 888). Schwarze (2021) argues that territorial stigma 'provides the groundwork and justification for urban redevelopment' (p.16). It follows, then, that an examination of the link between territorial stigma, image and urban regeneration is needed.

Larsen and Delcia (2019) contend that the expanding frontiers of territorial stigma directly implicate 'processes of gentrification and destructive urban renewal' (p.540), highlighting a close link to the discourse and practice of urban regeneration. Wacquant et al (2014) argue that the 'spatial taint' of territorial stigma connects directly with processes of de-industrialisation and the triumph of neoliberalism over Fordist-Keynesian production. Moreover, Sisson (2021) demonstrates that the emergent scholarly works on territorial stigma have increasingly articulated its centrality to neoliberal urban restructuring. For Wacquant, territorial stigma is central to the (re)production of the neoliberal regime of advanced marginality in the Global North which is characterised as the *spatial concentration* of 'destitution', ethnonational division and public violence (ibid). Crucially, this is a direct result of the dismantling of the social democratic welfare state, the fragmentation of wage

labour and the emergence of an increasingly punitive welfare state. Tyler (2020) contends that territorial stigma reproduces social hierarchies in a capitalist society via the expropriation of stigmatised places. In sum, territorial stigma is not an accidental (mis)representation of socio-economically disadvantaged places, but rather interacts with, and is produced by, broader processes of urban decline in tandem with political responses to de-industrialisation and urban marginality (Wacquant, 2008). Schwarze (2021) illustrates that there is a plethora of research that explores the relationship between territorial stigma, gentrification and the legitimisation of urban regeneration policies that displace local residents. It follows, therefore, that it is necessary to have a more detailed discussion of *how* specific urban policies contribute to the production of stigmatising area reputations.

Area-based initiatives (ABI's) have been at the forefront of urban regeneration policy in the UK over forty years (Muscat, 2010; Tallon, 2013). ABI's refer, broadly, to specific, time-limited interventions in particular pockets of urban deprivation designed to address particular issues within a locality (Lawless, 2006; Tallon, 2013). Examples of ABI's range from the 'New Deal for Communities' (NDFC) launched by the UK New Labour government in 1998 (see Lawless, 2006) or much earlier iterations such as the Community Development Projects (CDP) in the 1970s (see Tallon, 2013). To return to Paisley, the Ferguslie Park area of the town has been the target for a number of area-based interventions, beginning with the original iteration of CDP's in the 1970s, as well as Scotland-specific policies such as the New Life for Urban Scotland (NLUS) which ran between 1986 and 1999 (see Tarling et al, 1999; Crow et al., 2018).

In specifically selecting 'problem' communities that need to be 'fixed', ABI's run the risk of contributing to the production of territorial stigma (Tallon, 2013). Larsen and Delcia (2019) identify ABI's as a distinct modality of territorial stigma by highlighting the very issues they

have sought to address, thus highlighting the places themselves as 'problem areas'. In addition to this, even successful ABIs may not be necessary to reverse or combat territorial stigma (ibid). As Larsen and Delcia (2019) contend:

...the symbolic valorisation of physical space is not something which can be changed through simple discursive manipulation such as rebranding an area or changing its name. That is because the symbolic valorisation of space develops over a long time and takes considerable energy and resources to change or transform (p.549)

Processes of urban regeneration, specifically ABIs, cannot be easily decoupled from the production of territorial stigma. This, on the surface at least, presents a paradox insofar as policy and projects aimed at ameliorating processes of decline and urban inequality are implicated in a broader process which stigmatises the places they are designed to help. The paradox of urban regeneration in the production of stigma is less puzzling when deeper attention is paid to the ideological assumptions and discourses implicit within urban regeneration policy.

Urban regeneration policy, more specifically ABIs, run the risk of advancing a social pathology model of regeneration in which poverty and structural inequality are understood as the failure of the individual (Handcock and Mooney, 2012; Welshman, 2013). While there are parallels between the individualistic assumptions of neoliberal ideologies and social pathological responses to urban decline, discourses of social pathology are not a recent intervention. Welshman (2013) demonstrates that varied iterations of the 'underclass thesis' date back to the Victorian period. Nonetheless, in a more contemporary context, the underclass thesis connects closely with Slater's (2014) argument that:

...a familiar litany of social pathologies (family breakdown, worklessness, antisocial behaviour, personal responsibility, out-of-wedlock children, dependency) is repeatedly invoked by the architects of welfare reform to manufacture ignorance of alternative ways of addressing poverty and social injustice (p.948)

For Slater (2014), social pathology is reflected in the myth of 'broken Britain' – a term coined by former UK Prime Minister David Cameron - whereby narratives of social pathology and moral decay are invoked to strategically ignore the structural causes of poverty. Similarly, for Hancock and Mooney (2012), this myth of broken society is spatial insofar as areas constructed as deprived, in particular social housing estates, are represented as problematic.

As Larsen and Delica (2019) argue, territorial stigma cannot be read simply as a natural response to the wicked problems of socio-economic inequality and poverty. Rather, territorial stigma has become increasingly central to the logic of neoliberal urban governance and contemporary regeneration inasmuch as it legitimises radical policy measures such as demolition, privatisation and gentrification of stigmatised territories (ibid). It refracts dominant assumptions of neoliberalism with a greater emphasis on individual responsibility and fiscal austerity. The construction of stigma is not an accidental by-product of poverty and inequality. Rather, the stigmatisation of deprived areas connects with urban regeneration policy that targets specific areas, and in broader political discourses of welfare ghettos and social policy more generally. From this perspective, the stigmatisation of deprived areas is constructed around discourses of moral decay and personal (ir)responsibility. This is unsurprising given the proliferation of scholarship that draws explicit links between (negative) media reporting and the stigmatisation of specific spaces (see, for example, Kearns et al., 2012; Devereux et al., 2011; Liu and Blomley, 2013). As Power, Haynes and Devereux (2021)

argue, media framings have transformed disadvantaged areas from symptoms of inequality to causes. In sum, territorial stigma plays a central political role of (re)enforcing discourses of moral decay and urban decline that legitimise the implementation of neoliberal policy initiatives. In addition to this, however, the ‘blemish’ of place associated with stigmatised areas also legitimises attempts to leverage more positive representations of place aimed at transforming negative area reputations. More specifically, this legitimises culture-led interventions in place, which are often sold on their ability to transform the image and reputation of place (see Garcia, 2005; Richards and Wilson, 2006; Richards and Diuf, 2019).

2.4 Conclusion

Given the research objectives to explore how both decline and regeneration is represented in Paisley, and how discourse of cultural regeneration is produced, it is essential to understand the role of dominant political and economic discourses in shaping debates about towns and cities, and their representation. In this chapter, I have provided an overview of neoliberalism as a dominant political economic force. I have shown that, despite criticism as to its opacity, neoliberalism continues to shape the logic for managing the local state and, consequently, the management and construction of area and reputation. More specifically, I have shown that by drawing on Brenner and Theodore’s concept of ‘actually existing’ neoliberalism, we can account for the situated, contingent and context-specific nature of neoliberalism. While neoliberalism always exists at a more-than-neoliberal local level, this does not in itself discount the impact and influence of neoliberal ideas.

Building on this, I have also situated newspapers, and the mass media more generally, in the construction of area reputation, and in the broader construction of the ‘reality’ of places outwith our direct experience. I have located this within the concept of territorial stigma as

identified by Wacquant. Territorial stigma, as a concept, connects with the political and economic force of neoliberalism and urban regeneration by constructing areas as 'in need' of regeneration and redevelopment. However, this creates a paradox insofar as policies constructed to respond to the perceived problems of urban decline can reinforce and reproduce the stigma they attempt to alleviate. The production of territorial stigma is not a mere by-product of an objective 'reality' of 'deprived' places. Rather, territorial stigma is implicated in broader discourse of neoliberalism and urban entrepreneurialism. With this in mind, attention now turns to culture-led regeneration as a specific form of urban regeneration policy promoted for its perceived ability to transform the area reputation of towns and cities.

Chapter 3: Creative cities or creative destruction: culture, capital(ism) and cultural regeneration

3.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to explore debates about culture-led regeneration, and the role it plays in contemporary regeneration discourse. This is important insofar as the research aims and objectives are concerned. Indeed, it is important to understand debates about culture-led regeneration and creative placemaking to allow this research to explore discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley. In some circles, it is almost taken for granted that culture and creativity are to be the vanguard of urban renewal. Authors such as Richard Florida (2004, 2018) and Charles Landry (2000) have been particularly vocal in depicting a cultural panacea. For Florida (2004), the key to urban success is to attract and retain creative talent with trendy, bohemian neighbourhoods and place distinguishing urban lifestyles. Urban policymakers have enthusiastically heard this creative imperative and sought to align themselves with the emerging creativity mantra. This is summarised by Miles and Paddison (2005) who suggest that it is remarkable to note not only the speed at which culture has been incorporated into government and local development strategies to bolster urban economies, but also the extent to which this process has gone global. In the past two decades, culture has become a central component of urban regeneration strategies of cities old and new as they seek to revive former industrial sites, waterfront locations and city centres and gain an advantage in an increasingly competitive global economic landscape (Miles, 2020; Wise and Clark, 2017; Evans, 2005; Campbell, 2013).

There is, however, a substantial body of academic critique of culture-led regeneration strategies (see Oakley, 2015; Boren and Young, 2013; Peck, 2005; Mooney, 2004). Peck (2005)

posits that the creative imperative in urban policy operates under the neoliberal rubric of inter-urban competition and place marketing. As Peck (2005: 760) contends, '(the) neo-liberalised urban environment is, in fact, the backdrop of creative city development strategies'. From gentrification to uneven economic development, there are clear pitfalls from a regeneration agenda with increased economic competitiveness at its heart. From this perspective, the modus operandi of culture-led urban transformation has become ubiquitous within urban policy precisely because of its compatibility with the broader neoliberal paradigm of marketization and inter-urban competition (Mould, 2018; Peck, 2005; Zimmerman, 2008). It cannot be assumed, however, that the well-worn critiques of culture-led regeneration apply to every policy interaction between culture, place and regeneration. While, as Oakley (2015: 2) argues, critiques of culture-led regeneration are 'manifold and persuasive', it is important to go beyond critiques of culture-led regeneration. For Oakley (ibid), creative placemaking appears a promising vehicle for developing a more equitable relationship between culture and place by harnessing the positive effects of culture without the harmful effects of gentrification.

In this chapter, I explore debates about culture-led regeneration, creative placemaking and urban neoliberalism. I begin by exploring the creative city concept, mapping its emergence as a dominant force in urban policy and culture-led regeneration. I demonstrate the way in which both gentrification and creative city development strategies sit within the broader neoliberal paradigm of increased inter-urban competition, uneven geographical development and increased marketization. Building on this, I discuss other forms (or models) of culture-led and cultural regeneration. I discuss the role of flagship cultural projects, as well as bidding for and hosting events and festivals, in contemporary debates about culture-led regeneration

and the creative city. I conclude the chapter by discussing creative placemaking as a 'more holistic' vision of culture led regeneration (Oakley, 2015). More specifically, I discuss the emergent field of placemaking studies (Wilson, 2021) and the (im)possibility of breaking the link between culture, regeneration and neoliberal urban development via creative placemaking.

3.2 (Creative) Class struggle and the city: culture-led regeneration and neoliberal development

Much has been written about the creative city since the term was first popularised in the later years of the 1980s (see, for example, Landry, 2000; Florida, 2004, 2018; Bianchini and Parkinson, 1993; Amin and Thrift, 2002; Baris, 2003). In the years that have followed, the creative city mantra has proven to be a hugely seductive one for civic leaders around the world (Peck, 2005). Peck (2005) argues that Richard Florida's book *The Rise of the Creative Class* has been both an international best seller and a public-policy phenomenon. Since the book's initial publication in 2002, Florida's influence within the urban policy area has been enduring. Not only does he continue to share stages with civic leaders globally, but his creative credo has reverberated outward as far as Dublin, Singapore and London to name but a few (see Peck, 2005; Wainwright, 2017).

For Florida (2004), culture and creativity hold the key to urban economic growth in deindustrialising areas. He summarises the central premise in his most recent book *The New Urban Crisis* (Florida, 2018) arguing that the key to urban success is to attract and retain creative talent – the creative class. Furthermore, Florida also posits that cities with a high concentration of the creative class have also demonstrated strong economic development in the creative industries – anything from high technology, to arts and cultural workers (Florida,

2004; Kratke, 2010). Bayliss (2006) argues that, in addition to providing employment and generating income, the creative class can also provide the catalyst for the revitalisation and regeneration of run down inner city areas. Urban policymakers, then, should seek to attract the creative class with trendy, hip and bohemian neighbourhoods that embrace Florida's three t's of economic development (talent, technology and tolerance). Indeed, Florida argues that the war for creative talent can only be won by developing the sort of people climate valued by his much-fetishized creative class by creating open, diverse and cool urban environments (Florida, 2004: 27).

As Oakley (2015) argues, there is a growing consensus that policy in most parts of the world is moving in the same direction, and many of the problems associated with culture-led regeneration in a UK or US context are mirrored elsewhere. As Aspen (2013) contends, this reflects the emergence of a zombie urbanism in which discourses of culture-led or creative cities continue to flourish despite their increasing ontological inaccuracy. Cities, large and small, continue to adopt creative city development strategies irrespective of whether or not they work, or the cities adopting them have the sufficient cultural infrastructure (Oakley, 2015). Zimmerman (2008) argues that Florida's ideas have become assimilated into the infrastructure of urban entrepreneurialism in the US. Atkinson and Easthope (2009), writing in the Australian context, argue that creative city development strategies have become institutionalised common-sense insofar as Floridian assumptions about culture and economic development infiltrate urban (re)development strategies which do not explicitly fit under the umbrella of the creative city mantra.

Critique of Florida's model of urban development, therefore, is abundant, persuasive and comes from a variety of ideological perspectives (see Peck, 2005; Kratke, 2010; Mould, 2018;

Malanga, 2004; Stevenson, 2004). Such widespread criticism is something that Florida (2018) himself acknowledges in the preface of *The New Urban Crisis*. Indeed, some interpret the book itself (wrongly) as somewhat of a *mea culpa*, or at least a response to the intense criticism that has been levied at Florida (see Wilson, 2019). Conservative scholars such as Malanga (2004) have argued that the notion that cities must become trendy, happening places has become the imperative of what he believes to be leftish policy-makers and urban planners rushing to implement Florida's vision. For Malanga (2004), the notion that Florida's policy prescription requires state-intervention forms a substantial body of his critique. Malanga posits that the creative class thesis is tantamount to 'aggressive, government directed economic development (albeit with a new age spin)' (np). There is an astute observation, here, that the appeal of the creative class thesis within urban policy is precisely its compatibility within the existing political paradigm. However, the problem here is not one of state intervention *per se*, but rather the necessity of state intervention to actualise neoliberal policy initiatives that have crystallised around creativity as discussed below. Nonetheless, Malanga's critique of the creative class touches on the key contestation of conservative criticisms of Floridian thought – the bohemian effect in which economic growth and urban development directly correlate with how bohemian a neighbourhood is perceived to be. Glaeser (2004) finds little to no evidence of the bohemian effect within the data Florida presents. Rather, the urban economic growth that Florida observed could be explained through human capital endowments (as well as a tech bubble) without the need for hip and bohemian lifestyles. Critics from the political right do not have an issue with the economic logic of Florida's ideas but are more concerned by the veil of social progressivism that it is performed under in the creative city model. Peck (2005) succinctly points out that critics are

more concerned by cultural politics and eccentric *economists* as opposed to eccentric *economics*.

From the left, critics have drawn parallels between Florida's thesis and the logic of neoliberalism and inter-urban competition. Peck (2005) argues that neoliberalism is the backdrop to the creative city discourse. Indeed, Florida's thesis hinges upon the argument that the cities most endowed with the three t's to attract the coveted creative class. In doing so, they will gain competitive advantage over other, presumably less creative, places (O'Callaghan, 2010). Creative city development strategies have, therefore, emerged precisely because of their compatibility with the neoliberal logic of interurban competition and place marketing. The emergence of the creative city is, therefore, fundamentally an exercise in entrepreneurial urban governance (Harvey, 2019; Peck, 2005; O'Callaghan, 2010).

The *Rise of the Creative Class* has also attracted criticism for its neglect of the intra-urban inequality associated with neoliberal urban development. Leslie and Canungal (2012), for example, have argued that the popularity of the creative city concept with urban policy makers has at best perpetuated, and at worst exacerbated, urban class inequality. Indeed, there is little regard in Florida's work for those who find themselves outside of Florida's creative class. As Peck (2005) shows:

There is little regard for those who are on the thin end of Florida's 'thick labor markets', beyond the forlorn hope that, one day, they too might be lifted – presumably acts of sheer creative will – into the new overclass" (p.746)

Of course, the problem with Florida's conception of work is not limited to those out with his much-fetishized creative class. Even a cursory look at Florida's work reveals that much of the

text reads as a jovial celebration of the post-Fordist working arrangements of the 'gig economy' (see Morgan and Nelligan, 2018; Mould, 2018; Johnston and Kazlauskas, 2018). *The Rise of the Creative Class* simultaneously fetishizes and naturalises the contracted out, freelance economy concomitant with creative work. As Peck (2005) argues, an increasing economy of under labourers may well be a necessary side effect of Florida's lust for 24/7 engagement and designer coffee. Further, Baris (2003) demonstrates that this jovial interpretation of the creative class fundamentally fails to consider the potential downside of the unrestrained workforce and lifestyle he is celebrating, with little regard for the division of labour within this idealised no-collar workplace and flexibilizing economy. Donegan and Lowe (2008) demonstrate, for example, how Florida's thesis invariably exacerbates income inequality by design, not distortion. Indeed, the internal logic of creative city thesis posits that the new creative economy of post-industrial capitalism, predicated on catering to the consumption preferences of the creative class, increases demand for service sector employment. This is, of course, not a new phenomenon. Sassen (1990, 1991) notes that the influx of high-income professionals into cities is accompanied by a rapid increase in demand for 'low-end, low-paying service sector jobs. As Peck (2005) acknowledges, someone must launder the shirts in the creative utopia.

In geographical terms, the creative class thesis has also been linked with reinforcing existing spatial inequalities and stimulating gentrification (see Mould, 2018; Oakley, 2015; Peck, 2000). Stevenson (2004) shows that 'Florida's formula for measuring and developing the "creative class" as the basis of city re-imagining and cultural industry development clearly has a middle-class bias, and can be read as a prescription for gentrification and displacement' (p.122). This is unsurprising given the spatial and economic dimensions of Florida's thesis are predicated

upon the clustering of the creative class, often in formerly disinvested areas (See Florida, 2004, 2004b, 2017). Even a charitable reading of Florida's thesis would struggle to deny that creative migration, attracting external creativity, creates the problem of gentrification wherein the emerging creative class displace the pre-existing communities (Richards and Wilson, 2006; Waitt and Gibson, 2008). A deeper exploration gentrification is therefore needed.

3.3 The creative city and gentrification

Gentrification is a term first used by sociologist Ruth Glass in her book on urban change in London. First published in 1964, Glass describes gentrification as the process through which traditionally working class areas are invaded by the middle classes. More specifically, Glass was concerned about what she perceived to be the accelerating rehabilitation of Victorian lodging, a shift from renting towards property ownership and the subsequent price increases that led to the displacement of the working-class occupiers by middle class incomers (Slater, 2011). In the decades that have followed, the term has generated a vast international literature, so large it renders the task of precisely summarising and critically engaging with the term a considerable challenge (see Slater, 2011; Lees et al, 2010). On the one hand, there are those who suggest that gentrification should be understood in terms of the original definition presented by Glass – in which gentrification is understood in terms of the rehabilitation of decaying houses for middle-class occupiers (see Boddy, 2007). On the other hand, it is argued that gentrification refers to more large-scale reconstruction of urban space for middle-class consumption (Davidson and Lees, 2005).

One point of consensus is that gentrification today is very different from gentrification in the 1950s and 1960s (Lees, 2000; Lees et al, 2007). If nothing else, the sheer geographical scale

of gentrification renders the process itself almost an entirely different phenomenon from that which Ruth Glass observed in the 1960s (Lees et al, 2007; Slater, 2011). Indeed, as Smith (2011) remarked, 'the extraordinary thing about gentrification at the end of the first decade of the twenty-first century is its ubiquity' (p.15). Hackworth and Smith's (2001) paper 'The Changing State of Gentrification' remains one of the most prominent pieces of scholarship on the evolution of the process of gentrification. From this perspective, the increasingly pervasive nature of state-facilitated class transformation in New York reveals a compelling account of three distinctive waves of gentrification (Hackworth and Smith, 2001, Wyly, 2018). As Oakley (2015) sums up, Hackworth and Smith's thesis accounts for the way in which each wave of gentrification was ended by major recession and retreat of capital, which in turn creates the conditions for the next wave of capital investment. Gentrification is, then, a manifestation of the creative destruction required to sustain the capitalist growth imperative. Oakley (2015) echoes this perspective, positing that gentrification research has widened its remit from a concentration on housing, to consider commercial gentrification with a broader consideration for the role of consumption and capital within the process itself. Similarly, Shaw (2008) provides a particularly helpful overview of the modern state of play of gentrification when she calls it 'a generalised middle-class restructuring of place, encompassing the entire transformation from low-status neighbourhoods to upper-middle-class playgrounds' (p.2). With this in mind, Shaw (2008) explains that gentrification can no longer be understood simply as the redevelopment of run-down estates. Gentrifiers live, also, in new build luxury developments. They work in new downtown or dockland warehouse conversions. They shop in newly constructed shopping malls, and in small-scale boutiques. They socialise in trendy bars, coffee shops and art-galleries. From this perspective, gentrification is not simply about

housing, but the wholesale reconstruction of space remade in the image of the middle-class (see Zukin, 2011; Shaw, 2008; Smith, 1996; Smith and Williams, 1986). This creates space to acknowledge the role of culture in gentrification insofar as it is the image of hip, trendy neighbourhoods become the aesthetic of the gentrifying city (Slater, 2006).

Gentrification has become increasingly linked to arts and culture led urban redevelopment (Oakley, 2015; Bell and Oakley, 2014; Pritchard, 2016). There is a substantial body of work that builds upon the work of Bourdieu, particularly his explanations of the middle-class habitus (Slater, 2011). Bourdieu (1984), in his now classic book *Distinction*, argues that particular notions of taste, culture and aesthetic preference serve as a mechanism through which class distinction can be constructed, and privilege can be safeguarded. Bourdieu (ibid) argues that preferences in cultural consumption are dictated not by the innate superiority of one form of artistic expression over another – high art versus low art, for example. Rather, cultural consumption serves as a way to distinguish one class group from another. Podmore (1998), building on this, has argued that gentrification is nothing short of the spatial representation of class distinction and the middle-class habitus.

Zukin (1989) outlines the development of the loft identity, a process through which former industrial loft spaces are rehabilitated, and transformed into apartments for incoming wealthy occupiers, as well as a general influx of art galleries and studio spaces within former manufacturing areas. Important, here, is Zukin's concept of the artistic mode of production, which refers to the way in which major real estate interests have tried to use artists and culture to attract capital through middle class cultural consumption. Indeed, for Zukin:

...(artists) embody a switch in orientation from an industrial political economy to one that is dominated by the service sector. As both the site and symbol, the artists loft

serves a purpose in a world city of a new type: the capital of banking, finance, and art markets. In this sense it is not surprising that that declining manufacturing centres like New York have hailed artists as an industry (ibid: 112)

For Zukin, then, the artistic mode of production embodies the shift from manufacturing toward an economy based upon the consumption of artistic lifestyles. In this sense, the reconstruction of the city in the image of the middle class habitus is an inherently economic process. As Stein (2019) demonstrates, the modus operandi of capitalist development is to produce value through space. Therefore, it is no accident that the redevelopment of space through arts and culture for middle class consumption increases land values, as well as rent and living costs (see, for example, Stein, 2019; Smith, 1996; Ley, 1996; Cameron and Coaffee, 2005). Grodach et al (2016) argue that the cultural capital of artists and cultural producers is exploited to serve the interests of capital, by way of generating development and catering to the consumption preferences of incoming middle-class residents. As Neil Smith noted, 'for the real estate industry, art tamed the neighbourhood, refracting back a mock pretence of exotic but benign danger' (1996:19). Harvey (2019) posits that arts and culture are inextricable from the broader processes of capital accumulation and commodification simply because they also have other social, aesthetic and cultural values. As such, Harvey (2019) demonstrates how art is used to increase land values and to extract monopoly rents. That is to say, therefore, that culture is appropriated by capital and used a vessel for the inflation of land values, property costs and rent by exploiting local differences, cultural variations and aesthetics of place. Through this lens, culture and consumption are inextricable from the broader processes of capital accumulation.

Gentrification connects Florida's vision of creative utopias filled with hip coffee shops and trendy boutiques. It is clear that the spectre of gentrification is central to the logic of both urban neoliberalism and creative city development strategies (O'Callaghan, 2010; Peck, 2005). Florida's vision of the creative city has through its sheer ubiquity altered how culture-led regeneration is perceived in both the popular and governmental psyche. As Slater (2006) argues, the *image* of the hip, bohemian, cool neighbourhoods with street-level spectacles, trendy bars and luxury coffee supersedes the actually existing reality of working-class displacement and rent increases. Gentrification is no longer, as Smith (1996) observed, a dirty word, but rather a sign of healthy economic present and future for cities (Tickell and Peck, 2003).

In this sense, gentrification has itself become gentrified (Slater, 2006). Critiques of creative city development strategies raise important questions as to the scope and aims of culture-led initiatives. In short, it invites investigation as to *who* and *what* culture-led interventions aim to change. Despite the rhetoric from proponents of the creative city imperative of an inclusive urbanism set forth by unfettered creativity, there is a more critical perspective that posits that there is a distinct class element to the kind of urban development envisioned by the proponents of the creative city doctrine. O'Callaghan (2010) argues that 'the creative class concept is primarily tailored towards a core audience of urban elites and young high-earning professionals. Thus, the version of 'creativity' that is extolled fits neatly with the lifestyles and work practices of this group' (p.1610). However, art and cultural activity need not be inherently linked to gentrification, displacement and capital accumulation. Rather, this begs the questions as to how we might – to return to Oakley (2015) – test the (im)possibility of

new narratives of culture-led regeneration that might leverage the positive effects of culture without the harmful effects of gentrification.

3.4 Beyond the creative city: approaches to culture-led regeneration

Beyond the creative city and gentrification, Evans (2004) and Vickery (2007) demonstrate the myriad forms of culture-led and cultural regeneration. This interaction can range from culture-led regeneration - where culture is a vehicle for regeneration, to cultural regeneration that allegedly provides a more holistic and embedded version of culturally informed regeneration, to other forms of incidental cultural development. Edwards (2018) challenges the homogeneity of culture-led regeneration further by demonstrating the fragmented cultural policy of Glasgow during the 1980s. For her account (ibid), the lack of coherent cultural policy in the city in the years leading up to 1990 European Capital of Culture (ECOC) created a vacuum which could be filled by the demands of more concrete economic development agendas. From this perspective, Glasgow's cultural policy was led by the development of the city's economy. Thus, Edwards contends, 'rather than culture leading regeneration, regeneration led culture' (p.2). This is significant in that Glasgow is often held up as the model for culture-led regeneration and image transformation (Edwards, 2018; Livingstone and Clark, 2019; Mooney, 2004; Clark and Wright, 2018).

Despite the differences in terms of goals and methods, Richards and Wilson (2006) contend that there are – broadly speaking – four main forms of urban cultural development: iconic structures, heritage mining, events and thematization. Iconic structures rely on the use of iconic landmarks in the creation of urban and cultural spectacle. Heritage mining involves creating, and/or amplifying, narratives and messages about a city's – often rich – historical legacy as a means of reconstructing place identity. Thematization relies on attempting to

distinguish place by developing specific cultural themes, or as Richards and Wilson (2006) put it by becoming the 'something of somewhere', such as the dominant narrative of New York City as the 'cultural capital of the world'. Lastly, events and festivals are used as a stimulant of economic development and in the management of a city-wide brand (ibid).

3.4.1 Cultural events and festivals

There is, now, an increased focus on bidding for, and hosting, cultural events and festivals within cultural regeneration discourse (see Richards and Palmer, 2010; Garcia, 2004; Roche, 2003; Campbell, 2011; Smith, 2012). The Olympic Games in London in 2012, the 2014 Glasgow Commonwealth Games, and the UKCoC competition all demonstrate the strategic importance attributed to bidding for, and staging, myriad forms of events and festivals. McGillivray et al (2015) contend that the use of events as a mechanism for regeneration is rooted in the 1960s. Illustrating this is the 1960 Olympic Games hosted by the city of Rome. The games, now dubbed 'the regeneration games', embody the emerging narratives of physical and economic improvement within the legacy narrative of mega sport events (see Gold and Gold, 2008).

Beyond traditional mega sport events, such as the Olympic Games or the football World Cup, the use of cultural events and festivals, such as ECOC and UKCoC, have garnered increasing attention in both academic and political spheres. These events have become an increasingly integral facet of the event-led regeneration landscape (Liu, 2014; Smith, 2014; Richards and Wilson, 2004; Cunningham and Platt, 2018; Connolly, 2013). Evidence of this is littered throughout past decades, from Glasgow hosting the ECOC in 1990, Liverpool hosting the same event in 2008, Hull hosting UKCoC in 2017 and of course, Paisley's bid for UKCoC. In each example, event bidding has been positioned as a lever through which to achieve the regeneration of post-industrial cities (see Mooney, 2004; Garcia, 2005; Campbell, 2011).

Outwith merely being a mechanism for physical regeneration, event bidding is frequently positioned as a conduit for improving the image and reputation of place. Practically speaking, this means that cultural events are increasingly being used to change perceptions about cities with negative area reputations. From this perspective, event narratives, as well as the event itself, are leveraged to market towns and cities (Waite, 2003; Garcia, 2005;; Kidd, Clark and Kearns, 2017). Justification for such urban marketing posits that the creation of a symbolic legacy (wherein the city's image is remade in a more positive light) will stimulate economic development (Evans and Shaw, 2004). Richards and Wilson's research (2004, 2006) demonstrates this in relation to the Dutch city of Rotterdam, and the Cultural Capital of Europe event held in 2001. The event involved a regeneration programme aimed at stimulating the creative and leisure industries and managing the city's image. This, of course, raises the question as to how the cultural impact of such events should be measured. As such, the success of culture-led regeneration, in terms of cultural impact at least, must be measured separately from hard evidence of physical change and economic growth utilizing the soft indicators such as media and personal discourses (Garcia, 2005; Evans and Shaw, 2004). It is not necessarily clear, however, if discourse of creative cities, image transformation and urban neoliberalism might be applied outwith the context of larger cities and the events that they host (Mooney, 2004; McGillivray et al, 2015; Garcia, 2005).

Through the lens of the creative turn, we can see the proliferation of competitions which explicitly foreground *culture* as a means to selling the uniqueness of urban space (Richards and Wilson 2006; Aspen 2013). Cunningham and Platt (2018) note the tension within event (bid) led placemaking strategies between the *top-down*, criteria-led nature of the bidding process and the bottom-up approach that recognises local distinctiveness. Irrespective of this,

however, there are now numerous cultural events, similar in architecture and remit, which have seemingly become mainstays in the European cultural landscape (Richards, 2018; Griffiths, 2006; Connolly, 2013). Indeed, the city competition model has proliferated in recent years, with the emergence of competitions at an increasingly local scale such as the London Borough of Culture or the Greater Manchester Town of Culture (see Mould 2018). However, the growth in popularity of cultural events and festivals, perhaps inevitably, raises important questions as to the successes of hosting such events, and in the legacy that they leave behind. From this perspective, it becomes important to assess the long-term reputational effects of positive media coverage beyond the lifespan of the event/bid in question (Garcia, 2005; Mooney, 2004; Reason and Garcia, 2007).

Limited evidence suggests, however, that culture-led regeneration can change area reputations and leverage more positive newspaper and media coverage. The Cultural Cities Enquiry (2019) demonstrates the strategic importance of securing positive media coverage in the management of area reputation. In the case of Glasgow, and the 1990 ECOC, it is claimed that 60% of the international media coverage referred to the city's transformation into a cultural centre – this reflects the importance of using events in remaking external perceptions of place (Garcia, 2005; Paddison, 1993; Livingstone and Clark, 2019). However, it is difficult to conclude, a priori, that the short-term cultural impact of such festivals translates into a meaningful and sustainable cultural legacy. In short, without material economic or physical change, how long can civic pride instilled by cultural events survive? As discussed above, Mooney (2004) demonstrates this in relation to Glasgow following the ECOC success of 1990 by contending that the event, its narratives and legacy did little to materially change systemic issues. Logically, it follows that if systemic issues remain unaddressed then a permanently

enhanced image and reputation is unlikely. Nonetheless, it is clear that media campaigns surrounding events and festivals discussed above play an important part in managing and shaping perceptions of urban spaces and place marketing (see Garcia, 2005). What is missing from this discourse, again, is how this relates to smaller cities and towns. Additionally, questions as to the applicability of previous research on larger events to the more nationally focused UKCoC competition can be raised.

The city of Hull's year as UKCoC in 2017, it is claimed, significantly improved place impression both internally (with residents) and externally, resulting in an improved perception of the city among 46% of UK residents and 75% of visitors throughout the year (Cultural Cities Enquiry, 2019). Further, a preliminary evaluation of UKCoC events in Hull from the University of Hull (2018) demonstrates, again, the significance of gaining positive media coverage within placemaking discourse. Within the report, it is argued that the City of Culture event in Hull garnered over 20,200 pieces of media coverage across print, broadcast and online media that both raised the profile of the city itself and instilled a sense of pride in city residents. However, it is important to avoid the assumption that media representation is an end in itself. Event bids are often located within broader regeneration agendas (see Campbell, 2011; Edwards, 2018; Gray and Mooney, 2011). This is certainly true in the context of Paisley in which the UKCoC bid emerged with an aim of achieving specific economic development goals via culture and heritage (*The Untold Story*, 2014). In any case, event bidding can also be a useful way of leveraging physical infrastructure changes (Evans, 2003; O'Callaghan and Linehan, 2007). In this sense, the physical transformation associated with event bids connects with another key facet of culture-led regeneration – the construction of flagship projects (Oakley, 2015; Comunian and Mould, 2014)

3.4.2 Flagship projects

Building flagship cultural facilities, such as museums, has come to embody an archetypal model of culture-led regeneration (Richards and Wilson, 2006). Comunian and Mould (2014: 65) argue that ‘flagship cultural developments’ have come to be one of the most articulated methods of culture-led regeneration whereby constructing large scale cultural facilities is viewed as means of securing the economic regeneration of the broader area. Indeed, this reflects a model of culture-led regeneration that has, it seems, had enduring influence across much of Europe (See Mould, 2018; Richards and Wilson, 2006). As Mould (2018: 155) argues:

One of the ways which this (regeneration) happened was the building of large-scale flagship cultural projects. The Guggenheim museum in Bilbao, opened in 1997, is a successful example (at least economically) of how parachuting a large, expensive and culturally-significant institution into a declining area can help revive economic fortunes.

The economic impact of Bilbao’s Guggenheim triggered somewhat of a phenomenon within urban cultural policy, with the birth of the Bilbao effect as cities built, at dizzying speed, landmark cultural institutions in a bid to transform their economic fortunes (see Richards and Wilson 2006, Mould, 2018, Bell and Oakley, 2014). To return to Richards and Wilson (2006), this appears to reflect one of the dominant approaches under the banner of the creative turn in regeneration, the construction of iconic structures. This approach, for Richards and Wilson, is where cities are increasingly constructing iconic landmarks as a means of changing the image and reputation of place by focusing on cultural and economic activity.

Additionally, one of the most articulated benefits of flagship developments is the perceived development of the image and brand of the city. Developing landmark cultural facilities as means to leverage the reputational benefits associated with place-distinguishing landmarks contains somewhat of a paradox insofar as this runs the risk of increasing urban homogenisation as other cities seek to replicate the alleged success of previous flagship constructions (Aspen, 2013; Richards and Wilson, 2006). Richards and Wilson (2006) argue that this paradox represents the risk of serial reproduction when regeneration strategies, sold as a success by urban policymakers, are readily copied by other cities in a bid to replicate such success. The replication of culture-led initiatives is, of course, an inherent contradiction insofar as the search for place distinction leads to increasingly similar strategies being deployed (ibid). There are numerous examples of serial reproduction littered throughout the literature on culture-led regeneration. O'Callaghan and Linehan (2007) illustrate the influence of the Barcelona model in the city of Cork in Ireland, which constructed a Barcelona style Rambla to be the centrepiece of the 2005 ECOC festival hosted in the city.

The paradox of serial reproduction reflects what Aspen (2013) calls zombie urbanism in which top-down models of culture-led regeneration has led to an increasingly homogenized model of culture-led redevelopment which foregrounds leisure and retail led urban (re)development. Applying Beck's 'zombie concepts' which describe concepts which are still in use despite their ontological inaccuracy, zombie urbanism reflects the increasing homogenisation of (cultural) regeneration. Indeed, for Aspen (ibid):

...it seems that both the vocabulary used to describe challenges, ambitions, means and assets, as well as the strategies and plans that are increasingly prescribed for regenerating the city, are surprisingly formulaic and increasingly similar (p.183)

The proliferation of an increasingly similar toolkit of regeneration strategies is therefore based on 'on a fairly simple and stereotypical assumption about what constitutes vibrant urban public places' (Aspen, 2013: 193).

The construction of flagship regeneration projects as a means to leverage improved area representations intersects with broader discourses of neoliberalism, entrepreneurialism and inter-urban competition that have been central to discourses of culture-led regeneration and city branding (Richards and Diuf, 2019). To return to Mould (2018), if the rhetoric of creativity and creative cities has been subsumed by the logic of neoliberalism by the charge to do more with less, this creates the stigmatising assumption that complex urban inequality can be solved with creativity itself. More explicitly, Comunian and Mould (2014) demonstrate that flagship events connect with the neoliberal imperatives of image enhancement by seeking to upgrade the 'image' and 'brand' of the city (p.65) thereby making it more economically competitive in a globalised landscape. Culture-led regeneration conforms to the logic of urban neoliberalism in the same vein as creative city development strategies. In the next section, I explore Oakley's (2015) imperative to go beyond critiques of culture-led regeneration and test the possibility of new narratives of the relationship between culture and place. In doing so, I will explore how creative placemaking is poised to subvert or resist dominant strands of culture-led regeneration.

3.5 Creative placemaking and (re)theorising the role of culture in regeneration

Oakley (2015) correctly identifies that critique of culture-led regeneration has been 'manifold and persuasive'. This chapter has demonstrated the pitfalls of the creative city model for attracting inward development and thus regenerating (or gentrifying) urban spaces. However, it does not necessarily follow that the presence of art, culture and creativity within urban

regeneration initiatives is inherently negative. Mould (2018) argues that while the notion of creativity has been hijacked by neoliberalism, so too does it reveal emancipatory forms of urban living. Oakley (2015: 2) argues that it is necessary to 'go beyond critiques of cultural regeneration, not to negate them but to build on them'. In doing so, we can develop a counter-narrative, which can 'test the possibility of new narratives about the relationship between place and culture' (ibid). This, of course, raises the question as to what this relationship might look like. For Oakley, this involves small-scale cultural investment, which can have beneficial effects at neighbourhood level 'without the harmful effects of gentrification' (p.8). Evidence of this apparent success is generally located in the literature on creative placemaking (see Courage and McKewon, 2019; Zitcer, 2018; Courage, 2017; Courage, 2016). Creative placemaking, broadly speaking, refers to a process whereby 'partners shape the physical and social character of a town, neighbourhood, town, city or region around arts and cultural activities' (Markusen, 2013: 292). Marxist scholar Oli Mould (2018: 158), though broadly critical of creative placemaking, claims that the 'modus operandi of placemaking is to commission outdoor arts projects, community-based infrastructure and pedestrianisation schemes' all with the aim of 'fostering entrepreneurs and cultural industries that generate jobs and income'. Similarly, Courage (2017) argues that creative placemaking 'animates' public and private spaces, improves the visibility of local businesses and brings together local communities (p.29). When taken together, Oakley (2015) argues that creative placemaking might harness the positive effects of culture without the harmful effects of gentrification.

Kovacs and Park (2021) argue that creative placemaking is almost always discussed in a positive light. This is perhaps most true in smaller towns and cities with their 'relative

closeness of natural amenities, lower living costs and even older populations, who are more likely to spend money in cultural activities, may support the cultural scene of small cities' (Denise-Jacob, 2012, cited in Oakley, 2015: 11). Small cities represent an opportunity within placemaking to shift towards *liveable* places that foreground metrics such as access to recreational space or the quality of local schools as opposed to merely economic development (Oakley, 2015).

The emergent shift towards *liveability*, however, may not represent a substantial shift away from creative city development strategies. Mould (2018) argues that creative placemaking can be more accurately described as another mutation of creative city development strategies in which creative city advocates look to create the perception of a separate strategy that shuns the aesthetic of flagship cultural facilities while furthering the relationship between creativity and economic development. This new creative city, he argues, must 'have the veneer of 'edginess', appeal to hipsters and maintain a radical, progressive and perhaps even anti-capitalist aesthetic' (p.159) while, at the same time, furthering the process of instrumentalisation, economic development and gentrification. What Mould's (2018) new creative city cannot account for, however, is why smaller cities and towns that do not appear to be undergoing the process of gentrification are adopting increasingly similar strategies. As Hopkins (2019) contends, ordinary cities can champion their uniqueness without necessarily (re)producing the dominant revanchist discourses of the creative city.

Despite an emergent body of literature on creative placemaking and small cities (see Richards and Diuf, 2019; Gibson and Waitt, 2008; Lewis and Donald, 2010; Oakley, 2015), this scholarship remains somewhat overlooked in mainstream placemaking studies. Lewis and Donald (2010) contend, for example, that the very way in which creative capital is conceived,

with its reliance on inter-urban competition and league tables, tends to marginalise smaller cities. This is problematic insofar as it elides our understanding of how processes of creative placemaking in small cities and towns might differ from those implemented in major metropolitan areas. Indeed, the critique of the relationship between placemaking, regeneration and gentrification in large cities with generally greater levels of inequality, particularly in the context of housing, cannot be applied a priori to smaller towns and cities that are less impacted by these issues (Oakley, 2015). As such, there has been some interest in the extent to which smaller cities and towns can use culture to deliver outcomes that are more equitable or change the terms of the debate about culture-led regeneration (ibid).

That is not to say, however, that there is no space for critique in placemaking discourse. Mould (2018) argues that one problem with placemaking discourse is the way in which it relies on narratives of decline. In this sense, 'there is no place here, so let's make one' (p.159). The lexicon of placemaking can, however, often times be a byword for gentrification – beautifying run-down areas to increase land and property values. Stein (2019) illustrates that capitalist urban planning necessitates that improvement in the aesthetic and liveability of place will invariably increase land values. To return to the work of Hopkins (2019), however, it could be argued that the problem lies not in the presence of artists, arts or cultural projects but the way in which this has been hijacked by private interests and real estate capital in larger cities. Culture-led regeneration, and placemaking, must be seen therefore within the context of place. Arts-led gentrification in global cities, performed under the rubric of either placemaking or regeneration, should not necessarily be read as a comment on the potential impact of bottom-up cultural initiatives in smaller towns and cities.

For Richards and Diuf (2019), creative placemaking is able to achieve this with the incorporation of non-market processes that might thereby transcend top-down, marginalising responses to urban decline and urban inequality. Interestingly, discourses of creative placemaking - as articulated by Richards and Diuf (2019) - appear to pivot *away* from a more explicit focus on branding strategies and image enhancement as the principal aim of culture-led development:

placemaking, on the other hand, also involves non-market processes and an effort to improve the quality of lives of all those who use the place. An attractive external image should be a by-product of placemaking, not the goal (p.16)

It is unclear exactly how placemaking might break from the market processes of urban neoliberalism merely by including *non-market* processes, particularly as the foundational logic of both approaches appears to be remarkably similar. To return to the case study provided by Richards and Diuf (*ibid*), much of their argument pivots on how small cities might 'put themselves on the map' (p.1) and compete with larger cities in a post-industrial context via creative placemaking. Indeed, it is difficult to reconcile the argument that an attractive external image is not an end in itself with a discourse which proposes that 'in the contemporary urban world...one of the imperatives is competing for attention' (p.5). While creative placemaking, in this context, might provide a less totalising and more palatable relationship between culture and place (Oakley, 2015), it is unclear how the logic of inter-urban competition is challenged by an approach which uncritically accepts, and thus risks, naturalising inter-urban competition itself.

Placemaking narratives are often cloaked in the progressive rhetoric of social justice. This is perhaps clearest in the most comprehensive contribution to the emergent field of

placemaking studies (Wilson, 2021), the *Routledge Handbook of Placemaking*. Here, placemaking is represented as unapologetically progressive in its broad political outlook, with discourses of anti-racism, LGBTQ+ liberation and the rights of indigenous populations recurring themes across the text (ibid). More generally, discourses of what we might call 'progressive placemaking' are based on a framework of social justice (see Webb, 2014). Even more explicitly, Frenette (2017) argues that creative placemaking can be distinguished from creative city strategies precisely because placemaking foregrounds issues of inequality. While, for Frenette, both the creative class thesis and creative placemaking both foreground art and culture in the (re)development and well-being of place, creative placemaking 'incorporates a stronger emphasis on equity, and argues for artists to play a more expansive role in society' (p.342). In this vision, creative placemaking appears to foreground social justice in the (re)development of place, and this would certainly appear to mark a significant departure from narratives of the gentrifying neoliberal city. It is less clear, however, the extent to which this represents a departure from discourses of the creative city which is, itself, presented with somewhat of a progressive veneer (Peck, 2005; Mould, 2018).

The apparent eccentricity which with the creative class thesis was presented by Florida (2004) was a particular gripe among conservative critics (See Malanga, 2004; Glaeser, 2004; Lees and Melhuish, 2013). Malanga (2004) takes issue with Florida's alleged liberal bias, contending that the creative class has succeeded due to its popularity with leftist policymakers. While the substance of Malanga's critique does little to engage with the inequalities of de-industrialisation, uneven development and urban inequality, he does nonetheless remind us that the creative city is fundamentally an ode to bohemia, rooted in the notion that the well-being of places is secured by becoming trendy and fashionable. It is of course true that one of

Florida's (2004) infamous three t's of development was tolerance, which is reminiscent of the social justice framework of creative placemaking. LGBT+ rights and anti-racism appear to be features of both the trendy and bohemian neighbourhoods of the creative city and in the more equitable culturally led regeneration fostered by creative placemaking outlined by Oakley (2015). This is not to suggest that this continuity would necessarily dictate that we cannot, or should not, differentiate between creative placemaking and the creative city. However, given that discourses of social justice alone cannot differentiate them, it therefore appears that placemaking is unable to strive for this equality in practice, and therefore, it is unable to challenge, or at the very least resist, the dominance of neoliberalism in culture-led regeneration strategies (see Brenner, 2021).

Placemaking studies remains a rather contested, and at times contradictory, space. There are two perspectives which are important here. The first is that creative placemaking can be understood as a continuation of neoliberal culture-led interventions in place (Brenner, 2021; Pritchard, 2016). Mould (2018: 15), for example, argues that creative placemaking is merely the new epoch of creative city development strategies insofar as placemaking is the 'lexicon by which urban managers and developers leverage community responses and ideas, and implement them as gentrification schemes'. Pritchard (2016), in addition, contends that 'creative placemaking...is the soft power weapon of many property developers and councils' (n.p). From these perspectives, creative placemaking enlists artists as foot soldiers in gentrification, social cleansing and displacement (ibid). While such a polemic leaves little room for nuance, Prichard's (ibid) account reveals that placemaking, as a practice, is more palliative than productive insofar as it is unable to challenge the broader hegemony of

neoliberal urban development (Wilson, 2021a). Brenner (2021), though writing more specifically in the context of tactical urbanism, argues that:

it is less obvious how tactical urbanism could counteract neoliberal urbanism ... it seems reasonable to ask in what ways they actually do, in actuality, engender any serious friction against the neoliberal order, much less subvert it. (p. 314)

Brenner's reflections, though directed more specifically at tactical urbanism as opposed to creative placemaking, is useful in response to the emerging popularity of creative placemaking as a more holistic alternative top-down culture-led regeneration. Both creative placemaking and tactical urbanism posit that hegemonic processes of urban neoliberalism are best challenged by more grounded and bottom-up approaches to placemaking and regeneration. McKeown and Courage (2019) suggest that creative placemaking is poised to challenge, resist or subvert dominant global processes:

Creative placemaking projects...grounded in an inclusive systemic approach, there is an opportunity to explore and reconsider narrowly understood or ill-defined place-based solutions and harness its potential to facilitate understanding and scalable local solutions to systemic problems. (p.203)

We might ask, therefore, *how* creative placemaking offers a rift from extant discourse of top-down cultural regeneration, or how creative placemaking might test the possibility of new narratives about the relationship between culture and place (Oakley, 2015). The argument, from proponents of creative placemaking, represents a shift in *scale* towards more small-scale, localised interventions in place (ibid). However, it is not at all clear how a change in

scale alone challenges broader processes of neoliberalism, de-industrialisation and inter-urban competition.

3.6 Conclusions and guiding research questions

The aim of this chapter was to explore debates on culture-led regeneration. In this chapter I have argued that the dominant creative city discourse can be read as an expression of neoliberal urban development. I argued that gentrification is a state facilitated and economic driven process, though issues of consumption are also integral to the reconstruction of place. Culture and consumption serve only to open up new spaces for capital accumulation, particularly within an economic paradigm emerging in the wake of manufacturing decline, and in this sense is inextricable from the broader process of actually existing neoliberalism. I have also provided a critique of the continued dominance of creative city development strategies that exist within local governments. For such actors, creativity is seen as a saviour from the perils of de-industrialisation, in which cultural development can open up new avenues for growth in an increasingly globalised economic landscape. However, this strategy has a number of serious flaws. I contend that the fundamental issue with this thesis is not the veneer of cool it is performed under, but instead that creative city development strategies sit neatly within the process of neoliberal restructuring. Through this lens, the creative city is deeply entrenched in notions of uneven development, gentrification and inequality that is concomitant with neoliberalism itself. To return to aims and objectives of this thesis, it is clear that the logics of creative city development, as thus gentrification, continue to influence the conditions of possibility which shape how discourses of culture-led regeneration materialise. Finally, in this chapter I considered how culture-led regeneration discourses might transcend the creative city model. I warn against viewing culture-led regeneration as a homogenous

entity and demonstrate the value in understanding the contextual variance in regeneration approaches. Some commentators contend that there is growing evidence that small-scale cultural projects can be successful particularly outwith the gentrifying global centres at the epicentre of the post-industrial society. I show how place based, co-produced cultural practices can be valuable in fostering a place-identity that is genuinely reflective of the needs and interests of the local population, and one which imparts ownership of the regeneration process onto the community themselves. There is, as Oakley (2015: 2) puts it, 'counter-narratives of cultural regeneration, different understanding of culture and of creativity that can help build a body of evidence, which can inform policy and education in the future'. However, there is some scepticism to be had about claims that creative placemaking represents a radical shift from the logics of culture-led regeneration, neoliberal development and inter-urban competition.

Much is known (and debated) about the role of culture in the image transformation of post-industrial cities (Richards and Diuf, 2019; Garcia, 2005; Miles, 2020). However, little attention has been paid to ordinary cities, or peripheral towns and suburban space. Additionally, little is known about how discourses of cultural regeneration are constructed and enacted. This makes Paisley a suitable case study to explore the construction of discourses of cultural regeneration in smaller towns and cities. The overall aim and objectives of this study were outlined in chapter one. The research questions emanate from the literature based chapters and have been designed to address a significant gap in current knowledge about the relationship between place, culture and media representation. These research questions explore the development of key messages that have been communicated about Paisley, and how this is related to the broader development of cultural regeneration in the area:

- i. How have key narratives of cultural regeneration in Paisley been developed and who were the key actors involved and to what extent is this reflected in the media messages communicated about Paisley?
- ii. What key messages have been communicated about Paisley, its culture and regeneration between 2014 and 2020?
- iii. What is the local community receptions and reaction to representations of Paisley and cultural regeneration?

Chapter 4: Methodology

4.1 Introduction

In the preceding chapters, I have outlined debates in the literature concerning the construction of area reputation and the role of culture in contemporary debates on urban regeneration. A common theme through both has been the role of actually existing neoliberalism in shaping both how area reputation is constructed and discourses of culture-led regeneration are developed. The aim of this chapter is to outline the methodological structure adopted for this study. I begin by outlining the case for a methodological approach informed by the work of Michael Foucault and an understanding of discourses as fluid, discontinuous and discursively (re)constructed in different temporal contexts. With this in mind, representations of place and regeneration do not pertain to any actually existing reality, but rather reflect the dominant discourses that construct a certain regime of truth. I argue that discourse is, therefore, essential in understandings of cultural regeneration, insofar as we can delineate the conditions of possibility whereby certain ideas, narratives and voices become naturalised and accepted as true and trace these narrative shifts over time.

I then apply these theoretical perspectives to the specific *methods* used to conduct this study. I outline the collection and analysis of newspaper reporting of Paisley, as well as the collection of documentary and archival data used to locate the official discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley. I then discuss my approach to semi-structured interviews. I outline the selection and access to elite stakeholders for one-to-one interviews to understand the construction of official discourses representing cultural regeneration in Paisley. I also discuss online workshops held with local residents to better understand how the discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley are received and produced at a more grassroots level. The

chapter concludes with a discussion of the ethical considerations for doing fieldwork remotely and a discussion of the limitations of this study.

4.2. Foucault, social constructionism and a (brief) introduction to post-structural theory

This study seeks to understand and analyse the conditions of possibility that enable discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley to materialise, how these discourses are produced and how their receptions at a local grassroots level. As discussed in chapter two, discursive representations of stigmatised places are not politically neutral nor coincidental (Wassenberg, 2004; Schwarze, 2021). With this in mind, this necessitates a methodological approach that enables an analysis of how these discourses are themselves *constructed*. With this in mind, it is therefore important that this thesis be located within the broader intellectual tradition of Social Constructionism (SC), post-structural theory and more specifically the broad church of Foucauldian theory. However, it is necessary to first unpack *what* about post-structuralism justifies the prefix attached to it. Khan and MacEachen (2021) argues that the structuralist position is a scientific view of language and culture, which posits that a central *structure* or underlying system that organises and maintains the broader social structures of society. By contrast, post-structural theory centres on scepticism of meta-narratives – broad, over-arching claims to knowledge (see Carr, 2016; Inglis and Thorpe, 2019). As Lyotard famously proclaimed, the postmodern condition is defined by its incredulity to grand recites (Carr, 2016). This rests upon deconstructing claims of universality or over-arching truths contained within scientific discourses that claim to present an objective, empirical and scientific worldview (see Agger, 1991). Post-structuralism, therefore, is characterised by its general aversion to positivism (Inglis and Thorpe, 2019). In this sense, and

as a departure from the structuralist perspective, post-structural theorists assert that there is no unifying, over-arching truth or ultimate reality (Kahn and MacEachen, 2021; Bryman, 2012). Rather, post-structuralism posits that reality is a construction of *discourse*. Post-structuralism, then, might be placed within a similar (though by no means identical) intellectual tradition as SC.

SC posits that 'social phenomena and their meanings are continually being accomplished by social actors' (Bryman, 2012: 29). It implies that social phenomena are not only produced by social interaction but are in a constant state of revision' (Ibid). Kahn and MacEachen (2021) argue that SC illuminates how the meaning of our social action is *constructed* through our everyday interactions. It is clear, then, that constructivism as a general ontological position can be viewed in (and beyond) post-structuralism, both in the scepticism toward grand narratives and emphasis on the processes of (re)negotiation which creates and revises social phenomena and in the way in which reality and knowledge are themselves constructed through discourse. However, for Kahn and MacEachen (2021), SC does not acknowledge how the construction of meaning relates to the power imbalance(s) in society. Kahn and MacEachen (ibid) argue, therefore, that by turning our attention to Foucault, and Foucauldian Discourse Analysis (FDA) in particular, we can address the weakness in SC.

4.2.1 Foucault: power, discourse and knowledge

Scepticism of grand-narratives or universal truths is, undoubtedly, a feature of the work of Michael Foucault. For Foucault, 'there is no external position of certainty, no universal understanding that is beyond history and society' (Rabinow, 1984: 4). His strategy, therefore, is to proceed as far as possible in his analyses without recourse to universals (ibid). A broad and general reading of Foucault's work reveals that, at its core, is an investigation into the

way in which certain discursive formations (re)construct truth(s). Knowledge is an expression, and mechanism, of power whereby what is taken to be viewed as true at any given time within any given discourse is implicated in a complex assemblage of power relations, which in turn produce a certain regime of truth (Potter, 1996). Foucault demonstrates this through historical enquiry that destabilises the notion that scientific discourses progress towards an actually existing truth by characterising the history of ideas (scientific discourses) as discontinuous. As McHoul and Grace (1993: 4) demonstrate:

Foucault's counter-history (of ideas) also had to conceive of bodies of knowledge (discourses) as *discontinuous* across history rather than necessarily progressive and cumulative...Foucault's analysis of scientific change as discontinuous shows that it does not progress from stage to stage getting closer and closer to the truth; that it is not guided by any underlying principle which remains essential and fixed while all around it changes. The thesis of discontinuity is indeed a key element in his analysis and critique of 'official' or 'dominant' knowledges' (emphasis original)

Through this lens, what is to count as truth about, for example, issues such as mental health or sexuality are the construction of a specific set of techniques and discursive practices as analysed in the *Birth of the Clinic* or the *history of sexuality* (ibid). In sum, in viewing Foucault's work through the prism of post-structural theory and scepticism towards grand narratives that has enveloped the cultural turn, it is possible to locate this within the broader paradigm of SC (Waite, 2005). With this in mind, attention must turn to Foucauldian conceptions of discourse, knowledge and power in the construction of truth.

Discourse, for Foucault, is not simply a matter of asserting *what is said*, but rather a way of exploring *what can be said* (Waite, 2010). Young (1981), in introducing Foucault's *The Order*

of Discourse, notes that the paper introduces a view of discourse predicated on the systems, rules and procedures which constitute our will to knowledge. Here, discourse is not simply a matter of what can be said, or a mode through which humans communicate via language or semiotics. Rather, discourse refers to 'relatively well-bounded areas of social knowledge' (McHoul and Grace, 1993: 31). These areas of social knowledge are themselves constructed, mediated and historically contingent. From this perspective, discourse contours the limits of knowledge, in that what we say, think or write is, itself a product of discourse (ibid). Or, as Foucault (1981: 52) remarks:

in every society the production of discourse is at once controlled, selected, organised and redistributed by a certain number of procedures whose role is to ward off its powers and dangers, to gain mastery over its chance events, to evade its ponderous, formidable materiality

A discourse is, therefore, 'whatever constrains – but also enables – writing, speaking and thinking' at any given time (McHoul and Grace, 1993: 31). Discourse cannot be merely read as a representation of the real, and instead constitutes an essential part of its construction. Discourse is, however, neither fixed nor evolutionary but is historically contingent and therefore constantly in flux. For Potter (1996), Foucault's intellectual project was predicated on mapping and analysing how certain regimes of truth are produced in different historical contexts. Dreyfus and Rabinow (1984) argue that Foucault originally attempted to map the systems, techniques and rules that governed the emergences of discourses, and how knowledge is historically ordered. This phase of Foucault's *oeuvre* is known as the archaeological method. Foucault's archaeological method is typically ascribed to his earlier work that was concerned with the analysis of systems – such as systems of health, sexuality

and governance (McHoul and Grace, 1993; Kahn and MacEachen, 2021; Waitt, 2010). Consequently, Foucault was concerned with the production of knowledge and discourses (Kahn and Machen, 2021). Foucault's archaeological analysis was, therefore, concerned with 'examining the relations between different statements, the ways these systems are grouped together, and the conditions under which they emerge' (ibid, p.4).

In the *Archaeology of Knowledge*, Foucault (2002) attempts to map certain discursive formations that describe the principles that govern certain discourses, or:

Whenever one can describe, between a number of statements, such a system of description, whenever, between objects, types of statements, concepts or thematic choices, one can define a regularity (an order, correlations, positions and functioning's, transformation, we will say, for the sake of convenience that we are dealing with discursive formations (p.41)

Using this archaeological method, the (re)development of certain discourses can be said to be historically contingent. In *The Order of Things: Archaeology of the Human Sciences* (2001), for example, Foucault traces the emergence of *life, language and labour* (biological, linguistics and economics). Foucault also develops the concept of *episteme* that delineates the terms of acceptable knowledge within any given historical context (McHoul and Grace, 1993). In doing so, Foucault deconstructs the claims to objectivity made within each discipline, showing the techniques by which each discourse constructed its own regime of truth. Discourses cannot be seen to have the own unique access to truth, rather truth is a function of what can be said (Foucault, 1981b).

For Foucault, the process by which discourse and truth are constructed are not politically neutral or coincidental. In his later work, *Discipline and Punish* and *the Histories of Sexuality* Foucault outlines a new approach - genealogy - that illustrates how the reorganisation of knowledge is also intertwined with new forms of power and domination (Rouse, 1994). Genealogy, in Foucauldian terms, involves a tracing of discourses and truths while exploring the 'constitutive relation between genealogy and the subjectivity of the self' (Bronholt, 2021). Similarly, Saar (2002) argues that genealogy is a self-reflective practice that involves understanding the construction of our collective and individual subjectivities. There remains, however, a lack of clear, concrete prescription for conducting a genealogical analysis from a Foucauldian perspective. It is clear, however that, a Foucauldian genealogical analysis must deal with power – insofar as this relates to the construction of the subject itself (ibid). It is worth noting, however, that Foucault's conception of power differs substantially from traditional socio-political definitions. Rather than being a *negative* force that represses, excludes or censures, power is a productive force that produces reality or truth (Foucault, 1979).

Power is not a fetter on the subject, insofar as it does not conceal our true being. Rather, power produces the category of being itself - it produces parts of us that we have come to understand as intimate parts of ourselves (McHoul and Grace, 1993). This can be seen most clearly in *Discipline and Punish* when Foucault (1979: 27) argues:

Perhaps, too, we should abandon a whole tradition which allows us to imagine that knowledge can only exist where power relations are suspended and that knowledge can only exist outside its injunctions, its demands and its interests...We should admit rather that power produces knowledge (and not simply by encouraging it because it

serves power or applying it because it is useful); that power and knowledge directly imply one another; that there is no power relation without the correlative constitution of a field of knowledge, nor any that does not presuppose and constitute at the same time power relations'

Discourse is not a mere effect or product of pre-existing Power (power with a capital P). Nor is power owned by some privileged person or group and existing simply as an obligation or a prohibition on those who do not have it. Power, for Foucault is not just the ruthless domination of the weaker by the stronger (McHoul and Grace, 1993: 39).

In line with the broader schema of the post-structural intellectual project, in this study (via Foucault) I reject the notion that there is a universal real that is not, itself, constructed and mediated through discourse. I apply these broad theoretical axioms to the more specific context of cultural regeneration and the imperative of image transformation that has penetrated neoliberal forms of urban governance. In understanding the history of ideas and knowledge as situated, contingent and discontinuous it becomes apparent that concepts such as regeneration and area reputation cannot be assumed, *a priori*, to refer to a fixed reality, and should be viewed instead as products of the discourses which create them. Such a view has substantial ramifications for how we might study area reputation and the development of cultural regeneration in Paisley. A Foucauldian genealogical approach is clearly appropriate for this research given the research questions outlined previously, in that it provides a clear framework for unravelling the seeming coherence and homogeneity of *narratives* that have been projected about Paisley but also the conditions of positivity that govern *how* discourses materialise. In the next section, I bridge the broader theoretical axioms of Foucault, discourse

and power and the methods used in this study by discussing the usefulness of discourse analysis in urban studies.

4.2.3 Discourse analysis as a tool for investigating the city

Understanding the role of power/knowledge, the term introduced by Foucault to demonstrate the inter-relationship between power and knowledge, in the production of discourse, is a fundamental tenant of Foucauldian discourse analysis (FDA) (Lees, 2004; Waitt, 2005; Thorpe, 2008). What remains to be seen, however, is the way in which FDA, and discourse analysis more generally, has been utilised within the broad field of urban studies and urban geography. This section connects prior discussion of FDA with the spatial focus of this research by exploring the use of both FDA and Discourse Analysis (DA) in urban studies. Finally, in this section I discuss the use of FDA and Foucauldian thought within the context of cultural regeneration and placemaking.

Discourse analysis has been used more frequently within urban studies in recent decades (see Lees, 2004; Hastings, 1999), representing a cultural turn which foregrounds the role of discourse as a component of urban change (Hastings, 1999). However, there remains a lack of consensus as to what constitutes DA, or even what counts as discourse. Lees (2004) argues that, broadly speaking, there are two main forms of discourse analysis that have risen to prominence within the broad church of urban studies; the political economy approach and the Foucauldian approach.

The political economy approach to discourse analysis is rooted in the Marxist tradition and critique of ideology. Here, 'discourse is a tool for uncovering certain hegemonic ways of thinking and talking about how things should be done that serve certain vested interest' (Lees, 2004: 102). Eisinger (2000), for example, studied arts and culture-led urban redevelopment

and in doing so argued that state-led redevelopment (in the form of subsidized sports arenas and convention centres at least) served the interests of civic and business elites and the visitor class at the expense of local residents. Indeed, for Eisinger (2000: 322):

In pursuing big entertainment projects, local elites create a hierarchy of interests in which the concerns of visitors to cities – including commuters, day-trippers, tours and business travellers – take precedence over those of the people who reside in the city

From this perspective, discourse is synonymous with ideology insofar as it serves as a trojan horse, concealing power and forwarding bourgeois interests (Lees, 2004; Fairclough, 1992). This body of research differs from traditional Marxist theory insofar as it is not concerned with shared material interests, but rather on discourse and persuasion. Methodologically, the political economy approach requires particular attention be paid to rhetoric and phrases that are repeatedly used. The aim, therefore, is to discover certain narrative structures, issue framings and how storylines close off certain lines of thought and action at the expense of others (see, for example, Lees, 2004; Fairclough, 1992). As Rydin (1998: 178) puts it:

Here is an emphasis on the constraints imposed by linguistic structures and on the potential for using those structures purposively, in a dialectic manner reminiscent of structuration theory; discourses are reproduced through communicative action by actors and, in using the resources of available linguistic structures, actors can reshape those structures

Practically speaking, this means that rhetoric and language used in discourse influences the relationship between social actors as much as it reflects them. Discourse analysis is useful in this context in that it allows the researcher to identify who is on what side by focusing on

what they say. However, an account that positions discourse as that which conceals or legitimises the interests of the powerful pays insufficient attention to how power operates *on* and *through* the production of discourse itself (see Foucault, 1981). The political economy strand of discourse studies, therefore, is antithetical to the Foucauldian view in which power is *productive* inasmuch as it explicitly positions power as *repressive*.

The second strand of discourse analysis is rooted in post-structural theory, and the work of Foucault. The role of discourse, here, differs from political economy discourse analysis in terms of identity. In Marxist research, the identity of actors is assumed based on their relationship to structural or economic hierarchies, whereas discourse in post-structural research is part of a broader process through which identities are constructed (see Sharp and Richardson, 2001; Lees, 2003). In Foucauldian terms, discourse is not a mere reflection or (mis)representation of reality, but rather a construction of its own regime of truth (Foucault, 1980). A regime of truth refers to the way in which power itself has the capacity to shape what is considered to be true at any given time or place (Foucault, 1980). Stenson and Watt (cited in Lees, 2004: 103) argue that:

Discourses create, inter alia, a case list of political and economic agents which government must consider, objects of concern, agendas for actions, preferred narratives for making sense of the origins of current situations, conceptual and geographical spaces within which problems of government are made recognisable. They also create a series of absent agendas, agents, objects of concern and counter-narratives which are mobilised *out* of the discursive picture (Emphasis original)

This form of discourse analysis is a constructionist approach founded in the 'notion that language, knowledge and power are all interconnected through discourse' (Lees, 2004: 103).

In other words, 'language actively constructs actors and the relations between actors (Rydin, 1998: 178). In terms of method, FDA has found influence in, for example, critical human geography, cultural studies, feminist and postcolonial research. In the context of urban studies at least, the focus is on the wider construction of the city in rhetoric (see for example Lees and Demeritt, 1999). This can be attributed to the emergent post-positivist currents of cultural studies, which challenges the empiricism of traditional sociological research. However, there is a more salient theoretical divergence as well. FDA is less concerned with the empirical detail of who says what because of a belief that power is all-encompassing and, as such, the linguistic structures of discourse precede and help to construct agents themselves (Lees, 2004; Sharp and Richardson, 2001; Waitt, 2005).

While the dichotomy presented by Lees (2004) provides a useful framework for understanding the use of discourse analysis in urban studies, it is important to note the limitations of viewing discourse analysis in strictly binary terms. As Lees (2004: 103) acknowledges, 'in practice these two strands of discourse analysis have long been mixed'. This thesis focuses on a Foucauldian approach to discourse analysis as it is concerned with the conditions of possibility that constrict or enable discourse of cultural regeneration in Paisley. This marks somewhat of a departure from previous Foucauldian work that has tended to focus on the disciplinary functions (see Rabinow, 1989; Polger, 2008) of physical space as opposed to how *representations* of places are formed. This study is not concerned with the bio-political functions of physical space itself (see Polger, 2008) but rather the power relations that shape *representations* of place and how representations of place feed into broader cultural regeneration strategies. Now that I have provided an overview of the broad axioms of FDA, a more detailed discussion of *how* to conduct an FDA is needed.

4.3 'All my books are little tool boxes': doing Foucauldian discourse analysis

There remains a certain opacity to the practical act of *conducting* an FDA. However, it is certainly clear that a genealogical analysis requires that discourse be analysed in line with the axioms of Foucauldian thought (Bronholt, 2021). This creates somewhat of a challenge insofar as Foucault never specifically articulated a method for sociological analysis of discourse within empirical data (Arribas-Ayllon and Walkerdine, 2011; Waitt, 2010; Hewitt, 2009). Lees and Davis argue that DA is 'something like bike riding...which is not easy to render or describe in an explicit manner' (Lees and Davis, 2002, cited in Hewitt, 2009: 3). In lieu of a concrete analytical framework, Foucault outlines the tools for identifying discursive formations, the ideological regularities located in language used among people that produce discourse (ibid; Foucault, 2002). FDA is informed by methods that seek to identify and describe the construction of reality and the 'precariousness of knowledge claims' (McLaren, 2009: 1). McLaren (2009) argues that the best the researcher can do is to draw on Foucauldian thought however it fits our own theoretical perspectives or thematic research schema. As Foucault argues:

all my books...are little tool boxes...if people want to open them, to use this sentence or that idea as a screwdriver or spanner to short-circuit, discredit or smash systems of power, including those from which my books have emerged...so much better!
(Foucault, 1975 cited in McLaren, 2009: 2)

This does not imply, however, that FDA cannot be considered a coherent method in its own right. Rather, this is merely to suggest that there is considerable room for variation concerning the subject of study, the institutional scale of analyses, the methods of investigation and process of analysis (Sharp and Richardson, 2001). However, a paradox presents itself here. For FDA to be a viable research method, the researcher requires some appreciation of how

to conduct one. However, prescribing a concrete methodological structure to FDA would be distinctly ‘un-Foucauldian’ (Hewitt, 2009: 3). Nonetheless, for Sharp and Richardson (2001), FDA contains certain core elements. It is characterised by a critical stance towards taken-for-granted knowledge, a sensitivity to historical, cultural specificity, understands knowledge as a social process, and that knowledge and action go together (ibid). For Sharp and Richardson (2001) there are six key characteristics of the Foucauldian methodological approach:

- A view of social change as shaped by and shaping changes in communication
- A view of social change as shaped by and shaping changes in practices
- A view that ‘good’ social change cannot be pre-specified by theory
- A view that social change as shaped by power, conceptualized as competition between differing systems of meaning or ‘discourses’
- A view of discourse competition as shaped by power relations
- A view that a Foucauldian analysis can challenge the status quo through narrating changes in the field of discourse competition over time (p.198)

The challenge, therefore, is to translate the characteristics of Foucauldian research into research practice. In this study I utilize the methodological questions of FDA raised by Sharp and Richardson’s (2001) and Waitt (2005) to conduct an analysis of discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley, as outlined in Table 4.3.1.

How are different discourses identified for this research?	Before data collection, from the literature review and through informal observation.
Where are discourses manifested?	

	In newspaper reporting via specific narratives of cultural regeneration, in policy documents and in the utterances of local actors.
How are struggles between discourses manifested?	In changing strategic priorities and changing policy rhetoric (i.e shift from culture-led to cultural regeneration)
How are the outcomes of these struggles manifested?	New policy rhetoric and the institutionalisation of new policy practices and outcomes
How are the research aims focused into a manageable research project?	By focusing on changes in communication and how this fits within emerging institutional policy and practice
How can the story of discursive conflict be analysed and presented	By (re)constructing and analysing the emerging discourses of cultural regeneration in newspaper reporting on Paisley
Is this approach helpful in addressing the policy outcomes, implementation and broader social change?	Yes, by looking at discursive shifts in cultural regeneration in Paisley and how Paisley's image is constructed

Table 4.3.1 Methodological questions for Foucauldian research based adapted from Sharp and Richardson (2001) and Waitt (2005).

The methodological questions for conducting an FDA raised by Sharp and Richardson (2001) merit a more detailed examination as outlined in subsequent paragraphs. The first stage of my analysis was to identify which discourses would be the focus of my research. Waitt (2005) argues that this is an essential formative step of conducting any FDA. Sharp and Richardson (2001) argue that a key issue in this formative stage of analysis is the extent to which the researcher makes early choices that select some lines of inquiry while consequently closing

others off. The process of selecting discourses for analysis overlaps with the process of locating where discourses are manifested. Sharp and Richardson (2001) contend that textually orientated DA typically take two approaches: spoken or documentary. Spoken DA refers to an analysis of the 'utterances' of key actors (p.199). From this perspective, discourse is manifested at the level of the *spoken* responses from key actors such as politicians. Documentary DA, on the other hand, understands documentary data, such as policy documents, committee papers and other strategic documents as being the site of manifestation.

However, presenting *spoken* and *documentary* discourses as competing sites of discursive manifestation presents a distinctly un-Foucauldian methodological framework. Sharp and Lee (2001) argue that one of the benefits of an FDA that embraces practice is that it 'broadens the ways in which discourses can be understood' (p.199). Both documentary and spoken discourses directly imply one another insofar as 'discourses are understood to be manifested in policy rhetoric, but also in institutional structures, practices and events' (ibid). In the context of this research, therefore, discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley were explored with recourse to documentary, newspaper and oral data. The next section outlines the process of gathering and analysing newspaper and documentary data. In section 4.5, I outline the process for conducting and analysing interview and workshops (oral data).

4.4 Documentary and newspaper data

4.4.1 Newspaper data

It is useful to preface discussion of the use of newspaper data in this thesis with some practical considerations on researching the media, media coverage and representations of place. The term media, in and of itself, can be understood as somewhat vague – particularly in the

context of creating a manageable data set which can then be used for analysis. Bradley (2002) conceptualises media as any mechanism that has the capability to convey information. In this study I utilised newspaper coverage to outline and understand dominant narratives projected about Paisley. Newspaper coverage is appropriate for this research because of the strategic importance of newspapers in the construction of place reputation (see Kearns et al, 2013; Schwarze, 2021; Garcia, 2005; Devereux et al., 2011). Garcia (2017), for example, argues the volume of press coverage secured can be used to assert that image transformation has been achieved:

If media coverage about a particular place shows a significant change in focus and attitude over time, is voluminous enough and cuts across geographical (i.e local, national and international) and journalistic (i.e populist, broadsheet, specialised) variations, then it effectively becomes a key source of evidence of de facto image change and confirms the capacity for major events to catalyse cultural identity renaissance in some cities. (p.3179)

Within the context of stigmatised places, newspaper coverage plays an important role in the construction and (re)production of stigmatising discourse. Kearns et al (2013) argue that negative newspaper reporting is central to the construction of the negative area reputations of both the Sighthill estate in Edinburgh and the Redrow estate in Glasgow. Similarly, Schwarze (2021) demonstrates the role of newspaper coverage in the production, denigration and symbolic defamation of the South Shore community in Chicago by (re)producing an image of South Shore as a space plagued by violence and crime. In sum, newspaper coverage is essential to the construction of place. This can be demonstrated both in the context of territorial stigma and in the strategic attempts to rebrand urban spaces through, inter alia,

leveraging positive newspaper representations of place. Therefore, exploring newspaper reporting of Paisley and cultural regeneration is clearly appropriate for this research inasmuch as newspaper reporting is essential in understanding the construction of Paisley’s image and reputation.

Newspaper articles were identified using the Gale OneFile: News database, an online repository of newspaper coverage. Supplementary data was also identified using online search engines such as Google. The purpose of these searches was to identify, track and code newspaper coverage relating to cultural regeneration in Paisley. In order to do this, a number of searches were conducted using keywords including ‘Paisley’, ‘Regeneration’ or ‘City of Culture’ (for a full list of search terms, see Table 4.1). Further, each search was also run across different time periods corresponding to significant events in the development of Paisley’s regeneration strategy between 2014-2020. For example, searching corresponded to key events identified between 2014-2020, include the publication of baseline document *The Untold Story*, the UKCoC bid (and the immediate aftermath), and the launch of the bid legacy programme (Future Paisley). This produced a substantial dataset of 150 newspaper articles, which cut across local, national and international press outlets.

Search terms	Time Period
“Paisley” AND “City of Culture”	After 2014
“Paisley” AND “City of Culture” AND “Regeneration”	After 2014
“Paisley” AND “City of Culture” OR “Regeneration”	After 2017
“Paisley” AND “Culture” AND “Regeneration”	After 2014

"Paisley" AND "Heritage" and "Regeneration"	After 2014
"Paisley" AND "The Untold Story"	After 2014
"Paisley.is"	After 2017
"Paisley" AND "Town Centre" AND Regeneration"	After 2014
"Future Paisley"	After 2018
"Future Paisley" and "Cultural Regeneration"	After 2018
"Paisley" AND "Culture" AND "Events"	After 2017
"Paisley" AND "Museum"	After 2014
"Paisley" AND "Image" AND "Regeneration"	After 2014

Table 4.4.1 Search terms used

All newspaper data was analysed using the qualitative data management tool, NVIVO. NVIVO was used to store all qualitative data used in this research (newspaper data, documentary data and interview and workshop transcripts). NVIVO is useful for discourse analysis insofar as it provides a way of organising and classifying data. Araujo et al (2019) show that the primary functionality of programmes such as NVIVO is coding data into categories known within the programme as nodes, which can be further sub-divided into sub-nodes. The primary role of NVIVO in DA is thematic coding, which can be achieved through detailed reading of the data (ibid). Thematic coding allowed for the identification of commonly projected discourses through identifying textual patterns in the dataset(s).

Newspaper articles were organised and categorised to ensure that the data could be analysed. For Avraham (2004), the first stage of analysis was to qualitatively assess the type and tone of media coverage that Paisley received during both the UKCoC campaign, but also since the launch of Future Paisley in 2019. Practically speaking, this revealed the extent to which the newspaper representation of Paisley was positive, negative or neutral. Furthermore, this enabled me to track changes in the nature of newspaper representation of Paisley between 2014-2020. This reflects scholars who argue that the soft attributes of cultural regeneration such as image regeneration and place perception is best measured through understanding the media crafted narratives about urban places (see Garcia, 2005; Evans and Shaw, 2004). In conjunction with newspaper data analysis, the collection and analysis of documentary data enabled the development of discourse *within* the local authority and partners to be tracked by looking at changing language used to describe Paisley's approach to regeneration.

4.4.2 Documentary research

The use of documentary data, in the form policy documents, official reports, meeting minutes and internal documentation, is a common form of qualitative data analysis (Bowen, 2009; Bryman, 2012). In the context of this research, documentary data is useful insofar as it provides a clear insight into the official narratives that have been produced in relation to Paisley and cultural regeneration. By placing these documents in chronological order, it is possible to view the evolution of cultural regeneration strategies in Paisley. Second, by comparing the official narratives identified through policy documentation and reports with the narratives identified through analysis of newspaper coverage, it is possible to understand

the production of key messages about Paisley, regeneration and culture in greater depth and in doing so provide the basis for semi-structured interviews to take place (see section 4.9).

Data that is publicly available can be accessed in a similar way to media coverage through the use of online search engines. Specific websites including Renfrewshire Council's official webpage contain specific sections on cultural regeneration, with a rich selection of documents and reports that are publicly accessible. In addition to this, the launch of key documents such as *Paisley is open: A vision for Paisley town centre 2030* have generated significant media coverage in and of themselves, making it relatively straightforward to identify them as key documents. Beyond providing clear signposting, this also means that there is an inevitable overlap between press coverage and key reports. Additionally, this study has also been guided by the reflective practice outlined in chapter one, whereby the ability to meet with key stakeholders has provided invaluable insight by sharing key reports and documents that, while publicly available, would have been more difficult to locate.

In addition to publicly available reports and documentation, this study also makes use of privately held documents such as the UKCoC bid document. A full list of documents can be found in table 4.4.2. Access to documents was secured through broader academic-industry networks. Once again, this underlines the benefits of the collaborative studentship process, to secure access to sensitive and private documentation that would have otherwise been unavailable. Further, this is augmented by my physical presence at key meetings including FPPB meetings and events that have enabled me to develop an observational and reflective practice and in securing access to documents that were circulated at each meeting. In addition to this, several meetings were held on a one-to-one basis with a representative from the local authority's marketing and communications department during which documentation and

access was discussed and provided. While these meetings provided an invaluable insight into the communications being developed about Paisley from *inside*, there was a concern that representatives always appeared to stay on message, with a perceived reticence to divulge information that would be perceived to be critical of the local authority’s work. Admittedly, this is a relatively minor problem in the case of this data analysis. While there undoubtedly an element of selection bias on the part of key stakeholders, the aim of these meetings was not to coerce members of the local authority or partners into divulging or sharing sensitive information or share their critical perspective. Rather, the aim of the documentary and newspaper data analysis was to gain a fuller understanding of the *type* of messages communicated and *how* they have been developed. It is worth noting, also, that any inconsistencies, debates and tensions were teased out during the course of one-to-one interviews. Taken together, newspaper and documentary data allow me to answer research question one, by exploring *what* discourses have been projected about Paisley and cultural regeneration.

Year	Title	Publisher
2014	The Untold Story	Renfrewshire Council
2016	Paisley town centre action plan 2016-2026	Renfrewshire Council
2016	The Creative Renfrewshire Cultural Strategy	Renfrewshire Leisure
2017	Paisley City of Culture 2021 Bid Document	Paisley 2021 bid committee
2018	Paisley: Our Journey Continues	Renfrewshire Council

2018	Leadership Board Meeting – Cultural Regeneration, Legacy Planning Update	Future Paisley Partnership Board
2018	Cultural Regeneration - Legacy Programme Update	Renfrewshire Council
2018	Renfrewshire visitor Strategy 2018-2021	Renfrewshire Council
2019	Brand Journey 2019-2020	Renfrewshire Council/Paisley.is
2019	Future Paisley Core Brief	Future Paisley Partnership Board
2019	Future Paisley Evaluation Information	Centre for Culture, Sport and Events
2019	Future Paisley Partnership Board Update	Renfrewshire Council/Future Paisley Partnership Board
2020	Paisley is open: A vision for Paisley town centre 2030	Renfrewshire council

Table 4.4.2 List of documents

Once each phase of data collection was completed, all files were loaded into NVIVO for analysis. The first task was to organise material chronologically. As discussed throughout this chapter, the publication of the *The Untold Story* report has been used as a baseline document for this study. There were, however, some notable gaps in documents available. There is a notable lack of documentation from *during* the UKCoC bid process. This is perhaps unsurprising given the links between the researcher and the academic-industry network,

particularly given that the local authority no longer employs a number of personnel from the UKCoC bid. This is compounded by the creation of new posts to oversee the leadership of Future Paisley, and concomitant shift towards a more 'holistic cultural regeneration' (CCSE, n.d).

4.5 Interviews and workshops

In addition to newspaper and documentary data, semi-structured interviews and group workshops were also held. Interviews were held with key external stakeholders within the local authority, third-sector agencies and other key actors who were involved in creation of narratives relating to both Paisley's UKCoC bid, as well as the broader development of cultural regeneration within the area. In doing so, semi-structured interviews answered research question one, by exploring the way in which discourses of Paisley and cultural regeneration have been constructed during the research period (2014-2020). This section details the design, implementation and analysis of semi-structured interviews. In planning interviews, a number of ethical, theoretical and practical issues arose which merit comment. I begin by reflecting on the design of interviews by discussing access to participants, the style of interview chosen (semi-structured), and the decision to hold interviews online. In doing so, I explain why this is appropriate for this research project in ethical and theoretical terms. Building on this, I then discuss the execution of these interviews before discussing how data will be analysed.

4.5.1 Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews remain one of the most common qualitative research methods (see Bryman, 2012; Morris, 2015; Diccio-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006), and there are numerous advantages in conducting interviews in this manner. Bryman (2012) demonstrates that

interviews allow for the collection of rich qualitative data about the experiences, views and opinions of the respondent. Semi-structured interviews are typically organised around predetermined open-ended questions, with additional questions emerging from the interaction between the researcher and interviewee (Dicicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). The ability to probe and follow-up an interviewees initial answer to the pre-determined questions presents an immediate advantage of enabling greater flexibility when compared with more rigid forms of qualitative data collection such as survey-based research (Bryman, 2012). It is worth noting, however, that not all interviewees are receptive to this interviewing style, and in some cases, it is necessary for the interviewer to adopt a more direct approach (King et al., 2019). A degree of stylistic discretion is required when conducting interviews. It is true, therefore, that there is no one size fits all approach to interviewing.

For this research, I utilised one-to-one semi-structured interviews guided by pre-determined questions and themes, while allowing sufficient space for the interview to be influenced by the participant's interests, expertise and experiences. Utilising semi-structured interviews allowed me to go beyond understanding *what* narratives have been projected about Paisley and cultural regeneration (research question one) to explore *how* they have been created, as well as the decision-making process behind their construction (research question two). With this in mind, it was important to ensure that the appropriate voices were included in this research. This raises questions of access to, and selection of, interview participants.

4.5.1.1 Access to and selection of participants

In total, 16 respondents were interviewed for this research. The selection of interviewees was informed by the newspaper and documentary analysis, combined with the reflective process of being *within* the local authority throughout the research period via an industry-academic

partnership. Being *within* the local authority (to whatever degree) is important as being in close proximity to relevant local actors and institutions allowed me to observe the key actors and decision makers within the local authority and partners first-hand. These observations lend themselves to recruitment, as prominent figures, such as the Head of Marketing and Communications within the local authority and the former Strategic Lead for Cultural Regeneration, were immediately obvious to me as the researcher as important actors.

The relatively high status (relative to the local context) of participants recruited merits some further investigation. More specifically, it is necessary to reflect on the epistemological and methodological significance of elite interviews as a form of qualitative interview (Harvey, 2011). Interviewing 'up' - as opposed to 'across' or 'down' - refers to the differing positionality and power relationships that emerge when interviewing elite respondents (see Darbi and Hall, 2014; Harvey, 2011). When one interviews 'up', they interview someone in a position of relative power, which, in turn, alters the dynamic of the interview (Darbi and Hall, 2014). There are, however, enormous benefits in interviewing elites, inasmuch as elites are able to make available confidential or behind the scenes information which might otherwise not be available (Schoenberger, 1991, cited in Darbi and Hall, 2014). Elite interviews are important in seeking to understand and potentially change business and political decision-making processes (ibid). This is clearly essential in the context of my research in that elite perspectives are essential in understanding *how* key narratives of cultural regeneration in Paisley have been developed and by whom (see research question one).

However, not all respondents can be classified as elite. For example, while it is clear former council leaders or high-ranking employees might be given elite status, other respondents had less elite status, such as local activists or former business owners (see appendix A-4 for a full

breakdown of respondents). In such cases, there is an increased risk that an interview request might not be anticipated as voluntary. This is not a unique problem when doing research within organisations (see Bryman, 2012). Murray (2015), reflecting on her research with(in) Police Scotland, notes the methodological challenges of being both an outsider and a partner, insofar as this can create discomfort among participants who feel they are being researched. In the context of my research, this was mitigated by reassuring participants that their participation was voluntary during initial contact, prior to and on completion of the interview. Further, the risk of coercion was also reduced by ensuring participants were given the right to withdraw from the research at any point prior to the submission of the thesis.

All respondents were formally recruited via e-mail. Initial contact provided an overview of the research aims and a brief explanation of why the individual had been selected for inclusion in the study (see Appendix A-3). Email correspondence was sent from my university e-mail account, as doing so established a more formal, professional tone. Communicating professionally is particularly important when conducting interviews with elite participants inasmuch the:

...recruitment of elites, people in powerful positions, requires a formal approach. It is probably best to write a letter where you set out who you are, explain the study and say why you would like to interview the person concerned and how the interview will be used (Morris, 2015: 4)

Furthermore, a degree of flattery is needed insofar as the researcher must 'flatter the prospective interviewee by emphasising that his or her input would be beneficial to your research' (Richards, 1999 cited in Morris, 2015: 4). It is worth noting, however, that there was a degree of informality insofar as pre-existing networks between myself and the broader

industry-academic partnership created a pre-existing means of communication that helped secure access to participants. This is advantageous as it generated a greater willingness to take part in my research. As Morris (2015) acknowledges, elite participants are often reluctant to take part in a research project where no pre-existing relationship to the research(er) exists. The relationship between myself (as the researcher) and the broader academic-institutional network was cultivated since my recruitment to the project and given that the project pre-dates my recruitment it is clear that key stakeholders recognise the value of this research in and of itself. This is reflected by the successful interview recruitment, with no interview requests being declined by members within my academic-institutional network.

During recruitment, however, some potential participants out with my broader academic-institutional network declined an interview request. In total, 19 participants were contacted for an interview, with only three declining. There are a number of reasons why potential interviewee might decline to participate a research project. On practical grounds, trying to access high-level participants inevitably speaks to the competing priorities of potential participants (see Harvey, 2011). The low rate of refusal reflects one of the advantages of online interviewing (see Jenner and Myers, 2018), in that online interviewing enables a greater degree of flexibility with potential participants when scheduling interviews. When an interview request was not accepted, there is little could be done insofar as it is incumbent on the researcher not to pressure or coerce participation. This does, however, raise some theoretical issues. Given the Foucauldian theoretical perspective that this thesis has taken, interviews were not undertaken with a view toward constructing a grand narrative or uncovering a universal truth. Rather, the aim of interviews was to give participants a chance to share their perspective and the development of cultural regeneration policy in Paisley. For

key actors who declined an interview request, the absence of their voice was (re)constructed as far as possible from the available secondary data.

4.5.1.2 Ethics and consent

Prior to each interview, written informed consent was acquired. Given that interviews were held online, consent could not be gathered via a physical signature. This was overcome by sending participants copies of both the participant information sheet and informed consent form in advance of the interview taking place (see appendix A-1 and A-2). Participants were asked to review all relevant documents before signing and returning them to the researcher. No interview commenced before written consent had been returned. Furthermore, all participants were informed of their right to refuse to participate at any point prior to completion of the research project. Consent is more than a simple tick box exercise and is, rather, an integral part of the research process. Bryman (2012) argues that for written consent to be meaningful, it requires clear understanding from participants. This study used five criteria for assessing consent of participants:

1. Does the participant understand the research aims?
2. Why the participant has been selected for this research?
3. What will happen if they agree to take part?
4. What will happen to the data collected?
5. Can the participant withdraw from the study, retroactively or otherwise?

When assessing this study against these criteria it was clear that I could secure meaningful written (and verbal) informed consent from each respondent prior to each interview. As discussed, the recruitment of participants involved articulating the overall aims of the research, as well as why they had been selected in this study. This was supplemented by

further details about the research, as well as relevant documentation such as participant information sheet. Finally, this was augmented further by ensuring that, as the researcher, I was available to discuss any questions about the research prior to gaining participant consent. This ensured that the first three criteria for assessing informed consent were met. With regards to the final two criteria, participants were not fully anonymised but were informed of their right to retroactively withdraw consent or make small amendments to their interview transcript upon the completion of interviews.

Given the aim of the interviews is to articulate the role key actors in the development of key narratives about Paisley and regeneration it would make little sense to fully anonymise responses, as in doing so would make the task of exploring the key debates, tensions and issues that arose internally a significant challenge. The elite nature of the interviews means that anonymising their responses would strip the data of necessary context insofar as the elite status of respondents adds weight to their words by corroborating their influence in debates about Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration. Ellersgaard et al (2021) argue that it is difficult to contextualise the elite positions of interviewees when 'hard' anonymity (complete anonymity) is granted. However, 'soft' anonymity - where name and professional details are '*blurred*' - can provide an effective compromise (ibid, p.10). As such, this study has *blurred* the identity of respondents without making them fully anonymous. While respondents are not named in this thesis, their job title has been listed when quoting from their interview. One advantage of blurring the identity of respondents is that it can be done to varying degrees corresponding to the relative status of the respondents. For example, local community activists interviewed for this research cannot be said to have the same status as directors and

council leaders. With this in mind, it is necessary to blur their identity to a greater degree to protect a greater degree of anonymity.

4.5.1.3 Post-interview procedure

On completion of each interview, I produced a verbatim written transcript. Transcription is commonplace in qualitative research that contains a discursive component and translating audio materials into textual data is necessary in creating a data set that can be analysed (Bryman, 2012). I also produced written summaries which were used as a guide for the research in helping to organise and store data. All data was stored on my university laptop, which is password protected. Data was only accessible to my immediate supervisory team and myself (as the doctoral researcher). All data was stored, in addition, on a password protected OneDrive account to protect the data in the event of damage to the laptop.

Given that participants were not fully anonymised, each respondent was sent a full written transcript of the interview, as well as a written summary. Respondents were given the opportunity to request minor amendments, for example, the removal of small amounts of material. Allowing participants to review and potentially alter their interview ensures that interviewees do not feel misrepresented by the interview transcript, which is of heightened importance given a potential lack of total anonymity. This was also a useful mechanism for reassuring participants and thereby creating a more free-flowing dialogue during the interview itself. Asking a potential interviewee to go on the record without guaranteed anonymity or recourse to future amendments could cause distress to interviewees and inhibit their ability to speak candidly during the interview. Enabling the respondent to review and agree to a final interview transcript enables a degree of control for the respondent and can establish greater trust with the researcher.

There was a risk, of course, that participants would seek to retroactively censor controversial or critical material from the interview transcript. This was mitigated by establishing rapport and trust with the participant, but also in designing interviews effectively. The aim of the interview is not to deceive participants into disclosing information that would not otherwise be forthcoming, or to frame issues being discussed in a critical way. Rather, the aim is to allow the respondents space to articulate their views and experiences and in doing so shed light on the research questions. With this in mind, it was unlikely that allowing participants to request amendments to the transcript had any detrimental impact on this research and on the data gathered. Indeed, only one respondent requested any amendments, which amounted to the removal of swear words and unprofessional language while leaving the remaining content of the interview unchanged.

4.5.2 My Paisley, my stories: workshops with local communities

The final phase of primary fieldwork was conducted using online workshops with local residents to explore their perceptions of Paisley and how the town has been represented in the media. The purpose of holding workshops was to ensure a greater range of perspectives were included in the research and to explore how community voices can challenge (or confirm) the dominant narratives that have emerged during the course of this research. In sum, it is essential to decentre, to some extent, the official discourses of cultural regeneration that have circulated about Paisley by gauging local community knowledge, and perception, of these dominant discourses. From a methodological standpoint this fits within the Foucauldian theoretical framework outlined above insofar as this can attest to the importance of counter-narrative, and as well as power, in the production of discourse and knowledge of cultural regeneration in Paisley.

4.5.2.1 Access to and selection of participants

In total, three workshops were scheduled to take place between April and May of 2021. However, due to poor attendance, the first workshop scheduled had to be cancelled. As such, two workshops were included in the research study, with a total of seven respondents across workshop one and two (2 and 5 respondents respectively). Participants were recruited via a variety of methods. For workshop one, participants were recruited using an open call which was posted online, as well as distributed through various distribution lists of key community groups and third sector organisations. Information about the workshop - and details on how to participate - was distributed, via community groups, to community members – reflecting a snowballing method of sampling (Bryman, 2021; Handcock and Gile, 2011).

Workshop attendance was poor, reflecting the difficulty in recruiting participants to participate in online workshops and the problems associated with completing (online) fieldwork during the coronavirus pandemic. Participants in workshop one were local residents who had been actively involved in culture and heritage networks within Paisley, either voluntarily or through employment. Workshop two was facilitated in partnership with the Star Project, a local third sector organisation based in the North-West of Paisley, which typically works with vulnerable members of the community. The involvement of the Star Project led to an improved attendance for workshop two, enabling greater access to grassroots participants who would have otherwise been unlikely to participate in the research. This underlines the benefit of working collaboratively insofar as this enabled greater access to data and potential participants who would otherwise be unavailable (Bryman, 2012).

4.5.2.2 Workshop design

The two local resident workshops were facilitated online using the Microsoft Teams platform. Each workshop lasted two hours. Online workshops, similar to other group qualitative techniques such as focus groups, are a common research method (Bryman, 2012). However, the fixed, quasi-hierarchical question and response model of traditional focus groups is potentially problematic insofar as this runs the risk of limiting the data that can be gathered by limiting respondents to answering questions (Bryman, 2012). This is not to suggest, however, that the use of focus groups must be entirely dismissed. Rather, the ability to gain group insight is a key advantage of using focus groups during this research (Bryman, 2012; Breen, 2006). In addition, focus groups can also allow the respondent to feel more confident expressing their views, whilst also having the opportunity to listen to the perspective and opinions of other respondents (ibid). This provides the immediate advantage of providing a rich source of qualitative data from a range of respondents, simultaneously. However, there is a need to go beyond the question and response nature of traditional focus groups. Practically speaking, this means that in addition to more broad questions about the perceptions and experiences of cultural regeneration in Paisley, respondents were asked to respond to specific examples of media representation of Paisley in recent years specifically within the context of cultural regeneration. Additionally, discussion of Paisley was also supplemented with more interactive tasks, such as designing a 'postcard' from Paisley.

4.5.2.3 Ethical considerations for workshops

Consent for participation in workshops was gained using a similar method and principles as in interviews. Written and verbal consent was gained from respondents prior to the commencement of workshops. There were, however, some added challenges working with

potentially vulnerable members of the community. Given the power dynamic between established and trusted community organisations and members of the local communities, it was essential to ensure that participation was read as voluntary without any potentially coercive dynamics that could drive community members to participate. This was mitigated by advising all participants on the call that their participation was voluntary and that they were free to withdraw at any point during the meeting, and their response could be withdrawn from the final transcript until the submission of the final research project.

No personal information was collected during either workshop. Both workshops were recorded using Microsoft Teams for transcription purposes and a verbatim transcript of each workshop was produced. Each respondent was assigned a pseudonym to protect their anonymity while simultaneously ensuring each contribution could be noted and used for data analysis. All data was stored securely online, using the University's One Drive platform and was only available to the researcher. Data was stored on a password protected university issued laptop, with backups stored in a password protected university One Drive account. All personal data (such as email address or contact information) was deleted upon completion of the research.

4.5.3 Doing fieldwork remotely: practical and ethical considerations

The coronavirus pandemic from March 2020 onwards, presented serious challenges for conducting primary data collection, and social distancing measures in place during the summer of 2020 necessitated that primary fieldwork to be conducted in an online space. This presented no obvious disadvantage insofar as it enabled interviews and workshops to be completed as originally planned. As Janghorban et al (2014: n.p) posits, 'the online interview has overcome time and financial constraints, geographical dispersion and physical mobility

boundaries'. Further, for Archibald et al (2019: 2) there is an increasing 'understanding that online methods can replicate, complement, and possibly improve upon traditional methods, including in-person interviews and focus groups'. It is worth exploring, however, the practical considerations that arise when transitioning to online interviews.

The first consideration I was faced with relates to the type of interview to conduct. Given that the aim was for online interviews to mimic their face-to-face counterpart as much as possible, video calling was deemed preferable to other forms of remote interviewing such as instant messaging or telephone interviews (see Bryman, 2012; Hooley et al, 2012). Video calling allows for both researcher and respondent to see each other in real time via use of webcams, which in turn enables a closer simulation of a face-to-face interview (Janghorban et al, 2014). Being able to see the interviewee, albeit via a computer screen, can be advantageous for the interviewer by allowing an added layer of understanding and analysis during the interview. Jenner and Myers (2018) argue that being able to see the interviewee allows the researcher to gauge non-verbal cues and other non-textual responses that would not be apparent in audio or textual communication. These non-verbal cues can communicate important information to the researcher, about for example the participant's reaction to a particular question.

The shift from in-person to online interviews cannot, however, be considered unimportant merely based on (virtual) face-to-face interaction. To do so would be to discount the influence of spatial and material factors within the interview process and the data gathered. Some scholars have gone as far as to suggest that the removal of physical proximity inhibits the establishment of intimacy and rapport, which are integral to qualitative interviewing (see Jenner and Myers, 2014). However, criticisms of online interviewing have done little to stem

the rising tide of online methodologies, with video calling becoming an increasingly valued tool for qualitative research (Jenner and Myers, 2018). Or, as Weller (2017) puts it, digital technologies have continued to breach the methodological frontier. Jenner and Myers (2018) have concluded that, perhaps, the differences between in-person and online interviews have been overstated. In comparing data gathered via online video conferencing platforms such as Skype with data gathered via in-person interviews, the authors found that conducting interviews online has no impact on the quality or quantity of data collected when doing online interviews. More important, it is argued, is the privacy of the interview. Practically speaking, this suggests that interviews held in a private form (either online or in-person) generally yield better, more reliable data than interviews conducted in a more public setting (in, for example, a café). This can be both enabled and constrained by using online formats.

Protecting privacy is, perhaps, one of the unique challenges of doing research online. Moving to online creates immediate concerns about the use (and management) of personal data and the security of the video-calling itself. Privacy concerns have been exacerbated, particularly in relation to Zoom that has been at the forefront of recent security and privacy concerns, particularly in the early phase of the pandemic (see Archibale et al, 2019; Paul, 2020). Indeed, instances of 'zoom bombing', where a person gains unauthorised access to private meetings on the platform with the aim of disrupting them (often with recourse to verbal abuse), have risen sharply since the coronavirus lockdown was implemented (Paul, 2020). Concerns have arisen, also, about the use of personal data gathered by the company. This concern was heightened by controversial media reports over the (mis)handling of private data by the company, amid allegations that the company had been selling private data (*ibid*). This forced a number of changes to the platform to increase security but perhaps the recent controversy

over Zoom serves as a small example of the issues with conducting research online. The ubiquity of Zoom and Teams make it hard to discount their use in online research, which begs the question as to what measures must be taken to ensure adequate levels of privacy and data protection for respondents.

4.6 Study limitations

There has been, of course, a number of limitations to this study. A primary difficulty was stimulating engagement from local residents. More specifically, uptake for local workshops was poor, with a significant portion of registered attendees not attending the event they had signed up for. As an example, proposed workshops with the Paisley First business improvement district were unable to take place due to the group's inactivity during the pandemic, and their lack of online engagement with members. In sum, it is clear that issues pertaining to the COVID-19 pandemic have placed a number of practical limitations on this research and in particular conducting fieldwork with local residents and stakeholders outwith the purview of Future Paisley and the CCSE. This was mitigated by hosting a workshop with local community group the STAR project who encouraged their service users to take part. Nonetheless, the impossibility of hosting events in person made accessing target populations more difficult. It is clear, therefore, that the coronavirus outbreak and concomitant social distancing measures has had an impact on the methodological direction of this project. As such, this thesis makes greater use of data from existing newspaper reporting, semi-structured interviews and published reports and documents about cultural regeneration in Paisley.

Furthermore, in more methodological terms, the relatively small nature of Paisley has created a limit of the pool on potential respondents. This is, perhaps, most explicit within the UKCoC

bid team, as well as the FPPB. This created somewhat of a smaller saturation point insofar as the ability to generate more unique perspectives by incorporating additional perspectives diminished somewhat quickly after key actors had been identified and contacted. Thus, while access to respondents was generally good, there is a limitation in terms of the availability of suitable elite respondents, even if there was general willingness to participate among local government and third sector actors. When taken together, the relatively small sample size (in total 23 respondents) is perhaps a reflection of both the uncertain period through which the research was conducted as well as the complexities when researching a smaller town, with a more limited number of key actors eligible for selection.

4.7 Conclusion

In this chapter, I set out to outline the methodological approach used in this study. To begin, I outlined the dominant theoretical and methodological approach to the study of cultural regeneration and newspaper representation of Paisley. I have applied the theoretical axioms of Foucauldian discourse analysis to the context of discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley. Using a Foucauldian approach enabled an understanding of the relationship between discourse, power and knowledge. In turn, this enabled this research to understand the conditions of possibility that enable and constrain specific discourses and representations of Paisley to develop.

I have outlined the specific methods used to explore discourses and representations of Paisley, utilising documentary data, newspaper reporting, and data gathered during interviews and workshops. Newspaper and documentary data provide an in-depth and varied account of the official narratives and discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley, and the extent to which this has changed over time. Semi-structured interviews with elite

stakeholders provide a way of understanding construction of cultural regeneration discourse, the changing influence of certain ideas and personnel over time and how this is reflected in the narratives projected to represent Paisley. Finally, workshops with local residents, though somewhat limited in scope, provided an overview of local receptions to representations of Paisley. When taken together, the methodological approach adopted and the methods employed for this study enabled an in-depth exploration of discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley. Chapter five and six will present the findings from this study in light of the methodological considerations presented in this chapter. Chapter five will present newspaper and documentary data, while chapter six will present oral data gathered during interviews and workshops.

Chapter 5: Narratives of cultural regeneration in newspaper reporting on Paisley

5.1 Introduction

In previous chapters, I have discussed the construction of (negative) area reputations, and the role of cultural regeneration strategies as a means of changing them. The purpose of the first of two findings chapters is to explore the narratives communicated about Paisley and cultural regeneration in newspaper reporting since the publication of the baseline document *The Untold Story* in 2014. In this chapter, I present a detailed analysis of newspaper coverage (local, national and international) between 2014 and 2020, and in doing so explore the key messages that have been communicated about Paisley and cultural regeneration during a period of significant investment in the town's cultural infrastructure.

I begin by providing an overview of the dataset by discussing the *type* of coverage as well as the general sentiment of newspaper reporting. I break down the proportion of local, national and international newspaper reporting in the data gathered. Building on this, I then discuss the *content* of newspaper coverage of Paisley, culture and regeneration. The dominant focus of newspaper coverage is on Paisley's cultural offer, developing the town as a cultural destination, civic pride and changing attitudes about the town. In sum, discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley tends to foreground flagship cultural facilities, developing the visitor economy and town centre regeneration.

5.2 Exploring the sentiment and volume of newspaper reporting between 2014-2020

The purpose of this section is to explore the 150 newspaper articles analysed for this study. Table 5.2.1 details the newspapers that are included in the data, the type of newspaper

format of each publication, and their most recently available circulation figures. Each newspaper has been classified as either Broadsheet, Tabloid, or Online. Broadsheet newspapers typically refer to large print newspapers. Broadsheets, in popular perception at least, are believed to be ‘quality newspapers’, which typically have a more educated and middle-class readership and focus on ‘hard news’ (Foos and Bischof, 2021; Chakraborty et al., 2017). Tabloid papers are typically focused on less hard news, are written in less sophisticated prose and have more broad appeal (Johansson, 2007). Tabloid newspapers are typically defined by more sensationalist coverage and eye-catching headlines (Foos and Bischof, 2021). Online, for the purposes of this research, refers to a publication that is entirely web-based (for example, BBC news).

By breaking down newspaper reporting by format, it is possible to understand the intersection between the *type* of newspaper format, the likely reach of each paper (as indicated by circulation numbers) and where newspaper representation of Paisley was most prominent – this is discussed throughout section 5.2.1.

Paper	Type	Print Circulation
The Guardian	Broadsheet	108,687 (2020)
Financial Times	Broadsheet	157,982 (2020)
The Times	Tabloid	368,929 (2020)

The Independent	Online	N/A
Daily Record	Tabloid	104,343 (2020)
The Scottish Sun	Tabloid / Online	Unavailable*
The National	Tabloid	9,476 (2017)
The Herald	Broadsheet	25,869 (2017)
The Scotsman	Broadsheet	19,449 (2017)
Paisley Daily Express	Tabloid	8,959 (2017)
The Gazette	Tabloid (weekly)	5,016 (weekly) (2013)
Glasgow Times	Tabloid	20,874 (2017)
New York Times	Online	N/A
Irish Independent	Online	N/A

*Table 5.2.1 Type of Publication by Format & Circulation Figures (Audit Bureau of Circulation, 2020 and Press Gazette, 2018) *Figures from the Scottish Sun are not published publicly with only data from the UK-wide edition readily available*

Table 5.2.2 shows a fairly uneven distribution of the type of coverage, with a majority of articles appearing in local newspapers (57%), a large minority of articles published in national newspapers (40%), with only 2% in international publications.

Type	Number	Percentage
Local	86	57
National (Scottish only)	48	32
National (UK wide)	13	9
International	3	2
Total	150	

Table 5.2.2 Type of coverage by region

Breaking this down, Table 5.2.3 shows the uneven distribution of coverage between local newspapers. Just under three quarters (72%) of coverage of Paisley and regeneration appears in the *Paisley Daily Express*, with other local print media outlets such as the *Evening Times* (now the *Glasgow Times*) and *The Gazette* contributing just over 28% of all local coverage. This is perhaps unsurprising given the differing regions covered by each publication. While each of the three newspapers are *local* in the sense that they are not *national* publications and cover a region of the country that encapsulates Paisley, the *Paisley Daily Express* is the only local publication which focuses *specifically* on Paisley. The *Glasgow Times* covers the broader Greater Glasgow metropolitan area, while *The Gazette* covers the broader Renfrewshire region. The disproportionate amount of coverage in the *Paisley Daily Express*

appears to also be as a result of explicit focus or targeting from within the marketing and communications department of the local authority, as well as the Paisley 2021 media campaign team (Bold, 2018).

Newspaper	Number	Percentage of Local coverage
Paisley Daily Express	62	72
The Gazette	13	15
Evening Times	11	13
Total	86	

Table 5.2.3 Breakdown of local newspaper coverage between 2014-2020

Table 5.2.4 illustrates the more even nature of Scottish newspaper coverage. *The Herald* contained the highest concentration of articles in the national press (50%). Beyond this, there is an even spread of articles in national newspapers. Tabloid newspapers (such as *the Sun* and *the Daily Record*) account for a relatively small percentage of the overall data. Broadsheet outlets such as *the Herald* constitute the majority of newspaper coverage at the Scottish level.

Newspaper	Number	% of national coverage
Daily Record	7	15
The Scottish Sun	5	10
The Herald	24	50

The National	6	13
The Scotsman	6	13
Total	48	

Table 5.2.4 Breakdown of Scottish newspaper coverage between 2014-2020

Table 5.2.5 breaks down the sample of newspaper reporting that circulated throughout the entire UK. This does not include the Scottish only editions of national newspapers. For example, articles from the *Scottish Sun* have been categorised as Scottish newspaper as these articles were only circulated in Scotland (though, of course, are available online). Table 5.2.4 shows an even distribution of UK wide newspaper reporting. Both *The Guardian* and *The Times* had a similar number of stories about Paisley with four and six articles, respectively. Coverage was more limited in *The Independent* and the *Financial Times* with only two and one stories.

It is interesting to compare the difference between exclusively Scottish and UK wide newspapers. Clearly, a much greater percentage of articles in the dataset are from exclusively Scottish publications, with 48 (35%) articles coming from these newspapers compared to 13 (10%) from UK wide publications. The disparity between Scottish and UK wide publications suggests that representations of Paisley have been most prominent locally and within the Scottish national context with a comparative lack of representation at UK national and international levels.

Newspaper	Number	% of UK coverage
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The Guardian	4	31
The Independent	2	15
The Times	6	46
Financial Times	1	8
Total	13	

Table 5.2.5 Breakdown of UK newspaper coverage between 2014-2020

Table 5.2.6 breaks down the small amount of international newspaper coverage, with the majority of international coverage (67%) coming from the Irish edition of the *Independent*. This is unsurprising given that Ireland is the closest international country outside of the four nations of the United Kingdom. There are some omissions from the data, as the research focused only on English language newspapers. This means, therefore, that articles on Paisley which have appeared in, for example, Dutch paper *De Telegraaf* or Chinese language paper *The Chinese Weekly* have not been included in the sample. The exclusion of non-English language newspapers has a negligible impact on the findings presented from this study insofar as the aforementioned newspapers were the only discussed examples of non-English language newspaper reporting highlighted by the bid campaign team (see Bold, 2018).

It is unsurprising that international coverage accounts for a small percentage of total newspaper reporting within the context of both Paisley's 2021 UKCoC bid and cultural regeneration more generally. Garcia et al (2010), in their evaluation of media coverage prior to, during and in the wake of Liverpool's year as ECOC in 2008, demonstrate that international coverage typically constitutes a lower proportion of total media coverage of cultural events

and festivals. This is compounded by the more domestic focus of the UKCoC title that Paisley was bidding for. This creates a paradox here for the UKCoC bid team, given their stated aim to reinforce the international significance of Paisley, its heritage and its cultural offer discussed below in section 5.4.

Newspaper	Number	% of international coverage
New York Times	1	33
Irish Independent	2	67
Total	3	

Table 5.2.6 Breakdown of International Coverage between 2014-2020

5.2.1 Sentiment of coverage

In this section, I present the sentiment of newspaper reporting. The sentiment of newspaper reporting is, of course, a subjective measurement that cannot be objectively assessed. Nonetheless, as demonstrated above, measuring the purported sentiment of newspaper reporting is common in the literature extolling the virtues of reputational change and cultural events (see Garcia, 2005; Melville et al, 2008; Richards and Wilson, 2004). With this in mind, it is essential that some attempt is made to ascertain the broad sentiment of newspaper reporting of Paisley, cultural regeneration and the UKCoC bid. Sentiment, as presented in this section, was analysed on the basis of a variety of factors including: the volume of text which conveyed a particular image of Paisley, the ratio between conflicting images of Paisley presented within a single article (or in other words, the balance between positive and negative within the article itself) and the wider context through which Paisley is discussed.

For example, an example of 'negative' newspaper reporting can be found in the *Financial Times*:

If there was ever a town with image problems it is Paisley the former textile powerhouse just outside Glasgow that for decades has been a byword for drugs, deprivation and high street decline (Financial Times, 29 December 2019)

An example of positive newspaper reporting is this passage from *The Sun*

THIS will give Paisley a real injection of pride again. For a while places like Causeyside Street have been battered by Braehead shopping centre and the town started to feel a bit tired. But something like this is a reminder of the proud cultural past that we have in Paisley. (The Sun, 16 July, 2017)

While both excerpts depict similar discourses of town centre decline (discussed below), the passage from *The Sun* more explicitly reinforces the narrative that this clearly positions cultural regeneration as a positive force for reversing decline and changing perceptions. When taken together, these factors helped provide a more robust means of categorising the sentiment of newspaper reporting while resisting overly simplistic judgments of the overall sentiment of any given article.

Paisley, prior to 2014, had typically attracted negative media coverage, which focused on high levels of socio-economic inequality, poverty and unemployment in the town and the broader Renfrewshire area. However, the claim that Paisley had a poor image and reputation is difficult to fully substantiate given the hitherto lack of research on Paisley and how the town is represented in the media. Nonetheless, it is clear – as will be discussed in subsequent

chapters – there was a clear belief among respondents that Paisley’s representation was overwhelmingly negative prior to 2014. In terms of this research, newspaper coverage of cultural regeneration in Paisley has been overwhelmingly positive. Table 5.2.7 demonstrates that 78% of media coverage adopted a generally positive tone and only 14% generally negative. This is consistent with other research which illustrates that the build-up to (in this case the bid for), and period immediately after, cultural events and festivals produces positive coverage of both the event itself and the host town or city (see Garcia, 2005, 2003; Smith, 2012). Garcia et al (2010) demonstrate, for example, that Liverpool’s year as ECOC produced 70% positive or neutral press coverage.

Focusing on articles which relate only to cultural regeneration in Paisley can be argued to skew the sample towards more positive newspaper reporting insofar as this is, generally speaking, predisposed to more positive coverage (see Garcia, 2005; Comunian and Mould, 2014). On one hand, this speaks to the importance of cultural regeneration in leveraging positive newspaper reporting. On the other hand, this suggests that this is an incomplete picture, in that issues that tend to secure negative coverage (such as crime and unemployment) are not, generally speaking, spoken about in the data. Negative coverage, where it did appear, was generally used as a way of reinforcing either the need for regeneration or the success of past or present regeneration initiatives (such as Future Paisley or the UKCOC bid campaign). This is discussed in greater depth in section 5.3.

Sentiment	Number of articles?	% of articles?
Positive	117	78
Neutral	21	14
Negative	12	8
Total	150	

Table 5.2.7 Sentiment of coverage

In terms of local media coverage (as illustrated in Table 5.2.8), there are some clear differences when compared with the overall data. While the level of neutral coverage is consistent, there is a difference of around 10% in terms of both positive and negative coverage. 86% of local coverage was positive, with 12% neutral and only 5% negative coverage. When viewed as a proportion of the overall data, local coverage amounts to 53% of positive coverage, 38% of neutral and only 14% of negative coverage. This illustrates, again, that local media outlets played a central role in the circulation of positive media coverage in that it constitutes a slight majority of overall positive coverage, despite constituting only 57% of the overall data. This appears, however, to be reflection of the UkCoC bid team’s deliberate attempt to secure a positive local coverage via a partnership with the *Paisley Daily Express* (Bold, 2018).

Sentiment	Number	% of local
Positive	74	86

Neutral	9	10
negative	3	3
total	86	

Table 5.2.8 Sentiment of local coverage

In terms of national coverage, newspaper reporting was still overwhelmingly positive, as illustrated in Table 5.2.9, with 77% of coverage positive and 15% neutral, meaning that only 8% was negative. The majority of negative coverage about Paisley and its regeneration originated in Scottish national newspaper coverage. Breaking this down by publication, the majority of negative articles appeared in *The Herald* (3 articles). It appears, therefore, that negative articles did not feature in tabloid newspapers, at least insofar as this relates to regeneration in Paisley.

Sentiment	Number	% of National
Positive	37	77
Neutral	7	15
negative	4	8
total	60	

Table 5.2.9 Sentiment of Scottish National coverage

Table 5.2.10 demonstrates the sentiment of UK national coverage. 38% of UK-wide coverage was positive, with 31% being either negative or neutral. This breakdown suggests that UK-wide newspaper reporting was more evenly distributed between positive, neutral and negative articles than more localised coverage (i.e Scottish or local). Indeed, both local and Scottish newspaper coverage was overwhelmingly positive. A clear pattern emerges, insofar as newspaper reporting was *less* positive when published in more widely circulated publications at either Scottish or UK national level. In terms of specific national newspapers, *The Guardian* was the most likely to feature positive stories with three positive stories and one neutral. *The Times* had an even breakdown of positive, negative and neutral coverage, with each category contain two articles, with a total of six articles. *The Independent* contained one neutral and one negative article. The UKCoC bid also attracted coverage from the UK based *Financial Times* (FT) which, although UK-based, has a large international circulation (see Financial Times, N.D). The FT coverage featured Paisley in the midst of the UKCoC campaign, however unlike the other national and local coverage it depicted a different account of the bid, situating it within a more balanced discussion of the socio-economic inequality that, in turn, drives the need for regeneration in Paisley.

Sentiment	Number	% of UK
Positive	5	38
Neutral	4	31
negative	4	30

total	13
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Table 5.2.10 Sentiment of UK National Coverage

Finally, Table 5.2.11 demonstrates the sentiment of the limited amount of international coverage. A small number of articles were identified in international newspapers. Nonetheless, it remains useful to track the narratives projected about Paisley in international newspaper reporting in spite of the limited data available. In any case, positive press coverage was reported in the Irish edition of the *Independent*. In addition to this, the *Independent* also contained more neutral coverage, with their coverage generally focusing on Paisley’s UKCoC bid. The bid campaign also attracted attention from some heavyweight international publications, in the form of the *New York Times*. The *New York Times* piece, however, focused more on linking Paisley with economic misfortune in the context of Britain’s exit from the EU and in doing so, perpetuated the narrative that Paisley been ‘left behind’ that has become common place when discussing post-industrial cities in a globalised, neoliberal landscape (see Mondon and Winter, 2020). In sum, despite the limited number of international newspaper articles, the variation in ‘control’ over the narrative that, perhaps, explains a departure from national, and particularly local, press coverage insofar as it is not as distinctly on brand.

Sentiment	Number	% of international coverage
Positive	1	25

Neutral	2	50
Negative	1	25
Total	4	

Table 5.2.11 Sentiment of international coverage

5.2.2 Newspaper coverage over time

In addition to identifying the sentiment of newspaper reporting, it is also important to understand how newspaper reporting varies over time – before in volume but in also in the *content* of newspaper reporting. This reflects the Foucauldian methodological approach adopted by this thesis, as this allows an analysis of how ‘official’ discourses of cultural regeneration. This reflects Foucauldian theory insofar as understanding the (dis)continuity of discourse and unstable, situated and divergent evolution of knowledge and ‘truth’ is essential to the Foucauldian intellectual project (see McHoul and Grace, 1993). With this in mind, the remainder of this chapter will explore the *content* of reporting of Paisley and the *volume* of newspaper reporting and documentary data over time.

Table 5.2.12 breaks down the time period covered during this research. This has been broken down both by the year and by the season starting in the winter of 2014 through to the spring of 2020. The classification of the winter season covers both the previous month of December, as well as January and February of the following year. For example, the season categorised as ‘winter 2014/15’ refers to December 2014, along with January and February 2015. The winter

of 2014 is the exception. This is because data collection commenced during the winter period. As such, the winter 2014 period covers only January and February, and does not include December of the preceding year.

To begin, the period selected for this research coincides with the launch of *The Untold Story* in 2014. This launch generated a spike in newspaper reporting about heritage, regeneration and culture in Paisley at this time. Indeed, the winter and spring period of 2014 both included six articles, the highest concentration of coverage until autumn 2015. The data for winter 2014 predominantly consisted of local newspaper articles in the *Paisley Daily Express*, as well as one national piece featured in *The Herald*, which covered the launch of *The Untold Story*, as well as the potential bid for UKCoC. A similar trend was observable throughout the spring period, with exclusively local coverage focusing on heritage, *The Untold Story* and the potential economic benefits of exploiting Paisley's heritage assets, particularly in regenerating the town centre. Despite a slight drop off in volume of newspaper coverage, there was a similar trend until summer 2015, with each period containing between two and three articles. This is, however, until autumn 2015 where there was an increase to seven articles. This appears to coincide with the UKCoC bid gaining momentum, with national newspapers including the *Daily Record*, *The Herald* and *The Scotsman* each running stories on the UKCoC bid.

The preceding winter (2015/16) period contained no direct coverage of the UKCoC bid, with an overall decline in newspaper reporting to five articles. Local and national coverage focused, instead, on significant investment in Paisley Museum, the launch of the Paisley First business improvement district and plans for a cinema and arts space in the town centre. Spring 2016 saw a continued focus on Paisley town centre (albeit with less overall coverage, with only

three articles across local and national publications). Indeed, both the *Paisley Daily Express* and *The Gazette* focused on town centre regeneration, while the *Daily Record* had a more explicit focus on the UKCoC bid. In sum, there was some oscillation in terms of *volume* of newspaper coverage between the launch of *The Untold Story* and the summer period of 2016. In terms of *focus*, there is a degree of consistency, with newspaper reporting covering *The Untold Story*, the economic benefits of heritage investment and the launch of the UKCoC bid, though the bid had yet to generate significant media interest in the early stage of the process.

From summer 2016 onwards, the UKCoC bid did start to have a significant impact on the volume of media coverage focused on Paisley. Indeed, the period ranging from summer 2016 through to winter 2017/18 (with the exception of spring 2017), had consistently higher levels of newspaper coverage compared with immediately after the UKCoC bid period. In summer 2016, for example, seven of the nine published articles focused primarily on the bid. Focus on the bid came from both local and national newspapers. At the local level, the *Paisley Daily Express* featured a reflection on the first year of the bid campaign. At national level, there was a significant increase in reporting of the bid, with four articles in *The Herald*, and an article in *The Sun*. This trend continued into throughout autumn and winter period, with a more equitable distribution of national and local level coverage. Indeed, nine national articles appeared during this time, compared with ten local articles, as well as more internationally orientated features in the *Financial Times*. This is in quite clear contrast to the initial phase of *The Untold Story* and bid launch, which saw more limited national newspaper reporting with a strong emphasis on local coverage. This reflects the importance of the UKCoC bid campaign, and arguably the importance of event bidding more generally, in leveraging a greater volume of newspaper coverage.

There was, however, a slight decline in volume of newspaper reporting in the spring and summer of 2016 (to eight and then six, respectively). However, a similar trend was notable in national newspaper coverage, with eight national publications reporting on the UKCoC bid during this period. Similarly, five local newspaper articles were also published and two international stories. The *New York Times* discussed Paisley in the context of Brexit, Scottish Independence and the bid, and *The Independent* focused more explicitly on the bid itself. The consistently high levels of coverage at this time coincided with an important moment in the bid campaign, when Paisley was shortlisted for the UKCoC title. There was a spike in more neutral coverage at this time as reporting focused on reporting the shortlist rather than the narrative details promoted by the bid campaign itself. Finally, the autumn and winter of 2017/18 represented the peak in volume of coverage of the UKCoC bid. First, in winter 2017/18 it was announced that Paisley had been unsuccessful in the UKCoC bid, generating 18 articles in the built up to, and in the wake of, the announcement on the 7th December 2017.

The rhythm of newspaper coverage, both peaking during the bid and then receding after, is consistent with other research on the impact of cultural events on place-focused media coverage. Garcia (2010) demonstrates, in the aforementioned case of Liverpool 2008, that cultural events generate significant interest in the short to medium term. However, they also suggest that securing a longer-term narrative shift without the explicit focus of a headline event represents a more significant challenge. In addition to this, Hull's year as UKCoC in 2017 demonstrates a similar trend. A report from the Culture, Policy and Place Institute (2018) shows that broadcast and press reporting of Hull saw two significant peaks - at the beginning and at the end of the event year - demonstrating again the difficulty in securing long-term

coverage. There remains, however, little research, which demonstrates the impact of *bidding* for events and the associated legacy of an unsuccessful bid. Existing research illustrates, for example, that the bid process for events such as the ECOC or the UKCoC can generate media coverage, but it says little about media reporting of unsuccessful bid cities (or towns, in the case of Paisley).

To return to Paisley, there was a clear reduction in newspaper reporting following the conclusion of the UKCoC bid campaign. From the peak of 18 articles during the final months of the bid campaign, the following spring period saw a substantial drop to only four articles, with the summer period accounting for the joint lowest number of articles of the study period with just one article. There was a rebound in the autumn and winter 2018 period with some coverage (re)focusing on the UKCoC bid, with an article in the *Paisley Daily Express* backing the vision from the 2021 bid campaign, and another celebrating Paisley's selection for an Academy of Urbanism award following on from its UKCoC bid. The winter period, exactly one year after the end of the bid period, continued in this vein – with a selection of both local and national press coverage commemorating the anniversary of the UKCoC bid. At this point, there is, simultaneously, a shift *away* from the bid context towards the emerging Future Paisley agenda, though the title of the post-bid cultural regeneration programme had yet to be fully unveiled. Indeed, the year after the conclusion of the failed UKCoC bid marked a renewed commitment to cultural investment in Paisley, with the creation of a new role within Renfrewshire Council, the Strategic Lead for Cultural Regeneration. Additionally, there was reporting on the ongoing investment in Paisley Museum (which appeared consistently in newspaper reporting as a 'flagship' cultural investment in Paisley). Winter 2019/20 coincided with the launch of the *Vision for Paisley Town Centre 2030* report, which set out plans for

regenerating Paisley town centre. This period also marked the launch of the Paisley Book Festival, as well as an announcement about the (re)development of Paisley Museum (discussed in greater depth in section 5.3.3). When taken together, these plans generated an increase in newspaper reporting during the winter period (16 articles), including national newspaper reporting responding mostly to announcements about Paisley Museum and developments in the town centre strategy.

Table 5.2.12 Breakdown of coverage since 2014

In sum, newspaper reporting of Paisley and cultural regeneration peaked during the UKCoC bid campaign. This is particularly true in the case of national and international newspaper reporting. Indeed, while local newspapers (in particular the *Paisley Daily Express*) were fairly consistent with their coverage, particularly with regards to the town centre, national newspaper reporting was more sporadic, increasing in response to major events (such as the outcome of the bid announcement) but decreasing during quieter periods. However, while it

is certainly true that the bid campaign was successful in generating newspaper coverage, other events also had the capacity to generate significant newspaper reporting. This is best represented by the second peak in media coverage during the winter 2019/20 period with the launch of the *Town Centre 2030 vision*, and the *Future Paisley* programme. This is seen, albeit with newspaper reporting relating to other landmark events, including the publication of *The Untold Story* in 2014, which generated national newspaper reporting, as well as sustained local coverage. When considered within the context of the UKCoC bid team and, subsequently, Future Paisley's stated aim to 'radically change Paisley's image and reputation in Scotland, the UK and internationally' (CCSE, n.d), it appears that (in terms of newspaper coverage, at least) there was mixed success. Indeed, while the momentum from the bid campaign and broader cultural regeneration work has generated significant media coverage in local and national newspapers (60% from the local print press), there is little evidence to suggest that this has increased international reporting on Paisley.

Similarly, in the context of this research, and research question three, the prevalence of newspaper reporting in local, national and international contexts suggests that newspaper reporting on cultural regeneration have been most prominent at a local level, with the most sustained reporting coming from local newspapers. As discussed in chapter two, local awareness and engagement in creative placemaking is crucial in avoiding the top down, competitive logic of the creative city mantra. To that end, the prevalence of local newspaper reporting does not necessarily speak to a strategic failure on behalf of policymakers, but rather to the importance of local community engagement in the production of regeneration narratives themselves. However, a quantitative analysis of newspaper coverage provides insufficient insights into *who* and *how* discourses about Paisley have been constructed,

communicated and disseminated, and to what extent this reflects the changing discourses and (dis)continuities about heritage, cultural and regeneration in Paisley. In the next section, I unpack the key narratives projected about Paisley in newspaper coverage between 2014-2020.

5.3 Discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley

In preceding sections, I have broken down the newspaper reporting of Paisley, culture and regeneration since 2014. In doing so, I have demonstrated the breakdown of newspaper reporting across time period, and situated this within local, national and international contexts. Furthermore, I have also illustrated that the overwhelming majority of newspaper reporting had a positive sentiment. This finding is significant in and of itself given the lack of research on Paisley's image and reputation. Furthermore, it is consistent with current research on cultural events, bid legacy, cultural regeneration and creative placemaking more generally. It also demonstrates the extent to which certain narratives about Paisley are reflected in newspaper reporting. However, it also leaves two key unanswered questions: what were the narratives reported in newspaper articles, and who was responsible for their development? I return to the who question in chapter six. For now, I explore *what* narratives were projected about Paisley in newspaper reporting over the 2014-2020 period.

Three dominant themes emerged from the analysis of newspaper coverage: Paisley town centre, the international significance of Paisley's culture, and the heritage assets outlined in *The Untold Story*. The first theme is Paisley town centre in that the broader regeneration of Paisley has been framed, in part at least, in terms of growing the visitor economy to stimulate economic growth thereby regenerating the town centre. There is, it seems, a duality to this narrative insofar as changes in consumer behaviour are used to explain the decline of

traditional town centre spaces while providing an blueprint for regenerating them in a manner more compatible with the post-industrial epoch. Building on this, I then explore the second theme focused on the need to change perceptions of Paisley by utilising the town's cultural offer. I analyse the seemingly contradictory nature of positioning Paisley's cultural and heritage offer as internationally significant while simultaneously positioning the town, specifically in the context of the UKCoC bid, as an underdog. Finally, the third theme focuses on the importance of Paisley's heritage assets outlined in *The Untold Story* in newspaper reporting, with specific attention paid to Paisley Museum, and how this reflects dominant approaches to culture-led regeneration.

5.3.1 Paisley town centre: retail decline and post-industrial reimagining

The town centre was the focus of much of the newspaper reporting on Paisley's cultural renaissance. This is unsurprising given that the initial motivation behind the local authority's interest in exploring the town's heritage assets was to stimulate the town centre's struggling economy (see *The Untold Story*, 2014). In total, 45 of the 150 articles in the dataset had an explicit focus on the town centre. In addition to this, there were 58 references to the town centre in articles that did not have a *specific* focus on the town centre. Furthermore, focus on the town centre appeals both to the decline of the town centre (in the form of a declining retail offer) and the subsequent need to regenerate it. More specifically, newspaper reporting, in the initial period of regeneration at least, tended to posit that heritage is useful insofar as it can drive footfall into the town centre thereby regenerating the town centre and supporting businesses. This is demonstrated by an article in the *Paisley Daily Express*:

We can't turn the clock back, but we can look to the future and promote what makes our towns unique - which, in Renfrewshire's case, is great buildings, a unique heritage,

and brilliant events - to find new ways to bring people here and support local trade
(*Paisley Daily Express*, 24 January 2020)

The emphasis on the importance of the town centre was reinforced in early 2020, with the launch of *A Vision for Paisley Town Centre 2030* report, which served, inter alia, to cement the narrative around the changing use of town centre spaces:

The report sets out a series of radical ideas which imagine how the empty retail space in the town centre could be redeveloped to meet the future needs of our communities and uses Paisley as a test case for towns all across the UK (*Paisley Daily Express*, 24 January 2020)

A FIRST-OF-ITS-KIND study radically reimagining how Paisley town centre could look in a decade has been published and aims to show how High Street decline could be reversed across Scotland...The Vision for Paisley Town Centre 2030 is the result of a link-up between Renfrewshire Council, the Scottish Government and Scotland's Town Partnership and uses Paisley as a test case for bold ideas imagining how empty retail space could be better used. (*The National*, 24 January 2020)

Earlier iterations of the discourse surrounding the changing use of Paisley town centre were also present in newspaper reporting on the town centre, illustrated by these articles from 2017:

Our vision for Paisley is a new town centre economy based around heritage and culture as part of wider regeneration plans for the area...The private sector investment includes fitting both shop units with traditional shop fronts in keeping with Paisley's

heritage-led and cultural ambitions for the town centre. (*Paisley Daily Express*, 22 July 2017)

Changes in the way people shop have changed the role of the high street - but here in Paisley we are...investment in heritage, culture and events can be used to breathe new life into a town centre and bring in footfall which traders can benefit from (*The Gazette*, 12 March 2017)

But what is the problem that needs fixing in Paisley? Put simply, the town centre became, over decades, a husk... The long, grim decline of the centre of Paisley, as in other similar towns in the north of England, is partly down to the retail revolution and changing consumer behaviour. (*The Times*, 6 May 2017)

Narratives about the decline (and 'regeneration') of the town centre were crystallised in newspaper reporting on Paisley town centre over the study period (2014-2020). The economic decline of the town centre was used to justify culture and heritage-led projects focused on the *economic* regeneration of Paisley town centre. This narrative aligns with the notion that the traditional use of town centres has fundamentally changed in the post-industrial landscape, contributing to the economic decline of town centres of former industrial hubs. The discourse surrounding the decline of Paisley town centre reflects broader discourses which suggest that post-industrial society represents an irreparable rift with the previous industrial epoch, emanating from a substantial shift in the nature of manufacturing and consumption (see Chelsom Vogt, 2016; Bell, 1973).

The apparent need to regenerate Paisley town centre within the context of shifting consumer preferences in the (neoliberal) post-industrial service economy is compounded further by the

rise of out of town or peripheral shopping malls. In the context of Paisley, this threat has come from the popularity of Braehead shopping centre in nearby Renfrew, as well as the Silverburn shopping centre in the Southside of Glasgow. This is significant inasmuch as it has contributed to the narrative of town centre decline and the changing role of town centres in post-industrial towns which was common in newspaper reporting of Paisley's regeneration:

Under a radical ten-year plan, one proposal would see retail space at the Paisley Centre cut by more than 70 per cent and replaced with accommodation to boost population and vibrancy. Threesixty Architecture, which produced the blueprint, believes that there is too much retail space in the town, which cannot to compete with nearby Silverburn, Braehead and central Glasgow. Instead, it wants to repurpose empty units and unused stock areas above existing shops and turn them into a wide range of accommodation. (*The Times*, 25 January 2020)

The hammer blow of the construction, approved by Renfrewshire Council in 1999, of the out-of-town Braehead shopping centre, followed by the Glasgow City Council-owned Silverburn in nearby Pollok, means shoppers now simply drive past Paisley. (*The Herald*, 20 April 2017)

Home to a fine neoclassical town hall, medieval abbey church, and handsome museum, the huge success of the nearby Braehead shopping centre has been to the detriment of a town centre already down on its luck. (*The Herald*, 1 August 2016)

Paisley town centre had been on the slide since Braehead shopping centre opened in 1999. Most of the nightclubs closed after a series of fatal stabbings, and several pubs

pulled down the shutters when St Mirren football club moved out of town (*The Times*, 25 January 2020)

The narrative of town centre decline, framed in terms of out-of-town retail development, was more prominent within national newspaper reporting when compared with more localised coverage. Indeed, a total of 11 articles mentioned the Braehead shopping centre, with only three of those being local publications. The remaining eight came from national newspapers. In the international context, articles about Paisley in both the *New York Times* and the *FT* also commented on the decline of the town centre:

PAISLEY, Scotland — Between a palatial Baptist church, Europe’s biggest, and a 12th-century abbey, there are five thrift stores, four pawnbrokers and a dozen boarded-up shop fronts...The main street of Paisley, Scotland, looks like that of any struggling, postindustrial town just south of the border with England (*New York Times*, 16 March 2017)

If there was ever a town with image problems it is Paisley, the former textile powerhouse just outside Glasgow that for decades has been a byword for drugs, deprivation and high street decline (*Financial Times*, 29 December 2016)

Both national and international newspapers demonstrated a greater propensity toward negative reporting on Paisley town centre, inasmuch as articles published in these papers tended to have a greater focus on the decline of, and problems with, Paisley town centre. However, the sentiment of reporting town centre decline was not necessarily negative. Rather, it is more accurate to conclude that the emphasis on the *decline* of town centre is

used to legitimise attempts to *regenerate* the town centre to meet the needs of the post-industrial economic landscape.

In sum, Paisley town centre has been at the forefront of newspaper narratives about Paisley, regeneration and culture since 2014. More specifically, two key intertwined narratives about Paisley town centre (re)define how the relationship between culture, heritage and regeneration is to be understood. First, there is a consistent narrative about the nature of decline of Paisley's town centre. The narrative about the town centre's decline is punctuated with references to the changing use(s) of town centre spaces, amid the rise of other consumer preferences such as out-of-town shopping malls (including Braehead and Silverburn in the case of Paisley). Second, the decline in Paisley town centre justifies the culture and heritage-led regeneration projects designed to stimulate the local economy. Indeed, newspaper reporting on Paisley town centre is punctuated with references to the need to create a future-orientated town centre economy which utilises the town's culture and heritage offer (the international significance of which is the focus of the next section). Taken together, the narratives projected about Paisley town centre reflect the broader discourse of the post-industrial city, and more specifically the economic necessity of adapting to the post-industrial (neoliberal) landscape

5.3.2 The 'international significance' of Paisley's cultural offer

Garcia (2010), drawing on the Liverpool 2008 case study, argues that positive newspaper reporting of cultural events typically centres on the quality of the cultural offer of the host (in this case bid) city, as well as the (potential) economic impact of the hosting the event. In the case of Paisley, the newspaper reporting supports this perspective. This is, perhaps, unsurprising given the stated aim of *The Untold Story* (2014) was to, in effect, take stock of

the town's heritage assets, the economic impacts of which have been under exploited. Indeed, as noted in *The Untold Story* (2014: 74):

The Paisley Town Centre Asset Strategy is focused on key economic drivers and the latent potential of Paisley's cultural and heritage offer which is one of the most important elements of Scotland's tourism offering.

Paisley's cultural offer features prominently in newspaper reporting before, during and after the UKCoC bid. There are 230 references that are broadly focused on Paisley's cultural offer, often with the explicit aim of changing perceptions of Paisley. Beyond referencing Paisley's cultural offer in broad terms, it is worth exploring *what* is said specifically about it. In newspaper coverage from 2014-2020 there is a constant focus on the international significance of Paisley's culture and heritage assets. Indeed, 59 newspaper articles refer to international significance, including the following examples from local and national publications:

We are taking forward ambitious and far-reaching plans to use Paisley's internationally-significant heritage and cultural assets to transform the town's future.
(Paisley Daily Express, 25 May 2015)

These are being supported by Future Paisley - a programme of economic, social and physical regeneration building on the work already done to use Paisley's internationally-significant culture and heritage story to change the town's future.
(Paisley Daily Express, February 17 2020)

Far-reaching proposals included in the PTCHAS are designed to make the most of Paisley's heritage, described by experts as 'internationally significant.' (*Paisley Daily Express*, 15 April 2015)

The narrative espousing the international significance of the town's culture and heritage offer was common across newspaper reporting. Indeed, while this narrative was not prominent in international newspaper reporting, there is a fairly even distribution between national and local papers. Within the local and national coverage, the narrative positing the international significance of Paisley's culture and heritage offer is juxtaposed with the town's relatively small size to emphasise an underdog narrative. This narrative positions Paisley as a small town making a substantial and unusually large contribution to the world, particularly when compared with towns of a similar size. The underdog posturing is clearly identifiable in the dataset, with 18 articles adopting this tone:

For its size, Paisley's contribution to the world is absolutely massive and we have a list of assets to be proud of. (*The Herald*, 26 June 2016)

Paisley may have been seen an underdog in the competition, but we punched above our weight to reach the late stages of the process (*Paisley Daily Express*, 8 December 2017)

On top of that, it's a town that punches well above its weight, an ambitious underdog determined to take its place at the table and unapologetically show off its best bits (*Independent*, 20 June 2019)

There are few towns in Britain with a greater industrial and social history -- and a deader high street today...there is nowhere of comparable size -- 77,000 people -- that

has such a rich architectural, industrial and social history and that once mattered so much to the world (*The Guardian*, 15 August 2015)

Paisley may have been seen an underdog in the competition, but we punched above our weight to reach the late stages of the process...We will continue to show that Paisley is a vibrant, exciting and cultured town with lots to offer (*Paisley Daily Express*, 7 December 2017)

While local publications reported on the underdog narrative, it was also present in national newspaper reporting – with Paisley’s apparently disproportionately large culture and heritage offer featuring in a host of national publications including *The Guardian*, *The Herald* and *The Independent*. The underdog narrative also appeared in one international publication, the *Irish Independent*, albeit with a familiar narrative of decline as discussed above:

Many urban areas would love to have a measure of the pedigree that this postindustrial conurbation boasts. Aside from its textile legacy, and illustrious denizens - including 'Braveheart' William Wallace, who was educated here - Paisley, on the River Cart, has an incredible architectural heritage, from the 12th-Century Abbey, with its glorious Edward Burne-Jones windows, to its Victorian Observatory, to the stunning Art Deco Russell Institute. The decline of industry saw Paisley diminish from a proud centre of excellence to a place that suffered significant deprivation. (*Irish Independent*, 13 November 2017)

The underdog narrative prominent throughout newspaper reporting during Paisley’s UKCoC bid period is concomitant with the narrative that bidding – and the emergent cultural regeneration - helped put the town ‘on the map’, presumably suggesting that Paisley had

fallen off the cultural map as an outcome of the post-industrial economic landscape. Indeed, 16 newspaper articles made explicit reference to putting Paisley back on the map via its enhanced cultural offer:

Let's put Paisley back on the map...Earlier this week, I was proud to launch a blueprint which I believe can put Paisley on the international map once again and, in doing so, deliver a massive boost to Renfrewshire's economic and employment prospects (*Paisley Daily Express*, 27 June 2014)

Renfrewshire Council leader Mark MacMillian, also chair of the Paisley 2021 Partnership Board, said: 'We want to put Paisley at the heart of the world's cultural map. (*Daily Record*, 17 November 2015)

The legacy of this process is that Paisley has been put on the map. A lot of people in Paisley can lift their heads higher because they put together a fantastic bid. (*The National*, 8 December 2017)

Organisers say that, despite eventually losing out on the prestigious title to Coventry, Paisley has been well and truly placed on the map. (*Paisley Daily Express*, 20 February 2018)

This narrative that Paisley had fallen off the map emerges most prominently in the immediate aftermath of Paisley's UKCoC bid, marking a distinct narrative shift from the initial bid period towards its the legacy (see Wilson, 2021a). Paisley's UKCoC bid represents the peak of newspaper reporting on Paisley's cultural regeneration. As discussed in section 5.2, the immediate bid period received the most newspaper coverage, with the peak during the bid announcement in December 2016. This, of course, begs the question as to the content of

newspaper reporting during (and on) the UKCoC bid campaign, as well as the key narratives that were communicated about Paisley's bid, regeneration and the town more generally.

Beyond this, the UKCoC bid also helped Paisley receive international attention, thereby helping place Paisley back on the map, with each of the four international articles making reference to the UKCoC bid:

Paisley, which is bidding to be UK City of Culture 2021, has - along with the largest number of listed buildings outside of Edinburgh - a proud legacy proclaimed in its street names that bear testament to the town's textile history: Gauze, Cotton and Silk Streets, to name but a few...As with so many UK towns, the demise of the traditional High Street contributed to Paisley's slide, which, with the UK City of Culture bid, is now on the turn, through helping Paisleyites appreciate and cherish their considerable heritage, and reposition it proudly on a global stage... (*Irish Independent*, 13 November 2017)

Things may be changing, however. Paisley's bid to become the UK's 2021 City of Culture has sparked new interest in a town that was once one of Scotland's richest but which was gutted by the closure of its textile mills in the latter decades of the 20th century. (*Financial Times*, 29 December 2016)

As with the town centre narrative, the UKCoC bid was framed, in international newspaper reporting, around Paisley's economic decline and the persistent poverty in the area. Indeed, in both the more detailed reporting in the *Financial Times* as well as the *New York Times*:

The main street of Paisley, Scotland, looks like that of any struggling, post-industrial town just south of the border with England...But a mere five-minute drive away is

Ferguslie Park, a notorious housing estate, parts of which rank at the bottom of the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation. Child poverty is high, and knife fights not uncommon. Advertised on the white board in the community centre: a Narcotics Anonymous meeting and a coffee afternoon with Chest, Heart and Stroke Scotland. (*New York Times*, 16 March 2017)

If there was ever a town with image problems it is Paisley, the former textile powerhouse just outside Glasgow that for decades has been a byword for drugs, deprivation and high street decline. (*Financial Times*, 29 December 2016)

This is, ultimately a trend that is also prevalent in national newspaper reporting, in the context of the UKCoC bid:

Paisley faces major challenges. The town is home to some of the most deprived areas in Scotland and the empty units on our High Street tell the story of a town centre hit harder than most by a changing retail environment...But that's why we are bidding. UK City of Culture goes to a city that, like Hull and Derry in 2013, has a clear plan to use the accolade to change its fortunes for the better. As the DCMS reminded us this week, UK City of Culture is more than a title: it's about bringing communities together, building local pride, developing new partnerships and attracting tourists (*The Herald*, 13 January 2017)

Evidence of Paisley's former greatness is all around: the town centre boasts the highest concentration of listed buildings anywhere in Scotland aside from Edinburgh. But so too is evidence of post-industrial decline on the high street. What is not visible but palpable is a rediscovered optimism in a place too often defined in recent years

by Ferguslie Park, a housing estate that was once the site of thriving mills and is now the most deprived area in Scotland, according the index of multiple deprivation...In the context of this competition, culture becomes a shorthand for many things: regeneration, tourism, identity. (*The Guardian*, 22 November 2017)

The narrative of Paisley's UKCoC bid, and its cultural offer, have been framed around the decline in both Paisley's image and economy. In sum, the UKCoC bid campaign and newspaper reporting on Paisley's cultural offer, rallied around the imperative to highlight the international significance of Paisley's culture and heritage offer and, in doing so, put Paisley 'back on the map'. This speaks to the need to change how the town is perceived in order to leverage the apparent benefits of Paisley's cultural assets. On a more theoretical level, this reporting is reflective of dominant assumptions about the nature of inter-urban competition and urban entrepreneurialism. By constructing Paisley's economic situation as unfair in light of its international cultural offer, these narratives seek to (re)position Paisley within the neoliberal paradigm. Given the attention given to Paisley's cultural offer, in the next section I unpack this within the context of the heritage assets outlined in *The Untold Story* to understand how these have materialised in narratives about Paisley, its culture and regeneration.

5.3.3 Heritage assets and *The Untold Story*

The publication of the document *The Untold Story* generated newspaper reporting on Paisley and has informed the local government's regeneration strategy (at least insofar as this is predicated on regenerating Paisley town centre using the town's culture and heritage 'assets'). As outlined in *The Untold Story* (2014: 39):

The vision for the asset strategy is to harness the town's potential, develop its product or USP and then monetise this offer in the form of a realistic, deliverable and integrated asset strategy that regenerates and revitalises the town centre, but also creates a framework that helps address Paisley's underlying socio-economic issues.

Therefore, it is important to conduct a deeper exploration of how the assets outlined in the document have been featured in newspaper reporting on Paisley during the period highlighted by this research, and how, in turn, this has informed the narrative that has been projected about the town in recent years.

When assessing newspaper reporting on Paisley's cultural regeneration the redevelopment of Paisley Museum has been prominent. Indeed, in the sample there were 64 articles and 84 references to Paisley Museum, as well as the museum store – a temporary storage and exhibition of the museum collection of Paisley High Street. In addition to a focus on the international significance of its collection, the museum is also viewed as a central plank of the economic renaissance of Paisley:

The ambition we have will drive economic growth across Renfrewshire. We will invest £200 million in transforming the town over the next 10 years in a new town centre, new homes and improved transport links. We want to invest in our rich cultural assets with our flagship project to invest £56.7m to turn Paisley Museum into an international-class tourist destination based around our textile heritage (*The Herald*, 1 August 2016)

We are continuing to develop the business case for one of the *flagship* projects of our regeneration strategy for the town centre - a multi-million pound programme to

extend Paisley Museum and Art Galleries to create a national museum of textile and costume. (*Paisley Daily Express*, 23 December 2015 emphasis added)

More specifically, newspaper reporting on the redevelopment of Paisley Museum emphasised the ability of a revamped museum to help stimulate the visitor economy and develop Paisley's tourism offer:

a huge £42m overhaul of Paisley Museum...which is closed until 2022 while it's transformed into an 'international-class destination' that can handle four times the current number of visitors (*The Independent*, 20 June 2019)

The refurbished museum is expected to attract 125,000 visitors a year - almost four times current numbers - when it reopens its doors in 2022...And it's estimated that it will create huge amounts of visitors to Paisley town centre, as well as a £72m economic boost over 30 years. (*Paisley Daily Express*, 22 November 2018)

Plans for a new Paisley Museum which could attract hundreds of thousands of visitors to the town have progressed with details over its funding revealed...will triple current visitor numbers to 125,000 a year, be worth £75m to the local economy over the next 30 years and create 160 new jobs (*The Herald*, 20 November 2016)

The redevelopment of Paisley Town Hall also featured prominently in newspaper reporting. As with the museum, much of the newspaper reporting focused on the way in which the town hall had been underutilised before 2014 (echoing the broader arguments presented in *The Untold Story*) with the development of these assets as internationally significant, or world-class visitor destinations:

The town hall is undergoing a £22 million renovation, while a £42 million investment in the museum will deliver a world class visitor destination. (*Daily Express*, 7 December 2018)

The next stage of this evolution into kind of a Big Deal territory is a £100m investment in various infrastructure projects, including a £22m revamp of Paisley Town Hall (*The Independent*, 22 June 2019)

As more people are attracted to the area, we will have 21st century venues to accommodate them with major investment in Paisley Museum and Paisley Town Hall. (*Paisley Daily Express*, 19 September 2018)

The development of the town hall (alongside the museum) was reported as a key visitor attraction within the town, as outlined in *The Untold Story*. Or as former local MP Douglas Alexander put it following the launch of *The Untold Story*:

In recent days, I discussed with Mark MacMillian, the Labour Council Leader, the details of the Paisley Town Centre Heritage Plan...It includes the renovation and promotion of our museum, further development of key tourist attractions, such as our town hall, and the creation of a dedicated fashion and design centre. (*Paisley Daily Express*, 29 January 2014)

The theme of reimagining apparently forgotten heritage and cultural assets to stimulate the visitor economy is not limited to the physical realm. The need to further utilise – and even reimagine – the Paisley Pattern, a famous textile design, also featured heavily in *The Untold Story*, and within newspaper reporting on Paisley, before, during and after the UKCoC bid. Indeed 31 newspaper articles included 36 references to the Paisley Pattern. Further, the

Paisley Pattern is used within newspaper reporting to further position Paisley's heritage as world-class or internationally significant:

Paisley Pattern, a worldwide brand that still carries the town's name. That unique history bequeathed a legacy still prominent today, including Scotland's second-highest concentration of listed buildings and an internationally significant museum collection (*The Herald*, 14 January 2017)

The town is known worldwide for the Paisley Pattern and still has the legacy of its days at the heart of the global textile industry, as well as a thriving cultural scene which will form the basis for the town's UK City of Culture bid (*Paisley Daily Express*, 10 April 2015)

Just look at what Paisley town centre can already offer. We are the home of the Paisley Pattern -- a globally recognised brand (*Evening Times*, 6 November 2014)

More specifically, the need to reinvent or reimagine the Paisley Pattern cemented the narrative of forgotten or under-utilised heritage assets:

But could the 'Paisley Pattern' undergo a similar revival to the one which has seen Harris Tweed become so important to the economy of the Western Isles (*The Scotsman*, 24 October 2016)

We are reinventing our textile heritage for the 21st century, commercialising the global design symbol that is the Paisley Pattern (*The Herald*, 13 December 2017)

In reporting, the Paisley Pattern brand is also used to further the narrative that weaves through the reporting on the heritage assets and their ability to stimulate the visitor economy:

Celebrating the region's rich traditions - from weaving the Paisley Pattern to the iconic Paisley Abbey - and establishing Renfrewshire as a key visitor destination are at the centre of the regeneration plans. (*Paisley Daily Express*, 4 January 2019)

The narrative surrounding the Paisley Pattern has followed a similar discursive trajectory as the other heritage and cultural assets discussed throughout this chapter – in that it is argued that the Pattern, properly utilised, can help stimulate the town's struggling economy. Building on this, however, the Paisley Pattern is also central to a broader discourse about modernising heritage assets to make them more future focused. This reflects a broader discourse about modernisation and post-industrial society insofar as a reimagined Paisley Pattern is to be used to (re)develop the town's service-led visitor economy. The legacy of the Paisley Pattern, then, has been reinvented as a vehicle for the development of tourism and repurposing Paisley town centre.

The final heritage asset which featured prominently in newspaper reporting about Paisley and its cultural regeneration is Paisley Abbey. Indeed, 20 newspaper articles made 22 references to the Abbey. However, references to the Abbey appear more passing in nature, positioning it within the broader discourse on Paisley's architectural heritage, and featuring more as an example of the richness of Paisley's culture and heritage offer:

I am deeply proud of our cultural heritage, our iconic landmarks and historically significant buildings like the Abbey. (*Paisley Daily Express*, 29 January 2014)

...Incredible architectural heritage, from the 12th-Century Abbey, with its glorious Edward Burne-Jones windows, to its Victorian Observatory, to the stunning Art Deco Russell Institute. The decline of industry saw Paisley diminish from a proud centre of

excellence to a place that suffered significant deprivation (*Irish Independent*, November 13 2019)

The richness of Paisley's cultural heritage is used to cement the argument for developing the town's visitor economy, specifically utilising the Abbey as an iconic backdrop for animating and activating the built heritage via festivals and events:

Paisley Abbey provided the perfect backdrop for Halloween and has hosted a range of family activities throughout the winter events (*Paisley Daily Express*, 27 December 2018)

The distinctive architecture of Paisley Abbey and Town Hall will provide a unique backdrop to the Rally (a car rally event taking place in the town centre) (*Paisley Daily Express*, 21 January 2014)

Paisley Abbey has been characterised as a heritage asset without the subsequent need to be redeveloped or reimagined as with other assets outlined within *The Untold Story*. The Abbey has been included in the broader spatial reimagining of Paisley's town centre, along with the associated shift towards developing the visitor economy, thereby making it more future facing. This is evidenced by the use of Paisley Abbey as a backdrop or venue for events including concerts.

In sum, newspaper reporting on the assets outlined in *The Untold Story* foregrounds the purported economic benefits of developing cultural and heritage assets as a means of developing the visitor economy within the town. This narrative has been relatively static between 2014 and 2020. Flagship projects, such as the Paisley Museum redevelopment, have received regular coverage and including consistently similar narratives in newspaper

reporting. This suggests some degree of continuity in the regeneration strategy that has been pursued within Paisley, even amid the apparent strategic shifts from within the council and partners. While focusing on culture *leading* economic change certainly appears to delineate a more culture-led approach, this does not necessarily suggest that broader, more holistic cultural activity has not taken place. However, investment in flagship projects suggests that there has been a degree of consistency in approaches to regeneration, which in turn have continued to resemble the broader discourses of urban entrepreneurialism.

5.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, I have presented a detailed discussion of the narratives, messages and discourse that have been present in newspaper reporting of Paisley between 2014 and 2020. Placing newspaper and documentary data in the correct temporal context reflects the Foucauldian analysis conducted for this study insofar as it creates space to explore how changing discourses of cultural regeneration, culture-led regeneration and creative placemaking are represented through 'official' discourses of regeneration that have been identified through this research. I have demonstrated that newspaper reporting on Paisley has taken, as a starting point, the economic and physical decline of the town in recent decades, particularly the town centre. Dominant narratives in newspaper reporting focused on the nature of industrial decline and the emergence of post-industrial towns and cities. The narrative of post-industrial decline in Paisley, it appears, has informed the development of Paisley's cultural strategy, which seeks to harness the power of culture and heritage assets to help regenerate the town's economy, with a particular focus on the town centre. This echoes dominant neoliberal discourses, and in particular the logic of urban entrepreneurialism as outlined by Harvey (1989).

From this analysis of newspaper coverage, the messages communicated about Paisley appear to embody a competitive logic that focus on leveraging the economic benefits of cultural investment. This tends to suggest that Paisley has followed a culture-led regeneration strategy and promoted that in its external communications strategies. Pre-bid and beyond, newspaper coverage consistently focused on flagship projects and the anticipated economic outcomes from investment in heritage and cultural assets. This appears to be in tension with the professed commitment to a cultural regeneration strategy in that there is a clear continuity with a culture-led approach to investment in flagship cultural projects and stimulating the visitor economy. This does not suggest, as stated above, that there has not been any substantive qualitative strategic shift, rather it raises broader questions as to *why* this focus on economic and physical regeneration has remained remarkably consistent and to what extent this reflects *who* defines the stories, narratives and discourses that have been projected about Paisley. With this in mind, chapter six will explore how discourse of cultural regeneration is produced and by whom.

Chapter 6: 'Stop watering the weeds and start watering the flowers': constructing discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley

6.1 Introduction

The second findings chapter draws primarily on the results of interviews conducted with elite stakeholders, as well as artists, former business owners and community activists. Additionally, it includes findings from online workshops held with local community members. In doing so, I address research question one and research question three. I answer research question one by exploring how discourses of cultural regeneration are constructed by key decision makers and stakeholders in Paisley. I answer research question three by exploring local responses to cultural regeneration.

To begin, I explore how interview respondents conceived of Paisley's area reputation. I discuss how discourses of Paisley's (negative) reputation are based on an understanding of Paisley as a poster boy of post-industrial decline, and on the prevalence of poverty and inequality within the town. I then explore the strategies developed to alter perceptions of the town, focusing on the production and communication of specific narratives then reflected in the newspaper reporting of Paisley. Building on this, I discuss the assumptions upon which broader discourses of cultural regeneration of Paisley are based. In doing so, I emphasize how key decisions about cultural regeneration in Paisley have been informed by the logic of culture-led regeneration via elite networks of professionals working within the broader field of urban regeneration. Finally, I discuss how the role of the local community is constructed and in doing so demonstrate how respondents often invoke notions of the local and local community support to justify the process of cultural regeneration itself.

6.2 Paisley, reputation and regeneration

6.2.1 'Terror Town': exploring negative perceptions of Paisley

This section begins by exploring Paisley's negative area reputation. It is important to first discuss how respondents conceived of the town's reputation given the strategic importance placed on improving it. In the context of this research, there was a unanimous agreement among respondents that Paisley suffered from a generally poor area reputation. More specifically, respondents commented on the town's reputation for being potentially dangerous and blighted by issues of (sub)urban decline:

So that idea of Paisley being dangerous, and dirty, was the driver for a lot of this coming through and that title of terror town stuck (Respondent 1, Former Leader of Renfrewshire Council)

I've noticed a lot of people saying 'Aye, I'm from Paisley'. But there's a...there's a large number of people that shy away from that as well because of the reputation, and the reputation of us being a wee bit rough (Respondent 16, Local Community Activist)

Respondents expressed the view that these negative perceptions of Paisley have deprived the town and its local communities of confidence and civic pride, as well as a broader lack of awareness of the town's cultural offer and heritage assets. More specifically, the impact of de-industrialisation and the related economic problems were viewed as contributing to a loss of identity within the town:

It's...I just I think it's because you stay in Paisley; you don't appreciate what Paisley's got (Respondent 12, Former Business Owner and Community Activist)

So all of that decline has impacted...industrial decline has impacted on the psyche of the town in my view (Respondent 16, Local Community Activist)

You were making invisible how people identified with themselves. Yeah, how people identify themselves, yeah a real part of the town's story. So I think for me that that that kind of showed that there was a lack of leadership or the or it kinda there was a sense of at that Paisley was forgotten (Respondent 13, 2021 Bid Director)

Elite stakeholder perceptions about Paisley's negative image and reputation echo the key themes of *The Untold Story* in that there is a clear narrative that Paisley has been forgotten in the wake of post-industrial decline. The perception that Paisley has been left behind was reinforced in the views of local residents who confirmed that Paisley had a bad reputation, and linked this to negative (local) newspaper reporting which emphasised violent crime within the area:

I think it's (Paisley) got a bad reputation to be honest. Like going by example of the Paisley Express paper, I call it the Paisley depression because it is just full of bad news. 90% of everything in that paper is bad news. I think maybe it's not so bad now, but when I was younger it was all the knife crime, I know there is still knife crime and that, but Paisley was the worst place to live because you were always getting hit with something (Respondent 2, Workshop 2)

This quote directly implicates the local newspaper in the production of Paisley's negative area reputation. From this perspective, there is a disproportionate focus on the 'bad news'. While the perception that the local press disproportionately focuses on negative stories reflects previous work by Kearns et al (2013), this is in contrast the findings presented in chapter five,

at least in the context of cultural regeneration. Indeed, 86% of local newspaper stories about cultural regeneration in Paisley were coded as 'positive'. This suggests that the 'positive' discourses projected through the local press have had a more limited impact in changing how Paisley's image is constructed. With this in mind, attention can turn to how Paisley's reputation is constructed beyond the general sense among respondents that the town had a negative reputation and, more specifically, the way in which the decline of Paisley town centre contributes to 'negative' perceptions of the town itself.

6.2.2 Paisley town centre: From the 'poster-boy' of urban decline to coffee shop culture

As discussed in chapter five, discourses of Paisley town centre and its decline featured in newspaper reporting, emphasising broader discourses of retail decline, the rise of out-of-town shopping malls and the apparent changing use of town centres in a retail environment increasingly dominated by online shopping. The decline of Paisley town centre was also a prominent theme in interviews, illustrated in the response of the Director of Communities and Housing reflecting on the reason for the bid:

Paisley was obviously in a very difficult place at the time. The town centre was struggling, retail was very, very difficult, erm, I think Paisley had really suffered from out of town shopping and, you know, general stuff that was impacting on retail more generally like, em, online shopping etc. But Paisley had really struggled and it had quite a big retail area. (Respondent 2, Director of Communities and Housing, Renfrewshire Council)

Several respondents viewed the perceived decline of Paisley town centre as negatively affecting Paisley's image and reputation insofar as the town became defined as a textbook

example of high street decline. From this perspective, Paisley had effectively become the poster boy for town centre decline:

People in Paisley definitely had an opinion on Paisley high street, and it wasn't a good one. And people outside had an opinion of Paisley high street as well. And it's partly because it became the poster boy, poster child, of urban decline. (Respondent 1, Former Leader of Renfrewshire Council)

The phrase that is often used is that Paisley became the poster town for industrial decline, for poverty and for town centre and retail high street decline. It has a very grand high street, and it's spacious and it's elegant, but you know the shops have struggled for a variety of reasons and they've got battles like the rise of online, the rise of out-of-town shopping centres like Braehead and all those sort of things like everybody does. (Respondent 6, Former Strategic Lead of Cultural Regeneration for Renfrewshire Council)

I'm saying I guess, anecdotally what was coming through was coming through from the various meeting and events and workshops was the number one thing we could do to change perceptions of the place was to improve the high street (Respondent 15, Engagement Manager, UKCoC bid)

From this perspective, both visual and textual media representation(s) of Paisley town centre as increasingly vacant are juxtaposed with the town's architectural heritage to signify the broader process of 'mallification' and retail decline both within and out with Paisley. This is an interesting bridge between the (hyper) local site of Paisley and broader processes of globalisation, in which the shopping mall becomes the symbol of an increasingly placeless

globalised society (See, Auge, 2005). Workshops with local communities also reinforced the notion of decline in Paisley town centre, as a retail destination at least, producing negative perceptions of the broader town centre space:

I mean just all the shops and all that, I mean there's no shops in Paisley now, know what I mean? Every shop was full on the high street and now there's nothing, it's all boards with advertising. I remember there was the wimpy and the burger king upstairs and the play centre in the Burger King but there's nothing, absolutely nothing in Paisley now, Braehead has taken it all way (Respondent 2, Workshop 2)

Erm how has the town changed? Yeah I mean, death of the high street Paisley is a prime example of that. I think when McDonalds left that was the worst part...that we weren't even worthy of a McDonalds was a bit of a kick in the teeth. I...I do, yeah but again there is a lot of regeneration work going on...I think a lot of effort right now is on the regen, and they've put a lot into 'we are going to be better', going being the operative word (Respondent 2, Workshop 1)

Respondent discussion about the decline of Paisley town centre connects with broader discourses of the post-industrial society – as discussed in chapter five. There is an added specificity to the responses from local residents that is more grounded in a specific outcome of retail decline, such as the departure of big brands and chain stores in the town centre such as McDonalds or Marks & Spencer. What is particularly notable, however, is the extent to which the departure of certain brands, in this case McDonalds, compounds feelings of stigma associated with living in Paisley – Paisley was seen as not worthy of housing a fast food restaurant.

The decline of Paisley town centre and related departure of big businesses created a renewed imperative to regenerate the town centre space. Indeed, the departure of businesses serves to legitimise the construction of cultural regeneration strategies aimed at transforming the town centre space in a way deemed more appropriate for the post-industrial epoch. However, the vision of a regenerated Paisley town centre appears to reflect a somewhat archetypal articulation of the gentrified creative city with a focus on independent coffee shops and boutiques. This vision is seen most clearly in interviews in which respondents projected an idealised vision of Paisley as a cultural town that could be linked to a developing coffee shop culture of independents businesses, boutiques and cafes:

in my head, what I see Paisley being is a town that's known for its, em, creative, it's heritage, cultural heritage, but also it'll be small, independent, family run businesses that will make Paisley revived...you know the revival of Paisley (Respondent 10, Local Artist)

You know, a number of businesses that, like the café, that were opening up. So I think that for another demographic within the town. It was like, 'oh actually, we don't always need to go into Glasgow', or there is the option of, you know, hanging out here or those wee artisan this and that (Respondent 13, 2021 Bid Director)

even in kind of basic things like the town centre which I know is quite often part of the chat from kind of like big businesses being there to being more of a kind of boutique, small business, entrepreneurs kind of springing up and the coffee shop culture (Respondent 4, Create Paisley)

There is a clear link, here, between the vision of Paisley town centre populated by boutiques,

independent coffee shops and small businesses and the vision for the town centre published in early 2020 by Renfrewshire Council (Paisley Vision, 2020). There is a link, also, to the responses during workshops inasmuch as respondents expressed a need to foreground local and independent businesses in the regeneration of the town centre. The vision of a reimagined and repurposed Paisley town centre articulated throughout the document outlines how the town centre might re-attract the private sector with residential development and the rise of, presumably independent, restaurants and cafes (*ibid*: 21).

In sum, regenerating Paisley town centre has been at the centre of discursive formations of cultural regeneration in Paisley. To begin, the construction of Paisley town centre as in decline and as a poster boy of urban decline serves fits within the broader construction of post-industrial Paisley and serves to legitimise the need to *regenerate* Paisley using culture and heritage. However, discursive constructions of Paisley town centre are not limited to its decline. Rather, visions of a more bohemian high street, populated by cafes and trendy bars becomes central to discourses of cultural regeneration within the town.

6.2.3 Poverty, inequality and stigma in Paisley

In addition to narratives relating to de-industrialisation and town centre decline, poverty and inequality were also frequently associated with Paisley's negative reputation during interviews and workshops. There was a persistent view that Paisley's reputation was blighted by violent crime and drug (mis)use, as well as the more general perception that Paisley was a dangerous place, particularly throughout the 1980s and 1990s:

Because in the decades before, the story for Paisley had been about deprivation, drugs and violence and crime. And it was a place that you probably wouldn't want to go out

in, never mind visit (Respondent 2, Director of Communities and Housing at Renfrewshire Council)

That was undermined by quite a lot of crime, there will be narratives about the relationship of that to the drug problem that emerged in the town in some of its more deprived neighbourhoods. (Respondent 3, Regeneration Manager at Renfrewshire Council)

What was also clear, however, is that Paisley's reputation of high street decline, violence and drug mis(use) is woven into broader narratives of economic inequality and poverty, with specific areas of multiple deprivation such as Ferguslie Park, being seen as particularly problematic:

So yes, Paisley has had legacy issues as well, in terms of multiple deprivation and the areas are well known. So beyond Ferguslie Park, there's been issues in Shortroods, there's been issues in, eh, parts of Foxbar, in Gallowhill, in the east end of Paisley, particularly in the inner east end around Seedhill going back almost as long as anyone can remember, and there's a whole host of issues. (Respondent 5, Head of Economy and Development at Renfrewshire Council)

erm so that now the things that were starting to stick with people were negative stories. You know, the most vacant high street in the country, the most multiply deprived community in Ferguslie Park (Respondent 3, Regeneration Manager at Renfrewshire Council)

Additionally, respondents closely linked the issue(s) associated with poverty and inequality with the poverty league tables. More specifically, respondents acknowledged that Ferguslie

Park was frequently classed as the most 'deprived' area of Scotland, according to the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation. This, it appears, provided more empirical proof of economic inequality within the town, but also as a potentially stigmatising label that solidified negative perceptions of Paisley:

Posterboy-esque type positioning about town centre decline, Ferguslie Park being, eh, at the bottom of the league tables in terms of deprivation etc (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications at Renfrewshire Council)

Well so it's also known because we did this as part of our baseline research but we knew it anyway, that the number one area of deprivation, as set out by the SIMD stats, sort of belong to Paisley. So at that time, parts of Paisley were in the number one most deprived area in Scotland (Respondent 15, Engagement Manager UKCoC bid)

Negative area reputations and representations of poverty and inequality informed the messages that were developed to respond to these perceptions via cultural regeneration. Acknowledging poverty and inequality was believed to lend an authenticity to these campaigns by appearing to take ownership of the socio-economic issues in the town and that it legitimises and necessitates cultural regeneration itself:

But that postcode is still one of the lowest, the bottom in the SIMD index. So one of the most deprived areas, I think that's mostly obviously because I then leads into Shortroods. But still, it's in an, it's in technically a deprived area of Paisley and I think that's really important in terms of its regeneration power (Respondent 11, Chief Executive of PACE Theatre Company)

you had to acknowledge the real issue in the town the huge pockets of deprivation, the lack of digital connectivity, the health conditions. You know, I grew up in this street that topped the SMID index in in Scotland, so there was no way that that was going to be airbrushed. The opportunity was to create programmes for the year of culture or embedded within the partnerships, whether that be the NHS, the council etc...

(Respondent 13, UKCoC Bid Director)

Indeed, appealing to the persistence of socio-economic inequality was viewed as potentially advantageous in the bid campaign, given the regeneration-focused remit of both the bid itself and the broader UKCoC competition (see Cunningham and Platt, 2018):

Listen in the competition, let alone outside the competition, but for the competition there was no there was wins to be gained by erasing how much you needed this investment or that title (Respondent 13, UKCoC bid director)

There's nothing like a good competition to get people going. That we've had an unfortunate reputation but that should be different, that it's time to tell the world how brilliant and amazing Paisley is. That it was about improving our reputation, our town centre, and our creative industries. It was about helping lift our communities out of poverty, and it was about improving tourism and making Paisley be a world class destination (Respondent 9, STAR project)

Discussions about the effects of poverty and inequality mirror dominant discourses of culture-led regeneration that have shaped the cultural regeneration strategy within Paisley. Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration embodies similar trickle-down logic to that of culture-led regeneration whereby culture can alleviate the effects of poverty by growing the town's

economy. One of the strategic step changes in both the 2021 bid document and within the Future Paisley regeneration programme was to 'lift communities out of poverty' using culture (CCSE, n.d). It is unsurprising, then, that poverty and inequality were reflected in newspaper reporting of Paisley and newspaper representations of the town. However, this takes on a less politically neutral position in the minds of respondents, inasmuch as this creates an unfairly negative reputation for the town.

Respondents believed there had been a disproportionate focus on the negative at the expense of the positive in representations of Paisley. The notion that negative media coverage had dented local confidence and civic pride was a common theme throughout interviews. As one local artist put it:

When your town has been told that you're a shithole constantly, you actually start to believe it...you can't keep hammering home to people how crap they, how bullshit they are, you want to encourage people... It just pushes them down and down. How can you find positivity if you keep getting told you're shite? (Respondent 10, Local Artist)

I think in particular, as you'll know, north-west Paisley where we're based, around Ferguslie and Shortroods it's always in the newspaper...it's almost like our argument against that if you continue to tell people and places that they are just rubbish then, you know, they're going to believe that, and if it's all we're talking about and all we're thinking about and all we're seeing, then you stop seeing the good bits. And I think that's what had happened to Paisley. (Respondent 9, STAR Project)

Local community workshop respondents reinforced the idea that the town had become synonymous with narratives and images of decline inasmuch as Paisley was represented as the archetypal example of urban decline. More specifically, respondents emphasised the way the media had used Paisley as a visual representation for a run-down area:

And, you know, when you want to film a dump, you use Paisley (Respondent 1, Workshop 1)

But I think it's also because it's easy because STV, BBC, they always looking for a town that's run down so they come to Paisley because it is nearest and it's not that far but they could be a wee bit more proactive in showing the different side to Paisley than the alternative image. (Respondent 3, Workshop 2)

The perception that media coverage of Paisley was overwhelmingly negative was juxtaposed, in the minds of respondents at least, with the lack of focus on the positive stories of Paisley and the town's cultural and architectural heritage which creates an unfairly negative construction of Paisley as a violent and dangerous place:

I don't think Paisley's portrayed the way it should be... Because obviously we've got all these buildings, we've got the Coats Memorial, we've got the Observatory, we've got Paisley Abbey, Sma' shot, we've got loads of stuff, loads of lovely buildings and all that in Paisley, the Paisley Pattern. But it always seems to be 'violence', that's the way I see it, know what I mean? It's always violence that's spoke about and negative towards us when it doesn't need to be, as I've said last time it's the minority of people that give it a bad name (Respondent 2, Workshop 2)

When prompted to discuss what they felt was positive about Paisley, respondents' echoed the heritage assets outlined in *The Untold Story*, as well as popular events which have been increasingly promoted as part of the Future Paisley cultural regeneration programme. There is a clear synergy between the discourses of cultural regeneration outlined in newspaper reporting and how local stakeholders and residents conceived of the positive aspects of the town.

6.2.3.1 Local community resilience

Beyond the view that negative representations of Paisley had negatively impacted local civic pride, local communities were frequently referred to as resilient by stakeholders including third sector actors or those working directly for the local authority:

So I supposed what I witnessed was that fight back from local people about saying please don't capture the image of Paisley in this way, and actually kind of an awareness that that's the way Paisley has been shown for...You've got images of like Ferguslie Park quite typically and, again I'm not an expert on that at all because I'm not from there, having heard from people who live there and are part of that community talking about how they were just often talked about this, you know, deprived community. Top SIMD are etc., and they're like 'we're so much more' all this amazing culture and all this is going on here (Respondent 4, Create Paisley)

I think that probably what we found, and certainly what I had found was that a lot of local people were actually quite browbeaten by media coverage and by this rhetoric that took on a life of its own. (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

The view that stigmatised communities in Paisley were resilient was reinforced during workshops with local community members, who spoke both of the negative reputation of certain areas of the town, but also of a more generalised stigma associated with being from Paisley:

Erm so when I say I'm from Paisley people always say 'but you don't have the accent' as in, you don't talk like a ned...I do think just because of socio-economic problems, there's a lot of poverty in Paisley and, you know, people assume we're all neds and stuff (Respondent 2, Workshop 1)

Ferguslie and up the other schemes...that does have connotations that as soon as people hear them, em poverty, unemployment, everything like that (Respondent 1, Workshop 1)

I think it's hard to, though I think it's a wee bit better now, but it's hard to shake that title off because people will be like 'oh you're from Paisley' as if you're a big hard person, but we're not. So I do think it's got a bad rep when there is a lot of good about the town but I do think we've got reputation throughout... I do think it's hard to shake that title off, you know what I mean...not that we've got a title' (Respondent 2, Workshop 2)

This raises questions as to how stigma is produced and how it connects with the negative reputation that is clearly associated with town, in the minds of respondents at least. To return to Kearns et al. (2013), the local press is closely implicated in the production of stigma as well as the broader reputation of place, at least for local residents. When applied to the context

of Paisley, local respondents were highly critical of negative reporting of the local newspaper the *Paisley Daily Express*:

I was going to say every time I look at that paper, not that I buy it a family member buys it, every time I look at it somebody's at court, somebody's at court the day for doing this, somebody's at court for that. There's not a day goes by without somebody been in it for court, and it is all bad things (Respondent 2, Workshop 2)

Criticism of the local press is interesting insofar as it contradicts the findings from chapter five, wherein the *Paisley Daily Express* reporting was more likely to contain more positive content than national or international publications. However, while local newspapers are more likely to publish positive stories, this is not to suggest that this is because the proportion of their coverage is generally more positive than national or international newspapers. Rather, the sheer volume of coverage in a more localised context means that more negative stories are still dominant. Attempts to change the balance of reporting in Paisley can be seen through target attempts to push certain narratives and stories about Paisley out into newspaper reporting, as well as targeting specific newspapers.

6.2.4 Changing perceptions: projecting narratives of Paisley through newspaper coverage

Attempts to target certain publications, at a local and national level, appears to have been a central part of the strategy to change perceptions of Paisley through cultural regeneration. Breaking this down, the strategic approach to communications for the UKCoC bid and subsequent Future Paisley programme sought to focus on separate, yet interrelated, internal and external aspects of Paisley's reputation. In practice, this meant generating more consistent day to day positive stories in the local press while simultaneously targeting London-based national publications:

Well, the local press were really important to us, because we needed them to be our just day to day champion of what we're doing in the bid and they were wonderful to us. But we also knew that we wanted to get into a lot of the London papers and UK wide, we worked really, really hard to get the Guardian. We worked really hard to look at the Telegraph, and we had a list of a lot of the different people we knew we wanted in our camp and we just actively pursued that. (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

This comment highlights that targeted media and public relations efforts can influence the nature of newspaper reporting about Paisley. Moreover, beyond targeting well-known newspapers, specific journalists known for covering issues of cultural regeneration were also seen as high priority targets:

We were really, really careful to look at who were the commentators in the media who were looking at cultural regeneration. Erm it was a really tactical approach and quite forensic in the detail that sat behind. Every newspaper, every supplement where there was a column or a pitch or an angle that spoke about cultural regeneration in its widest sense and the power of culture in terms of, you know, social renewal and what can be achieved we made sure that we spoke to that journalist, that we spoke to that commentator that we had really, really compelling stories to pitch and then we played on top of that almost like the events programme, so that we were then demonstrating our cultural credibility as part of the campaign. (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

The targeted communications strategy to generate press attention from both local and national newspapers was successful in the sense that coverage was forthcoming (see chapter

five) but not all stakeholders recognised the benefit to their activities. Targeted efforts from the local state to project specific narratives about Paisley may have generated some success, however it appears that some of those out with the local state were able to benefit from Paisley's increased profile as a result of greater press attention. The Chief Executive of a local theatre company suggested that:

we're always fighting to get even reviewers to come to our shows, or erm to get press that's outwith the Paisley Express or you know we got some stuff recently in the Scotsman for the launch of our theatre project. But, you know, it's really hard to get people to, the whole industry, press or other theatre industry people or funders or whoever to see what's happening here seriously and you know take it seriously and see it as an important thing that's happening out with Glasgow and Edinburgh
(Respondent 11, Chief Executive of PACE Theatre Company)

This suggests that there was, seemingly, a difficulty in attracting press attention outwith more local newspaper outlets. This runs counter to claims that the UKCoC bid had succeeded in putting Paisley back on the map. Indeed, this suggests that those out with the local state continued to struggle to attract newspaper attention even during the bid campaign. It is interesting, therefore, that Respondent 11 appeared supportive of the narrative that the UKCoC campaign had helped put Paisley back on the map and grow the town's reputation.

I think the whole Paisley 2021 bid was really positive in that regard, in terms of drawing press attention and industry attention to Paisley. And I do think it has changed, em, a lot of people's perspectives...but I do think that if a lot of the work that was being done in Paisley was being done in the Tron (laughs) it would be a different...there would be

a different story really. It would be a lot more widely covered. (Respondent 11, Chief Executive of PACE Theatre Company)

There is an interesting juxtaposition here – the UKCoC bid is articulated as a positive force for changing perspectives on Paisley by drawing press attention to the town, while there is a simultaneous acknowledgement that increased press attention (during the bid or otherwise) does not necessarily level the playing field. While the UKCoC is believed to have boosted Paisley’s reputation by garnering media coverage, this does not necessarily lead to immediate local benefits or challenge existing cultural place hierarchies.

6.2.4.1 Strategies for projecting narratives of Paisley

In order to answer research question one, it is important to understand how publications were targeted and how narratives of cultural regeneration in Paisley were produced and communicated. Indeed, if we are to understand *how* discourses of cultural regeneration are constructed, and the extent they are reflected in newspaper messages communicated about Paisley, then it is important to explore how key decision makers *projected* desired narratives about the town. Additionally, to return to Foucault (1982; 1989) if discourse is therefore what *can be said* as opposed to just *what is said*, then it is important to determine the conditions of possibility that enable or constrain discursive constructions of Paisley and cultural regeneration.

In the context of the UKCoC bid and the launch of the Future Paisley in the post-bid period, two main strategies through which key messages and narratives were pushed to the press are evident. First, celebrities with connections to the town through residency or familial connections were recruited to support the communications strategy for the bid team and to publicly ‘back the bid’:

We also actively looked at key influencers, and looked at who were the people with a connection to the town who had gone on to do things nationally and internationally that were important to our cultural story. And we actively pursued them and everybody that we had on our list. We had Paulo (Nutini), we had Gerard Burns, em we had David Tenant, we had the Straight Outta Paisley t-shirt. So we managed to activate this network of really high profile supporters, who just added to that swell of local voice (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

While not directly related to newspaper coverage, using high profile celebrities with local connections was a key medium both for promoting the bid campaign but also for projecting specific narratives about the town, the bid and the value of cultural regeneration. Beyond celebrity endorsement, local connections to celebrities, such as Paulo Nutini, was itself an integral part of the overarching narrative insofar as it is used to demonstrate a degree of credibility that Paisley was a cultural town. This was most clearly articulated by Respondent 2 who suggested that:

I think as part of our reputation, we have a lot of pride in our success stories, um, so for example like Paulo Nutini who is like Paisley's biggest celebrity, you know. And everyone pretends like he's their cousin and is really proud of him. But I think he is like really good representation for the town, 'oh look we can actually produce something that's good'. Erm, he's always going on about how he's proud to be from Paisley and stuff, so that's nice. That's a positive. (Respondent 2, Workshop 1)

When taken together, local celebrity influencers appear to have been purposefully utilised by key personnel such as the Head of Marketing and Communications, both as a conduit for the

promotion of the bid, and to push particular narratives via specific endorsements, and a source of positive representation in and of themselves. From this perspective, celebrity influencers such as Paulo Nutini take on an ambassadorial role, representing the town positively both actively (by becoming involved in promoting the more explicating as, for example, during the UKCoC campaign) and passively (by being associated with the town more generally).

The second strategy for projecting agreed narratives was hosting press visits, particularly to attract journalists from (inter)national newspapers (The Guardian, 2016; Independent, 2018). The process for planning and hosting press visits operated in a similar way to the use of celebrity influencers, targeting recruitment and suggesting content:

Well, it's the exact same principle, we put a lot of work into look at having our list of targets. So we, erm, at the beginning of every season we do our sort of forecast where we look at long leads, we look at short leads, we look at features, we look at all the seasonal stuff that's going to be running. We look at commentators, the writers and all these different things, and then we actively look at pitches that we know will be interesting to those specific journalists. Our events give us a huge sort of momentum
(Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

More specifically, organising press visits around certain key events, or designing packages to display a particular aspect of the town enabled key personnel to push certain agreed messages about Paisley and its transformation through culture:

What we have also done is, on a couple of occasions, is work with the city. Work with Glasgow or work with our other areas to give that sort of dual purpose visit. So you

maybe come out to Paisley and do the Halloween festival, next day recover at a SPA and then maybe go up to loch Lomond etc. so to really try and make that if we're bringing journalists up we pack the itinerary for them, they get to see different sides of the town, they get to speak to interesting people and we do feel, you know, we're big enough and we're good enough to also show them another part of Scotland as well
(Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

There are a number of specific messages that were used to market Paisley during press visits. Most obvious, here, is Paisley's favourable geographical proximity to other tourist destinations in Scotland, as well as the town's peripheral geography within the greater Glasgow metropolitan area. This reflects discourses of culture-led regeneration which focus on a more instrumental relationship between culture and developing the visitor economy. Interestingly, this reflects the initial logic behind the UKCoC bid insofar as it was based around utilising Paisley's geographical proximity to key amenities to develop the visitor economy:

But Paisley's got the highest concentration of listed buildings outside of Edinburgh...than anywhere else in Scotland. It's got an Abbey, it's got the Baptist cathedral and, you know, the coats memorial church. It's got this museum that the untold story, no-one knows. All this stuff has just been sitting here, underused, under-utilised.... (Respondent 1, Former Leader of Renfrewshire Council)

Specific narratives of Paisley, and thus implicitly of regeneration, have been pushed out in a controlled and tactical fashion. Representations of Paisley, the bid and regeneration cannot be assumed, therefore, to be accidental nor politically neutral.

However, this targeted approach to place marketing can be contrasted to respondents in workshops, who were either critical or unaware of the marketing approach being used in Paisley:

But I bet there's lots of places and lots of things that you don't know about, and even I don't about. But unless you go really looking for it, you don't know it's there. So I feel, I don't know what you would say, marketing? I don't know if that's the word you would say, marketing getting it out there to local people, what's out there, what's available kind of thing. (Respondent 4, Workshop 2)

I think people like who who've lived here (all their life) obviously, aye I'll know. But people like R1 for instance who's not from Paisley so she's maybe relying on maybe like all of us to help her with this and that and where X, Y and Y is. I don't think there's enough marketing now, em, for like new comers coming to the town unless you do your research on it yourself. I don't think there's enough out there letting people know what's here...I certainly don't think there's enough marketing out there to let people know what's in Paisley, even like the murals and all the nice buildings we've got around the town, and the museum which obviously is closed the now anyways but yeah I don't think that unless you live here to be honest (Respondent 2, Workshop 2)

The discourse that Paisley was not being marketed sufficiently also appears to mirror the rhetoric of *The Untold Story* insofar as the document emphasised the need to promote knowledge which is common locally but apparently unknown beyond this. What is interesting, therefore, is that the participant's lack of awareness of the broader marketing of Paisley comes through so strongly six years after the publication of *The Untold Story*, in the wake of the UKCoC bid and the launch of the Future Paisley. Given that *The Untold Story* sets out a

model of heritage-led or culture-led regeneration, it is important to discuss how discourses of cultural regeneration have shifted and mutated between 2014-2020.

6.3 Discourses of regeneration

6.3.1 'Doing a Dundee': models and methods of cultural regeneration in Paisley

From the interview and workshop findings, Paisley's proximity to Glasgow appears to be understood as having both a *negative* and a *positive* impact on the town. In terms of negative impact, the rise of Glasgow as a retail and leisure centre was understood as further exacerbating the perceived decline of Paisley town centre. The town centre was frequently defined by its proximity to Glasgow city centre. Respondents often invoked the (perceived) ability of Paisley's previous retail offer to attract visitors from Glasgow as both a testament to its former strength and current decline:

I think, so, my understanding is that Paisley used to be this place that was like so well known. So like the image that I get when people who have been in Paisley for longer than I or have a sense for the past of Paisley would be that Paisley would be this place you come to for retail. I mean this is probably more recent history this isn't...like you'd have like the most incredible fashion stores, like you wouldn't go to Glasgow you'd come to Paisley to go shopping. (Respondent 4, Create Paisley)

Well, you know, going back to my early days, you know, Paisley was the place to be. Glasgow folk used to come Paisley when the shops all shut on a half day in Glasgow (Respondent 12, Former Business Owner and Community Activist)

Additionally, the decline of Paisley town centre is also, it seems, accompanied by the relative rise of Glasgow city centre as a retail destination:

But the knife into Paisley as a centre came from the (Glasgow) city centre, and the growth of the city centre as a retail magnet... But the starting point is, for me anyway, was way, way back with Glasgow city centre and the strength of that post-Garden (festival) city and the going as far back as the 1980 (Respondent 5, Head of Economy and Development at Renfrewshire Council)

However, while the rise of Glasgow city centre is invoked in Paisley's decline, is also constructed as essential to the regeneration of the town centre by utilising the pull of Glasgow as a major urban centre:

It's been a major competitor for Paisley, but at the same time it gives Paisley and awful lot of options and opportunities to, if you like, piggyback on the back of that as well...Because you've got a lot of people coming to visit Glasgow. You've got a lot of people coming internationally to visit Glasgow in normal times, pre-COVID. And therefore Paisley can surely benefit from some that by having some of its own offer to put on the table (Respondent 5, Head of Regeneration at Renfrewshire Council)

More generally, in invoking the Glasgow model appears to point towards a culture-led approach redevelopment. From this perspective, Paisley stands to benefit economically from Glasgow's culture-led redevelopment which can be leveraged to stimulate the visitor economy. In addition to Glasgow, the redevelopment of the waterfront area of Dundee, a city in the north east of the Scottish Lowlands, and – in particular - the recent construction of the V&A museum has had a clear influence on the development of regeneration in Paisley:

we were looking at what Dundee was doing...Not everybody goes and sees the V&A in Dundee, but lots of people talk about it that will never go into that building. But it still

has developed this...allowed Dundee to then spend not just £100 million but probably a billion round about (Respondent 1, Former Leader of Renfrewshire Council)

Well I think Dundee's done an amazing job so I wouldn't want to say that we made it up. Not at all. I think if we were able to pull of what Dundee did. I mean what Dundee did was they had a 20-year vision for change, and they followed that blueprint and culture was their catalyst for that (Respondent 2, Director of Communities and Housing at Renfrewshire Council)

when you looked around other areas in Scotland – Dundee being the obvious example, and Glasgow as well – you would see how they had harnessed the energy attached to their assets (Respondent 14, Chief Executive of Engage Renfrewshire)

I think that really comes across in the same sort of way that Dundee has managed to do that, I think there's the same passion in Paisley to look at culture as a way of regenerating what is town that has had its problems over the years and has been economically impacted over the year (Respondent 11, Chief Executive of PACE Theatre Company)

There was no sense that local decision makers simply wanted to copy or replicate Dundee's strategy. Instead, they expressed the difference in Paisley's approach, as smaller in scale and without the need to bulldoze and reconstruct areas of the town. The difference between refurbishment and rebuilding was emphasised to distinguish the Paisley approach and the Dundee approach:

I mean Dundee will be an example but Dundee, as I said, is very, very different because what Dundee basically did is take a bulldozer. No disrespect, great amount for Mike

Galloway and the team and the new team that's up there in terms of what they've done. But they've basically demolished the waterfront and started again. We've had to try and do the same thing, or we're working towards trying to do the same thing without basically knocking anything down or knocking anything of heritage down in Paisley town centre (Respondent 5, Head of Economy and Development at Renfrewshire Council)

Paisley wasn't about building new big shiny things, it was about how do we harness the assets that we already have in our urban environment? Both physical, built environment, as well as outside open space (Respondent 8, technical bid advisor)

Now Paisley, em, Paisley doesn't need to build a V&A because we've got that kind of we've got our museum already. But we've got a real opportunity to build in a very similar way and to actually have that longer term vision that will guide us in that way (Respondent 2, Director of Communities and Housing at Renfrewshire Council)

The notion that Paisley's approach was to build on what is already there, in the view of respondents within the local authority and their advisors at least, belies a subtle but important difference in approach – in that Paisley is building on already existing assets and investing in them, as opposed to more drastic measures seen in other regeneration approaches. There is a clear narrative cohesion between a discourse that champions Paisley's ability to invest and (re)develop its culture and heritage offer and the narratives outlined in *The Untold Story*. Additionally, there is also clear emphasis on replicating specific models of regeneration in which culture *leads* the broader transformation of place and how it is perceived.

6.3.2 The role of external discourses in shaping cultural regeneration in Paisley

The findings from this study have also demonstrated the level of importance placed on external influences in developing Paisley's cultural regeneration strategy, via the broader networks that have emerged between stakeholders in Paisley and those working in other regeneration projects, and broader consultants working across the regeneration sector:

...Luckily, for us, one of the consultants on the team, eh, hailed from Derry, Derry-London Derry, and it was just in the year that Derry was UK City of Culture. And he could see the parallels, I think, between Paisley and Derry and he pointed us very much in that direction and said 'look, you should look places like Dundee and also Derry and see if you can kind of carve a path for Paisley (Respondent 1, Former Leader of Renfrewshire Council)

So Dundee had bid to be UK City of Culture the year that Derry had won it, so they hadn't been successful Derry had been, so right we know people in Dundee so we'll go off and speak to them about all that (Respondent 3, Regeneration Manager at Renfrewshire Council)

Respondents did not conceive of Paisley's approach as a mere replica of other culture-led regeneration strategies. Paisley's approach, it was argued, can be differentiated in that it is viewed as more holistic than other top-down modes of culture-led regeneration projects:

So whether that's the Guggenheim in Bilbao, or whether it's the Barcelona Olympics, or Glasgow Commonwealth Games there led by a one-off thing whether it be the opening of a building, albeit it has a life beyond its opening, or a major event coming in. Because we didn't get the major event, we thought we had an opportunity to do

something that was slightly different, and therefore we would think about the economic, the physical, the social and the cultural bits together rather than just thinking about what the mass...you know the multi-event cultural UK City of Culture would be or if we think about a new building would be...it culture-led vs cultural regeneration, and for us the distinction came down to being that we wanted something holistic. (Respondent 6, Former Strategic Lead of Cultural Regeneration for Renfrewshire Council)

However, the view that Paisley was adopting a cultural regeneration approach, which was most prominent from those who began working in Paisley in the wake of the bid is contrasted with views from both internal and external stakeholders and consultants involved in the UKCoC bid who tended to view Paisley's approach as being more 'culture-led':

For Paisley it probably borders more on culture-led. Which I think for them is the right approach. You know, utilising the assets they had whether that's in the town hall, or the abbey or the refurbished museum building as centre pieces I think is really important (Respondent 8, Technical Bid Advisor)

So, I think the key people who were driving this as an initiative, they were looking at a year of culture as a catalyst for change. So, a catalyst for changing the economy, a catalyst for changing perceptions and so on and so forth (Respondent 15, Engagement Manager UKCoC bid)

For the former Leader of the local authority, the UKCoC bid clearly reflected an opportunity for economic development and the development of Paisley's visitor economy:

So that's where doing this stuff on culture immediately translates into money, and jobs...it's the whole idea of tourism, you give you something to come and see, advertise it properly, tell you about it, make you interested and make it dead easy for you to come. And why you do come, somewhere for you to stay, and other things for you to buy. So it...we, yeah it was the one thing with culture that I could then directly translate that into a financial benefit for Renfrewshire (Respondent 1, Former Leader of Renfrewshire Council)

There is a clear contrast in the visions put forward here. In the latter vision, speaking about the formation of the bid campaign and the approach to regeneration which was to underpin it, respondents articulated a much more instrumental relationship between culture and place. In this articulation, cultural assets can be leveraged principally for an economic benefit to the local area, particularly insofar as this pertains to the development of the visitor economy within Paisley. This vision reflects a more *culture-led* approach (see Richards and Wilson, 2006; Miles, 2020; Miles and Paddison, 2005). On the other hand, the vision of *cultural* regeneration discussed by Respondent 6 marks a discursive shift *away* from the more instrumental logic of culture-led regeneration, from the physical and economic realm exclusively, to incorporate the social (Future Paisley, 2019). What is also interesting about this discourse is that it also (re)positions the unsuccessful UKCoC bid campaign as a positive part of a wider process. Here, *not* winning and subsequently delivering a major event is positioned as an opportunity to break with the established logic of culture-led regeneration.

The discursive shift to incorporate the social into broader discourses of cultural regeneration is reflected in the approach taken during this period clearly reflecting *some* shift away from the familiar framework of culture-led or creative city development strategies. This does not

mean, however, that Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration can be separated entirely. The redevelopment of flagship cultural venues such as Paisley Museum and Paisley Town Hall which were given prominence in newspaper reporting after the UKCoC bid show some level of continuity with other culture-led regeneration strategies. However, for the former Strategic Lead for Cultural Regeneration, this does not mean that we cannot disaggregate *cultural* regeneration from more instrumental forms of culture-led regeneration:

Yeah, it would if it (investing in 'flagship' assets) was just that you were doing but that's just one part of what we're doing. So, it's about trying to understand the whole mix, and the accumulative and aggregated benefit of all of it together if that makes sense. It depends how you also do the museum (Respondent 6, Former Strategic Lead of Cultural Regeneration for Renfrewshire Council)

While there certainly appears to be a strategic similarity between both culture-led and cultural regeneration in Paisley, discourses of place, culture and regeneration have not been static nor necessary evolutionary during the bid period and after. Rather, there is an evident shift, which seeks to go beyond a purely instrumental relationship between culture and place. Notwithstanding these uncertainties, the language used to describe the process of cultural regeneration in the post-bid period more closely resembles the language of creative placemaking inasmuch as there is an increased focus on bottom-up creative activity (see Wilson 2021, Oakley, 2015).

6.4 Local community engagement

6.4.1 The 'aye right' test: Discourses of local community support

A claim frequently associated with event bidding, cultural regeneration and image transformation is that it can boost levels of civic pride in local communities (see Richards and Wilson, 2004, 2006; Bell and Oakley, 2014). In the case of Paisley, respondents made it clear that enhancing local perceptions of place and instilling a sense of local pride was a key benefit that they sought to leverage from the bid campaign and subsequent launch of Future Paisley:

I think the message from Paisley really is that we've got a real solid base to build on. The 2021 (UKCoC) bid highlighted that and gave us internally a wee bit of belief that we're from a decent place and it could get better, and projected out the way that that place Paisley is not bad by the way (Respondent 16, Local Community Activist)

There was a real civic pride in Paisley from the people of Paisley that I think probably wasn't there before, and if it was it was buried so deep you would have never of found it. And there was, one of the biggest things, was that people's expectations had been raised considerably. And rightly so because with that increase in civic pride, there was a self-belief from the people of Paisley that actually, you know what, we might not have won but look what've done in the process. (Respondent 8, Technical Bid Advisor)

But I think that it to a person, and from over the arc of the bid journey, that that pride in place and positive, people loved seeing positive stories about the bid in the papers or about the town, not the bid per se, or on the telly all that stuff (Respondent 13, Bid Director)

These responses can be tied more closely to discourses of creative placemaking than culture-led approaches because of their focus on increasing levels of confidence from local communities is implicated in broader discourses of co-production and in giving local communities a space to articulate both the positive and negative aspects of their communities:

That was the thing that was most potent was actually the speed and which local people stepped forward, and the confidence they had in actually championing their town, owning the issues (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

The view that local confidence, as well as civic pride and participation, were boosted by the bid echoes discourses of creative placemaking insofar as it reflects a commitment to local engagement and local community empowerment (see Courage, 2021a). That is not to suggest, however, that local community support for both the UKCoC bid and broader cultural regeneration initiatives within Paisley can be assumed, *a priori*, to be uncritical and homogenous. Among respondents, for example, there was a consistent narrative that local communities were initially displeased by culture-led redevelopment plans within the town, but that they were won over as the bid campaign progressed and gained momentum:

I think the bid began with cynicism, but the way the bid engaged and opened up a conversation brought about, I think, the most enormous change in how people felt about their town, its place in the world and their confidence in it (Respondent 6, Former Strategic Lead of Cultural Regeneration for Renfrewshire Council)

More specifically, this was referred to as the 'aye right test' which plays on the local dialect to illustrate the way in which local communities, as well as external commentators, were initially shocked by the idea that a town such as Paisley was bidding for UKCoC. From this perspective, the relative prestige of culture and the UKCoC title is juxtaposed with the negative image and reputation of the town:

I joined at the time we were launching our bid for UK City of Culture and was very aware of us having to go through that 'aye right' test. So, at that time, if you searched for Paisley what you were thrown up was a lot of pretty negative articles about the town...I did think when we were launching the bid there was that 'aye right' test to pass and whether people would react to the news, and what we saw initially, there was a flurry of quite bemused...a sort of bemused reaction, not a negative one but a bemused reaction (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

Who was it that used to say 'aye right'? (Laughs)... there was the aye right moment but people got past that really quickly. And you always have knockers don't you? You always have people who are going to...but they were the minority. They were absolutely the minority of voices (Respondent 2, Director of Communities and Housing at Renfrewshire Council)

The 'aye right test'. That you've got to get to the stage where if I say that to you and you say 'aye right very good', and then you tell them about it and then they start to realise 'oh right ok, I get that'. And then it uses that negative energy and becomes a positive thing (Respondent 1, Former Leader of Renfrewshire Council)

It is interesting to note the extent to which the 'aye right' test echoes the narratives outlined in *The Untold Story* in that it implies that the richness of Paisley's culture and heritage offer is secondary to negative perceptions of the town. From this perspective, local responses to the UKCoC bid and culture-led redevelopment was met with scepticism because Paisley was not viewed as being a cultural town, however this was changed by (re)focusing on the international significance of Paisley.

Despite what was described as an initial cynicism from local communities, respondents were firm in their view that the UKCoC bid and associated cultural regeneration projects have resulted in a positive reputational shift in how the town is viewed:

I think there's been a reputational and image shift for Paisley, despite not winning the bid. And I think I've always said, I didn't matter if we won or not, we were going to win anyway. This was a winning journey for Paisley, and I do think that there was only positive that came from that (Respondent 2, Director of Communities and Housing at Renfrewshire Council)

So, I think that the reputation is changing, I do think the reputation is changing and I think people are looking at Paisley and I suppose the proof you have for that is the way that national funders and partners are coming around it (Respondent 6, Former Strategic Lead of Cultural Regeneration for Renfrewshire Council)

Even respondents who were highly critical of the UKCoC bid, and of cultural regeneration more generally, were of the view that the bid – from an external 'PR' standpoint was a 'magnificent success':

Overall, the bid from a PR point of view was a magnificent success. You can't argue with that, there's no negative from me on that. Paisley 2021 bid for UK City of Culture, from an outward PR point of view was a magnificent thing, a magnificent success
(Respondent 16, Local Community Activist)

To return to chapter five, the UKCoC bid helped Paisley to improve its reputation demonstrated by a clear increase in positive newspaper reporting of the town. What is less clear, however, is the extent to which this can be applied past the broad quantitative rubric of newspaper reporting. During workshop one, which was attended by respondents more closely involved with other cultural, leisure and heritage focused activities within the town in either a professional or voluntary capacity, respondents were generally supportive of the bid, if sceptical of the campaign's overall impact on how Paisley was perceived:

yeah I guess. I mean I backed the bid, I supported it and I'm happy that it's kick-started a lot of regeneration in the town centre which is sorely needed. Um, but I always knew that we wouldn't get it... think it is just...you know sometimes you know things, and I think it is a west of Scotland defeatist attitude, you know 'nothing good ever happens here, we're not going to get anything (Respondent 2, Workshop 1)

While most respondents backed the bid, there was clearly a lesser degree of enthusiasm in as much as they did not believe that Paisley would succeed in the bid campaign. This appears to contradict the claim from elite stakeholders that the bid campaign increased local pride and confidence insofar as, at the very least, local respondents lacked the confidence or belief that the town could actually become UKCoC. To return to the 'aye right' test, the bemused reaction to the UKCoC campaign was remarked on by local residents unprompted by the researcher:

...and when the city of culture was happening it was a bit of a joke at some points –
'aye right Paisley? What's that all about?' (Respondent 1, Workshop 1)

In workshop two, however, there was a less clear recollection of the bid campaign among any of the respondents, who were typically residents from socio-economically disadvantaged areas of Paisley:

The first I've heard about it (the bid) is from yourself! (Respondent 1, Workshop 2)

It was a wee while ago now, I canny remember now. It was basically bidding to be a city, but we lost. You know, I can't remember much. I did support it, but it's been a wee while now that I can't remember (Respondent 2, Workshop 2)

The 'aye right' test articulated by elite stakeholders reflects, to some extent, the local responses to the bid campaign in Paisley. Indeed, the aye-right test reflects at least some belief among elite stakeholders that there was a sceptical reaction to the UKCoC bid from at least some local residents. With this in mind, the next section discusses the tendency to construct sceptical local residents as 'naysayers'.

6.4.2 The naysayers

While the local responses to creative placemaking and the UKCoC was positioned as initially sceptical but overall very positive, there was an acknowledgement of some more critical responses by local residents. What is interesting, however, is the discursive construction of those who opposed or criticised the bid as 'naysayers':

don't get me wrong, you know...there was a lot, a lot of people who were distinctly unimpressed about the idea at the start, and perhaps even unhappy. 'What do you

think you're talking about, you know Paisley...city of culture? You're kidding...you know, there's this happening and look at that building falling down' (Respondent 14, Chief Executive of Engage Renfrewshire)

Oh aye there was doubters you know, thinking it's a waste of money, who's going to have to pay for that. But if you were involved in any way, any small way like I was, you could see what the benefits would be. (Respondent 12, Former Business Owner and Community Activist)

And you always have knockers don't you? You always have people who are going to...but they were the minority. They were absolutely the minority of voices (Respondent 2, Director of Communities and Housing at Renfrewshire Council)

There was an awful lot of naysayers, you know, there was an awful lot of people going 'what are we doing that for, what a waste of money', 'Paisley's rubbish, Paisley's this', and I thought 'imagine talking about your own place like that (Respondent 9, STAR Project)

Opposition to event bids is certainly not a new concept, particularly within the context of event-led development plans which rely on hosting major and mega events such as the Olympic Games (See Lauermann, 2016; McGillivray et al., 2019; McGillivray and Turner, 2017). What is interesting, in the case of Paisley, is the extent to which the smaller (sub)urban context pacifies the dominant strands of event protest we have witnessed in larger bids and cities. This perspective does not suggest that local communities were necessarily more supportive of the bid campaign. Rather, there was a sense that local communities and

community groups had no option but to support the bid, particularly given the relative power of the local authority:

That's what I was talking earlier (pre-recording) about waving the flag. The flag was given to us and you had no choice but wave it. No matter what it represented. Now this is only my view, and my personal view...I believe we were given what the potential answer was, there's a flag with 2021 on it, and you couldn't say you didn't support it. Publicly you couldn't not support it...So everybody waved the flag. 'Yay, aren't we great', 'Isn't Paisley a magnificent place', 'look what we're going to do', '2021 we're going to be fantastic'...'what is it again'? Oh you're doing up the town hall and museum, nobody asked about doing up the town hall. Nobody asked us about doing up the museum. It was a fait accompli in a document by a consultant from Dublin in consultation with people behind closed doors (Respondent 16, Local Community Activist)

What is striking about this quotation is the extent to which it outlines the relative (in)ability felt by a local community group to challenge or question the dominant discourses of the UKCoC bid or flagship regeneration projects in Paisley. Additionally, this contradicts the co-produced and democratic basis of creative placemaking projects insofar as it is suggested that local communities lacked the ability to shape the direction of the bid and could only, therefore, provide tacit support to the bid campaign. However, the need to move beyond the local authority as an institution to show support from the entirety of the community did, it seems, feature explicitly in the marketing and communications strategy for the UKCoC bid:

that was something we had quite carefully crafted and engineered into all our PR activity was the fact that nobody moves to a place or thinks a place is great because a council has

said that it is, it relies on the people of the place to share their stories (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

The importance placed on co-producing narratives of Paisley belies, it seems, an explicit awareness of the importance for the bid campaign, and the broader marketing and destination branding in Paisley, to be read by both local communities and external audiences as 'authentic'.

The awareness, within the local authority, of the need to sell an authentic narrative of Paisley reflects an interesting tension within the production of discourses and how this correlates to power. There emerges a paradox insofar as the communications surrounding Paisley's cultural regeneration is constructed as at once engineered, authentic and co-produced. The use of words such as engineered or crafted seem to imply that a certain level of control was maintained by the local authority insofar as they strived to engineer community engagement to produce authentic narratives of place. This selling and manufacturing of authenticity was further reflected throughout the interview(s) with personnel involved in the bid campaign and within the local authority:

Because if all you did was throw stuff out, going 'isn't this a great campaign?' all people would ever want was 'aye, it's alright I suppose'. But if you actually get folk to lead the campaign, then it becomes entrenched and the ideas (Respondent 14, Chief Executive of Engage Renfrewshire)

what we were able to do, and it was probably because of our relatively smaller scale, was engage so many people in town in the development of the narrative and the sort of key components of the bid so that when we were able to, and I've done this at a

couple of conferences since actually, when we were able to talk about the engagement of 36,000 people in a conversation about the town (Respondent 2 Regeneration Manager at Renfrewshire Council)

So, it had to be authentic, what we did had to be authentic to Paisley. It couldn't be something that, you know, someone else had had written. It had to absolutely be authentic to Paisley. And I think one of the things that we did really, really successfully was the community engagement and there was a massive investment in all of that...we had a massive, something like 37,000 individuals engaged with us in the development of the bid. (Respondent 2, Director of Communities and Housing at Renfrewshire Council)

This is not to suggest, however, that ideas of co-production and co-ownership have not been a focus of elite decision makers within Paisley:

It was about basically saying we're creating this for the town, and it's over to you to use and use in a way that you think befits the place that you live and the place that you love... So it was quite remarkable in terms of ownership that the key thing behind the strategy was ownership and allowing real people to lead, real people to you know for it to be real voices, real people to lead, the stories of authenticity from people on the ground and to create this brand and campaign that was so flexible that irrespective of who you were or what your connection to Paisley was you could use it...The whole principle about our communications was about being co-produced, about it being of the place (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

Despite the discourse of co-production surrounding the bid campaign, it is clear that the local authority remained at the forefront of cultural regeneration and place marketing activity. This is reflected by an acknowledgement that the Council was at the forefront of managing communications, at least in the context of UKCoC bid:

I think as well, what you've got to maybe look at this in the context of as well, it was a council was driving the comms on this, albeit on behalf of a bid partnership. And that's quite a risky ground for a council to move into (Respondent 7, Head of Marketing and Communications for Renfrewshire Council)

There is an evident tension within the narratives projected by the local authority and partners. On the one hand, there is a stated belief that the bid messaging had to be, and was, authentic and came from local communities. On the other, however, the local authority remained the primary vessel for communication, strategy and development of placemaking and marketing in Paisley. The politics of representation, particularly within the context of destination branding remain contentious within creative placemaking discourse, despite the term becoming seemingly synonymous, in rhetoric at least, with a broader agenda around community engagement and social justice (See Courage, 2021; Oakley, 2015; Markusen and Gadwa, 2010). This raises questions as to the existence of a counter-narrative to the claim that cultural regeneration represents more than just a 'council gig' (Respondent 16, Local Community Activist).

6.5 Conclusions

In this chapter, I have explored the dominant discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley emanating from semi-structured interviews with elite stakeholders and workshops with local residents in Paisley. In doing so, I addressed research question one and three, by exploring

how discourses of Paisley are constructed and local responses to these representation of the town. I have demonstrated how respondents conceived of Paisley's area reputation. More specifically, both discourses are based on post-industrial decline, town centre decline, and the persistence of poverty and inequality to legitimise cultural regeneration projects within Paisley. Building on this, I analysed the formation of discourses of regeneration in Paisley, drawing clear links between the broader academic literature on creative placemaking and culture-led regeneration, as well as newspaper reporting of regeneration in Paisley. I identify a tension between the holistic approach to cultural regeneration as outlined through both newspaper reporting and interviews with key stakeholders and the prominence of flagship cultural projects in newspaper reporting of Paisley, especially in the pre-UKCoC phase. Finally, I explored how elite stakeholder narratives of cultural regeneration frequently invoke discourses of the local community when discussing the success of cultural regeneration and creative placemaking projects. Elite stakeholders tended to emphasise the extent to which initial scepticism was overcome with positive media representation. Despite this, however, there remained a group of 'naysayers' within the local community who remained unsupportive of the bid campaign and flagship projects, such as the museum redevelopment. This raises interesting questions about tensions between local communities and local authorities within placemaking discourse that champions a 'bottom-up' and 'democratic' ethos.

Chapter 7: Post-industrial Paisley and the ‘actually existing’ hybridity of cultural regeneration

7.1 Introduction

As outlined in chapter’s five and six, the decline of Paisley as an industrial and retail centre is clearly integral to narratives of cultural regeneration in the town. Discourses of decline are frequently invoked to both contextualise and legitimise the broader process of cultural regeneration. In particular, discourses of post-industrial decline are common in media representations of regeneration projects. As noted by Kearns et al (2013: 50), newspaper reporting of regeneration tends to ‘provide an opportunity to restate why change was needed’ and to identify what is missing from places undergoing processes of regeneration. What this elides, however, is how narratives of cultural regeneration - the change itself - are themselves constructed, mediated and context-specific. As discussed in chapter three, the plurality of cultural regeneration and creative placemaking approaches and their broader political implications necessitates a deeper investigation of the conditions of possibility that enable or constrain narratives of cultural regeneration in Paisley, and the extent to which these narratives reflects dominant approaches to culture-led regeneration and creative placemaking.

In this chapter, I analyse the narratives of cultural regeneration (chapter five) and their formation (chapter six), to outline how discursive representations of Paisley are predicated on discourses of post-industrial decline while at the same time reflecting dominant discourses of culture-led regeneration and neoliberal urbanism. To begin, I analyse the formation of post-industrial discourses in the context of Paisley. I discuss the role of event bidding, culture-led regeneration and creative placemaking in initiating and driving reputational change. I then

explore how the imperative of image transformation itself reflects dominant assumptions of inter-urban competition and urban neoliberalism. Building on this, I then analyse the relationship between discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley and broader discourses of culture-led regeneration. I outline the prominence of flagship capital projects that appear to reflect the assumptions of culture-led regeneration.

Finally, I outline the emergence of what I call 'hybridised placemaking' as a tool for analysing the nuances by which we might begin to differentiate Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration. Hybridised placemaking demonstrates the path dependent, situated and mutating process of placemaking that emerges within a framework in which global discourses of neoliberalism and inter-urban competition inform *what can be said* about culturally informed placemaking practices. In Paisley, cultural regeneration discourses simultaneously represents a more 'holistic approach' more in line with creative placemaking, alongside the familiar axioms of a more 'top-down' culture-led regeneration approach.

7.2 Post-industrial Paisley and cultural regeneration

Throughout this thesis, I have argued that discursive constructions of (sub)urban decline are integral to modern discourses of cultural regeneration insofar as narratives of decline are invoked to legitimise the process itself. However, to date, there has been limited scholarly focus on the impact of post-industrial decline on smaller urban settings like Paisley, specifically within the context of cultural regeneration. A deeper analysis is needed of the extent to which narratives of town centre decline, poverty and inequality, as well as the broader narrative of (sub)urban decline, are implicated in broader discourses of the post-industrial society and the process of actually existing neoliberalism(s) (Brenner and Theodore, 2002; Boyle et al., 2007). This reflects the emergence of what I call post-industrial Paisley.

Post-industrial Paisley reflects the narratives identified in previous chapters in which representations of the town invoke images of town centre decline, retail restructuring, unemployment, and the loss of traditional manufacturing industries. At the most basic level, post-industrial Paisley reflects broader discourses of the post-industrial society as outlined by proponents such as Bell and Tourian (Chelsom Vogt, 2016). Contemporary representations of Paisley emphasise the decline of traditional manufacturing industries such as the closure of thread mills and the persistent narratives of unemployment in the town. Most prominently is the representation of Paisley town centre as a poster boy for town centre decline and the death of the high street.

Additionally, discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley are also implicated in the post-industrial Paisley narrative. This is most clearly seen in newspaper reporting which emphasises the substantial shift in the nature of retail and manufacturing which, itself, serves to legitimise the process of cultural regeneration by constructing it as a necessary adjustment to the post-industrial economic landscape. From this perspective, cultural regeneration is a mechanism for growing the visitor economy, leveraging events for economic growth, and contributing to town centre regeneration (see *The Untold Story*, 2014; Renfrewshire Visitor Strategy, 2018). This is most clearly articulated in the 'Vision for Paisley Town Centre 2030' (2020) document:

Buddies have a fierce loyalty to their town and there is a strong sense of belonging and rootedness to place. We often denigrate it with "the High Street's a disgrace" but this is born out of a memory of a bustling 70s/80s retail-led centre which isn't coming back (to any town). (p.7)

This brief excerpt clearly invokes discourses of town centre decline, specifically in a post-industrial, post-retail context. This is unsurprising when returning to Tallon (2013), who suggests that contemporary forms of urban regeneration are deeply implicated in discourses of urban decline and the post-industrial society. More specifically, however, retail decline is used to legitimise a specific *type* of regeneration strategy that foregrounds culture, heritage and leisure amid changing patterns of consumption in post-industrial society. Ritzer (1999) argues that cultural resources become the means of consumption in a (post-industrial) consumer society. Discourses of post-industrial decline are, it seems, not unique to Paisley. In the case of Glasgow, for example, rapid economic decline was argued to have given the city a particularly poor image which legitimised leisure and cultural-led investment (Boyle et al., 2007: 315). In Glasgow, investment in the city centre was done to put the city back on the map for investors and accomplish a city makeover, as well as building a post-industrial economic sector (ibid). Discourses of post-industrial decline are therefore tied to broader discourses of territorial stigma insofar as it connects with negative area reputations.

7.2.1 Post-industrial Paisley and territorial stigma

Foregrounding narratives of decline, poverty and inequality in Paisley reflects the emergent body of scholarly attention to processes of territorial stigma (see Larsen and Delica, 2019; Wacquant et al, 2014; Wacquant, 1993; Handcock and Mooney, 2013). In its early inception, territorial stigmatisation was defined as the negative public image of specific places, which, in turn, recasts their inhabitants as social outcasts while simultaneously depriving them of their collective representation and identity (Wacquant, 1993 cited in Larsen and Delica, 2019). Territorial stigmatisation is predicated on narratives of urban decline and even the ghettoization of central urban spaces (Wacquant 2008). These discourses have been

particularly influential with placemaking gurus such as Richard Florida (2004, 2018) who frequently rely on narratives of urban decline and de-industrialisation to legitimise the creative city agenda. More specifically, Florida (2018) frequently invokes the urban crisis of the 1960s, 1970s and 1980s:

As cities lost their core industries they became sites of growing and persistent poverty: their housing decayed; crime and violence increased; and social problems, including drug abuse, teen pregnancy, and infant mortality, escalated (p.5)

Florida's words sound eerily familiar to the narratives of urban decline found in the context of Paisley. They are also similar to the broken-windows model of regeneration, which foregrounds certain social pathologies and moral decay in the decline of inner-city areas (See Slater, 2014; Larsen and Delcia, 2019). Moral panics about, to use Florida's example, teenage pregnancy in the inner city have been implicated in political discourse that foregrounds individual misbehaviour to elide broader comment on the systemic nature of (urban) inequality (see Slater, 2014; Handcock and Mooney, 2013). However, narratives of urban decline are not politically neutral accounts of economic processes. Rather, they are closely related to dominant political discourses, either simply as a way of legitimising regeneration programmes – as we have seen in the case of Paisley – or in the more nefarious processes of social pathology. If, as Mould (2018) suggests, placemaking plays on urban imaginaries of decline, then perhaps this imaginary is also central to the stigmatisation of declining urban places.

More recently, there have been attempts to implicate different modalities of territorial stigma in broader discourses of urban regeneration, placemaking and gentrification (Kallin and Slater, 2014). However, there is a relative lack of research on the link between cultural

regeneration and territorial stigma (Larsen and Delica, 2019). In Paisley, negative newspaper representations reflect a broader stigma associated with the town. Foregrounding process(es) of decline and the post-industrial Paisley narrative, representations of cultural regeneration in the town risk further entrenching stigmatising discourses. There is a continued stigma around certain problem areas in Paisley, notably Ferguslie Park but also areas such as Shortroods and Gallowhill. In the forthcoming paragraphs, I will analyse how this stigma was understood and activated in interviews with elite stakeholders and local residents.

To begin with local government stakeholders, it is clear that respondents (re)produced dominant discourses of territorial stigma in Paisley insofar as they consistently highlighted problem areas of the town, including Ferguslie Park. This reflects one of the modalities of stigmatisation identified by Larsen and Delcia (2019), in that local political stakeholders become implicated in the broader (re)production of stigma and in the symbolic valorisation of space. However, unlike Ian Duncan Smith's Easterhouse moment (see Slater, 2014) in which seeing a deprived area merely confirmed the existence of social pathologies within the community. In Paisley, there appeared to be a greater emphasis placed on local community resilience and community spirit within deprived parts of the town by stakeholders who worked both in the local authority and in third sector agencies. Foregrounding resilience embodies the more progressive rhetoric of creative placemaking (Courage, 2021). However, relying on narratives of local community resilience also risks further pathologising residents in stigmatised communities. Mould (2018) argues, for example, that the valorisation of creativity and local community empowerment fit neatly within neoliberal urban development insofar as creativity legitimises both the logic of austerity (by charging us to do more with less by 'being creative') and the 'big society' mode of community development.

Beyond the purview of elite stakeholders, it is important to examine the bottom-up, grassroots (re)production of territorial stigma. From this perspective, we can see that local residents have a tendency to reproduce negative stereotypes associated with Paisley. It was generally accepted by respondents that Paisley suffered from a particularly poor reputation. In particular, it was accepted that Paisley had a reputation for violence and being a 'wee bit neddy'. This is not, in and of itself, surprising in that previous research has shown that local residents are *aware of why* the local area has a poor reputation (see Kullberg et al., 2010; Garbin and Millington, 2013; Power et al., 2020). However, beyond merely being aware of *why* Paisley has a particularly poor image and reputation, local residents in Paisley become active participants in production of stigmatising discourses as they distanced themselves and the majority of the town from the undesirable population, thereby reflecting broader discourses of the 'underclass' (see Welshman, 2013). The bad behaviour of 'nedds' (a Scots term for typically young traditionally working-class men who engage in, inter alia, anti-social behaviour and other petty offences) or young people are held responsible for the towns poor area reputation. This reflects what Wacquant (2009) calls submissive responses to stigma in which local residents internalise spatial stigma. It is worth noting, however, that Wacquant appears to have corrected his alleged overemphasis on submissive responses to stigma (see Pasquetti, 2019). Within this expanded framework of spatial stigma, there emerges a complex interplay between submissive and defiant responses to stigma which are deployed in different contexts in that defiance can be used with other residents and more submissive responses used when communicating with outsiders (ibid). This expanded rubric perhaps helps explain the duality of local responses insofar they seem to reflect defiance to stigma – in that local residents spoke of being proud of the town – and more submissive responses – by (re)affirming negative stereotypes about Paisley. In sum, it is clear that the post-industrial

Paisley discourse informs how Paisley's reputation is constructed. However, as discussed, it is also important to discuss how this informs attempts to *change* this negative area reputation through event and culture-led regeneration strategies. Post-industrial Paisley, as a concept, demonstrates somewhat of a paradox in which towns and cities construct culture-led regeneration strategies that *lean in* to the demands of the post-industrial economy that are simultaneously responsible for their economic decline. Discourses of the post-industrial society and town centre decline are invoked to justify an increasingly similar arsenal of culture-led regeneration strategies irrespective of their likelihood of success (however defined).

7.3 Changing perceptions: event bidding, cultural regeneration and neoliberalism

Garcia et al (2010) argues that the notion that event-led regeneration strategies, or even just hosting large events, can enhance the image and reputation of place is a particularly common discourse within the context of cultural festivals such as the ECOC or, by extension, the UKCoC. Indeed, in the case of Liverpool 2008 (Garcia et al., 2010) and Glasgow 1990 (Garcia, 2005) - the previous UK winners of the ECOC – there was a marked increase in newspaper reporting and media attention as a result of holding the title. Mooney (2004) acknowledges, in his critical account of Glasgow 1990, that hosting the ECOC is associated with a period of rebranding for the city:

Overwhelmingly, the dominant narrative that emerges from accounts of Glasgow's period as ECOC, and of culture led regeneration in the city per se, is that it was 'good for Glasgow' and that '1990' helped to 'transform' it. While there are a number of different dimensions to such claims, among key elements are that Glasgow's national and international reputation was considerably enhanced and that the city's image and

reputation was overhauled. Throwing off its long-term image as a place of grim urban decay, poverty, violence and industrial unrest, Glasgow was re-branded as 'vibrant', 'post-industrial', 'fashionable' city (p.329)

Garcia (2018) has also argued that image making is one of the dominant legacy assumptions behind hosting cultural events such as the ECOC. Despite this, there has been little research which has explored the impact of unsuccessful bids for cultural festivals, despite the body of literature on leveraging failed event bids in major and mega event contexts (see, for example, Bason and Grix, 2017).

Bason and Grix (2017) argue, in the context of the Olympic Games, that failed bids can generate positive outcomes for bidding cities, and bidding nations more generally. They argue that the bidding process represents three main opportunities to lever positive outcomes: taking stock, national interest and the acceleration effect. Taking stock, simply put, provides an opportunity to catalogue the assets and infrastructure already existing in place and highlight areas for future investment in order to maximise the potential success of the bid for the host. National interest represents an opportunity for bidding cities to attract attention from central government, but perhaps could also be applied to increasing the reputation of bidding cities by generating media interest. Finally, the acceleration effect is effectively a combination of the previous two insofar as a bid can 'force a city to be introspective, and bring external attention, but specific deadlines must be met' (p.10). These deadlines, it is argued, can accelerate the process of development due to the time constrained nature of event bidding. While Paisley's UKCoC bid operated in a different context, insofar as the UKCoC is a much smaller competition than the Olympic Games, many of Bason and Grix's (ibid) opportunities can also be applied to smaller bid contexts. Evidence from Hull's year as UKCoC

in 2017 suggests that the desired outcomes of hosting UKCoC appear remarkable similar (though reflective of the smaller urban context) to that of larger events and festivals (Cultural Cities Enquiry, 2019). From this perspective, smaller towns may host smaller events, but the desire to leverage events for economic development and regeneration purposes remains (see Smith, 2012).

In Paisley, elements of taking stock, generating national interest and acceleration are evident in the build up to, and in the wake of, the UKCoC bid. Taking stock can be closely related to the publication of *The Untold Story* inasmuch as this was an exercise in taking stock of the town's heritage assets that in turn formed the basis for both the UKCoC bid and broader placemaking strategies within the town. National interest also appears closely related to both the bid and placemaking in the town. At the most basic level, this is reflected in the step changes that were set during the bid process and that continue to influence policy in the present. This includes the aim of 'radically changing' the town's image and reputation, and establishing Paisley as 'a centre for cultural regeneration' (CCSE, n.d). The stated aim(s) of changing Paisley's image and reputation via cultural regeneration suggests that gaining (inter)national interest was a strategic aim of the bid team and Future Paisley – which was set up to manage the post-bid regeneration projects within the town. At the very least, this reflects the increased national press attention generated during the 2021 UKCoC bid campaign (see chapter five). Finally, the 2021 UKCoC bid was able to accelerate the process of cultural (re)investment in Paisley. This is most clearly seen in the investment in flagship capital projects including Paisley Museum. To return to Mould (2018), this acceleration narrative reflects the appropriation of creativity by neoliberalism insofar as funding for cultural facilities is dependent on participation in a competitive bidding process with

instrumentalised outcomes including increasing visitor numbers and developing the visitor economy (see Oakley, 2015; Groadach and Silver, 2013; Boren and Young, 2013).

In any case, there remains a considerable gap in current knowledge of the UKCoC bidding competition and the sort of legacies that bidding cities are able to generate. Cunningham and Platt (2018) have given some scholarly attention to the UKCoC bidding process and, in doing so, note that despite the top-down and criteria-led nature of the process, bidding cities can nonetheless leverage positive legacies. It is clear, from this study, that the Paisley UKCoC bid campaign, and subsequent reporting, generated a significant amount of newspaper reporting between 2014 and 2020 (see chapter 5). This suggests that the bid campaign, and subsequent cultural regeneration activity in the town, was able to achieve some of its stated aims. However, while the bid was successful at generating newspaper coverage, it is important to discuss the specific narratives that were projected about Paisley and cultural regeneration. In doing so, I address research question one by discussing *how* key decision makers attempted to construct discourses of Paisley and cultural regeneration.

7.3.1 Putting Paisley 'on the map'

The rhetorical shift from culture-led to cultural regeneration in Paisley reflects one of the key tensions within debates about the interaction between place, culture and regeneration. Cultural regeneration, rhetorically speaking, shifts away from culture-led regeneration and is more closely aligned with creative placemaking. However, newspaper reporting consistently highlights how Paisley has been placed back on the map. Richards and Diuf (2019) contend that image enhancement and reputation change should be viewed as a by-product of creative placemaking and not an end in itself. This clashes with the explicit step-change, introduced during the UKCoC bid, to radically change the town's image (CCSE, n.d), and appears to mark

some continuation of a more culture-led approach. For Richards (2017), placemaking must go beyond purely shaping physical space into the imagined or symbolic space of the city and involve the lived experience of local communities, thereby giving greater meaning to local residents. Richards narrative elides the way in which representations of place are neither coincidental nor politically neutral. The imperative to represent places as creative or authentic is attractive precisely because of how this discourse connects with the imperatives of inter-urban competition and neoliberal development (See Zukin, 2011; Peck, 2005; Platt, 2017). Dominant narratives of both the Paisley UKCoC bid campaign and cultural regeneration more generally invoke the idea that the ‘international significance’ of the town’s culture and heritage offer can ‘put Paisley back on the map’ (see Wilson, 2021a).

The need to put places constructed as needing regeneration on the map is a rhetorical move, which has come to be a truism within urban regeneration discourse. It is, therefore, worthy of some broader reflection on how this might connect with the imperatives of neoliberal (re)development and culture-led regeneration. As I have argued elsewhere, this reflects the construction of a cartographical absence in which post-industrial towns are constructed as having fallen off the map, losing their economic, social and physical relevance in the post-industrial, globalised landscape (Wilson, 2021). Putting a town or city back on the map becomes central to making it more competitive in a globalised landscape and raising awareness of place. As Baffour-Awuah (2018) argues:

“on the map” has become an overused buzzword in regeneration. With increased competition between cities to attract businesses, investment and visitors, public- and private-sector organisations have wholly embraced the idea of brand and identity as devices to increase recognition and build value for places. A place is “on the map”

when it is rooted in collective imaginations”. It is “on the map” when a stranger in the street can tell you where and why you’d want to go there...it spins a thousand stories into a simple narrative and constructs a marketable identity (p.336)

The ubiquitous idea that cultural regeneration can put a place on the map therefore packages the demands of inter-urban competition, place branding and neoliberal development into a presentable soundbite. There is, however, a doubly pernicious logic to the phrase insofar as it is coded in the implicit logic of decline and absence. If, as Baffour-Awuah (ibid) begins, the Royal Docks is a ‘real place’ but at the same time ‘it doesn’t really “exist”’ because, presumably, the area has lost its usefulness within the broad process of neoliberal development, then perhaps this is a telling insight into how placemaking (and cultural regeneration) presupposes that places don’t ‘exist’ prior to placemaking or regeneration. Or to return to Mould (2018):

placemaking as a strategy plays on the urban imaginary of decline; there is no *place* here so let’s make one. It is in the same vein as terms such as ‘revitalisation’, ‘urban renaissance’ and renewal that are deliberately invoked to claim a site of gentrification; as if the site being developed were not vital to people who live, work or play there (p.159, emphasis original).

Similarly, Cunningham and Platt (2018) contend that this reflects the familiar romanticism of urban managers, and the assumed capacity to ‘recreate place through place-learned entrepreneurialism’ (p.4, emphasis original). In Paisley, putting the town on the map clearly speaks to the importance of inter-urban competition. This reflects the continuing influence of the logic of culture-led regeneration as an externally focused, instrumental and top-down use of culture to transform the image of place. In Paisley, therefore, while there has been clear

shift in cultural regeneration strategy, *representation* of this strategy still foreground narratives that continue to project the competitive logic of inter-urban competition and neoliberalism.

7.3.2 Community participation, event bidding and 'authenticity' in Paisley

If, as Richards (2017) argues placemaking must go beyond purely shaping physical space into the imagined or symbolic space of the city and the lived experience of local communities, it is therefore important to analyse how local residents are engaged in shaping how their place is represented, and the broader process(es) of place branding. This is, again, reflected by Richards and Diuf (2019: 141) who argue that, for smaller cities, traditional forms of place branding are giving way to 'broader concepts of place marketing' which takes a 'more holistic approach to positioning the city'. Central to this more holistic process of branding is finding new ways of constructing and projecting stories about places that brands are supposed to represent (see Richards and Diuf, 2019; Richards, 2017). The holistic branding most closely connects with broader discourses of creative placemaking in the purported values of co-production and local community participation (see Grenni et al, 2020; Richards and Diuf, 2019; Richards, 2017). Indeed, as Courage (2021) claims, if placemaking is an approach that foregrounds the community in shaping how their place *looks* and *functions*, then perhaps this might be extended to how it is *represented*.

In Paisley, this can be seen not only in the language of *The Untold Story* – a document fundamentally centred on finding new ways of telling Paisley's stories - but also in the way in which certain narratives have been purposefully projected by local decision makers within the town. Specific narratives about the international significance of its culture and heritage attempt to project a new image of Paisley to counteract the town's poor external area

reputation. There is a clear tension between the construction of narratives to make Paisley more competitive and drive regeneration sit and the (allegedly) more holistic process of place branding in which local voices are amplified. Cunningham and Platt (2018) argue that the top-down competitive logic of bidding for UKCoC can prove fruitful inasmuch as people are *forced* to reflect on the nature of *their* places, and what makes them unique.

While bid campaigns might force bid teams to take stock of their place(s) and how they are perceived, it is unclear whether local community reflections meaningfully impact the content of bid campaigns and how they are represented in media coverage. Indeed, local stakeholders involved in the UKCoC bid remarked on some of the difficulties engaging local communities in the bidding process. This can be seen in the 'aye right' test articulated by respondents, inasmuch as it juxtaposes the initial 'sceptical' or 'bemused' reaction with the eventual success of the bid campaign. Previous UKCoC bid teams have also expressed difficulty in fostering grassroots contributions to bid campaigns, suggesting that it can be difficult to stimulate community participation in the UKCoC bidding process (Wilson and O'Brien, 2012 cited in Cunningham and Platt, 2018). In Paisley, this is clearly reflected in the extent to which dominant narratives of both the 2021 bid campaign, as well as broader cultural regeneration, frequently invoke discourses of local community support and local community engagement as a marker of both the success of local engagement and of authenticity of representations of Paisley.

For Zukin (2011), however, authenticity is a slippery concept within the context of urban neoliberalism and an epoch of post-industrial urban development characterised by the commodification of uniqueness. She contends that authenticity is selectively constructed to make places more marketable, arguing that:

The process of branding always merges developers' interests and consumers desires with officials' rhetoric of growth; branding tries to make each city appear different from and better than the competition...The result, though, when all cities pursue the same modern, creative image is not authenticity; it is an overbearing sameness (Zukin, 2011: 231)

Zukin (ibid) contends that authenticity is projected onto *things* and *experiences* as opposed onto *people* thereby making authenticity something which can be consumed. The result, she argues, is the weaponisation of authenticity insofar as the authentic can be wielded to claim space and further the revanchist process(es) of urban dispossession. Mould (2018) similarly argues that placemaking is a process whereby urban managers and developers leverage community responses and ideas and implement them as gentrification schemes. In this framing, creativity and the experience economy are appealing to policymakers because of their compatibility with neoliberalism (Peck, 2005) as opposed to challenging or subverting the process of urban neoliberalism (see Brenner, 2021). In Paisley, authenticity was constructed by foregrounding narratives of local community support, while disregarding more sceptical voices as 'naysayers'. From this perspective, authenticity in Paisley reflects Zukin's conception insofar as it merges developer and consumer interests to put forward a vision of Paisley that is more amenable to the needs of the post-industrial epoch.

The commodification of authenticity need not be a criticism of creative placemaking or cultural regeneration per se, but rather a specific *type* of culture-led regeneration that is overly top-down, *inauthentic* and leads to urban homogenisation (Cunningham and Platt, 2018). This is what Courage (2017) calls place faking where placemaking is more akin to astroturf inasmuch as it is a synthetic process with the *aesthetic* of grassroots participation.

Platt (2017) argues that the consistent emphasis on representing cities as creative places can lead to placemaking strategies which are uneven or misrepresent local communities. She challenges the dominant assumptions of the creative city by focusing on local, everyday creative practices. This reflects the emergent literature of intangible cultural heritage and everyday creativity inasmuch as this necessitates (re)thinking what counts as culture and heritage, as well as incorporating the intangible into broader discourses of heritage and place (see McCandlish and McPherson, 2020; Hopkins, 2019; Bell and Oakley, 2014). Returning to Platt (2021), it is important to (re)examine who is included and excluded in processes of creative placemaking and in the construction of place image.

In the case of Paisley, local residents expressed the feeling that not enough was being done to market the town and to raise awareness of its culture and heritage assets. This is interesting as it echoes the discourse of *The Untold Story* (2014) and the broader imperatives of place branding as outlined by Grenni et al (2020). It also suggests that local residents, within the difficult to reach demographic (Barnes and McPherson, 2019), lacked awareness of the extensive marketing undertaken under both the banner of Future Paisley CCSE, n.d). This suggests a lack of engagement with the *process* and *narratives* of place branding and cultural regeneration in Paisley. I have demonstrated that local residents were critical not of the process of branding itself, nor the logic of culture-led development but rather that not *enough* was being done (to their knowledge). That local residents might adopt similar language to that of developers and the local authority is not necessarily surprising. Baffour-Awuah (2018) argues, for example, that in the context of the Royal Docks in London, there was a synergy between council officers, developers and local residents in the belief that the area needed to be put on the map. Similarly, Kidd, Clark and Kearns (2017) argue that local communities are

generally receptive to event-led urban regeneration initiatives to develop new infrastructure and improve area reputation. This raises questions about the extent to which local participation and engagement alone might be able to challenge dominant discourses of inter-urban competition and neoliberal development. Or, to return to Zukin (2011), local residents do not appear to challenge the logic of branding to demonstrate difference from, and superiority to, other towns and cities. While it is not, in and of itself, problematic for local residents to strive for a more positive representation of their place, it is, nonetheless, important to situate the power relations between the local authority – as the arbiter of official discourse of regeneration – and local residents.

From a perspective in which power is *productive* it is not surprising that local resident discourses align with those of place branding and inter-urban competition insofar as power/knowledge set the boundaries of acceptable discourse. To return to Foucault, power is constituted through discourse, and the construction of truth (Rabinow, 1991):

Each society has its regime of truth, its “general politics” of truth: that is, the types of discourse which it accepts and makes function as true; the mechanisms and instances which enable one to distinguish true and false statements, the means by which each is sanctioned; the techniques and procedures accorded value in the acquisition of truth; the status of those who are charged with saying what counts as true (Rabinow, 1991: 73)

Truth is not outside power, nor lacking power. When viewing power as productive enables a deeper examination of the way in which the local community become participants in the (re)production of dominant narratives of cultural regeneration in Paisley. However, reducing

representations of place to binary distinctions between authentic and inauthentic is based on a (mis)representation of power and discourse in how this relates to local communities.

In Paisley at least, discourses of cultural regeneration as articulated by local residents are not necessarily inauthentic merely because of their compatibility with top-down narratives of culture-led regeneration and neoliberalism. Rather, local communities become embedded within the production of discourse itself, insofar as this is reflected by the broadly similar accounts of decline, regeneration and Paisley, and the consistent logic of inter-urban competition and place branding. It is therefore important to recognise the situated, messy process of hybridised placemaking. With this in mind, I now discuss the changing discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley. In doing so, I demonstrate that while discourses of cultural regeneration have shifted to incorporate the language of creative placemaking in the post-bid period, there remains a familiar logic of neoliberalism and inter-urban competition.

7.4 Hybridised Placemaking: Situating discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley

7.4.1 Neoliberalism, cultural regeneration and post-industrial Paisley

In order to address research question one, it is important to return to neoliberalism itself, and explore how the logic of neoliberalism, or actually existing neoliberalism(s) (Brenner and Theodore, 2002), is reflected in narratives of Paisley, placemaking and cultural regeneration. It useful to (re)turn to Harvey's (2007) definition of neoliberalism in which he argues it has become a 'hegemonic mode of discourse' which (re)constructs how we understand the world. Harvey's account (ibid) is, perhaps, closer in relationship the Marxian (more accurately Gramscian) strain of discourse studies in which discourse analysis represents 'a tool for uncovering certain ways of thinking and talking about how things should be done that serve certain vested interests' (Lees, 2004; 102). While such an account is useful in illuminating the

pervasive influence of neoliberalism within elite political discourse, it pays insufficient attention to how power operates in the construction of discourse. From a Foucauldian perspective, where power is *productive* as opposed to merely *repressive*, operating through the top-down rubric wherein power is exerted *on* and *through* discourse from elite actors, we can understand the plurality of ways in which power *produces* what can be said as opposed to just what is said (Foucault, 1977; McHoul and Grace; 1993; Waitt, 2010). Here, power is not only a vehicle for the subjugation of other discourses outwith the interests of those who hold it, but rather *produces* new regimes of truth. It determines the conditions of possibility through which discourse is constructed.

Applying this to the context of placemaking and regeneration, the logic of neoliberalism constitutes an essential part of the construction of how place, placemaking and cultural regeneration are understood. There is, of course, a wealth of literature which explores the symbiotic relationship between culture-led redevelopment and neoliberalism (see Peck, 2005; Oakley, 2015; Mould, 2018; Miles, 2020). As Peck (2005: 740) argues, creative city development strategies ‘go quietly with the grain extant “neoliberal” development agendas’. Florida’s (2004) questionable quantitative metrics (see Oakley, 2015; Kratke, 2010) such as the now infamous creative class indexes demonstrate the extent to which the creative city simultaneously naturalises and valorises the logic of inter urban competition so central to urban neoliberalism. More generally, the creative city stands as perhaps the most explicit link between neoliberalism and the creative turn in urban regeneration discourse (Richards and Wilson, 2006) as it (re)produces the marketised, competitive logic of neoliberalism itself (Peck, 2005; Kratke, 2010). This does not suggest, however, that the broad church of creative placemaking and cultural regeneration practices is necessarily an ad hoc (re)production of the

creative city script (Oakley, 2015; Courage, 2021; Wilson, 2021a). Rather, it raises questions about how dominant discourses of cultural regeneration naturalise the relationship between culture, place and neoliberalism, and how they might be resisted.

In the Australian context, Atkinson and Easthope contend that, while key actors may not necessarily be 'Florida groupies' (p.78), this does not necessarily mitigate the influence of the creative city per se:

The general absence of documented creative city strategies belies the fact that a creative city-influenced understanding of economic growth and city development is deeply embedded among policymakers and key personnel working within state, city and other 'upper level' institutions in Australia (Atkinson and Easthope, 2009: 78)

If, therefore, decision makers are not necessarily (re)producing an ad hoc creative city template, then this begs the question as to why Florida's ideas continue to hold such influence? Aspen's (2013) conception of zombie urbanism in which culture-led regeneration strategies continue to proliferate in spite of their increasing ontological inaccuracy. Building on Ulrich Beck's description, zombie concepts are the conceptual living dead - they are alive in our heads and language, but no longer useful ways of describing the world (see Beck and Williams, 2004, cited in Atkinson, 2007). Applying this to discourses of cultural regeneration, zombie urbanism can account for the process by which culture-led redevelopment strategies continue to proliferate in the minds of urban policymakers across the globe. Zombie discourses of urban development and the creative city, therefore, appear to run forward and spread on their own, independent of what characteristics and challenges that cities adopting them have. To return to Foucault (1979), this embodies the extent to which discourses of the creative city continue to, implicitly or otherwise, produce *how* the relationship between

culture, place and regeneration is conceived. Once naturalised, assumptions about the importance of creativity and economic development become strongly embedded within discourses of regeneration itself (Atkinson and Easthope, 2009). This is important insofar as it reflects the (im)possibility of escaping, or resisting, dominant neoliberal discourses of the relationship between place and culture within an explicit regeneration framework.

In the context of Paisley, the underlying logic of cultural regeneration has remained relatively consistent with the demands of urban entrepreneurialism and urban neoliberalism. However, discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley have not remained static. There has been a clear shift in recent years in how cultural regeneration is articulated by political actors in Paisley from an approach that was culture-led to a process of cultural regeneration. In the period preceding the UKCoC bid campaign, and indeed during the bid itself, there was a clear focus on culture-led or heritage-led regeneration in which culture and heritage were conceived principally as mechanisms for economic development and town centre regeneration (*The Untold Story*, 2013: 2). As outlined in the cultural strategy published in 2016:

Work on a new regeneration strategy was concluded in 2014, and sets out a 15 year strategy based on Paisley's rich history and culture. It identifies the remarkable base of assets within the town from which to *drive* its economic regeneration and establish itself as a 'must do' destination for Scottish culture and arts (Creative Renfrewshire Steering Group, 2016: 13, emphasis added)

This strategy seems close to the familiar discourse of culture-led regeneration as it is based principally on exploiting heritage assets for economic redevelopment in the post-industrial landscape. This was reflected in interviews with key personnel involved in shaping discourses at this time who tended to foreground issues of economic growth, particularly in post-

industrial sectors such as tourism and events, and town centre regeneration. Culture-led regeneration, in Paisley, clearly reflects broader discourses of neoliberalism and urban entrepreneurialism where much of Paisley's cultural regeneration strategy was structured around the neoliberal axioms of economic growth and inter-urban competition. Culture, from this perspective, is a means of selling the city as a spectacle for (external) consumption (Miles, 2020; Luna-Garcua, 2008).

Cultural regeneration, however, allegedly represents a shift towards a more holistic understanding of the value and use of culture, 'not solely culture-led, but describes an integrated process of cultural regeneration in which culture can both lead and support' (Centre for Culture, Sport and Events, n.d). This seems to more closely reflect creative placemaking as articulated by Richardson and Diuf (2019: 1) as 'the adoption of more strategic, holistic placemaking strategies that engage all stakeholders'. This seems remarkably similar to the definition of cultural regeneration that has risen to prominence in Paisley insofar as this is based upon transcending the somewhat simplistic, instrumental logic of culture-led regeneration. This was reflected clearly in the findings presented in chapter six in particular, with respondents involved in placemaking *after* the UKCoC bid keen to articulate and embed a more holistic approach which accounts for the physical, economic and social wellbeing of the town. More specifically, this is seen with the appointment of a strategic lead for cultural regeneration and a cultural regeneration officer, both of whom were closely involved in shifting discourse *away* from the culture-led approach.

However, while there has been *some* shift in approach in Paisley, the shift to cultural regeneration has not drastically altered the relationship between place, culture and neoliberalism. There is some evidence that changing discourses of cultural regeneration in

Paisley might have destabilised the assumption that neoliberalism operates as a totalising, hegemonic and monolithic force in placemaking. It is difficult to deny that the familiar narratives of inter-urban competition and the post-industrial society are present in representations of Paisley, it is also clear that the shift towards cultural regeneration marks a broader incorporation of the non-market processes that Richards and Diuf (2019) associate with creative placemaking. However, changing approaches to cultural regeneration in Paisley do not, necessarily, mean that the influence of neoliberalism is mitigated. To return to Brenner and Theodore's (2002) conception of actually existing neoliberalism – neoliberalism always exists in a more than neoliberal context, in that its global influence may well be geographically uneven, but no place can claim immunity from it. It would be unwise to assume that discourses of regeneration and placemaking in Paisley can claim immunity from the influence of neoliberalism. Rather, cultural regeneration is more of an evolution than a revolution, insofar as shifting away from *culture-led* regeneration does not in and of itself mitigate the influence of neoliberal discourses. It is therefore necessary to situate cultural regeneration within the emergent literature on creative placemaking as a means of resisting urban neoliberalism.

7.4.2 Cultural regeneration in small towns and cities

Despite an emergent body of literature on creative placemaking and small cities (see Richards and Diuf, 2019; Gibson and Waitt, 2009; Lewis and Donald, 2010; Oakley, 2015), current scholarship still has a tendency to overlook smaller urban places. Lewis and Donald (2010) contend, for example, that the very way in which creative capital is conceived of, with its reliance on inter-urban competition and league tables, tends to marginalise smaller cities. This is problematic insofar as it elides our understanding of how processes of (creative)

placemaking in small cities and towns might differ from major metropolitan areas. Indeed, a critique of the relationship between placemaking, regeneration and gentrification in large cities with generally greater levels of inequality can be applied to smaller towns and cities that are less impacted by these issues (Oakley, 2015). There has been some interest in the extent to which smaller cities and towns can use culture to deliver more equitable outcomes or change the terms of the debate about culture-led regeneration (ibid).

Some scholars have argued that smaller cities utilise different methods of placemaking than their larger counterparts (See Markusen, 2013; Courage, 2021; McKeown and Courage, 2019). Richards and Diuf (2019) argue that borrowing size from larger cities can be a fruitful placemaking strategy for smaller towns and cities. Borrowing size is a process whereby smaller cities extract value from their geographical proximity to larger cities not by competing with them but by developing a complementary offer which can allow small cities to punch above their weight (Kresl and Ietri, 2016 cited in Richards and Diuf, 2019). Or in other words:

Cities can therefore “borrow size” through being well embedded in (inter)national networks, and being a tourist destination linked to flows of mobile consumers also helps to sustain more metropolitan functions because it gives a boost to the resident population (Richards and Diuf, 2019: 35)

Borrowing size is clearly applicable to the case of Paisley insofar as the town’s proximity to the city of Glasgow and other geographical advantages such as the rail and air transport connections, are assets that can be levered to develop the tourism and events sector. However, emphasising the visitor economy in this way is unlikely to challenge the axioms of urban neoliberal development. Rather, this serves to reinforce discourses of inter-urban

competition, and the demands of economic development more associated with (heavily critiqued) top-down forms of culture-led regeneration.

Kovacs and Park (2021) argue that creative placemaking is almost always discussed in a positive light. This is perhaps most true in smaller towns and cities with their 'relative closeness of natural amenities, lower living costs and even older populations, who are more likely to spend money in cultural activities, may support the cultural scene of small cities' (Denise-Jacob, 2012, cited in Oakley, 2015: 11). Small cities represent an opportunity within placemaking to shift towards *liveable* places, which foreground metrics such as access to recreational space or the quality of local schools as opposed to merely economic development (Oakley, 2015; Boren and Yong, 2013). The shift towards *liveability*, however, may not in itself represent a substantial shift away from creative city development strategies.

Mould (2018) argues that creative placemaking can be more accurately described as another mutation of the creative city development strategy in which creative city protagonists look to (re)create the perception of a separate strategy that shuns the aesthetic of flagship cultural facilities while furthering the relationship between creativity and economic development. This new creative city, he argues, must 'have the veneer of 'edginess', appeal to hipsters and maintain a radical, progressive and perhaps even anti-capitalist aesthetic' (p.159) while, at the same time, furthering the process(es) of instrumentalisation, economic development and gentrification. This reflects the way in which cultural regeneration in Paisley – a largely state-led endeavour – is positioned as subversive, trendy and cool. Cultural regeneration – and specifically town centre regeneration – in Paisley was specifically linked developing a 'coffee shop culture' which reflects the vision of a town centre populated by boutiques, trendy coffee shops and independent businesses (*Vision for Paisley Town Centre 2030*, 2020). On one hand,

this appears to closely resemble new creative city discourses where the culture-led regeneration is replaced with the rhetoric of 'hip' bohemian urban spaces. On the other, as we have seen, Paisley's approach directly contradicts the new creative city inasmuch as it directly *foregrounds* the aesthetic of flagship cultural facilities in that media representations consistently emphasize the (re)development of Paisley Museum.

What Mould's (ibid) new creative city *cannot* account for is why smaller cities and towns which do not appear to be undergoing the process of gentrification are adopting increasingly similar strategies. Paisley is not undergoing a process of gentrification or social cleansing similar to that which Mould describes in London. Smaller cities adopting the *logic* of gentrification – where the logic of attracting new, wealthier residents persists even with an absence of the *process* of gentrification itself – more closely reflects the dominance of zombie urbanist discourses in which the language of inclusive, creative, and sustainable economic growth is invoked despite its increasingly ontological inaccuracy (Aspen, 2013). The logic of creative city growth continues to influence cities, irrespective of the likelihood of success. As Oakley (2015) argues, the strategies which 'small cities seem to adopt are often based on a "cultural industries" model despite the fact that these cities lack the critical mass of cultural industries that would make these strategies feasible' (p.10). Paisley does not fit neatly within either articulation of creative placemaking or culture-led regeneration in smaller towns and cities. Paisley's version of cultural regeneration projects the *language* of creative placemaking while, simultaneously, investing in flagship regeneration projects. This reflects the pervasive tendency for smaller cities to (re)produce placemaking strategies that reflect the assumptions of creative city development strategies implemented, with considerable critique, in larger urban centres (Oakley, 2015; Richards and Diuf, 2019; Van Heur, 2010).

The duality of Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration reflects the messiness of what I call *hybridised placemaking*. Hybridised placemaking accounts for the situated, context specific and mutating process by which discourses of cultural regeneration evolve. Hybridised placemaking builds on the Foucauldian methodology adopted in this thesis by exploring the conditions of possibility through which discourse of place, placemaking and regeneration materialise. Localised discourses of placemaking are always implicated in broader global discourses, but this does not necessarily mean that local interactions with these processes do not exist. In this context, applying Brenner and Theodore's (2002) actually existing neoliberalism as a mechanism for accounting for the diversions, mutations and contradictions in the implementation of neoliberalism proves fruitful. The apparent contradictions in Paisley's approach reflects the process of actually existing hybridised placemaking insofar as the implementation of cultural regeneration strategies, and how these strategies are themselves constructed and understood, is not a simple evolution. Rather, changes in approach are *discontinuous* and shaped by the influence of different actors across different time periods.

As previously discussed, from 2014-2020 there has been a clear shift from the language of *culture-led* regeneration projected through *The Untold Story* and the UKCoC bid campaign to more holistic narratives of cultural regeneration. What emerges, therefore, is a hybridised discourse that absorbs both the logic of culture-led regeneration and the more holistic language of creative placemaking. It is worth unpacking this purported shift in approach in more detail, both in terms of the UKCoC bid and the role of event bidding in shaping cultural regeneration, as well as the flagship projects themselves and this might be applied to the changing models of culturally driven regeneration in Paisley.

7.4.3 Flagship projects and culture-led regeneration

Flagship projects have been frequently associated with culture-led regeneration approaches spanning across decades (see Mould, 2018; Oakley, 2015; Miles and Paddison, 2005). The flagship approach has been robustly critiqued and linked to processes of inter-urban competition, neoliberalism and even gentrification. The reliance on flagship cultural development projects can be problematic for small towns and cities. It is argued that 'small cities cannot compete effectively if they think like big cities' (Evans and Foord, 2006 cited in Richards and Diuf, 2019: 12). This is potentially problematic insofar as it accepts, uncritically, the competitive logic of urban neoliberalism in that it is assumed, a priori, that the role of placemaking should be to make cities more competitive on a global stage. As Evans and Foord suggest, too often there is a reliance on 'flagship cultural buildings, iconic cultural institutions, cultural and heritage quarters alongside cultural events, festivals and markets...to kick start both physical regeneration and visitor economies' (ibid). Somewhat prophetically, Evans and Foord also note how smaller cities can be seduced into bidding for cultural competitions (ibid). Flagship cultural development projects reflect creative city placemaking strategies inasmuch as they are viewed as a mechanism for attracting a desired demographic of visitors thereby regenerating the town, and the town centre in particular (Mould, 2018).

There are some striking rhetorical similarities between newspaper reporting of the Paisley Museum redevelopment and the familiar rhetoric of culture-led regeneration projects elsewhere. The consistent description of Paisley Museum as a flagship regeneration project which will stimulate the visitor economy echoes the *modus operandi* of culture-led regeneration (Miles and Paddison, 2005; Oakley, 2015; Boren and Young, 2013; Comunian and Mould, 2014). The discourse on Bilbao's Guggenheim as discussed by Mould (2018) and

the rhetoric around the redevelopment of Paisley Museum is nearly identical. In particular, the focus on the international cultural significance of the (re)developed museum reflects the logic of inter-urban competition insofar as it (re)enforces the importance of projecting a positive vision of Paisley *externally* and of emphasising the need to (re)affirm this significance both discursively (through media representation) and physically (through flagship projects).

Additionally, the use of the word flagship is also telling. Foregrounding flagship projects is in tension with the holistic vision of cultural regeneration promoted in Paisley since the failed UKCoC bid. Anticipating the museum, as well as other large-scale cultural events, to lead an economic renaissance within the town is reminiscent of other models of culture-led regeneration, whereby culture is instrumentalised as a vehicle for a broader economic agenda (Bell and Oakley, 2014). For Mould (2018), flagship cultural projects, such as museums, have come to be implicated within the broader creative city agenda, with cultural institutions and enhanced public spaces serving as a vehicle for attracting the desired cultural demographic. The presence of flagship projects, particularly when foregrounded in newspaper reporting, undermines the legitimacy and effectiveness of shifting away from culture-led models of regeneration within Paisley.

However, Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration has not remained static merely because of continued investment in the Paisley Museum project. While it is certainly true that this trend, particularly prominent in newspaper reporting of Paisley cannot be disregarded, it is nonetheless important to develop a more nuanced understanding of how cultural regeneration might (re)structure how investment in Paisley Museum is conceived of, engaged with and represented within the town, as articulated in chapter five. From this perspective, investment in Paisley Museum to stimulate the visitor economy might (re)turn to the familiar

terrain of culture-led regeneration if that is the principal practice of regeneration. Paisley's approach, however, can be differentiated by the focus on a more holistic approach that takes account of the broad physical, economic and social issues within the town. More specifically in the context of the Museum, this is seen in the focus on co-production and inclusivity in which local partners and the local community are more closely involved. This would, at a surface level at least, more closely resemble creative placemaking practice (Bell and Oakley, 2014; Oakley, 2015).

Barnes and McPherson (2019) argue that museums, imbued with the values of co-production, can become hybrid spaces where the visitor is at once able to look at and challenge what they see, while also contribute to the selection of what they see. Co-production can, it is argued, become a useful tool for engaging traditionally difficult to reach or socially excluded groups which can 'turn museum rhetoric of community engagement into practice' (p.267). It is not difficult to see how these narratives of a practice of community engagement, particularly within the social justice framework outlined above, might be appealing to proponents of creative placemaking. Indeed, co-production itself is central to the artistic practice most commonly associated with projects labelled as creative placemaking (see Edwards-Vandenhoeck, 2021; Courage and McKeown, 2019; Courage, 2020). While Paisley Museum appears at first glance to (re)produce dominant assumptions of top-down culture-led regeneration. This reflects Platt's (2021: 143) argument that the 'binary between top-down and bottom-up (or community-led) placemaking need not be in conflict' which could thus make space for a 'more collaborative and ethical' approach to placemaking.

The problem, however, is that such a reading requires the binary between top-down and bottom-up to exist in the first place. As I have already discussed, from a Foucauldian

perspective, the dichotomy between top-down and bottom-up misrepresents how power and discourse themselves produce ways of being, and knowing, the world (see McHoul and Grace, 1993; Foucault, 1981). Power is *always* a process of co-production insofar as it is not a merely repressive force. It is harder, therefore, to differentiate creative placemaking on this basis alone. In the context of culture-led regeneration, if dominant assumptions about creative city economic development pervade, often subconsciously, elite discourse of placemaking (Atkinson and Easthope, 2009), then this also applies to local articulations of place, image and regeneration in a post-industrial context. This is compounded by the relative (in)ability of local residents to influence the decision-making processes or creative placemaking strategy at a more fundamental level, as outlined by local activist(s) in this study who felt that their engagement in regeneration was tokenistic.

To return to Paisley's UKCoC bid example, on one level the process was reduced to a flag waving exercise in which the local community supported the bid campaign because they *couldn't* be seen *not* to back the bid. There was, however, a debate about the extent to which the bid campaign was something there was a genuine hunger for within the town and was instead something which has to be sold to the town. This is not without a broader academic precedent. Wilson and O'Brien (2012 cited in Cunningham and Platt, 2018) suggest that previous iterations of the UKCoC bidding process have been marked by a difficulty in generating grassroots participation and challenges in stimulating community participation. Where Paisley might differ from this is that there was an apathy that could be overcome, and a more general dissatisfaction with high levels of cultural investment (see chapter six).

It is clear that there were *some* dissenting local voices, as was acknowledged by interview respondents and their construction of the 'naysayers'. However, it is important to

acknowledge the way in which dominant discourses delineate *what can be said* about Paisley from a Foucauldian perspective. Local community criticism cannot exist without dominant discourses of regeneration, place and post-industrialism. Respondents' perceptions of place and regeneration were implicated in broader discourses of economic development, urban decline and, most prominently, town centre regeneration. If, as Tallon (2013) suggests, contemporary urban regeneration is closely linked to discourses of urban decline and the post-industrial society, then the inclusion of local voices alone will not be able to challenge, subvert or resist the imposition of these discourses.

When taken together, discourses of cultural regeneration found in Paisley fail to pose a substantial challenge to dominant methods of culture-led regeneration. There are differences between a more engaged process of creative placemaking and archetypal examples of culture-led regeneration. However, local representation alone is unlikely to challenge the dominant assumptions of urban neoliberalism and inter-urban competition insofar as the local community are themselves implicated in the (re)production of dominant discourses of post-industrialism, decline and regeneration. As I have argued elsewhere, this might suggest 'a placemaking practice which is more palliative than productive' in which the focus on bottom-up and community-led placemaking elides the relative (in)ability to challenge dominant assumptions which underpin placemaking and regeneration processes (Wilson, 2021: 2). Nonetheless, it is important to recognise the context specific, hybridised nature of actually existing placemaking by avoiding relying on overly simplistic archetypes of culture-led regeneration approaches (Oakley, 2015). Indeed, it is difficult to conclude that Paisley's approach has remained entirely culture-led merely because of continued investment in the museum and other 'flagship' projects. It is with this in mind that the context of Paisley and

the UKCoC opens space to (re)think the relationship between place, culture and placemaking (see Cunningham and Platt, 2018).

7.4.4 Hybridised Placemaking: The hybridity of cultural regeneration in Paisley

Courage (2021) argues that placemaking, and in particular creative placemaking, is part of the paradigmatic shift in urban design, planning, and policy to 'include the user and, in situ community voice; in the arts sector's increasing concern for, and operation in, place-based community development; and the surge of culturally-led regeneration' (p.lvi). It is difficult to conclude that placemaking breaks from the market processes of urban neoliberalism merely by including *non-market* processes, particularly as the foundational logic of both approaches is remarkably similar (See Richards and Diuf, 2019). Much of Richards and Diuf's (ibid) argument pivots on how small cities might 'put themselves on the map' (p.1) and compete with larger cities in a post-industrial context via creative placemaking. It is difficult to reconcile the argument that an attractive external image is not an end in itself with a discourse which proposes that 'in the contemporary urban world...one of the imperatives is competing for attention' (p.5). While creative placemaking, in this context, might provide a less totalising and more palatable relationship between culture and place (Oakley, 2015), it does not alter the logic of inter-urban competition. There are clear similarities between Richards and Diuf's (2019) definition of creative placemaking in which small towns and cities celebrate their uniqueness to 'put themselves on the map' and the discourses of cultural regeneration evident in Paisley. Indeed, narratives of Paisley's UKCoC bid, cultural offer and regeneration itself are based on nearly identical ideas of putting Paisley back on the map, and the town's unique and internationally significant culture and heritage offer. The need to be on the map is a particularly prominent feature of how cultural regeneration is represented both in the

context of Paisley and in broader discourses of placemaking itself. The imperative to put places on the map represents a clear connection between discourses of placemaking, the imperatives of neoliberalism and inter-urban competition.

An alternative view on creative placemaking suggests that a more bottom-up approach to community engagement and urban (re)development can enable a more equitable relationship between place, culture and social justice (see Oakley, 2015; Courage, 2021b; Webb, 2014; Platt, 2021). This view has permeated academic discourses of creative placemaking which is 'nearly always framed in a positive light' (Kovacs and Park, 2021: 101). Despite this, however, concepts such as artwashing and gentrification continue to have an uneasy relationship to creative placemaking discourses. As Kovacs and Park (2021) argue gentrification and artwashing remain tied to projects often labelled as creative placemaking. Indeed, this is demonstrated in the culture-led redevelopment of the Ihwa-dong 'moon-village' in Seoul, South Korea wherein the instillation of murals led to issues of over-tourism, local community displacement and gentrification (ibid). What this suggests is that there is no one size fits all approach to creative placemaking, nor should placemaking be reducible to a monolith in itself. Or, to return to Oakley (2015) placemaking is not a panacea. Instead, it must be viewed as situated and case-specific, particularly when exploring the way in which creative placemaking is often implicated within social justice agendas.

Discursive constructions of the community and the power dynamics that emerge between planners and governments on the one hand and local residents on the other is crucial to debates about creative placemaking. Placemaking is positioned, in the critical literature, as a continuation of, or insufficient response to, top-down processes of urban neoliberalism. What both these narratives elide, however, is a deeper examination of how power operates *on* and

through discursive constructions of the community, place and regeneration. Power *produces* ways of understanding and engaging with discourses of placemaking. From this perspective, the dichotomy between top-down and bottom-up pivots on a *repressive* view of power in which placemaking is imposed on local communities. Such a view does not account for the role of the local community as both a subject and an object of placemaking, itself implicated in the reproduction of dominant discourses of place, placemaking and neoliberalism.

Using Paisley as an example, we can explore the (in)ability of relying on simplistic dichotomies of top-down or bottom-up to challenge the culture-led regeneration paradigm, thereby understanding what I call 'hybridised placemaking'. There has been a shift in strategy to incorporate the principles of creative placemaking in Paisley. Importantly, this strategic shift emphasises a remarkably consistent discourse of a holistic process whereby local partners are engaged in shaping the physical, social and economic processes of cultural regeneration. However, challenging established discourses of culture-led regeneration and neoliberalism through cultural regeneration is not so simple. The relatively small population and peripheral geography of Paisley means that it is somewhat overlooked in broader debates about placemaking, culture-led regeneration and gentrification. Much of the critique of culture-led regeneration, and latterly creative placemaking, has centred on examples of actually existing neoliberalism, displacement and gentrification with little (critical) attention paid to peripheral (sub)urban geographies.

Building on Atkinson and Easthope (2009), there is evidence of a more subtle method through which creative city discourses continue to influence decision makers in Paisley. Key actors in Paisley might not be 'Florida groupies' but that is not to say that the imperatives of creative city discourse, neoliberalism and inter-urban competition can be read as unimportant. From

this perspective, creative cities have come to embody a broader vision of a 'healthy' (sub)urban economy. Visions of trendy neighbourhoods populated by boutiques and independent coffee shops become a target for local policy makers to aim for, demonstrating the enduring influence (implicit or otherwise) of Florida's vision (see Slater, 2011).

Elements of Paisley's approach (for example, flagship cultural projects) reflect dominant strands of neoliberal creative city development discourses, though that does not mean that the process exists only as a vector for gentrification and revanchist displacement of local communities. Rather, a hybridised approach emerges in discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley. Elite stakeholders who were involved in the UKCoC bid process, tended to emphasise the success of large-scale projects in boosting civic pride and local confidence by generating positive newspaper reporting. Actors who entered the process *after* the UKCoC bid, as well as local respondents during workshops, tended to focus less on the bid campaign and more on broader processes of cultural regeneration – such as the redevelopment of Paisley Museum or the installation of public art such as murals. In Paisley, there is a duality at play in which cultural regeneration and newspaper representations of regeneration embody a similar logic of neoliberalism and entrepreneurialism and, in places, creative city development as identified in larger urban areas, but cannot be seen as the frontier of gentrification and revanchist dispossession. Paisley's approach – while retaining certain logics of the creative city approach – is neither culture-led nor creative placemaking, but rather a hybrid emerges in which *both* the top-down imperatives of culture-led regeneration and holistic language of creative placemaking persist.

7.5 Conclusion

In this chapter I have discussed the construction of discourses of Paisley as a post-industrial town blighted by issues of inequality, unemployment and town centre decline. I have demonstrated how representing Paisley as a poster boy for post-industrial decline legitimises cultural practices insofar as the foundational logic of anything that has come to be associated with regeneration is predicated on urban decline or inequality. Building on this, I have discussed how key stakeholders both within and out with the local authority have attempted to change perceptions of Paisley using cultural regeneration. I have demonstrated how event-bidding strategies are situated within a broader neoliberal development agenda. Key narratives which have been used represent Paisley before, during and after the bid are not merely apolitical representations of the positive aspects of Paisley's culture and heritage offer. Rather, the imperative to put Paisley back on the map or to tell an authentic story inspired by local voices congeals around the neoliberal logic of inter-urban competition. Finally, I have discussed Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration and how it has developed between 2014-2020. While Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration cannot be understood as a static, archetypal reproduction of creative city discourses, neither can it claim immunity from it. This reflects, again, the way in which cultural regeneration in Paisley is implicated in broader discourses of place, culture and regeneration.

Addressing research question one, it is clear that discourses of Paisley, culture and regeneration and their representation have shifted between 2014-2020. This is best captured by (re)theorising discursive shifts as a process of actually existing hybridised placemaking that accounts for situated, context-specific and, at times, contradictory shifts in discourses of placemaking in Paisley. The idea of actually existing placemaking accounts for discourses in

Paisley taking on the language of creative placemaking while (re)turning to the familiar rhetoric of culture-led investments in flagship projects. Understanding creative placemaking, therefore, must account for the mutating, path dependent nature of discursive shifts. Hybridised placemaking can also provide a more satisfactory answer to research question two, in as much as it provides a framework for understanding how messages have been developed and who the key actors involved have been. Initial conceptions of culture-led regeneration in Paisley lean heavily on the ubiquitous axioms of creative city, culture-led development. However, this shifts clearly in the post-bid period. Hybridised messaging emerges from the changing personnel responsible for shaping it. Indeed, we can see that the initial phase regeneration and the 2021 UKCoC bid campaign were influenced by a more culture-led approach which has shifted with the introduction of more personnel to incorporate the language of cultural regeneration and creative placemaking.

Chapter 8: Conclusion

8.1 Introduction

This study aimed to contribute to debates about culture-led regeneration, creative placemaking and neoliberal urban development. In doing so, this thesis explores how area reputations are constructed, and the role of (negative) area reputation in legitimising cultural regeneration strategies. To achieve this, I have drawn on the Scottish town of Paisley as a context and analysed changing discourses of culture-led and/or cultural regeneration taking place within the town. This qualitative study utilised a variety of techniques including semi-structured interviews and workshops, and analysis of newspaper and documentary data. Interviews were held with key decision makers and stakeholders who were involved in either the UKCoC bid campaign or cultural regeneration within the town. Workshops were held with local residents recruited both independently and collaboratively with a local community group. Analysis of both newspaper reporting, as well as documentary materials produced *within* the local authority such as reports and policy documents revealed the official discourses of cultural regeneration within the town.

In this concluding thesis, I draw together the arguments presented in previous chapters into a clear conclusion. I begin by outlining the key contributions to knowledge that this thesis has made. I discuss the emergence of post-industrial Paisley – the discursive construction that foregrounds narratives of town centre decline, poverty and inequality - in justifying cultural regeneration strategies. I discuss a key theoretical contribution of this thesis, the concept of hybridised placemaking, arguing that it provides a useful lens for understanding the shift in regeneration strategy with Paisley from being an ostensibly culture-led approach to a more hybridised model of cultural regeneration that reflects *both* discourses of culture-led

regeneration and the more inclusive language of creative placemaking. In the penultimate section, I discuss the limitations of this study, including the difficulty in recruiting local participants to take part in workshops, the difficulties associated with doing fieldwork during the coronavirus pandemic and some of the potential pitfalls associated with operating within an industry-academic partnership. Finally, I provide concluding thoughts, and propose fruitful avenues of future research. I propose that future research on territorial stigma in Paisley, as well as exploring grassroots responses to cultural regeneration are areas in which the ideas developed in my thesis can be further developed.

8.2 Study aim and objectives

In concluding this thesis, it is useful to begin by restating the aim and objectives that guided this study. The study aim was to explore how discourses of cultural regeneration are formed and subsequently represented in newspaper reporting in Paisley. To achieve this stated aim, I have developed three specific objectives. The first objective was to explore how discourses of decline and regeneration are connected to each other insofar as narratives of post-industrial decline are invoked to legitimise cultural regeneration strategies. I sought to analyse the way in which newspaper representations of Paisley represent images of decline and regeneration within the town. The second objective was to explore the conditions of possibility that enable or constrain certain discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley. The third objective was to critically analyse the changes in Paisley's approach from one that is ostensibly culture-led to cultural regeneration that more closely resembles the language of creative placemaking, and the extent to which this reflects a changing relationship between culture, place and regeneration in Paisley.

In furtherance of these objectives, and based on the literature review and the emergent gaps in the literature, this study sought to answer three research questions:

- i. How have key narratives of cultural regeneration in Paisley been developed and who were the key actors involved and to what extent is this reflected in the media messages communicated about Paisley?
- ii. What key messages have been communicated about Paisley, its culture and regeneration between 2014 and 2020?
- iii. What is the local community receptions and reaction to representations of Paisley and cultural regeneration?

In bringing this thesis to a close, I conclude by discussing how the research questions discussed above have been addressed in the present study. However, I also go beyond the localised context of Paisley to discuss the implications of this study for debates about culture-led regeneration, creative placemaking and the construction of area reputation. All three research questions have been answered utilising a variety of qualitative research techniques. Based on these findings, I have outlined the two main theoretical contributions to knowledge made by this study: post-industrial Paisley and hybridised placemaking.

8.3 Key Findings: Post-industrial Paisley and hybridised placemaking

8.3.1 Post-industrial Paisley

In exploring discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley, I have discussed the formation of post-industrial Paisley. Post-industrial Paisley is the narrative construction that legitimises the cultural regeneration and placemaking interventions within the town by foregrounding narratives of industrial decline, unemployment, inequality and changes to the retail sector. In turn, post-industrial Paisley invokes, or at the very least leans into, imaginaries of Paisley as a

former industrial hub blighted by the effects of broader global processes. In this sense, discourses of cultural regeneration are difficult to uncouple from discourses of decline and territorial stigma.

Paisley has suffered from a particularly poor reputation, with specific themes of poverty and inequality, violence and town centre decline featuring prominently both in newspaper reporting and in responses from local politicians, stakeholders and residents. Paisley's poor external reputation reflects the recent proliferation of scholarship on territorial stigma. In this thesis I have illustrated the way in which problem areas of the town such as – but not limited to – Ferguslie Park, Shortroods or Gallowhill have come to embody negative stereotypes associated with poverty, unemployment and violence. The negative reputation of problem areas appears to be closely linked to both negative newspaper reporting, insofar as it consistently foregrounds these areas and the purported problems therein, and in the more empirical metrics by which poverty and inequality is measured such as the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) in which these areas have performed particularly poorly. More generally, I have suggested that there is some evidence that stigmatising discourses in Paisley are perpetuated through negative newspaper reporting. This suggests that there may be a negative sentiment towards the local press, as illustrated in the limited responses from local respondents, particularly during workshops.

The significance of the post-industrial Paisley discourse is most clear when examining discursive formations of Paisley town centre. From this perspective, the rise of online shopping and out-of-town malls are invoked in newspaper reporting and local authority reports and documentation to advance the need to rethink the traditional role of town centres. The need to rethink Paisley town centre is used to demonstrate the importance of

culture as a means to regenerating post-industrial spaces. Post-industrial Paisley is a discursive formation that is constructed by and through key personnel trying to project specific narratives of Paisley. These discursive formations are, in turn, reflected back in newspaper coverage. However, discourses of decline and de-industrialisation do not exist only as a means of legitimising regeneration that is *strategically* projected. Rather, post-industrial Paisley is essential to the production of Paisley's poor image and reputation. In chapter five, I demonstrated how newspaper reporting foregrounded issues of town centre decline and the implications of out-of-town malls and online shopping on the future of Paisley town centre. In chapter six I showed how negative perceptions of Paisley locally were influenced both by negative *internal* perceptions of the town centre, but also on how this impacted on *external* perceptions. This was mostly clearly seen in the view that Paisley was a poster child for the death of the high street.

The post-industrial Paisley notion is consistent with previous findings on discourses of urban regeneration. As Tallon (2013) points out, discourses of urban regeneration are closely linked to discourses of the post-industrial society. Foregrounding discourses of the post-industrial society also necessitates a specific *method* of regeneration, in which culture, heritage and the experience economy become increasingly prominent. In chapter seven I demonstrated that narratives of (sub)urban decline are central to the formation of creative city discourses as articulated by proponents including Florida and Landry. Landry (2000), more specifically, famously argued that culture has emerged as the sum of a city's amenities in the post-industrial epoch and thus become the means by which globalised cities project their uniqueness and develop their economy.

I also argue that there is a paradox present in which broad, global processes of post-industrial decline are used to legitimise culturally informed regeneration strategies that *lean into* the broader global processes that are responsible for this decline itself. Imaginaries of decline are used to leverage placemaking and/or cultural regeneration strategies that aim to make cities more competitive and marketable. In Paisley, this was true in the initial articulation of culture-led regeneration within the town. As outlined in chapter five, the baseline document *Paisley: The Untold Story*, played an important role in (re)positing Paisley's culture and heritage as internationally significant to be leveraged to put Paisley (back) on the map. Similarly, in chapter seven, I demonstrated how the imperative to put places back on the map reflects the idea of cartographical absence (see Wilson, 2021). Indeed, the notion that Paisley must be put back on the map suggests at a minimum that the town has fallen off it, thereby implicitly reflecting discourses of decline (ibid). Additionally, Baffour-Awuah (2018: 336) argues that using (cultural) regeneration strategies to put places back on the map has come to become an overused buzzword in regeneration discourse that connects with the need to construct marketable identities to attract inward investment. However, the need to put declining places back on the map is integral to the logic of placemaking itself. Mould (2018) argues that placemaking plays on images of decline to legitimise itself.

When taken together, understanding the discourse of post-industrial Paisley is important in answering the study's research questions. For research question one, post-industrial Paisley is a useful way of conceptualising a specific kind of narrative that has been used to represent the town in recent years. Post-industrial Paisley, as a discourse, emphasises the importance of de-industrialisation and town centre decline in the construction of Paisley's reputation, and how this informs the basis of cultural regeneration approaches within the town. In addressing

research question's two and three, I have shown how the notion of post-industrial Paisley has been used by key actors to legitimise cultural regeneration strategies. However, it is also clear that post-industrial Paisley exists outwith the purview of (re)branding Paisley and reflects the construction of the town's poor external and internal reputation.

Beyond the local context of Paisley, the post-industrial Paisley discourse reflects a broader trend in how culture-led/cultural regeneration strategies in smaller urban contexts (smaller cities and large towns) are represented, and the conditions of possibility through which these strategies emerge. Kearns et al (2013) argue that newspaper coverage of regeneration tends to (re)produce negative images and stereotypes in order to legitimise the implementation of regeneration strategies themselves. By using the concept of post-industrial Paisley, this study demonstrates that discourses of post-industrial decline are central to the logic of cultural forms of regeneration in smaller urban contexts. Indeed, discourses of the post-industrial society legitimise entrepreneurial discourses of the visitor economy and/or the creative economy by (re)positioning them as the salvation for the ills of the contemporary urban condition. In a landscape of economic decline and socio-economic inequality, culture becomes the last remaining means through which towns and cities might escape the perils of town centre decline. However, this creates the problem of homogenisation, as towns and cities adopting increasingly similar strategies in response to the common problems associated with post-industrial decline. In sum, post-industrial Paisley illustrates the increasingly similar foundations on which discourse of cultural regeneration is based – post-industrial decline. Similarly, this also feeds into broader zombie urbanist discourses in which both the *problem* and *solution* to the contemporary urban condition is articulated in increasingly similar ways. By applying the zombie urbanist discourses, Post-industrial Paisley, conceptually, contributes

to understanding the convergence in approaches between larger metropolitan areas and smaller cities and towns.

8.3.2 Hybridised placemaking: Paisley, culture and regeneration

If post-industrial Paisley is the basis on which discourses of Paisley's regeneration are predicated, then it is important to discuss what regeneration means within the context of Paisley. As shown in chapter two, it has become somewhat of a truism within urban regeneration discourse that culture, creativity and the arts must be the vanguard of urban renaissance. Self-styled urban gurus such as Richard Florida or Charles Landry have been particularly prominent in advancing the notion that cities must become creative, trendy and bohemian places to thrive in the post-industrial economic environment. In recent years, this discourse has been thoroughly critiqued, with clear links being drawn by critics between the creative city, urban neoliberalism, inter and intra-urban inequality and gentrification. However, the relationship between culture and place cannot be disregarded as inherently top-down, extractive and instrumentalised. Rather, I have shown that there is a growing literature that positions creative placemaking as the basis of a more equitable relationship between culture and place that can foreground community participation, co-production and the development of small-scale cultural interventions (Markusen, 2013; Courage, 2021a).

Building on Oakley's (2015) work on creative placemaking, I have explored the possibility of new relationships between culture and place by developing the concept of hybridised placemaking. Hybridised placemaking provides a tool for understanding how the compositing imperatives of culture-led regeneration and creative placemaking can exist simultaneously. I have questioned how Paisley's approach to regeneration could be understood, particularly within a well-documented (internally at least) shift *away* from an approach which is culture-

led to a more holistic process of cultural regeneration. I demonstrated that in the initial regeneration period from the publication of *The Untold Story* in 2014 until the culmination of the UKCoC bid campaign in 2017, there is clear evidence of a *culture-led* approach. This was evident in the policy documentation, newspaper reporting (chapter five) and interviews with former local politicians and bid team members (chapter six). Indeed, in this period, Paisley's cultural regeneration strategy resembled the well-worn model in which culture is an instrument in driving broader processes of economic regeneration. Most notably, this was clear in the significant investments made in flagship cultural venues including Paisley Museum and Paisley Town Hall. Redeveloping Paisley's cultural offer was seen an opportunity to leverage economic benefits by developing the visitor economy thereby delivering town centre regeneration. This reflects, in part, the criteria-led nature of the bid process in which bidding cities are encouraged to think about developing the visitor economy and utilising culture as a means of economic development more generally (Cunningham and Platt, 2018).

However, Paisley's approach cannot be reduced to the logic of culture-led regeneration. The process of cultural regeneration itself, including how it was conceived, has been subject to change over time. The post-bid period marked a rhetorical shift *away* from the culture-led model, necessitated by the conclusion of the bid campaign. Partly, this shift was related to the UKCoC bid failure which meant the town had less resource to expand on following through its commitments. In the case of Paisley, *not* winning the UKCoC title provided an opportunity to pivot *away* from the top-down method of culture-led regeneration as facilitated through the winning the title towards a more holistic process of physical, social and cultural regeneration. In Paisley, significant changes in personnel after the bid (specifically the introduction of the Strategic Lead for Cultural Regeneration) also marked a clear shift into a

model that, while certainly not discarding economic development, sought to incorporate a greater sensitivity to social and physical regeneration. The term cultural regeneration was foregrounded from this point onwards, reflecting a more holistic approach that also aligns closely with the language of creative placemaking.

Paisley's post-bid shift in approach is of significance to debates about the role of event-bids and event-led placemaking strategies, insofar as it suggests that both event bids can be successful at garnering attention and allowing bidding cities to take stock of their assets – as discussed in chapter seven. However, this also suggests that not being bound by the expectation to deliver the event itself can create the possibility to break with the strictly top-down, criteria led approaches that event-led strategies tend to foster. This suggests that bidding towns and cities may be able to leverage the benefit of the event-bid, without being bound by criteria of the event itself. However, throughout the thesis I have argued that there remain clear parallels in the new language with the culture-led model. This is most clearly seen in the consistent prominence of flagship projects in newspaper reporting of Paisley, and in the continuing calls to utilise culture to regenerate Paisley town centre, develop the visitor economy and the creative industries. I suggest that this reflects a form of hybridised placemaking practice.

Hybridised placemaking refers to the messiness of creative placemaking and cultural regeneration insofar as these processes do not develop or evolve harmoniously. Adapting Brenner and Theodore's (2002) conception of actually existing neoliberalism, I propose that hybridised placemaking accounts for the development and mutation of placemaking in conceptually impure, situated and varying ways. Hybridised placemaking reflects the reality of placemaking practice that connects with both internal developments and broader global

processes. Placemaking does not operate in a vacuum, free from broader global influences including inter-urban competition, neoliberalism or de-industrialisation, nor does it peacefully evolve in a necessarily consistent manner. In Paisley, hybridised placemaking is a reflection of locally specific particularities, incorporating the imperatives of culture-led regeneration while simultaneously pivoting *away* from them towards a more socially just agenda of cultural regeneration.

Hybridised placemaking also incorporates the Foucauldian ideas adopted in this thesis. Hybridised placemaking in Paisley reflects the conditions of possibility that enable or constrain the production of discourse. While Paisley's approach to cultural regeneration exists independently of creative city, creative placemaking and culture-led regeneration discourses, it is clear that it also reflects these contradictory discourses. Reflecting on the way in which discourse represents *what can be said* as opposed to what is said, discourses of cultural regeneration in Paisley are clearly shaped by external discourses that shape the conditions of possibility of cultural regeneration. Others have argued that creative city discourses infiltrate how cultural regeneration can be understood, even in absence of a formal creative city approach (see Aspen, 2013; Atkinson and Easthope, 2009). Visions of trendy neighbourhoods filled with boutiques and coffee shops – as noted in Paisley's desire to stimulate a coffee shop culture – can attest to the enduring influence of Florida's vision of creative cities. In this sense, a Foucauldian understanding of power as productive (Foucault, 1982; McHoul and Grace, 1993) enables an understanding of *what can be said* about cultural regeneration.

The concept of hybridised placemaking helps address the research questions guiding this study. For research question one, hybridised placemaking represents a way of explaining the relative continuity of culture-led imperatives of flagship cultural infrastructure, inter-urban

competition and developing the visitor economic in newspaper reporting. This is as an example of hybridised placemaking insofar as the task of *representing* cultural regeneration is situated between the global imperatives of neoliberalism, inter-urban competition and the path-dependent development of Paisley's own approach. In Paisley, the logic of culture-led regeneration is not discarded but rather incorporated into broader discourses of cultural regeneration. For question two, hybridised placemaking helps understand how messages were developed and by whom. From this perspective, we can see how changes in personnel begin to challenge the existing orthodoxy of regeneration within the town, while reflecting the conditions of possibility that govern *how* cultural regeneration is understood. More specifically, this suggests that while local actors can certainly influence and shape the approach to cultural regeneration, there remains a degree of path dependency insofar as both broader global processes and previous institutional paths shape *what can be said* about cultural regeneration in Paisley.

Beyond the local context of Paisley, hybridised placemaking has clear implications for the study of cultural forms of regeneration and creative placemaking more generally. If Brenner and Theodore (2002) demonstrate that actually existing neoliberalism can account the divergent and contradictory trajectories of neoliberal development in different local contexts, then hybridised placemaking provides a framework for understanding the conditions of possibility through which local variations of cultural forms of regeneration and placemaking emerge. From this perspective, cultural forms of regeneration are still influenced by broader global processes of neoliberalism, economic development and inter-urban competition. This reflects the (im)possibility of challenging creative city-inspired regeneration agendas through creative placemaking and small-scale cultural investments in smaller towns and cities (Oakley,

2015; Hopkins, 2019). Creative placemaking may well ‘test the possibility of new narratives’ about cultural forms of regeneration (Oakley, 2015: 2). However, the conditions of possibility through which the relationship between culture, place and regeneration is governed by broader global processes of inter-urban competition and economic development.

Using the context of a large town – as opposed to a major metropolitan area on the frontiers of gentrification, this study contributes to emerging debates about ordinary places (Howcroft, 2021; Hopkins, 2019; Richards and Diuf, 2019). In this study, I have demonstrated that small cities adopt broadly similar strategies to their larger metropolitan counterparts. The logic of economic development fostered through constructing large flagship projects and mega-event bidding does not appear to be challenged by a smaller urban context. Aspen (2013) argues that zombie urbanist discourses reflect the relatively simplistic assumptions upon which culture-led regeneration strategies are built. Post-industrial Paisley demonstrates that the replication of cultural forms of regeneration do not simply spread and mutate *across* larger metropolitan areas, but also filter *down* to smaller urban contexts – such as larger peripheral towns or smaller cities.

Two main examples of cultural homogenization were discussed during this thesis: event bidding and flagship projects. First, the replication of event bidding is two-fold, both in terms of the towns or cities that bid, and in the events that they bid for. Indeed, using Paisley as an example, we can see that smaller urban places have increasingly turned towards bidding for mega-events as part of a broader regeneration agenda. However, the emergence of competitions such as the UKCoC (Cunningham and Platt, 2018) or the London Borough of Culture (Mould, 2018) illustrates that more localised events have emerged to cater for the emerging demand for smaller towns and cities to host faux-prestigious titles as a means to

igniting a cultural regeneration agenda. Second, though often related, is the construction of flagship projects to stimulate economic development. While the construction of flagship landmarks is most frequently associated with culture-led regeneration, it is clear that this continues to play a role in cultural regeneration strategies – albeit with a more progressive spin. Finally, exploring the conditions of possibility that enable or constrain local discourses of cultural regeneration demonstrates the benefit of a Foucauldian approach. A Foucauldian understanding of power, knowledge and discourse has allowed this study to understand *how* discourses of cultural regeneration are constructed. In doing so, I have advanced a new theoretical perspective to debates about cultural regeneration and creative placemaking by going beyond the well-worn critiques of culture-led regeneration and the creative city without disregarding the importance of these discourses in determining the conditions of possibility through which discourse of creative placemaking and cultural regeneration materialise.

8.5 Study limitations

This study has a number of limitations connected primarily to research design and methodology. Additionally, it is clear that conducting research during the COVID-19 pandemic has accentuated issues relating to conducting primary fieldwork. The COVID-19 pandemic greatly affected the development of this thesis. It is difficult to escape the impact of a global pandemic on everyday life and thus on research itself. Working from home arrangements, in this regard, were both a help and a hindrance to this research. This made it easier to schedule interviews with participants. Interviewing online also allowed geographical boundaries to be transcended more easily thereby enabling the inclusion of respondents outwith the local area. However, the uncertain nature of the pandemic and practical matters such as the

proliferation of technical issues presented challenges – particularly in producing accurate transcripts due to poor audio quality.

Notwithstanding the context of a global pandemic, a primary limitation of this research is the scope of the research and the choice of topic. As discussed in chapter one, the close industry-academic partnership that funded this research has, inevitably, impacted on what could be studied in the context of this research and on the independence of the researcher. Edwards (2018) argues that one potential pitfall of a collaborative studentship award where an external partner organisation is also the object of study is that research findings may not always be complementary to the funding organisation. This can, in turn, create a conflictual relationship that stalls research progress. It is important to note, however, that a conflictual relationship between funder and research is by no means inevitable. To return to Edwards (*ibid*), it is possible to develop a mutually beneficial relationship that allows for some degree of embeddedness while maintaining some degree of critical distance as a researcher. Nonetheless, it is clear that there are epistemological, pedagogical and practical risks associated with the academic-industry partnership model of doctoral funding (Malfroy, 2011).

While I have maintained a good relationship with the FPPB/CCSE network through my research, it is nonetheless true that the power dynamic between funder and student could create a reticence to engage in a critical line of inquiry inasmuch as this could displease the key partners. This is accentuated in the context of this study, which presents a critique of both local cultural regeneration policy itself and the broader processes through which cultural regeneration itself emerges. This was managed most successfully by taking an active approach to engaging with local decision makers. As opposed to being a critical outsider, I have remained close to the broader CCSE/FPPB networks but not necessarily within them.

This has allowed me to be proactive in gaining access to participants and other forms of data that have aided this study. However, I have also sought to present research findings and insights throughout the duration of my studentship. In doing so, I have maximised this study's potential for impact by informing the Future Paisley strategy as it develops.

Beyond the potential pitfalls of operating within an academic-industry partnership, this study was limited in the fullness of data with regard to attendance at workshops with local residents. It is worth noting that this cannot be entirely separated from the context of the COVID-19 discussed above, insofar as this placed a number of practical constraints upon conducting fieldwork. In addition to this, as discussed in chapter four, stimulating engagement from local residents was difficult. This is reflected in the relatively poor attendance at three scheduled workshops (with only two workshops actually being completed). While, as a qualitative study, I was not concerned with the generalisability of the data, it is difficult to draw concrete conclusions from local workshops alone. This creates some difficulty in answering research question three, which deals more specifically with local responses and reactions to representations of Paisley and of cultural regeneration itself. Despite these limitations, when viewed alongside newspaper, documentary and interview data, I have been able to produce a comprehensive study that contributes to debates on cultural regeneration and the construction of area representation.

8.6 Contribution to knowledge

Within the local context of Paisley, it is clear that there has been a changing approach to cultural regeneration in Paisley between 2014-2020. This is reflected both in the changing representations of the town's regeneration in newspaper reporting, and in interviews with key personnel who have been involved in shaping Paisley approach before, during and after

the 2021 UKCoC bid campaign. In the initial pre-bid phase, it is clear that policy makers were initially interested in a heritage-led, or culture-led approach, as outlined in *The Untold Story*. The initial epoch of regeneration, therefore, was based upon utilising under-exploited heritage assets to grow Paisley's economy. The 2021 UKCoC bid campaign saw a broad continuation of this strategy, with the additional focus of bidding for a major event. Changes to Paisley's strategy, at this point, were dictated by the criteria-led nature of the bidding process. Crucially, this further fed the imperative to focus on flagship events and growing the visitor economy and, therefore, reflecting a broadly culture-led regeneration approach. However, it is clear that the approach *after* the UKCoC bid campaign marks a shift away from a purely culture-led approach. The launch of Future Paisley and the purported shift to a more holistic cultural regeneration more closely resembles the language of creative placemaking. However, there is a persistent focus on developing the visitor economy, the international significance of Paisley's culture and heritage offer and investing in flagship cultural facilities. It is clear, therefore, that the logic of culture-led regeneration, inter-urban competition and neoliberal urban development persist in Paisley's approach. In this sense, cultural regeneration in Paisley represents the hybridity of placemaking, where there is *both* the language of creative placemaking and of culture-led regeneration exist simultaneously.

Looking beyond the local context of Paisley, this study has contributed to debates about cultural forms of regeneration (particularly in smaller urban contexts), as well the broader construction of area reputations. Beyond understanding the local context of Paisley, this study also makes a methodological contribution to debates about conducting FDA.

To begin with methodological contributions made by this study, this study has shed some light on the practical act of conducting an FDA. As scholars have noted, despite the ubiquity of use,

there remains a certain opacity to the act of conducting an FDA (Hewitt, 2009; Lees, 2004). This study draws on the methodological questions raised Sharp and Richardson (2001), and Waitt (2005), As illustrated in table 4.3.1, this study provides some framework for conducting an FDA, without compromising the theoretical axioms of Foucauldian methodologies. Practically speaking, this study has posited some questions about discourse analysis from a Foucauldian perspective that may be of use to future researchers. In addition to this, this study also makes a more specific methodological contribution to debates about culture-led regeneration and creative placemaking. Despite an enduring intellectual legacy, Foucauldian ideas have been hitherto underutilised in these aforementioned debates, despite a proliferation of Foucauldian scholarship in urban studies more generally (see Lees, 2004). In this context, this study reveals to possibilities of applying a Foucauldian understanding of discourse and power/knowledge to debates to the emergent field of ‘placemaking studies’ (Wilson, 2021). Understanding power are *productive* enables an analysis of the conditions of possibility through which discourses of cultural regeneration materialise.

Using a Foucauldian approach, this study makes two main conceptual contributions to knowledge: post-Industrial Paisley and hybridised placemaking Post-industrial Paisley analyses the way in which cultural regeneration is legitimised by discourse of post-industrial society and retail decline. Hybridised placemaking illustrates the way in conditions of possibility that enable – or constrain – discourses of cultural regeneration.

Hybridised placemaking reflects the manner in which local directions about cultural forms of regeneration reflect broader global discourses of neoliberalism, inter-urban competition and economic development. Additionally, hybridised placemaking reflects the trend toward homogenisation of approach across urban areas of varying sizes. The logic of economic

development and inter-urban competition though cultural development does not only apply, it seems, to the frontiers of the gentrifying metropolis, but also to the smaller urban contexts of smaller cities and large towns.

8.7 Areas for future research

This study has clear implications for a variety of different audiences including both academics and policy makers. This study makes a contribution to a plurality of disciplines including urban studies, placemaking studies and cultural policy studies. More specifically, it contributes to debates about culture-led regeneration, creative placemaking and neoliberal urban development. The findings of this study have several implications for future research. To begin, it is clear that Paisley is a town with a negative area reputation. I have shown that Paisley's image and reputation connects with broader discourses of territorial stigma. Future research would benefit from exploring this link in greater depth. Additionally, it is clear that *some* local respondents interviewed for this research were explicitly critical of both the UKCoC bid and cultural regeneration more generally. However, the difficulty in recruiting local respondents makes it difficult to make concrete claims based on workshop data alone. Therefore, future research would benefit from exploring grassroots responses to cultural regeneration in more depth. Finally, future studies can benefit from applying the idea of hybridised placemaking as a useful way of conceptualising the messiness of changing discourses of cultural regeneration. In this study I have provided a conceptual map for navigating competing discourses of culture-led regeneration, creative placemaking and neoliberal urban development that others can build on empirically in their towns and cities

References

- Agger, B. (1991) Critical Theory, Poststructuralism, Postmodernism: Their Sociological Relevance. Annual Sociological Review. Vol. 17(1), pp.105-131.
- Amin, A. and Thrift, N. (2002) Cities: Reimagining the Urban. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Araujo, C., Do Carmo, E., and Fraga, R. (2018) Describing the Experience of Young Researchers in Interdisciplinary Qualitative Research Based on Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) using NVivo. In: Costa, P., Reis, L., and Moreira, A (eds). Computer Supported Qualitative Research. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, Vol 861. New York: Springer.
- Archibald, M., Ambagtsheer, R., Casey, M., and Lawless, M. (2019) Using Zoom Videoconferencing for Qualitative Data Collection: Perceptions and Experiences of Researchers and Participants. International Journal for Qualitative Methods. Vol. 18(1), pp.1-8.
- Arribas-Ayllon, M., & Walkerdine, V. (2011). Foucauldian Discourse Analysis. In C. Willig, & W. Stainton-Rogers (Eds.), The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research in Psychology. London: Sage.
- Aspen, J. (2013) Oslo – The Triumph of Zombie Urbanism. In: El-Khoury, R. and Robbins, E. Studies in History, Theory and Urban Design. London: Routledge
- Atkinson, R. and Easthope, H. (2009) The Consequences of the Creative Class: The Pursuit of Creativity Strategies in Australian Cities. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 31(1), pp. 64-79.
- Auge, M. (2005) Non-Place: An introduction to supermodernity London: Verso.
- Avraham, E. (2004) Media Strategies for Improving an Unfavourable City Image. Cities. Vol. 21(6), pp. 471-479.
- Baffour-Awuah, R. (2018) Does This Place Exist? Identity Making in the Royal Docks. In: Duma, A., Hancox, D., James, M., and Minton, A. Regeneration Songs: Sounds of Investment and Loss From East London. London: Repeater Books.
- Baris, M. (2003) Review of Richard Florida: The rise of the creative class. The Next American City. Vol. 1, pp. 42-45.
- Barnes, P. and McPherson, G. (2019) Co-Creating, Co-producing and Connecting: Museum Practice Today. Curator: The Museum Journal. Vol. 6(2), pp.257-267.
- Bason, T and Grix, J. (2017) Planning to Fail? Leveraging the Olympic Bid. Marketing, Intelligence and Planning. Vol. 36(1), pp. 138-151.

- Bayliss, D. (2006) The Rise of the Creative City: Culture and Creativity in Copenhagen. European Planning Studies. Vol. 15(7), pp. 889-903.
- Bell, D. (1976) The Coming Of Post-industrial Society. New York: Basic Books.
- Bell, D and Oakley, K. (2014) Cultural Policy. London: Routledge.
- Bianchini, F. and Parkinson, M (1993) Cultural Policy and Urban Regeneration: The West European Experience. Manchester: Manchester University Press
- Birch, K and Mykhneko, V. (2009) Varieties of Neoliberalism? Restructuring in large industrially dependent regions across Western and Eastern Europe. Journal of Economic Geography. Vol. 9(3), pp. 355-380.
- Boddy, M. (2007) Designer Neighbourhoods: new-build residential development in non-metropolitan UK cities – the case of Bristol. Environment and Planning A. Vol. 39(1), p. 86-105.
- Bold, B. (2018) Case Study: Paisley 2021 Bid for UK City of Culture rekindles Scottish town's sense of identity. PR Week. Available at: <https://www.prweek.com/article/1464779/case-study-paisley-2021-bid-uk-city-culture-rekindles-scottish-towns-sense-identity> (Accessed: 10th June 2020)
- Boren, T and Young, C. (2013) Getting Creative with the 'Creative City'? Towards New Perspectives on Creativity in Urban Policy. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 37(5), pp. 1799-815.
- Bourdieu, P. (1984) Distinction. London: Routledge.
- Bowen, G. A. (2009) Document Analysis as a Qualitative Research Method. Qualitative Research Journal. Vol. 9(2), pp. 27-40.
- Boyle, M, McWilliams, C and Rice, G. (2008) The Spatialities of Actually Existing Neo-Liberalism in Glasgow, 1977-Present. Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography. Vol. 90(4), pp. 313-325.
- Breen, R. (2006). A Practical Guide to Focus-Group Research. Journal of Geography in Higher Education, 30(3), pp. 463-475.
- Brenner, N. (2021) Is 'tactical urbanism' an alternative to neoliberal urbanism? In: Courage, C., Borrup, T., Jackson, M., McKeown, A., Platt, L., Schuhbach, J. (eds) The Routledge Handbook of placemaking. London: Routledge.
- Bronholt, T. (2021) Governed by Algorithms: Facebook, Foucault and the Digital State. PhD Thesis. University of the West of Scotland.

- Brownhill, S. (1999) Turning the East End into the West End: the lessons and legacies of the London Docklands Development Corporation. In: Imrie, R and Thomas, H. British Urban Policy: An Evaluation of Urban Development Corporations. London: Sage.
- Bucerius, S. (2013) Becoming a “Trusted Outsider”: Gender, Ethnicity, and Inequality in Ethnographic Research. Journal of Contemporary Ethnography. Vol. 42(4), pp. 690-721.
- Cameron, S. and Coaffee, J. (2005) Art, gentrification and regeneration – From artist as pioneer to public arts. European Journal of Housing Policy. Vol. 5(1), pp. 39-58.
- Campbell, P. (2011) A Catachresis of Creativity? Liverpool '08, culture-led regeneration and the creative industries. PhD Thesis. The University of Liverpool.
- Campbell, P. (2013) Imaginary Success? The Contentious Ascendance of Creativity. European Planning Studies. Vol. 22(5), pp. 995-1009.
- Campbell, P., (2011) Creative industries in a European Capital of Culture. International Journal of Cultural Policy. Vol. 17(5), pp. 510-522.
- Carr, D. (2016) Husserl and Foucault on the historical apriori: teleological and ant-teleological views of history. Continental Philosophical Review. Vol. 49(1), pp.127-137.
- Castree, N. (2006) From Neo-liberalism to Neoliberalisation: Consolations, Confusions and Necessary Illustrations. Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space. Vol.38, pp. 1-6.
- Centre for Culture, Sport and Events. (n.d) Place-Focused Cultural Regeneration. Available at: <http://ccse.uws.ac.uk/place-focused-cultural-regeneration/> (Accessed 11 November 2021)
- Chakraborty, A., Sarkar, R., Mrigen, A., and Ganguly, N. (2017). Tabloids in the Era of Social Media?: Understanding the Production and Consumption of Clickbaits in Twitter. Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction. Vol.1, pp 1-21.
- Chelsom Vogt, C. (2016) The post-industrial society: from utopia to ideology. Work, employment and society. Vol. 30(2), pp. 366-376.
- Clark, J., and Wright, V. (2018) Urban regeneration in Glasgow: looking to the past to build the future? The case of the ‘New Gorbals’. In Clark, J., and Wise, N. (eds) Urban Renewal, Community and Participation: Theory, Policy and Practice. New York: Springer.
- Collins, C. (2003) Urban Policy, 'Modesty' and 'Misunderstanding': On the Mythology of 'Partnership' in Urban Scotland. In Blazyca, G. (ed) Restructuring Regional and Local Economies: Towards a Comparative Study of Scotland and Upper Silesia. London: Routledge.
- Comunian, R., and Mould, O. (2014) The weakest link: Creative industries, flagship cultural projects and regeneration. City, Culture and Society. Vol. 5(2), pp. 65-74.

Connolly, M. G., 2013. The 'Liverpool model(s)': Cultural planning, Liverpool and Capital of Culture 2008. International Journal of Cultural Policy. Vol. 19(2), pp. 161-180.

Courage, C. (2017) Arts in Place: The Arts, the Urban and Social Practice. London: Routledge.

Courage, C. (2020) The art of placemaking: A typology of the art practices in placemaking. In Edensor, T., Kaladides, A and Kothari, U. The Routledge Handbook of Place. London: Routledge.

Courage, C. (2016) Making places: performative arts practices in the city. PhD Thesis: University of Brighton.

Courage, C. (2021) Preface. In: Courage, C., Borrup, T., Jackson, M., McKeown, A., Platt, L., Schuhbach, J. (eds) The Routledge Handbook of placemaking. London: Routledge.

Courage, C. and McKeown, A. (2019) Introduction: Curating research, theory and practice. In Courage, C. and McKeown, A. (eds) Creative placemaking: Research, Theory and Practice. London: Routledge

Creative Renfrewshire Steering Group (2016) Culture Strategy. (Online) Available at <https://www.renfrewshireleisure.com/about-us/cultural-strategy/> (accessed October 23 2019)

Crossley, S., and Slater, T. (2014) Benefits Street: territorial stigmatisation and the realization of a “(tele)vision of divisions”, available at: <https://values.doc.gold.ac.uk/blog/18> (Accessed 21 September 2021)

Crow, G., Rawcliffe, S. & Harris, B. (2017). Not ‘radical’, but not ‘kailyard’ either: The Paisley Community Development Project reconsidered. Community Development Journal, Vol. 52(52), pp. 1-18.

Culture Place and Policy Institute. (2018) Cultural Transformations: the Impacts of Hull UK City of Culture 2017. Hull: University of Hull. Available at: <https://www.hull.ac.uk/work-with-us/research/institutes/culture-place-and-policy-institute/report/cultural-transformations-the-impacts-of-hull-uk-city-of-culture-2017-summary.pdf> (Accessed 12 May 2019)

Cunningham, I., and Platt., L. (2018) Bidding for UK city of culture: Challenges of delivering a bottom-up approach “in place” for a top-down strategy led scheme. Journal of Place Management and Development. Vol. 11(3), pp. 262-265.

Cuny, C. (2019) Residents’ Response to ‘Territorial Stigmatization’: Visual Research in Berlin. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 43(5), pp. 888-913.

Darbi, W., and Hall, M. (2014) Elite Interviews: critical practice and tourism. Current Issues in Tourism. Vol. 17(9), pp. 832-848.

- Davidson, M. and Lees, L. (2005) New-build “gentrification” and London’s riverside renaissance. Environment and Planning A. Vol. 37(7), pp. 1165-1190.
- Degen, M. & García, M., (2012). The Transformation of the 'Barcelona Model': An Analysis of Culture, Urban Regeneration and Governance. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 36(5), pp. 1022-1038.
- Devereux, E, Haynes, A., and Power, M. (2011) At the Edge: Media Constructions of a Stigmatised Irish Housing Estate. Journal of Housing and the Built Environment. Vol. 26(2), pp.123-142.
- Devereux, E., Haynes, A., and Power, M. (2011) Tarring everyone with the same shorthand? Journalists, stigmatization and social exclusion. Journalism. Vol. 13(3), pp. 500-517.
- Dicicco-Bloom, B., & Crabtree, B. F. (2006). The qualitative research interview. Medical education. Vol. 40(4), pp. 314–321
- Donegan, M. and Lowe, N. (2008) Inequality in the Creative City: Is There Still a Place for “Old-Fashioned” Institutions? Economic Development Quarterly. Vol. 22(1), pp. 42-62.
- Dreyfus, H. & Rabinow, P (1982). Michel Foucault – Beyond Structuralism and Hermeneutics. Hertfordshire: Harvester Wheatsheaf.
- Edwards, C. (2018) Regeneration-led Culture: Cultural Policy in Glasgow 1970-1989. PhD Thesis. The University of Glasgow.
- Edwards-Vandenhooek, S. (2021) More than a mural: Participatory placemaking on Gija country. In: Courage, C., Borrup, T., Jackson, M., McKeown, A., Platt, L., Schuhbach, J. (eds) The Routledge Handbook of placemaking. London: Routledge.
- Eisinger, P. (2000) The politics of bread and circuses: building the city for the visitor class. Urban Affairs Review. Vol. 35(3), pp. 316-333
- Ellersgaard, C., Ditlevsen, K., and Larsen, A. (2021) Say my name? Anonymity or not in elite interviewing. International Journal of Social Research Methodology. EPUB Ahead of Print. Available at: DOI: [10.1080/13645579.2021.1932717](https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2021.1932717) (accessed 10 September 2021).
- Evans, G. (2003) Hard-branding the cultural city – from Prado to Prada. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 27(2), pp. 417-449.
- Evans, G. (2005) Measure for Measure: Evaluating the Evidence of Culture’s Contribution to Regeneration. Urban Studies. Vol. 42(5/6), pp. 959-983.
- Evans, G. and Shaw, S. (2004). A review of evidence on the role of culture in regeneration. London: Department for Culture, Media and Sport.

- Evans, M. and Lee, B. (2020) Neighbourhood reputations as symbolic and stratifying mechanisms in the urban hierarchy. Sociology Compass. Vol. 14(10), pp. 1-15.
- Fairclough, N. (2003) Analysing Discourse: Textual Analysis for Social Research. London: Routledge.
- Financial Times (no date). Audience. Available at: <https://commercial.ft.com/audience/>. (Accessed 22nd November 2021)
- Fischer, K. (2009). The influence of neoliberals in Chile before, during, and after Pinochet. In: Morowski, P and Plehwe, D. (Eds.), The road from Mont Pelerin: The making of neoliberal thought. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Fisher, M. (2009) Capitalist Realise: Is there no alternative? London: Zero Books.
- Fisher, M. (2021) Post-Capitalist Desire: Mark Fisher The Final Lectures. London: Repeater Books.
- Florida, R. (2004) Cities and the Creative Class. London: Routledge.
- Florida, R. (2004) The Rise of The Creative Class: And How It's Transforming Work, Leisure, Community and Everyday life. New York: Basic Books.
- Florida, R. (2018) The New Urban Crisis: Gentrification, Housing Bubbles and What We Can Do About It. London: Oneworld.
- Foos, F., and Bischof, D. (2021) Tabloid Media Campaigns and Public Opinion: Quasi-Experimental Evidence on Euroscepticism in England. American Political Science Review. pp. 1–19
- Foucault, M. (1981) Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison. London: Penguin.
- Foucault, M. (1981) The Order of Discourse. In: Young, R (ed). Untying the text: A post-structuralist reader. Boston: Routledge and Kegan Paul Ltd.
- Foucault, M. (1981b) Questions of Method: An interview with Michael Foucault. Ideology and consciousness.
- Foucault, M. (1982) The Subject and Power. Critical Inquiry. Vol. 8(4), pp. 777-795.
- Foucault, M. (2002) The Order of Things: Archaeology of the Human Sciences. London: Routledge.
- Frenette, A. (2017) The rise of creative placemaking: Cross-sector collaboration as cultural policy in the US. The Journal of Arts Management, Law and Society. Vol. 47(5). Pp. 333-345.
- Gains, F, John, P and Stoker, G. (2005) Path Dependency and the Reform of English Local Government. Public Administration. Vol. 83(1), pp. 25-45.

Garbin, D and Millington, G. (2012) Territorial Stigma and the Politics of Resistance in a Parisian Banlieue: La Courneuve and Beyond. Urban Studies. Vol. 49(10), pp. 2067-2083.

García, B. (2004) Urban Regeneration, Arts Programming and Major Events. International Journal of Cultural Policy. Vol. 10(1), pp. 103-118.

Garcia, B. (2005) Deconstructing the city of culture: The long-term cultural legacies of Glasgow 1990. Urban Studies. Vol. 42(5/6), pp. 841-868.

Garcia, B. (2017) 'If everyone says so...' Press narratives and image change in major event host cities. Urban Studies. Vol.54 (4), pp. 3178-3198.

Garcia, B., Melville, R., and Cox, T. (2010) Creating an Impact: Liverpool's experience as European Capital of Culture. Available at https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/media/livacuk/impacts08/pdf/pdf/Creating_an_Impact_-_web.pdf (Accessed 11 January 2020)

Glaeser, E. (2004) Book Review of Richard Florida's "The Rise of the Creative Class". Creative Class.org. Available at: https://scholar.harvard.edu/files/glaeser/files/book_review_of_richard_floridas_the_rise_of_the_creative_class.pdf (accessed 12 March 2019)

Glass, R. (2010) From London: Aspects of Change. In: Lees, L. Slates, T and Wyly, E (eds). The Gentrification Reader. London: Routledge.

Gold, J. and Gold, M. (2008) Olympic Cities: Regeneration, City Rebranding and Changing Urban Agendas. Geography Compass. Vol. 2(1), pp. 300-318.

Gough, J. (2003) Neoliberalism and Socialisation in the Contemporary City: Opposites, Complements and Instabilities. Antipode. Vol. 34(3), pp. 405-426.

Grant, J and Rosen, G. (2009) Armed Compounds and Broken Arms: The Cultural Production of Gated Communities. Annals of the Association of American Geographers. Vol. 99(3), pp. 575-589.

Gray, N., and Mooney, G. (2011) Glasgow's New Urban Frontier: Civilising the Population of Glasgow East. City. Vol. 15(1), pp. 5-27.

Greener, I. (2005) The Potential of Path Dependence in Political Studies. Politics. Vol. 25(1), pp. 62-72.

Grenni, S., Horlings, L.G and Soini, K. (2020) Linking spatial planning and place branding strategies through cultural narratives in places. European Planning Studies. Vol. 28(7), pp. 1355-1374.

Griffiths, R. (2006) City/culture discourses: Evidence from the competition to select the European Capital of Culture 2008. European Planning Studies. Vol. 14(4), pp. 415-430.

Groadach, C., and Silver, D. (2013) The Politics of Urban Cultural Policy: Global Perspectives. London: Routledge.

Groadach, C., Foster, N., Murdoch, J. (2016) Gentrification, displacement and the arts: Untangling the relationship between arts industries and place change. Urban Studies. Vol. 55(4), pp. 807-825.

Grube, D. (2016) Sticky Words? Towards a theory of rhetorical path dependence. Australian Journal of Political Science. Vol. 51(3), pp. 530-545.

Hackworth, J and Moriah, A. (2006) Neoliberalism, Contingency and Urban Policy: The Case of Social Housing in Ontario. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 30(3), pp. 510-527.

Hackworth, J. and Smith, N. (2001) The Changing State of Gentrification. Journal of Economic and Social Geography. Vol. 92(4), pp. 464-477.

Hancock, L. and Mooney, G. (2012) Welfare Ghettos” and the “Broken Society”: Territorial Stigmatisation in the Contemporary UK. Housing, Theory and Society. Vol. 30(1), pp.46-64.

Handcock, M., and Gilet, K. (2011) Comment: On the concept of Snowball Sampling. Sociological Methodology. Vol. 41(1), pp. 367-371.

Harris, R., and Hendershott, K. (2018) How newspapers portray suburbs: A paradox. Journal of Urban Affairs. Vol. 40(7), pp.974-991.

Harvey, D. (1989) From Managerialism to Entrepreneurialism: The Transformation in Urban Governance in Late Capitalism. Geografiska Annaler. Series B, Human Geography. Vol. 71(1), pp. 3-17.

Harvey, D. (1990) The Condition of Postmodernity. Malden: Blackwell Publishers.

Harvey, D. (2006) Neo-liberalism as creative destruction. Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography. Vol. 88(2), pp. 145-158.

Harvey, D. (2007) A Brief History of Neoliberalism. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Harvey, D. (2019) Rebel Cities: From the Right to the City to the Urban Revolution. London: Verso.

Harvey, W. (2011) Strategies for conducting elite interviews. Qualitative Research. Vol. 11(4), pp. 431-441.

Hastings, A. (1999) Discourse and Urban Change: Introduction to the Special Issue. Urban Studies. Vol. 36(1), pp. 7-12.

Hewitt, S. (2009) Discourse Analysis and Public Policy Research. Centre for Rural Economy Discussion Paper Series No. 24: Centre for Rural Economy. Available at: <https://www.ncl.ac.uk/media/wwwnclacuk/centreforruraleconomy/files/discussion-paper-24.pdf> (Accessed 17 July 2021)

Holgersen, S. (2014) Economic Crisis, (Creative) Destruction and the Current Urban Condition. Antipode. Vol. 47(3), pp. 689-707.

Hooley, T., Wellens, J., and Marriot, J. (2012) What is Online research? Using the Internet for social science research. New York: Bloomsbury Academic.

Hopkins, E. (2019) Cities don't have to copy hipster trends to prosper – they can embrace what makes them unique. The Conversation. (October). Available at: <https://theconversation.com/cities-dont-have-to-copy-hipster-trends-to-prosper-they-can-embrace-what-makes-them-unique-100139> (Accessed 2 September 2019)

Hughes, C., and Jackson, C. (2015) Death of the high street: identification, prevention, reinvention. Regional Studies, Regional Science. Vol. 2(1), pp. 237-256.

Inglis, D. and Thorpe, C. (2019). An invitation to social theory. 2nd ed. Cambridge: Polity.

Jaffee, D. (2019) Neoliberal urbanism as 'Strategie Coupling' to global chains: Port infrastructure and the role of economic impact studies. Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space. Vol. 37(1), pp. 119-136.

Janghorban, R., Roudsari, R., and Taghipour, A. (2014) Skype Interviewing: The new generation of online synchronous research. International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being. Vol. 9(1).

Jenner, B., and Myers, K. (2014) Intimacy, rapport and exceptional disclosure: a comparison of in-person and mediated interview contexts. International Journal of Social Research Methodology. Vol. 22(2), pp. 15-177.

Jessop, B. (2002) Liberalism, Neoliberalism and Urban Governance: A state-theoretical perspective. Antipode. Vol. 34, pp. 452-472.

Johansson, S. (2007) Reading tabloids: tabloid newspapers and their readers. Stockholm: Södertörns högskola.

Johnston, H. and Kazlauskas, C. (2018) Organizing on-demand: Representation, voice and collective bargaining in the gig economy. International Labour Office: Conditions of Work and Employment Series. No. 94.

Johnstone, C. and McWilliams, C. (2005) Urban policy and the city in the 'new' Scotland. In: Mooney, G. and Gill, S. Exploring Social Policy in the 'New' Scotland. Bristol: The Policy Press.

- Kallin, H. and Slater, T. (2014) Activating Territorial Stigma: Gentrifying Marginality on Edinburgh's Periphery. Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space. Vol. 46(6), pp. 1351-1368.
- Kearns A., Kearns, I., and Lawson, L. (2013) Notorious Places: Image, Reputation, Stigma. The Role of Newspapers in Area Reputations for Social Housing Estates. Housing Studies. Vol. 28(4), pp. 579-598.
- Keil, R. (2002) "Common-sense" neoliberalism: Progressive conservative urbanism in Toronto, Canada. In: Brenner, N. and N. Theodore, N. Spaces of Neoliberalism: Urban Restructuring in North America and Western Europe. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Khan, T., and MacEachen, E. (2021) Foucauldian Discourse Analysis: Moving Beyond and Social Constructionist Analytic. International Journal of Qualitative Methods. Vol. 20, pp. 1-9.
- Kidd, M., Clark., and Kearns, A. (2017) After the Event: Perceptions of Change and Issues of Perceived Fairness in Dalmarnock, Glasgow: Report of a Qualitative Study With Residents in the Host Community, Two Years After the Commonwealth Games. GoWell/ Glasgow Centre for Population Health. Available at:
https://www.gowellonline.com/assets/0000/3932/After_the_event_perceptions_of_change_-_Gowell_report.pdf
- King, N., Horrock, C., and Brooks, J. (2019) Interviews in qualitative research. 2nd Edition, London: Sage.
- Kintrea, K. (1998) Towards a Comparative Study of Scotland and Upper Silesia. Housing Studies. Vol. 11(2), pp.287-306.
- Klein, N. (2007) The Shock Doctrine. London: Penguin.
- Kovacs, J., and Park, H. From Moon Village to Mural Village: The consequences of creative placemaking in Ihwa-dong, Seoul. In: Courage, C., Borrup, T., Jackson, M., McKeown, A., Platt, L., Schuhbach, J. (eds) The Routledge Handbook of placemaking. London: Routledge.
- Kratke, S. (2010) 'Creative Cities' and the Rise of the Dealer Class: A Critique of Richard Florida's Approach to Urban Theory. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 34(4), pp. 835-853.
- Kullberg, A., Timpka, T., Svensson, T., and Lindqvist, K. (2010) Does the perceived neighborhood reputation contribute to neighborhood differences in social trust and residential wellbeing? Journal of Community Psychology. Vol. 38(5), pp. 591-606.
- Landry, C. (2000) The Creative City: A Toolkit for Urban Innovators. London: Earthscan.
- Larner, W. (2003) Neoliberalism. Environment and Planning C: Society and Space. Vol. 21, pp 509-251.

- Larsen, T. and Delica, K. (2019) The production of territorial stigmatisation: A conceptual cartography. City. Vol. 23(4), pp. 540-563.
- Lawless, P. (2006) Area-based Urban Interventions: Rationale and Outcomes: The New Deal for Communities Programme in England. Urban Studies. Vol. 43(11), pp. 1991-2011.
- Lees, L. (2000) A Re-appraisal of Gentrification: Towards a Geography of Gentrification. Progress in Human Geography. Vol. 24(3), pp. 389-408.
- Lees, L. Slater, T and Wyly, E. (2010) The Gentrification Reader. London: Routledge.
- Lees, L., and Melhuish, C. (2013) Arts-led regeneration in the UK: The rhetoric and the evidence on urban social inclusion. European Urban and Regional Studies. Vol. 22(3), pp. 242-260.
- Leitner, H and Sheppard, E. (1998) Economic uncertainty, interurban competition and the efficacy of entrepreneurialism. In: Hall, T and Hubbard, P (eds). The Entrepreneurial City. Chichester: Wiley.
- Leslie, D. and Catungal, J.P. (2012) Social Justice and the Creative City: Class, Gender and Racial inequalities. Geography Compass. Vol. 6(3), pp. 111-222.
- Lewis, N., and Donald, B. (2010) A New Rubric for Potential in Canada's Smaller Cities. Urban Studies. Vol. 47(1), pp.29-54.
- Liu, S., and Blomley, N. (2012) Making news and making space: Framing Vancouver's Downtown Eastside. The Canadian Geographer. Vol. 57(2), pp. 119-132.
- Liu, Y. D. (2014) Cultural Events and Cultural Tourism Development: Lessons from the European Capitals of Culture. European Planning Studies. Vol. 22(3), pp. 498-514.
- Livingstone, M., and Clark, J. (2019) Living in the urban renaissance? Opportunity and challenge for 21st century Glasgow. In Kintrea, K., and Madgin, R. Transforming Glasgow: Beyond the Post-Industrial City. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Low, S. (2001) The Edge and the Center: Gated Communities and the Discourse of Urban Fear. American Anthropologist. Vol. 103(1), pp. 45-58.
- Low, S. (2006) How private interests take over public space: zoning, taxes and incorporation of gated communities. In: Low, S and Smith, N (Eds.). The Politics of Public Space. New York: Routledge.
- Luna-Garcia, A. (2008) Just Another Coffee! Milking the Barcelona Model, Marketing a Global Image, and the Resistance of Local Identities. In: Cronin, A. and Hetherington, K. (eds). Consuming the Entrepreneurial City: Image, Memory, Spectacle. London: Routledge.

MacLeod, G. (2002) From Urban Entrepreneurialism to a “Revanchist City”? On the Spatial Injustices of Glasgow’s Renaissance. Antipode: A Radical Journal of Geography. Vol. 34(3), pp. 602-624.

Malanga, S. (2004) The Curse of the creative class. City Journal (Winter). Available at: <https://www.city-journal.org/html/curse-creative-class-12491.html> (Accessed 12th June 2019)

Malfroy, J. (2011) The impact of university-industry research on doctoral programs and practices Studies in Higher Education. Vol. 36(5), pp. 571-584.

Markusen, A. (2013) Fuzzy concepts, proxy data: why indicators would not track creative placemaking success. International Journal of Urban Sciences. Vol. 17(3), pp. 291-303.

Markusen, A. and Gadwa, A. (2010) Creative placemaking. National Endowment for the Arts. Available: <https://www.arts.gov/> (accessed 23 August 2019)

Massey, D. (2005) For Space. London: Sage.

McCandilsh, A., and McPherson, G. (2020) Promoting tangible and intangible hidden cultural heritage: local communities influencing civic decision-making and international cultural policy. International Journal of Cultural Policy. Vol. 5, pp. 683-698.

McCandilsh, A. (2019) Bidding for City of Culture Status: revealing hidden heritage through creative research methods and the role of digital cultural asset mapping PhD Thesis. University of the West of Scotland.

McCarthy, J. (2010) Social justice and urban regeneration policy in Scotland. Urban Research and Practice. Vol.3: Learning Cities in Knowledge-Based Society, pp. 241-256.

McGillivray, D. and Turner, D. (2017) Event Bidding: Politics, Persuasion and Resistance. London: Routledge.

McGillivray, D., Lauermann, J., and Turner, D. (2019) Event bidding and new media activism. Leisure Studies. Vol. 40 (1), pp. 69-81.

McGuirk, P and Dowling, R. (2009) Neoliberal privatisation? Remapping the public and the private in Sydney’s masterplanned residential estates. Political Geography. Vol. 28(3), pp 175-185.

McHoul, A. and Grace, W. (1993) A Foucault Primer: Discourse, Power and the Subject. London: UCL Press Limited.

McKewon, A., and Courage, C. (2019) Conclusion: Moving into the beyond – What’s next for creative placemaking? In Courage, C. and McKewon, A. Creative Placemaking: Research, Theory and Practice. London: Routledge.

McLaren, H. (2009) Using “Foucault’s toolbox”: the challenge with feminist post-structural discourse analysis. Foucault 25 years on. Centre for Post-colonial and Globalisation Studies, Adelaide, the Hawke Research Institute. Available at: <https://www.unisa.edu.au/siteassets/episerver-6-files/documents/eass/hri/foucault-conference/mclaren.pdf> (accessed 12 August 2021).

McWilliams, C. (2004) Including the Community in Local Regeneration? The Case of Greater Pollok Social Inclusion Partnership. Local Economy: The Journal of the Local Economy Unit. Vol. 19(3), pp.264-275.

McWilliams, C., Johnstone, C. and Mooney, G. (2004) Urban policy in the new Scotland: The role of social inclusion partnerships. Space and Polity. Vol. 8(3), pp. 309–319

Meade, R. (2021) Territorial Stigmatisation in theory and practice, and its implications for community development: an introduction to the themed section. Community Development Journal. Vol. 56(2), pp. 191-202.

Miles, S and Paddison, R. (2005) Introduction: The Rise and Rise of Culture-Led Urban Regeneration. Urban Studies. Vol. 42 (5/6), pp. 838-839.

Miles, S. (2020) Consuming culture-led regeneration: The rise and fall of democratic urban experience. Space and Polity. Vol. 24(2), pp. 210-224.

Mondon, A., and Winter, A. (2020) Reactionary Democracy: How Racism and the Populist Far Right Became Mainstream. London: Verso.

Mooney, G. (2004) Cultural Policy as Urban Transformation? Critical Reflections on Glasgow, European City of Culture 1990. Local Economy: The Journal of the Local Economy Policy Unit. Vol. 19(4), pp. 327-340.

Morgan, G. and Nelligan, P. (2018) The Creativity Hoax: Precarious Work in the Gig Economy. London: Anthem Press.

Morris, A. (2015) A Practical Introduction to In-depth Interviewing. London: Sage.

Mould, O. (2014) Tactical Urbanism: The new vernacular of the creative city. Geography Compass. Vol. 8(8), pp. 529-539.

Mould, O. (2018) Against Creativity. London: Verso.

Mudge, S. (2008) What is Neo-liberalism? Socio-economic review. Vol. 6(4), pp. 703-731.

Murray, K. (2015) The Proactive Turn: Stop and Search in Scotland (A study in elite power). PhD Thesis, University of Edinburgh.

- Muscat, R. (2010) Area Based Initiatives – do they deliver? Centre for Local Economic Strategies. Available at: <https://www.cles.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2011/01/Area-Based-Initiatives-do-they-deliver.pdf> (Accessed 16 May 2021)
- O’Callaghan, C. (2010) Let’s Audit Bohemia: A Review of Richard Florida’s ‘Creative Class’ Thesis and Its Impact on Urban Policy. Geography Compass. Vol. 4(11), pp. 1606-1617.
- Oakley, K. (2015) Creating Space: A re-evaluation of the role of culture in regeneration. London: Arts and Humanities Research Council.
- O’Callaghan, C. and Linehan, D. (2007). Identity, politics and conflict in dockland development in Cork, Ireland: European Capital of Culture 2005. Cities. Vol. 24(4), pp. 311-323.
- Paddison, R. (1993) City Marketing, Image Reconstruction and Urban Regeneration. Urban Studies. Vol. 30(2), pp. 339-349.
- Paton, K., McCall, V., and Mooney, G. (2017) Place revisited: class, stigma and urban restructuring in the case of Glasgow’s Commonwealth Games. The Sociological Review. Vol. 65(4), pp. 578-594.
- Paul, K. (2020) Zoom releases security updates in response to 'Zoom-bombings'. The Guardian. 23rd April. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2020/apr/23/zoom-update-security-encryption-bombing#:~:text=Zoom%20will%20allow%20hosts,require%20a%20password%20to%20enter>. (Accessed 23 June 2020)
- Peck, J and Tickell, A. (1995) Searching for a new institutional fix: The after-fordist crisis and the global-local disorder. In: Amin, A (ed) Post-Fordism: A reader. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Peck, J and Tickell, A. (2002) Neoliberalizing Space. Antipode. Vol. 34(2), pp. 380-404.
- Peck, J, Theodore, N and Brenner, N. (2013) Neo-liberal Urbanism Redux. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 3(3), pp. 1091-1099.
- Peck, J. (2004) Geography and public policy: constructions of neoliberalism. Progress in Human Geography. Vol. 28(3), pp. 392–405.
- Peck, J. (2005) Struggling with the Creative Class. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 29(4), pp.740-770.
- Peck, J., Theodore, N., and Brenner, N. (2009) Neoliberal Urbanism: Models, Moments, Mutations. SAIS Review of International Affairs. Vol. 29(1), pp. 49-66.
- Platt, L. (2017) Crafting place: Women’s everyday creativity in placemaking processes. European Journal of Cultural Studies. Vol.22(3), pp.362-377.

Platt, L. (2021) Preface: The Problem with placemaking. In: Courage, C., Borrup, T., Rosario Jackson, M., Legge, K., McKeown, A., Platt, L., and Schupach, J. (eds) The Routledge Handbook of placemaking. London: Routledge.

Podmore, J. (1998) ReReading the 'Loft Living' *Habitus* in Montreal's Inner City. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 22(2), pp. 283-302.

Polger, J. (2008) Foucault's *Dispositif* and the City. Planning Theory. Vol. 7(1), pp.51-70.

Potter, J. (1996) Representing Reality: Discourse, rhetoric and social construction. London: Thousand Oak.

Power, M., Haynes, A., and Deveroux, E. (2021) Indelible stain: territorial stigmatisation and the limits of resistance. Community Development Journal. Vol. 56(2), pp. 244-265.

Pritchard, S. (2016) Creative placemaking, Or a Violently Anti-Working-Class Vision of the Urban Pastoral. Colouring in Culture, 23rd December. Available at: <https://colouringinculture.org/blog/violentcreativeplacemaking/> (Accessed 25 May 2021)

Rabinow, P. (1984) Introduction. In Rabinow, P. (ed) The Foucault Reader: An introduction to Foucault's Thought. London: Penguin Books.

Reason, M. and Garcia, B., (2007) Approaches to the newspaper archive: content analysis and press coverage of Glasgow's Year of Culture. Media, Culture and Society. Vol. 29(2), pp. 304-331.

Renfrewshire Council., (n.d) Future Paisley. Available at: <https://www.renfrewshire.gov.uk/futurepaisley> (Accessed 4 January 2022)

Rice, G. (2009) Actually existing neo-liberalism in Glasgow: The case of Buchanan Galleries. Urban Research and Practice. Vol. 2(2), pp 189-205.

Richards, G and Wilson, J. (2006) The Creative Turn in Regeneration: Creative Spaces, Spectacles and Tourism in Cities. In Smith, M. K (ed). Tourism, Culture and Regeneration. Wallingford: CABI.

Richards, G. (2017) From Place Branding to placemaking: The Role of Events. International Journal of Event and Festival Management. Vol. 8(1), pp. 8-23.

Richards, G. and Diuf, L. (2019) Small Cities with Big Dreams: Creative placemaking and Branding Strategies. London: Routledge.

Richards, G. and Palmer, R. (2010) Eventful Cities: Cultural Management and Urban Revitalisation. London: Routledge.

Richards, G. and Wilson, J. (2004) The Impact of Cultural Events on City Image: Rotterdam, Cultural Capital of Europe 2001. Urban Studies. Vol. 41(10), pp. 1931-1951.

- Ritzer, G. (1999) Enchanting a Disenchanted World: Revolutionizing the Means of Consumption. Pine Forge Press: Thousand Oaks, California.
- Rydin, Y. (1998) The enabling local state and urban development: resources, rhetoric and planning in East London. Urban Studies. Vol. 35(2), pp. 175-191
- Saar, M. (2002) Genealogy and Subjectivity. European Journal of Philosophy. Vol. 10, pp. 231-245.
- Santos, P., and Mari Thune, T, (2021) Social capital and university-business collaboration in doctoral education. Industry and Higher Education. EPUB ahead of print. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/09504222211069804> (accessed 30 Jan 2022).
- Sassen, S. (1990) Informalization: Imported through immigration of a feature of advanced economies? Working USA. Vol. 3(6), pp. 6-26.
- Sassen, S. (1991) The Global City: New York, London and Tokyo. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Schumpeter, J. (1942) Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy. New York: Harper & Row.
- Schwarze, T. (2021) Discursive practices of territorial stigmatization: how newspapers frame violence and crime in a Chicago community. Urban Geography. EPUB ahead of print Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723638.2021.1913015>. (Accessed 1 December 2021).
- Scottish Government (2020) Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation 2020. (Online) Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/collections/scottish-index-of-multiple-deprivation-2020/> (Accessed 4 January 2021)
- Scottish Government. (2011) Building a Sustainable Future: Regeneration Discussion Paper. Edinburgh: The Scottish Government.
- Sharp, L., and Richardson, T. (2001) Reflections of Foucauldian discourse analysis in planning and environmental policy research. Journal of Environmental Policy and Planning. Vol. 3(3), pp. 193-209.
- Shaw, K. (2008) Gentrification: what it is, why it is, and what can be done about it. Geography Compass. Vol. 2(1), pp. 1-32.
- Sisson, A. (2021) Territory and territorial stigmatisation: On the production, consequences and contestation of spatial disrepute. Progress in Human Geography. Vol. 45(4), pp. 659-682.
- Slater, T. (2006) The Eviction of Critical Perspectives from Gentrification Research. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 30(4), pp. 737-757.

- Slater, T. (2011) Gentrification of the City. In: Bridge, G and Watson, S (eds). The New Blackwell Companion to the City. London: Blackwell.
- Slater, T. (2014) The Myth of “Broken Britain”: Welfare Reform and the Production of Ignorance. Antipode. Vol. 46(4), pp.948-969.
- Smith, A. (2012) Events and Urban Regeneration. London: Routledge.
- Smith, N and Williams, P. (1986) Alternatives to Orthodoxy: Invitation to Debate. In: Smith, N and Williams, P (eds). Gentrification of the City. London: Unwin Hyman.
- Smith, N. (1979) Towards a Theory of Gentrification: A back to the city movement by Capital, not people. Journal of the American Planning Association. Vol. 45(4), pp. 538-548.
- Smith, N. (1996) The New Urban Frontier: Gentrification and the Revanchist City. London: Routledge.
- Smith, N. (2002) New Globalism, New Urbanism: Gentrification as Global Urban Strategy. Antipode. Vol. 34(3), pp. 427-450.
- Smith, N. (2008) Uneven Development: Nature, Capital and the Production of Space. Georgia: University of Georgia Press.
- Smith, N. (2011) The Evolution of Gentrification. In: Berg, J. Kaminer, M, Schoonerbeek, M and Zooneveld, J (eds). Houses in Transformation: Interventions in European Gentrification. Rotterdam: NAI Publishers.
- Stein, S. (2019) Capital City: Gentrification and the Real Estate State. London: Verso.
- Stevenson, D. (2005) “Civic Gold” Rush. International Journal of Cultural Policy. Vol. 10(1), pp. 119-131.
- Tallon, A. (2013) Urban Regeneration in the UK. London: Routledge.
- Tarling, R., Hirst, A., Rowland, B., Rhodes, J and Taylor, P. (1999) An Evaluation of the New Life for Urban Scotland initiative. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.
- Thorpe, H. (2008) Foucault, Technologies of Self, and the Media: Discourses of Femininity in Snowboarding Culture. Journal of Sport & Social Issues. Vol. 32(2), pp. 119-229.
- Tickell, A. and Peck, J. (2003) Making Global Rules: Globalisation or Neoliberalisation? In Peck, J and Yeung, H.W.C (eds). Remaking the Global Economy. London: Sage.
- Tyler, I. (2015) Classificatory struggles: class, culture and inequality in neoliberal times. The Sociological Review. Vol. 63(2), pp.493-511.
- Tyler, I. (2020) Stigma. The Machinery of Inequality. London: Zed Books.

- Venugopal, R. (2015) Neoliberalism as a concept. Economy and Society. Vol. 44(2), pp. 165-17.
- Vickery, J. (2007) The Emergence of Culture-led Regeneration: A policy concept and its discontents. Centre for Cultural Policy Studies. Available at: http://wrap.warwick.ac.uk/36991/1/WRAP_Vickery_ccps.paper9.pdf
- Wacquant, L. (1993) Urban Outcasts: Stigma and Division in the Black American Ghetto and the French Urban Periphery. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research. Vol. 17(3), pp. 366-383.
- Wacquant, L. (2008) Urban Outcasts: A comparative Sociology of Advanced Marginality. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Wacquant, L., Slater, T., and Pereira, V. (2014) Territorial Stigmatisation in Action. Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space. Vol. 46(6), pp. 1270-1280.
- Wainwright, O. (2017) 'Everything is gentrification now': but Richard Florida isn't sorry. *The Guardian*, 26th October. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/cities/2017/oct/26/gentrification-richard-florida-interview-creative-class-new-urban-crisis> (Accessed 17 June 2019)
- Waitt, G. (2005) Doing Discourse Analysis. In: Hay, I (ed). Qualitative research in human geography. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Waitt, G. (2010) Doing Foucauldian Discourse Analysis - Revealing Social Realities. In: Hay, I (ed). Qualitative research in human geography. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Waitt, G. and Gibson, C. (2008) Creative Small Cities: Rethinking the Creative Economy in Place. Urban Studies. Vol. 46(5-6), pp. 1223-1246.
- Wassenberg, F. (2004) Renewing stigmatised estates in the Netherlands: A framework for image renewal strategies. Journal of Housing and the Built Environment. Vol. 19(3), pp. 271-292.
- Watt, P. (2020) Territorial Stigmatisation and Poor Housing at a London 'Sink Estate'. Social Exclusion. Vol. 8(1), pp. 20-33.
- Wayne, D. (1998) Leisure, Lifestyle and the New Middle Class: A Case Study. London: Routledge
- Webb, D. (2014) placemaking and Social Equity: Expanding the Framework of Creative placemaking. Artivate. Vol. 3(1), pp.35-48.
- Weber, R. (2002) Extracting Value from the City: Neoliberalism and Urban Redevelopment. Antipode. Vol. 34(3), pp. 519-540.

- Webster, C. (2002) Gated cities of tomorrow. Town Planning Review. Vol. 72, pp. 149-169.
- Weller, S. (2017) Using internet video calls in qualitative (longitudinal) interviews: Some implications for rapport. International Journal of Social Research Methodology. Vol. 20(6), pp.613-625.
- Welshman, J. (2014) Underclass: A history of the excluded since 1880. London: Blumsbury.
- Williams, H. (2011) Strategies for conducting elite interviews. Qualitative Research. Vol. 11(4), pp. 431-441.
- Willing, C. (2013) Discourse and Discourse Analysis. In: Flick, U. The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Data Analysis. London: Sage.
- Wilson, C (2019) Book Review: The New Urban Crisis: Gentrification, Housing Bubbles, Growing Inequality, and What We Can Do About It. Conorsphd.wordpress.com (Accessed 19 November 2019)
- Wilson, C. (2021) Heritage, Hauntology and Future Paisley: Visions of the Future and Absence in Urban Regeneration Discourse. Remaking the Future: 70th Anniversary Virtual Conference. 14th April, Online.
- Wilson, C. (2021) The Routledge Handbook of placemaking Edited by Cara Courage, Tom Borrup, Maria Rosario Jackson, Kyle Legge, Anita McKeown, Louise Platt, and Jason Schupach, Abingdon/New York, Routledge, 2021, 531pp., £190 (hardback), ISBN 978-0-367-22051-8, £35.99 (ebook) ISBN978-0-429-27048-2. Cultural Trends. Vol. 30(4), pp. 388-390.
- Wilson, D. (2004) Toward a Contingent Urban Neoliberalism. Urban Geography. Vol. 25(8), pp. 771-783.
- Wise, N., and Clark, J. (2017) Introduction. In Wise, N., and Clark, J. (eds) Urban Transformations: Geographies of Renewal and Creative Change. London: Routledge.
- Wood, A. (1998) Making sense of urban entrepreneurialism. Scottish Geographical Magazine. Vol. 114(2), pp. 120-123.
- Wright, V. (2018) Tinkering at a local level: Unemployment, state intervention and community agency in Ferguslie Park, Paisley c. 1972-1977. Scottish Labour History. Vol. 53, pp. 192-211.
- Young, R. (1981) Post-structuralism: An Introduction. In: Young, R (ed). Untying the text: A post-structuralist reader. Boston: Routledge and Kegan Paul Ltd.
- Zimmerman, J. (2008) From Brew town to cool town: Neoliberalism and the creative city development strategy in Milwaukee. Cities. Vol. 25(4), pp. 230-242.
- Zitcer, A. (2018) Making Up Creative Placemaking. Journal of Planning Education and Research. Vol. 40(3), pp. 278-288.

Zukin, S. (1989) Loft Living: Culture and Capital in Urban Change. New Brunswick: Rutgers University Press.

Zukin, S. (2009) New Retain Capital and the Neighbourhood Change: Boutiques and Gentrification in New York City. City & Community. Vol. 8(1), pp. 47-64.

Zukin, S. (2011) Naked City: The Death and Life of Authentic Urban Place. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Appendices

A-1 Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Culture, Media and the Transformation of Place Impression: Narrative, Media and 'Regeneration' in Paisley

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the work is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to explore the intersection of place, image and regeneration in Paisley and how this has developed over time. More specifically, the research explores the nature of messages communicated about Paisley, culture and regeneration since the publication of the 'Paisley: the untold story' in 2014, through the bid to become UK City of Culture and in the launch of new destination brand Paisley.is and Future Paisley.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because you have been identified as a professional who has been involved in cultural regeneration in Paisley, as such your views and experiences are of interest to the researcher.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to participate in a one-to-one interview about your experience of media, communication and regeneration in Paisley. This discussion will take place online using a secure network and will take around 60 minutes. All interviews will be recorded and transcribed verbatim following any interview. Please note that you will have the opportunity to review any completed transcript and to request amendments should you wish. No transcript/data will be included in this research without your approval. Please note, that interview transcripts **will not** be anonymised in this research.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no known risks to taking part in this study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no known benefits to taking part in this study.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and she can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

Detail any intended recipients of personal data if not explained elsewhere, and also advise if any personal data will be transferred outside the EEA, and if so to where.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results from this study will be disseminated via a PhD thesis. Results may also be disseminated via conferences and academic publications.

Who has reviewed the study?

BCI Ethics Committee-Approval Number: 2020-13185-10575

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Conor Wilson

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Thank you for taking part in this study.

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Culture, Media and the Transformation of Place Impression: Narrative, Image and 'Regeneration' In Paisley

Ethics Approval Number: 2020-13185-10575

Investigator(s) name(s): Conor Wilson

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.

Initials

I consent to the processing of my personal information for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

Initials

I understand that my data will not be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work may report data which identifies me.

Initials

I agree to having my voice/likeness digitally recorded.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

A-3 Interview Recruitment Template

Dear ***insert name***,

I hope this email finds you well. For a little bit of background on my research and myself, I am a PhD student within the Centre for Culture, Sport and Events at UWS. My research, in its broadest sense, explores the development of cultural regeneration in Paisley between 2014-2020. Specifically, I'm interested in:

1. The changing way in which the relationship between culture, place and regeneration has been understood in Paisley, broadly since the publication the 'Untold Story'.
2. How Paisley has been represented, and has sought to represent itself, in media coverage during this time period.

In terms of your involvement, I'd to invite you to be interviewed as part of my research. I think your perspective as ***insert role and rationale for interview*** will offer a unique insight and perspective for my research.

All interviews are being conducted remotely, preferably using Microsoft teams. If that does not work, then we could also speak over the phone. In either case, I am hoping to record the meeting for transcription purposes (once my project is complete all recorded data will be deleted). Given the nature of the interviews, I **will not** be fully anonymising the data before including it in my research. However, I will provide you with a full written transcript and you will be able to request any amendments you wish.

I have attached a participant information sheet and a consent form for you to sign (this can be done digitally given the online nature of the fieldwork). If you have any further questions, please don't hesitate to get in touch.

A-4 List of Interviewees by Role

Respondent	Role	Date
Respondent 1	Former Leader of Renfrewshire Council	10.02.21
Respondent 2	Director of Communities and Housing, Renfrewshire Council	05.03.21
Respondent 3	Regeneration Manager at Renfrewshire Council	16.11.20
Respondent 4	Chief Executive of Creative Paisley	05.11.21
Respondent 5	Head of Economy and Development at Renfrewshire Council	03.03.21
Respondent 6	Former Strategic Lead of Cultural Regeneration for Renfrewshire Council	11.09.21
Respondent 7	Head of Marketing and Communications at Renfrewshire Council	02.10.20
Respondent 8	2021 UKCoC technical bid advisor	22.10.20
Respondent 9	Project Manager, STAR project	23.09.20
Respondent 10	Local Artist	11.03.21

Respondent 11	Chief Executive of PACE Theatre Company	11.11.20
Respondent 12	Former Business Owner and Community Activist	05.03.21
Respondent 13	UKCoC 2021 Bid Director	21.09.21
Respondent 14	Chief Executive of Engage Renfrewshire	21.09.21
Respondent 15	Engagement Manager UKCoC bid	30.10.20
Respondent 16	Local Community Activist	18.01.21

A-5 My Paisley, My Stories Workshop Plan

My Paisley, My Stories: Workshop outline

Introduction (10 minutes) (Pre-recording)

- Go around and introduce each participant
- Brief icebreaker task

Paisley, Media and Representation (Start recording)

- **Part 1: General questions:**
 - o How do you feel about living in Paisley?
 - o How has the town changed in recent years?
 - o What would you like to be done to improve the town?
- **Exercise:** How would you describe Paisley to someone who has never visited the town?
- **Part 2: Local Perceptions of Paisley and Paisley's Image and Reputation**
 - o How do you feel the town has been perceived?
 - o Do you feel this perception is accurate?
 - o How do you feel Paisley has been represented in the media?
 - o What impact do you think the 2021 City of Culture bid and ongoing cultural regeneration has had?
 - o How would you like to see Paisley represented in the future?
- **Exercise 2:** Design a postcard from Paisley

Negative Reporting of Paisley

Each theme will consist of one slide using selected newspaper extracts as a starting point for discussion

- **Poverty and inequality**
 - o "What is not visible but palpable is a rediscovered optimism in a place too often defined in recent years by Ferguslie Park, a housing estate that was once the site of thriving mills and is now the most deprived area in Scotland, according to the index of multiple deprivation" (The Guardian, 2017)
 - o "The decline of industry saw Paisley diminish from a proud centre of excellence to a place that suffered significant deprivation" (Irish Independent, 2017)
 - o "One in three children in Paisley live in poverty. This town is still in decline: since we launched the bid there's been 1,000 job losses announced" (The Guardian, 2017b)
 - o "At the same time, we can't and won't hide from the fact Paisley has challenges -- but the UK City of Culture process is about building the economic and community capacity to face those challenges and make a far-reaching social impact" (The Herald, 2016)

- **Violence and drugs**

- Child poverty is high, and knife fights not uncommon (New York Times, 2017)
- A wave of crimes involving heroin and prescription Temazepam tablets known as jellies in the 1990s saw Paisley dubbed Scotland's "drugs capital" — a title that locals insist was unjustified but which scared off visitor (Financial Times, 2016)

- **Town centre decline**

- "Except that, sadly, too much in my home town HASN'T moved on. Too many stunning buildings have been allowed to decay...Too many misguided planning decisions have reduced its once thriving High Street to a wheezing shambles. (The Sun, 2017)
- "Paisley, even to its own population, had begun to seem no more than a catalogue of social problems. Out-of-town shopping centres have killed the high street; its housing estates contain some of the worst deprivation in Scotland. It's a poor place, rich in history" (The Guardian, 2017)
- "If there was ever a town with image problems it is Paisley, the former textile powerhouse just outside Glasgow that for decades has been a byword for drugs, deprivation and high street decline" (Financial Times, 2016)
- "Paisley High Street has become the universal if, to my eyes, rather tired symbol of retail decline. The Guardian newspaper recently dubbed it "Tumbleweed Town", the Financial Times said it is "the byword for drugs and decline" and the New York Times noted its pawnbrokers, thrift stores and boarded-up shop fronts" (The Herald, 2017)
-

Key Narratives from the City of Culture bid

- **Paisley: the underdog**

- "Paisley may have been seen an underdog in the competition, but we punched above our weight to reach the late stages of the (City of Culture competition) process" (Paisley Daily Express, 2017)
- On top of that, it's a town that punches well above its weight, an ambitious underdog determined to take its place at the table and unapologetically show off its best bits (Independent, 2019)
- "For its size, Paisley's contribution to the world is absolutely massive and we have a list of assets to be proud of." (The Herald, 2016)

- **Putting Paisley 'on the map'**

-

- "Let's put Paisley back on the map...Earlier this week, I was proud to launch a blueprint which I believe can put Paisley on the international map once again and, in doing so, deliver a massive boost to Renfrewshire's economic and employment prospects" (Paisley Daily Express, 2014)

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- “Paisley has been well and truly placed on the map” (Paisley Daily Express, 2018)
- **Investment in culture and town centre regeneration**
 - The town hall is undergoing a £22 million renovation, while a £42 million investment in the museum will deliver a world class visitor destination. (Daily Record, 2018)
 - The work is part of a wider programme aimed at using Paisley's unique cultural and heritage story to change its future - including major transformations of the museum and town hall and a new library in a formerly-empty High Street retail unit. (Paisley Daily Express, 2019)
 - More than £100 million is currently being invested in Paisley town centre's cultural venues as part of plans to use the region's rich heritage to drive its economic regeneration (Paisley Daily Express, 2019)
- **International Significance of Paisley’s cultural offer**
 - The (city of culture) bid hopes to transform Paisley's future using its internationally-significant heritage and cultural story. (The Herald, 2017)
 - Now we are setting out our full legacy plans which will use our unique and internationally-significant heritage and cultural story to transform our future (Paisley Daily Express, 2018)
 - The town is known worldwide for the Paisley Pattern and still has the legacy of its days at the heart of the global textile industry, as well as a thriving cultural scene which will form the basis for the town's UK City of Culture bid (Paisley Daily Express, 2016)
 - Celebrating the region's rich traditions - from weaving the Paisley Pattern to the iconic Paisley Abbey - and establishing Renfrewshire as a key visitor destination are at the centre of the regeneration plans (Paisley Daily Express, 2019)